

University of the West of Scotland

**Teachers` perceptions of and experiences towards the inclusive
education of physically and sensory disabled learners in
mainstream primary schools in Algeria**

Houria Benkahla

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the University of the West of Scotland for the award of
Doctor of Philosophy**

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Author's Declaration

I hereby declare that this thesis, titled “Teachers’ perceptions of and experiences towards the inclusive education of physically and sensory disabled learners in mainstream primary schools in Algeria” is the result of my own original research. The work presented in this thesis has not been previously submitted for examination which has led to the award of a degree.

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Houria Benkahla

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ABSTRACT

In Algeria, inclusive education is a recent concept that seeks to ensure that all students, both with and without disabilities, have access to equal educational opportunities in mainstream settings. Schools, as part of society, should strive to improve the well-being of all learners by providing high-quality teaching and learning experiences. Nevertheless, the school culture, which reflects the school's values, norms, and practices, is essential for fostering an inclusive learning environment. This study examines teachers' perceptions of and experiences towards inclusive education of physically and sensory disabled learners in public primary schools in Algeria, as teachers are crucial in fostering inclusive education through their teaching methods.

To accomplish this objective, the study incorporates a comprehensive literature review of inclusive education, integration, models of disability, and an overview of the educational system in Algeria. Considering the nature of this research, an interpretive epistemological perspective was employed. This research utilises an exploratory qualitative case study approach to gather, analyse, and report the results of this doctoral research. Thematic analysis was used to analyse the qualitative data collected through focused group discussions and semi-structured interviews; The study included 27 teachers from general primary schools in Ammi-Mossa city, Relizane province, Algeria, of whom 7 participated in a focus group and 20 in individual semi-structured interviews.

The research findings indicate that many teachers in the Algerian primary schools in this province have a limited understanding of inclusive education. Some educators view inclusion through a medical lens, while others adopted a social model. Despite this, some teachers express positive attitudes toward including students with physical and sensory disabilities in mainstream classrooms. Teachers who employed diverse teaching strategies were more likely to hold these optimistic views, even if they were unfamiliar with specific inclusion policies. However, not all teachers in this study share this positive outlook. Some educators express reservations about inclusion, suggesting that special schools are better suited for students with disabilities. These negative views are influenced by factors such as lack of knowledge of inclusive education policies, lack of teachers' training and personal development in inclusive education, lack of instructional resources and materials, physical school environment as a barrier to the implementation of inclusive education, lack of curriculum adaptation, and lack of teacher- parents collaboration.

Inadequate report at the school level, and lack of support and guidance from the Algerian Ministry of Education are identified as being significant contributors to the exclusion of students with disabilities from mainstream schools.

The participants propose some strategies to improve mainstream schools so that all students could learn together. These strategies include providing appropriate professional development and teacher training, increasing teacher motivation through financial support, improving school facilities and services, enhancing collaboration for inclusive education, raising awareness and commitment to inclusive education, and developing relevant laws and policies.

While research in other cultural and geographical contexts have come to comparable results, this study presents the first in-depth research into issues around inclusive education in mainstream school in Algeria, particularly since the relatively recent release of inclusive education policies in the country. Being the first of its kind in this context, the study highlights the disconnect between the introduction of well-intended policy by the Ministry of Education and its implementation in schools' every-day practices. The results of this doctoral research project allow for wider conclusions both on inclusive education in policy and practice globally and in the context of Algeria.

Key Words: Inclusive Education, learners with physical and sensory disabilities, perceptions, experiences.

DEDICATION

To my late father, whose dream of seeing me complete my studies has been a constant source of motivation. He has always encouraged me to strive for excellence, set high standards, and persevere in the face of challenges. His unwavering encouragement and the opportunities he provided me have been invaluable. His memory will forever be a source of inspiration.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

APCCPPI: Association for Parents of Children with Cerebral Palsy for Promotion and Integration

APD: Association of People with Disabilities

BERA: British Educational Research Association

DREDF: Disability Rights Education and Defence Fund

HIA: Handicap International Association

ICF: International Classification of Functioning

ICF-CY: International Classification of Functioning for Children and Youth

IEP: Individualized Education Plans

ITT: Initial Teacher Training

MA: Ministry of Education

NASPD: National Association for Support of People with Disabilities

SEN: Special Educational Needs

UNCRPD: United Nations Convention on the Right of Persons with Disabilities

UNESCO: United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization

WHO: World Health Organization

1 Chapter One: General Introduction

1.1 Background of the research and general context

In all parts of the world, there are people living with disabilities or circumstances that have an impact on them realising their potential to accomplish everyday activities, take part in academic journeys, and in public life in comparison to individuals without disabilities (World Health Organization- WHO, 2002) . According to the WHO, (2002) disability is a broad term or a word that covers a universal collection of conceptions, for instance impairments or circumstances that limit an individual's activity and participation. Approximately ten per cent (10%) of people in the world have a disability (World Health Organization, 2022) . For a majority of disabled people, their access to 'standards of living' are different from those without disabilities; people with disabilities reveal their experiences of being exposed to poverty, social exclusion, and discrimination. Around 80% of disabled people live in separated rural regions in the developing countries, over 62 million are primary school-age children live with disabilities, and 186 million disabled children have not finished their elementary school education (UNESCO, 2009).

Across the globe, approximately 240 million children, or 1 in 10 of those aged up to 17 years old, cope with a severe or moderate disability (UNICEF, 2021). The overall image of the prevalence of disabled children was further disclosed in research carried out by the Global Burden of Disease. The results demonstrate that approximately 93 million (5.1%) children aged up to 14 years old who were living with severe or moderate disabilities, and 13 million (0.7%) children were experiencing severe difficulties (World Health Organization, 2011).

Chan and Zoellick (2011) stress that a number of disabled children do not have equal access to education and health care. Another study indicates that 65 million children of primary and lower secondary school-age in the developing countries have disabilities in which half of that are marginalised and are not attending school (Liliane Foundation, 2017). The aforementioned excluded children are those with special education needs around the world that are categorised as having moderate, mild, or severe learning impairment that call for further strategies for actions in the learning and teaching situations.

Students from around the world, representing over 185 countries, come from diverse backgrounds. They differ significantly in terms of race, customs, cultural norms, ethnicity, nationality, language, and physical appearance (Hanassab, 2006). Findings from various studies all over the world

highlight that teachers and schools are making efforts to respond to the diverse range of learners, which leads teachers to work hard to ensure that graduates possess the essential competences, confidence, and characteristics to plan and provide inclusive educational programs for a vast array of students(European Agency for Development in Special Needs Education, 2020). Despite the internationalization of the notion of inclusive education, due to various cultural, historical, financial, and social reasons, its implementation remained unequal over the world (Mitchell, 2010).

The decree number 02-09 of 8 May 2002 refers to the promotion and protection of the rights of people with disabilities in Algeria. In May 2009, Algeria ratified the United Nations Convention on the Right of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD). In 2011 it launched a National Disability Survey as the foundation for a further policy development and implementation (HI, 2016). In Algeria, the prevalence of disability is estimated to be 5.5% or between one million eighty-eight thousand (1088000) and one million six hundred five thousand one hundred sixty (1605160) individuals with disabilities (Rohwerder, 2018).

The Algerian decree prevents prejudice against people with disabilities in accessing health care, employment, and education. Disability supporters revealed that disabled children on rare occasions attend schools (USDS, 2017). Both private and public schools usually lack trained teachers to deal with disabled learners (USDS, 2017).In cooperation with the Ministry of Education, the Ministry of National Solidarity, Family, and the Status of Women has been working to incorporate disabled children in general schools in order to enhance inclusion. Though the United States Department of State (USDS, 2017) discovered that most of the educational programs for learners with disabilities were in social service centres and not in general schools.

According to the Algerian Ministry of National Solidarity, as of 2014, there were 630,000 children with disabilities in the country. However, only 125,000 of these children (20%) were receiving support from various organisations, with 104,000 supported by the National Education system, 14,532 by specialized public centres, 5,000 by the associative network, and 1,452 by private integrated classes. This data highlights a significant gap in support for children with disabilities in Algeria (Bessai, 2018).

As discrimination against disabled children in Algeria is prohibited, the state party pursues efforts to support them in public activities through providing direct and indirect help. The United States

Department of State (2023) acknowledged that the Algerian government is making efforts to improve educational programs and strategies to assure that disabled children have equal opportunities with the ordinary children to access education, health, and social services. In the same vein, the Committee on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities recommended the support and launch of awareness raising campaigns regarding the situations of disabled children, their potential, their special needs, and their rights, with the purpose of changing misconceptions, prejudices, and negative attitudes that abuse towards them. All professionals dealing with disabled children should be trained including paramedic, social workers, and teachers(Committee on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, 2018).

In 2009, the number of disabled people of school age was around 54584. Among them about 22780 were enrolled (14320 learners in regular public schools and 8460 in special schools) for an enrolment ratio of 41.73%. During the school year 2008-2009, the rate of success of all learners with disabilities in different exams (elementary, middle, and secondary final exams) was about 79% (The Algerian Network for the Defence of the Rights of the Child, 2011). According to The Algerian Network for the Defence of the Rights of the Child (2011), sensory disabled children in Algeria receive special education in 24 schools for the visual disabled children and 42 schools for those with hearing disabilities. Additionally, children with motor disabilities are placed in six (06) social care centres for motor disabilities. The educational staff who work with these children are trained by the National Centre for Training of Specialised Staff (The Algerian Network for the Defence of the Rights of the Child, 2011).Moreover, the Ministry of National education has applied a system that support the integration of children with mild or moderate disabilities into public or special schools in their neighbourhoods. The estimated number of disabled children registered in public schools gradually increased from 1033 in 2007 (Djaffer, 2015) to 32,500 in 2018, with the ability to accommodate them considerably improved (Committee on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, 2018).

In response to this a framework ("Education for All: toward the inclusion of children with disabilities in the Algerian education system") was developed and started in January 2010 and ran for three years. The Handicap International Association (HIA), together with the Association of People with Disabilities (APD), the Association for Parents of Children with Cerebral Palsy for Promotion and Integration (APCCPPI) of Setif, and the National Association for Support of People

with Disabilities (NASPD) El Baraka in Ain Taya conducted a regional survey about the barriers to learning for children with disabilities. The focus of the study was on disabled children who were enrolled in mainstream schools; but do not benefit from an organized, inclusive, and welcoming environment that allow them to access learning. The study targeted 143 families, 33 principals, 8 school doctors, 9 school inspectors, 72 teachers, and 112 children. The findings revealed that there are several challenges to the inclusion and participation of disabled children in public schools. In which 80% of principals claimed that they usually refuse to enrol a child just due to his disability, about 40% of teachers revealed their negative attitudes towards the inclusion of disabled children, approximately 60% of disabled children stated that they do not feel comfortable with their ordinary peers' behaviours. Likewise, transportation is another barrier for disabled children in which that a study revealed that around 70% of them disabled children access to the schools on foot, (39 % among them face difficulties) and about 30% of them are using public transport where 69% among them face challenges. Moreover, the research highlighted that disabled children do not receive enough psychological support as well as they are not aware of the legal provisions set up for them. Additionally, it showed that segregation of disabled learners in schools is even more remarkable in the rural communities (The Algerian Network for the Defence of the Rights of the Child, 2011).

There is an increased awareness in Algeria that learners with various needs populate today's classrooms. This diversity requires the creation of inclusive classrooms; thus learners' needs and differences can be accommodated in the learners' journey. The main purpose of inclusive education is to ensure equal opportunities to learners irrespective if they do not have sufficient commonality, meeting their different needs, and celebrating their personal differences. Basically, the major concern of inclusive education is to integrate learners with different needs within one classroom where diversity is considered as a normal aspect that forms personalities (Hoadjli and Latrache, 2020). Inclusive education means that all learners have to be educated in the same classrooms together with their peers, regardless of any differences or difficulties that they could have, with the purpose of offering all children the appropriate support and resources in accordance with their needs (Materechera, 2014). Among the principle of inclusive education is to address and respond to the various needs of learners by enhancing participation in communities, cultures, and learning, and decreasing exclusion from and within education (Ras, 2008). Similarly, Tabane (2009) stated that inclusion means to allow learners with and without special educational needs

and regular learners to be educated in the same classrooms and instructed by general class teachers. At the present time, inclusive education is essential requirement for successful learning and teaching approaches, along with the need for good quality of teachers who are well prepared to address all learners needs (Verity, 2010). However, teachers are anxious, concerned, and unsure about teaching learners from diverse backgrounds (Allison and Rehm, 2006), though many countries like Canada and the European union member states claim that they have implemented inclusive education successfully, other countries, including Algeria, are still trying to realise this aim (Nguyet and Ha, 2010).

1.2 Overview about Algeria

Algeria is considered as Africa`s largest country by surface area of 2381741 square kilometres. It is situated in Northern Africa. It is surrounded by Libya and Tunisia from the East; Mauritania, Western Sahara and Morocco from the West; Mali and Niger from the South; and the Mediterranean Sea from the North. Its capital city is Algiers. The major cities of Algeria are Batna, Annaba, Sétif, Constantine, Tizi-Ouzou, Béjaïa, Blida, Boumerdes, Médéa, Chlef, Tiaret, Mostaganem, Tlemcen, Sidi-Bel-Abbès, Oran, Ghardaïa, Biskra, Adrar, Béchar, Laghouat and Tamanghasset.

The Algerian weather is warm and temperate Mediterranean climate. It includes four main relief areas. Firstly, from north to south: the Tell, a steppe which extends alongside with the Mediterranean seaboard. Secondly, two main sierras extending from east to west, surrounded by desert areas. Thirdly, the Hoggar Mountains. Finally, a vast desert that covers 80% from the total area of the country. Furthermore, the total resident population of Algeria in 2016 was 40.4 million. In addition, Algeria is a people democratic republic. The republic President is the supreme magistrate of the country. As well as the state religion is Sunni Islam. Moreover, according to the new constitution in 2016, the official languages of the country are Arabic and Tamazight. Additionally, the French language is used as a lingua franca. Education is estimated to be 1.88% of the entire government`s expenditure (Saidani and Khecheni, 2017).

Figure 1 Map of Algeria showing the 48 current administrative districts and their bioclimatic status. By (Amrani et al., 2015).

Islam, a religion deeply rooted in Algerian culture, promotes the significance of education for all individuals, regardless of their status, gender, sect, or disability. This belief is reflected in the Algerian educational policy, which safeguards the rights of learners with disabilities. Islamic principles emphasize that all people, regardless of their social, gender, or physical status, are equal before God and deserve equal opportunities. While there may be regional or cultural factors that contribute to discrimination against disabled people, these practices are not derived from Islamic teachings. Islam views disability as a morally neutral condition, neither a blessing nor a punishment from God. The Quran, a holy text in Islam, reinforces this perspective by emphasizing that the most honoured person in God's sight is the most righteous, regardless of their physical attributes.

According to (Mubaraq *et al.*, 2021) Islam and education are closely intertwined, and Islamic principles support the right of all individuals to receive an education. Mubaraq et al. (2021) further emphasises the importance of inclusive education in Islamic perspective and highlight the need to ensure that all learners, regardless of their disabilities, have access to quality education. Hasnain, Shaikh and Shanawani (2008) also contribute to this discussion by examining the Qur'anic perspective on disability and emphasizing that disability is not a moral judgment. Islamic principles and Algerian educational policies converge in their commitment to inclusive education. These principles provide a strong foundation for creating an educational environment where all learners, regardless of their abilities, can thrive and reach their full potential.

1.3 National Policies and Fundamental Principles

According to Saidani and Khecheni (2017) once the Algerian country achieved independence in July 1962, education became a legitimate interest for the Algerian people. The institution of teaching and education has passed through different stages, namely, from 1962 to 1976, instantly after the independence, there has been a necessity to get a roadworthy system for the Algerian schools. During this time, education became wider spread, and schools were established even in the deprived regions. The content inherited from the French colonial system was adjusted and education was progressively 'Arabised'. Such action led to the formation of technological institutes to train field application engineers and advanced technicians. Additionally, an increasing number of training centres for teachers of primary, middle, and secondary schools were established. The second stage from 1976 to 1999, this period started with the signature of the decree 76-35 on 16 April 1976, which was about the organisation of training and education in Algeria. This law readjusted the educational system during the social and economic changes that had happened, consecrating the act of nine year of compulsory and free basic education, as well as regulating the main policy guidelines of the national educational system in addition to a further focus on science and technology. The decree's provisions were implemented in the academic year 1980-1981 and so forth. In 1998, the ordinance No 98-382 on 2 December 1998 returned universities, which has been repealed by the law of 1971. The third stage is from 1999 to the present time. The Algerian faculties are currently grappling with significant challenges, including the need to reconcile the demand for equal access to higher education with the growing need for

high-quality training in a rapidly evolving world characterized by knowledge and information-driven societies and economic globalization (Saidani and Khecheni, 2017).

After conducting a complete review of the current higher educational system in Algeria, the sector of Higher Education and Scientific Research instigated three major transformation reforms, namely: pedagogy management, course structure, and the content of the educational programs. These reforms aimed to enhance the quality and accessibility of higher education, including for students with disabilities. Since the academic year 2004-2005, the higher education is presently arranged into three stages, which are bachelor's degree, master's degree and Doctorate. This tiered system provides a clear pathway for students, including those with disabilities, to progress through their higher education studies (Saidani and Khecheni, 2017).

1.4 School system in Algeria

The education in Algeria is free of charge and mandatory for nine years starting age of six. It comprises five years of elementary school and four years of middle school (lower secondary school). After the accomplishment of mandatory schooling, students take up the Basic Education Certificate. Therefore, students can decide to register in secondary education for an extract three years, which leads to the general certificate of secondary education (Baccalaureate) (The National Recognition Information Centre for the United Kingdom (NARIC), 2012). The responsibility for all educational grades is shared between three government services, namely, the ministry of professional training, the ministry of higher education and scientific research, and ministry of national education. The Algerian educational system is comparatively focal, especially in relation to teaching in schools, in which the ministry of national education has an overall responsibility for the organization of schooling, teaching methods, study programmes, staff members, inspections, school timetables, and examinations (The National Recognition Information Centre for the United Kingdom (NARIC), 2012).

1.4.1 Teaching requirements in Algeria

Generally, the qualifications required to join teaching profession are demonstrated in terms of "Baccalaureate +", in accordance with the duration of study post-Baccalaureate. The higher secondary school diploma is a necessary requirement to enter to higher education programmes;

this includes initial teacher training (ITT) programmes. There is not a particular discipline requirement for all ITT acceptance on a national level; Yet a specific stream or a subject of higher secondary school certificate in regard to the learner's selected speciality for ITT is necessary in order to be accepted in a particular programme. Subjects like mathematics and native language (Arabic) are popular in all branches; however, other fields differ based on whether the person had taken a science or an arts stream. Furthermore, the governmental ordinance in July 1999 stated that the certificate of basic education teacher, a (Baccalaureate plus three) qualification is needed in order to teach in primary schools. However, the certificate of lower secondary education, a (Baccalaureate plus four) qualification is required to teach in middle schools, as well as possessors of an undergraduate level in teaching may teach in this level. A baccalaureate Plus five qualification is needed to teach in higher secondary schools. In addition to that, the job as a teacher may also be accessible through a bachelor's degree in a certified subject as well as a competitive exam (contest) for individuals who wish to work at lower secondary degree. Whereas a degree of master's degree alongside with a success in the contest is required for individuals who want to teach at higher secondary level. People who access teaching through passing the contest will enter a preparative educational training with the duration, organization and content established by the ministry of national education in order to be acknowledged as teachers (The National Recognition Information Centre for the United Kingdom (NARIC), 2012).

1.4.2 The teacher training and professional development in Algeria

Education has always been an influential instrument and a crucial interest in the country's development framework (Ghedjghoudj, 2014). According to Boudersa (2016) in the current Algerian educational framework, it appears to be an immediate need for an educational system that enhances and supports active participation and thoughtful learning and teaching. Generally, it is agreed that the educator is the most crucial schools or universities- based element in identifying the educational achievements. Although, claims regarding permanent emerging deficiency in educators' abilities and in the quality of learning have often been raised as issues and been considered as having a potentially harmful and direct effect on the educational system as a whole. Even in countries like Switzerland, where educators are generally trusted, there is a recognized need for adjustments to the educational system (Hardmeier and Dell' Ambrogio, 2018). Concerning the effectiveness of the schooling system, there is a broad agreement in regard of the needs for the

adjustments in education and in in-service training (OECD, 2019). Both general and private Algerian schools frequently lack educators trained to work with learners with disabilities (USDS, 2017). Similarly, Boudersa (2016) states that at any stage in the educational personnel, all the time there is a need for educators and the quality of teaching and learning. Both novice teachers and experienced teachers should undertake an ongoing teaching and career advancement trainings determined by schools, universities, any private or cooperating organisation, in order to be encouraged to develop and build themselves in their particular area of specialty, and that will help to influence their teaching practices in the classrooms. Therefore, professional development programs and teachers' training are argued to be major elements in the educators' career advancement and improvement (Germuth, 2018), indeed their ongoing professional development.

Boudersa (2016) highlights that the Algerian universities do not generally involve learners in and provide them with any professional improvement programs and teaching training. Both experienced teachers and future students-teachers take the full responsibility in order to construct themselves as educators, yet, mostly, they encounter challenges and difficulties while they are involved in the job of teaching (Stewart and Jansky, 2022). The challenges faced by novice teachers and pre-service teachers are not solely due to a lack of experience, skills, or preparedness. Instead, these challenges often stem from broader issues within the education system, such as inadequate support, high workloads, and conflicting expectations (Stewart and Jansky, 2022). In most situations, incompetency in the field concerned and the evaluation capacities may lead many beginner teachers to be less confident and might even dislike and criticize the job (Nwoko *et al.*, 2023). As a result, they only stay having a hard time since they do not have any other solution to address their experiences and issues around competencies. Moreover, others may consider teaching as a financially rewarding profession, which they may not leave it under any hard circumstances they may be in. This kind of teachers can be considered as a direct reason for the poor quality of teaching because they do not take any type of development teaching programs that make them well prepared for the difficult tasks of education (Hanushek and Rivkin, 2010).

In contrast to the Algerian universities, the Algerian educators' training schools and colleges offer the future students-teachers with some type of educational training. That educational training firstly begins in the classrooms with students, who are willing to become teachers, to learn various relevant subjects about teaching. Taking the form of the important transmission of knowledge, competence and capacities development, and so forth. For example, within these training

institutions learners of English are educated subjects that will encourage and prepare them to master the language, build aims and learning outcomes in courses, design lectures, increase their understanding concerning the significance of effective warm-up in a lesson, improve skills and mastery of knowledge in particular specialty, and to learn the various techniques and methods used for education and so forth (Boudersa, 2016). In addition to that, there is another type of training that has been organised in the graduation stage and in the context of primary, lower and upper secondary levels, through which learners are involved in educating young students just like their real teachers. Such training takes place in a specific school, and learners are located in real educational settings, and their teaching comes with a tutor to accompany them on their learning journey to become teachers and educators. This type of academic institutions, that are addressed to form new Algerian teachers, provide a big proportion of the system that trains proficient students-teachers who will feel confident and well prepared for the job (Boudersa, 2016).

As stated by Boudersa (2016) a number of occupational advancement and teachers' trainings programmes may be arranged and equipped by different organisations. For instance, in teaching English as foreign language in Algeria, the British Council in Algeria, arranges each year some significant events aimed to gather the Algerian teachers and inform them about modern techniques, strategies, and methods of teaching in regard of various subjects. Additionally, they provide them with useful and updated perceptions that can encourage them in their learning process. Although such moderate efforts help the Algerian teachers to get better knowledge and develop their teaching quality, they continue to remain restricted, not to say ineffective. Further to this, the Algerian academic institutions should make considerable efforts and actions in order to introduce the professional development and teachers training programs. The Algerian Ministry of Higher Education (AMHE) and the Ministry of Education (MA) should help in forming regional and national councils that consists of professionals in a given specialty and educational degree. In order to set up programs of trainings and cooperate with universities and schools to achieve common objective, that is developing and updating the Algerian educational level via quality of teaching and learning.

According to Boudersa (2016), the important aspects which is generally neglected in the universities and schools of Algeria is that educators are allowed to access the job of teaching based on their levels. To take the profession, a teacher can be engaged in a type of contest then he or she

may pass an interview. Yet, no interest is given to the qualifications of teaching, not just for being able to access the job of teaching, but to be prepared and appropriate for this job as well. Furthermore, this lack of qualifications, poor knowledge and deficiency in mastering the subject-matter and educational evaluation competences puts teachers in a hard situation to accommodate themselves and to teach in effective way. Lack of knowledge in regard to the educational program content, lessons plan, division, methods of teaching, classroom organisation, and methods of assessments and so forth, will prevent educators from teaching efficiently and learners from learning effectively. Students' perceptions of their teachers' subject-matter expertise can significantly impact their motivation and confidence. A lack of perceived proficiency can lead to a decline in student engagement and learning outcomes. To address this issue, it is essential to focus on professional development and teacher training programs by working together, educators, schools, universities, and policymakers can create a supportive environment that fosters effective teaching and learning in Algeria.

Presenting the paper, the Minister for National Solidarity, Family, and Women of Algeria, Ghania Eddalia, confirmed that equity before the law and equal opportunities is a right preserved in the legal system of the country. Moreover, all children from the age of six have the right to access to schools. Algeria was aiming to realise the full inclusion of children with special needs, in which 37,000 children with disabilities were incorporated into the educational system, including 32,500 children who were in public schools. In relation to this, there were 61 organisations in different states of the country taken care of 7,551 disabled children (United Nations, 2018). As well as there had been a creation of specialized classrooms, with providing particular help by the Centre for Mental Disabilities, in addition to 232 specialized organizations which give particular supports to disabled children. This commitment was underpinned by a special budget provided by the government to disabled people amount of 10 billion Algerian dinars. In order to facilitate the access to schools for learners with hearing impairments, sign language was being used, and in 2017/2018 the bachelor examination had been allowed to all learners with special needs (United Nations, 2018).

In addition to that, as reported in the United Nations (2018), the professional juries underlined positive information about the laws that preserved the rights of disabled individuals; however, their emphasis was on the significant gap between the laws, policies, and practices. They highlighted that Algeria seemed to confuse the notion of inclusive education with educational integration, in

which they questioned if the critical disability assessment was a human right-based, also whether various practices had been cancelled with the concept of developing consistency and clarity making decisions. A special problem of interest was that over than 7,000 children with disabilities were still in social centres, whereas they could stay with their families and within inclusive settings.

Algeria is considered among the first countries that have confirmed the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities. Over 108,000 parties were engaged and certified by the Ministry of Education, and more than 1,700 parties arranged education to children with special needs like Federations, associations in states or in the capital, and National Unions. Algeria had selected a diverse method that support the incorporation of learners with special needs, namely, learners with visual, and hearing impairments, and learners with Down syndrome and Autism (United Nations, 2018).

According to Bessai (2019), although there are many legitimate provisions that assure education as a right for all children without prejudice in Algeria, a significant delay is noticed in regards of providing care for children with special needs in the real-life situation. Specifically, there is a shortage of materials and resources to support the inclusion of disabled children in mainstream education programs in Algeria. Specialized support services are limited to a small number of general organizations under the control of the Ministry of National Solidarity. Despite the theoretical framework for inclusive education in Algeria, practical implementation has been slow. One of the contributing factors is the lack of robust research on the education of children with disabilities and family practices related to education. This lack of research has created complexities in the development and implementation of effective support systems.

1.4.3 The Algerian Experience of Disabled Children Care Services

In regards of the Algerian experiences of supporting children with disabilities, Bessai (2018) states that despite the huge number of valid provisions that assure the right of education to all children without discrimination, there is a serious delay to encourage disabled children mostly in schools. Similarly, Bessai (2019) claims that the civil institutions are not adequately supplied and organised to face the barriers of inclusive education. The Algerian Ministry National Solidarity (2014) declared that there are 630,000 disabled children, in which only 125,000 among were

supported by some institutions; namely, the National education (10400), special public centres (14532), private integrated classes (1452), and Network (5000). In spite of this, most parents find it challenging, and they are faced with negligence from these centres that are supposed to encourage them, and they feel that they are left alone. According to the same source, this leaves over 9,000 children with disabilities in Algeria waiting for help and assistance.

1.5 Statement of the Problem

This doctoral research addresses the crucial issue facing educational systems (Clark, Dyson and Millward, 2018) in the context of ‘inclusive education’ in Algeria. Educational quality has long been acknowledged to be the foundation for the development of pro-social identity (European Agency for Development in Special Needs Education, 2012). This means that learners have to obtain an education that guarantee their social, professional, and personal development. Nevertheless, this confirmation composes a complicated problem for learners with disabilities who likely to be marginalised. There is general agreement that for students to obtain the chance of receiving quality education their individual context such as their medical, psychological, economic, or social conditions; play a key part and are the main tenet of general education (Allan, 2007). Arib (2021) stresses that the creation of an encouraging inclusive settings in the general schools’ sector have yet to be achieved. The challenge is to overcome the marginalisation of learners with disabilities and break down the common stereotypes that operate as a barrier for students with disabilities to access the general schools. Consequently, if stakeholders desire to meet the needs of all learners, they have to conceive the pre-service training for general educators (Carter and Abawi, 2018).

In Algeria, the education is mandatory and free for all learners aged 6 to 16. Although there exist several legislative provisions ensuring the right of education for all learners without discrimination; there are long-term obstacles to realise these aims for students with disabilities (Bessai, 2018). In one recent study, Boutebal and Yahi (2018) highlighted the significance of working more hardly in order to incorporate learners with disabilities into inclusive schools. The teachers’ perspectives play a great role in identifying the possibility of longstanding success of that effort. Despite of the educational reforms that influenced the teaching methods in the Algerian schools in the last decades; teaching learners with different needs, preferences, background, and

learning styles, is still considered as a hard task on the part of the educators, both veteran and novice ones.

Generally, teachers have to accommodate different types of students and be knowledgeable about their needs. There are a number of students who face difficulties because of special additional needs; hence they may experience many challenges in learning and being successful. Education is extremely important in individuals' life, and all children must have equal opportunities to access education without any discrimination irrespective of their disabilities. Chong, Forlin and Lan (2007) stress that inclusive education does not just mean teaching students with disabilities together with their peers in the same classroom, indeed, it signifies teaching by use of appropriate pedagogy to address the needs of those with learning disabilities

Florian and Pantić (2017) concur that teachers are required to be well trained in order to teach learners with various needs and accept their diversity. This statement guarantees the crucial role of teachers in the formation of new methods that support diversity with minus encountered issues. Likewise, Campbell, Gilmore and Cuskelly (2003) stress that teachers' perceptions of educational needs is crucial in order to create inclusive classrooms. Additionally, it might change the attitudes of teachers to be more positively towards learners who encounter various challenges. Therefore, the significance of conducting this research is that a plethora of several academic research have been carried out in various countries on the subject of teachers' perceptions and experiences towards inclusive (Newton, Cambridge and Hunter-Johnson, 2014; Bursa and Ersoy, 2016; Mngo and Mngo, 2018; Pérez-Jorge et al., 2021; Haji, 2018; and Boitumelo, Kuyini and Major, 2020). The researcher found that there have been no similar studies in relation to the Algerian context. However, teachers' perceptions and experiences towards the inclusion of students with physical and sensory disabilities are very important for an effective inclusive education and meeting the needs of learners. Hence, this doctoral research will support the Algerian educational system and shed light on physical and sensory disabilities through exploring the teacher's perceptions and experiences toward inclusive education in mainstream primary schools.

1.6 Aims of the study

The main aim of this exploratory qualitative research is to examine the teachers' perceptions of and experiences towards the inclusive education of physically and sensory disabled learners in the mainstream primary schools in Algeria. Further to this, the present research seeks to:

- Explore the notion of inclusive education from the general teachers` perspectives.
- Investigate the teachers` knowledge, skills, attitudes, and experiences towards the inclusion of learners with physical and sensory disabilities in Algerian public schools.
- Explore the potential implication for teachers` knowledge, attitudes, and experiences of learners with physical and sensory disabilities in Algeria in relation to the education policy.

1.7 Research Questions

Given the research objectives outlined above, this study will adopt a qualitative research approach. Data will be collected through focus group discussions and individual semi-structured interviews. The following research questions will guide the empirical investigation:

1.7.1 Main Research Question

What are the perceptions, attitudes, and experiences of general teachers concerning the inclusive education of students with physical and sensory disabilities in the Algerian public primary schools?

1.7.2 Sub-research questions

- How do general teachers understand and conceptualize the inclusive education of physical and sensory disabled learners?
- What are the challenges that teachers encounter when teaching students with physical and sensory disabilities in inclusive classes?
- How can these challenges be met to provide an improved inclusion policy for students with physical and sensory disabilities?

1.8 Significance of the study

The present study is important since it provides the ability to benefit societies, education stakeholders and policy makers, teachers, and disabled learners particularly those with physical and sensory disabilities in Algeria. This study will encourage great emphasis on strategic plans for inclusive education and formulating suitable standards in order to direct educators on how to implement inclusive education successfully. This study will generate broader knowledge and practical tips to solve current challenges of inclusive education. It will become a significant source of granting strategies that could change the general educators` views that all learners with special

needs have to be taught in special schools and enhance the efficiency in adopting the inclusive methods. The researcher believed that the outcomes of this study will significantly contribute to the domain of inclusive education of learners with physical and sensory disabilities in Algeria. The results are valuable in which it evaluates the present situation in detail in the context of Algeria particularly in Ammi Mossa City in the province of Relizane. The researcher selected Ammi Mossa City in Relizane province as their study site because it is a rural area, which can offer unique insights into the challenges and opportunities faced by general teachers who work with students with disabilities in rural settings. Relizane is also relatively accessible and representative of the broader Algerian context, making it a suitable choice for this research. Additionally, the results of this research will determine the components and characteristics of a successful inclusive education in this particular context on the basis of the teachers' views, attitudes, feelings, and experiences. The research findings will help the researcher to suggest a procedure of reconstructing and reforming practices and activities in order to ameliorate the inclusive education quality as well as to assure that all physically and sensory disabled learners access education in public schools in Algeria. Moreover, the results of this study will contribute to a better knowledge of inclusive education of physically and sensory disabled learners, in hopes that these results could be used to change the present policies of the inclusive education in Algeria. The researcher is expected that stakeholders and policy makers could use the research outcomes in which it could grant them with insights about the type of services needed for physically and sensory disabled learners and the degree of responsibility that is required from general schools' teachers toward inclusive education. Lastly, it is expected that this research could be a sample for further research in inclusive education in the way that it reveals the possibility and value of utilizing qualitative approach in research, particularly for exploring the perceptions and experiences of educators who try to deliver inclusive education. As opposed to previous research related to this subject which had used quantitative approaches this research adopted an interpretive paradigm (constructivism) in which it investigates what individuals think they do and what they do in reality through (focus group discussion and semi-structured interviews). The current study provides the basis for more research in Algeria in terms of utilizing qualitative methods for data collection including focus group discussion and individual semi-structured interviews.

1.9 Overview of the Research Method

Considering the research questions and the research aims and objectives, the researcher adopted a qualitative approach, and the research is grounded in the interpretive paradigm in which it will scrutinize the participants' interpretations of the social world (Crotty, 2020). Therefore, it is expected that participants could provide valuable data from their experiences in regard of the inclusion of learners with physical and sensory disabilities in the mainstream schools. In contrast with various Algerian research about inclusive education (Arib, 2021; Hoadjli and Latrache, 2020; Hebbali, 2020; Bessai, 2019; and Bessai, 2018).

The study adopted a qualitative approach in order to provide an in-depth understanding of the participants' views and practices of inclusive education of physically and sensory disabled children. The data collection in this research has been done through two steps. The first step, exploratory focus group discussion with general teachers of learners with physical and sensory disabilities. This has been done to explore their perceptions and to gain further understanding about the situation of inclusive education of physically and sensory disabled learners. Considering that, there is a lack of literature about the particular problems impacting inclusive education of physically and sensory disabled learners in the Algerian context, conducting focus group discussion seemed to be useful for giving relevant subjects and questions for the next step.

Additionally, in this study, the focus group discussion provided a general understanding of the context in which its major aim is to develop ideas and generate themes rather than collecting findings (Oppenheim, 1992). The information and data collected from this stage demonstrated particular developments for some of the questions for the individual semi-structured interviews in the second phase of the study. In the second phase, the researcher prepared the questions of the individual semi-structured interviews after examining the initial phase of focus group discussion and after doing extensive reading about relevant literature. Instead of depending on general personal answers indicated by the focus group discussion, the researcher used individual semi-structured interviews in order to gather further in-depth information. The data was recorded on audiotape. All the collected information was analysed by using thematic approach. Themes were formed and derived after in-depth analysis of the participants' perceptions and experiences (Braun and Clarke, 2006). These themes were then classified into sub-themes, as well as a clear connection between the data analysis and research questions were conserved. The participants' answers in the form of quotations were translated from Arabic to English, by consulting professionals in

translation. The researcher used a purposive sampling method. The full sample of this study was 27 participants. The participants were general teachers` who teach learners with physical and sensory disabilities in public primary schools in Relizane province. More details are given in chapter three.

1.10 The Structure of the thesis

The introduction chapter presents an overview of the study and the research problem. this section has extensively explained the research's context. A brief description of the Algerian background, a brief review of the country's educational history, an overview of the Algerian educational system, the education of students with disabilities in Algeria. In addition to the problem statement, with the objectives and significance of the study.

Chapter 2 presents the relevant literature that was examined for this research. It is split up into three parts. To begin with, the researcher defined a number of essential terms related to the research issue at the beginning of this chapter, including a discussion on the ICF and ICF-CY framework as the central idea supporting the current investigation. The final section of this chapter presents the researcher's findings from past studies that are relevant to the current study. This includes the role of teachers in inclusive education, the impact of teachers` perception, attitudes and experiences in inclusive practices, and adaptation in the classroom and throughout the school, as well as pre-service and in-service training for teachers' professional development.

The third chapter addresses the methodology of the study which and discusses in detail the research approach, design, and the methods used in this research. The role of the gatekeeper in granting access to study participants has also been covered in this section. Lastly, this chapter also covers the data analysis process and the importance of ethics in research.

The fourth chapter presents the data analysis and study outcomes. The main themes that developed during the data analysis have been preserved, along with additional conclusions drawn from the literature. The primary themes include teachers` understanding of the concept of inclusive education, teachers` attitudes, experiences, and perceptions of inclusive education, the challenges that Algerian regular primary school teachers face when implementing inclusive education, and teachers` perspectives on methods and strategies to improve inclusive education.

The fifth chapter links the findings of the research to its original research questions, outlines the study's limitations, suggests possible directions for further study, and offers recommendations. Here, conclusions are drawn from the data and suggestions for topics in need of more study are made.

2 Chapter Two: Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

The concept of inclusive education is a key concern for global policymakers, researchers, teachers, and parents alike. At its core, inclusion is rooted in the social constructivist view of schooling (Brčić, Luketić and Petani, 2015), which both acknowledges the varied requirements and backgrounds of all students and identifies the organizational and societal obstacles that limit access to high-quality learning. A body of research consistently shows that achieving successful inclusion is essential for a society committed to equity, equal opportunity, and appreciating diversity (Evans and Lunt, 2002). Even with broad international agreement on its fundamental aims, the literature reveals that the concept of inclusion remains an active area of academic study, especially regarding the specific methods through which classrooms can effectively implement it (Azorín and Ainscow, 2018; Tharp, 2018).

This chapter aims to establish the theoretical, political, and practical context for the present study. Literature review is an integral part of this process, enabling the researcher to define the research problems and consider what previous researchers have learned about issues of disability, exclusion in education, pedagogic policy and practice, and inclusive education. The specific purpose of conducting this review, therefore, is two-fold: to obtain a better grasp of the subject and to learn about other countries' practices in order to assimilate what Algeria could potentially learn from them in developing and improving its own inclusive education framework.

The chapter is organized into six primary segments: The first Section (this introductory overview) sets the stage and outlines the chapter structure; the second Section will establish the core terminology by reviewing the historical and conceptual shift from integration to inclusion. Following that, the third Section will review the international rights-based policies that mandate inclusion. Furthermore, Section four will establish the critical terminology, conceptualizations, and scope of language used in this thesis. Moving to the fifth section which will examine the Critical Models of Disability. Finally, the concluding sections will conduct an evidence-based review of the three critical frontline components—teacher disposition, pedagogical strategies, and systemic barriers—that mediate the success of inclusion for children with physical and sensory disabilities.

2.2 The Conceptual Shift: From Integration to Inclusion

2.2.1 Integration

According to Education and Skills Committee (2005) the word integration was first presented in the Warnock Report 1978 which referred to the notion of integrating students with special educational needs into an ordinary schools' systems. The notion has already developed to the inclusion of all students to express the concept that it is not for learners with special educational needs to be in some way integrated into general schools but that education in general should be completely inclusive for all students. Likewise, Rodriguez and Garro-Gil (2015) defines Integration as the practice of providing equal access to education for students with and without disabilities, ensuring that all learners have the opportunity to participate in mainstream classrooms and benefit from a shared learning environment.

Moreover, Fish (1985) describes integration as a process of active participation and interaction within a community, involving ongoing communication with others and the freedom to join different groups. Additionally, Rispen (1994) states that each part of integration such as definition, goals, motives, and stages, reveals a huge difference in practice. This difference causes the difficulty in drawing general results and improving an extensive perception of integration. Furthermore, Warnock Mary (1978) claims that integration refers to a learner's presence at a less isolated framework than specialist institutions, for instance either a mainstream setting or a special education class in mainstream schools. This refers to the general perception and explanation of integration which was introduced firstly by (Warnock, 1978), as there were three forms of integration. Firstly, social integration where social ordinary communication appears during breaks time, extracurricular tasks, family gathering, leisure time and after-school clubs, yet students with special educational needs are educated differently. Secondly, locational integration where students with disabilities are educated at the public settings as nondisabled students but in particular special units or classes. Finally, functional integration where students with special educational needs take part in regular classes and follow the national educational programme (Garner, 2009).

In terms of the Warnock's classifications, locational proximity is essential, yet it is a scant starting step, since placing all students together for some time in the same classes, dining room, or playground area is insufficient itself to enhance functional or social integration. Likewise, learners with special educational needs who are educated in isolated special classes in a regular mainstream

school can have limited chances. Additionally, Beveridge, (1999) criticized the Warnock's hierarchical perception of integration that it has become noticeable that functional and social integration have to be viewed as connected. This means, if students with special educational needs are expected to improve active and continual relationships with their classmates, so it is possibly to involve their participation together in prepared cooperative learning tasks.

According to Hornby (2001), integration is an approach relying on the medical model that focuses on the learners' demands and strengths. Consequently, integration presents several forms of exclusion for learners with disabilities because it focuses on the location and placement of the disabled student while integration is a responsibility of parent and children (Evans and Lunt, 2002) which are supposed to fit and adjust in without the need of schools' adaptations (Mittler, 2012). Furthermore, Frederickson and Cline (2002) have stated that integration is also about preparing basic plans for students with special needs at regular settings, which can be a theme of equivalent and legal access discourse. Additionally, Barton (1988) defined integration as a conception connected to the medical model of the perception of disability and special education, which suggests the right of accessing to the closest regular schools. Therefore, Lewis and Doorlag (1995) claim that the concepts of integration and mainstream were used to indicate that individuals with disabilities have to be integrated in ordinary mainstream education without any adjustment of the educational program to support cooperation. Likewise, Ainscow (1995) stated that integration is related to forming a restricted number of plans for learners with special educational needs in schools.

2.2.2 Inclusion

It is important to distinguish between the terms "integration" and "inclusion". The term inclusion has currently replaced the word integration as the concept which refers to individual rights concerning the education of children with disabilities and learning difficulties. That is the critical point in the use of the word "inclusion" as introduced by (UNESCO, 1994) with the Salamanca Declaration. Deiner (2009) states that there is one issue with inclusion in which there are many descriptions of that term. In relation to this, Ainscow, Booth and Dyson (2006) reveal that there are various definitions of the word inclusion by different members according to their backgrounds. Topping and Maloney (2005) define the term inclusion as a general concept that refers to the admission of all individuals in community. Additionally, Enock (2011) describes inclusion in a

broad meaning as a primary right of individuals. Whereas the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Educational Organization (UNESCO) (2005) explains inclusion from its educational views, as a system of forwarding and replying to the variety of needs of all students via rising cooperation in cultures, communities and learning. On the other hand, decreasing exclusion from and within education requires a set of transformations and adjustments in format, content, procedures, and methods, alongside a universal perception that caps all infants of the relevant age range and a confidence that it is the duty of the formal scheme to educate all infants. Furthermore, Salend (2008) explains inclusion as a philosophy that gather learners, families, societies to establish schools based on general perspectives. He claims that inclusion spotlights on different types of students and not only on disability. Additionally, it is a demonstration of variety in the classroom where ordinary and disabled students are respected equitably. Moreover, according to Daniels (1999) inclusion means bringing all learners into the same setting and learning the same lectures, and reciprocal existence. However, the Ministry of Education (2012) understands inclusion as a (set of) procedure(s) of modifying the setting to hold students with special educational needs counting disabled learners, as well as providing chances for all students to enter school equitably.

More than that, Forlin *et al* (2013) state that inclusion in education assigns to a primary individual right and the basis for more impartial and identical community. Likewise, QianTang (2017) claims that inclusion is becoming proactive in determining the difficulties that students face in trying to get chances for equitable education, and in eliminating those obstacles and difficulties which cause the exclusion. Further to this, inclusion is a system that conquers the obstacles hindering the cooperation, attendance, and success of students. In addition, Sebba and Ainscow (1996) describe inclusion as a system where schools try to reply to all learners by reviewing its educational programmes arrangements. That looks like a great important manner of defining the concept of inclusion, or at least a few prospects of it, because it describes inclusion as a continued practice and not a case. Furthermore, it highlights that all learners have to be included and not only some learners. Another point from this definition that it limits the responsibility of ordinary local education in doing a review for its systems and arrangements to accommodate learners with special needs which can be seen as a matter of placing. Similarly, Dreyer (2017) states that the concept of inclusive pedagogy discusses the defects of the earlier conceptions through involving all segments of a global policy, that is to say, all students, teachers, educational needs, evaluation and pedagogy.

Moreover, Hayes and Bulat (2017) state that inclusion means that all learners are sincerely participated in learning. However, not only through their presence at regular school but it is more essential to learn together (O'Brien, 2001). So, this involves being appreciated and accepted, fully engagement for more achievement, which rely on the reorganization of ordinary schools to improve functional methods which help all learners (Ainscow, 2005). Nutbrown and Clough (2006) concur that inclusion is a method of learning and inclusive standards instead of an interest with special team of young individuals and infants. Furthermore, Ainscow, Booth and Dyson (2006) present resources to encourage cooperation and education. Additionally, Booth *et al* (2002) state that this encouragement is interpreted as all tasks given to all learners, in addition to those presumed to be co-curricular or extracurricular, which raise the capacity of schools to reply to variation.

Moreover, Farrell (2003) claims that learners are described by another aspects in addition to their special educational needs. For instance, social disadvantage, ethnic group, gender, or family background which are crucial in defining and realizing students' needs. In general, Cooper and Jacobs (2011) state that the term inclusion is usually defined as the system by which an institution seeks to improve the meaning of academic and social collaboration, in order to realize the social, individual, and personal educational needs of all learners (Ainscow, 2005). McMahon et al. (2016) elaborates and identifies four factors which should be convinced in order for a learner to be counted as "included", namely, social inclusion, academic inclusion, organizational inclusion, as well as assessment and planning for inclusion. According to McMahon et al. (2016) social inclusion refers to the process that encourage learners with special educational needs in their socialization as well as support and give them chances to interact with different ordinary students. Moreover, McMahon et al. (2016) define the academic inclusion as method that allow learners with special educational needs to totally collaborate in academic tasks in the inclusive settings with all learners. Likewise, it refers to a learner's capacity to participate in classroom conversations (Olsson, Dag and Kullberg, 2017). Additionally, Olsson, Dag and Kullberg (2018) describe it as assuring that all learners get the fundamental education, they need to utilize their complete personal capacity. Furthermore, McMahon et al. (2016) state that assessment and planning for inclusion requires evaluating the learner's needs, aims, and capacities. Which means, they proposed to consider the personal diversity among learners and to give them relevant academic help assistance, instead of waiting for learners to adapt by their own to the academic setting. According to Kubat (2018)

personal diversity between learners includes differences like gender, intelligence, physical characteristics, interest, capacity, personality traits, perception, and learning styles. Finally, McMahon et al. (2016) explain organizational inclusion as school-wide processes which demonstrate the valuation of all learners over school-wide organizational intentions, for instance team and educators' commitment to inclusive practices, leadership support, organizational resources, and staff progress.

Booth et al. (2002) describe an overlap between the concept of integration and most recent perception of inclusion. In fact, these words are occasionally utilized interchangeably (Thomas, Walker and Webb, 2006), especially so in the arab countries such as Saudi Arabia, and Egypt in which the single arabic word “دمج- damg” is used to translate both terms “integration” and “inclusion”; as well as it is the same in the Algerian context. It could be said that although the terms integration and inclusion are mostly used inter-changeably, yet there is a clear difference between them. To begin, inclusion is the educational process that allows the full placement of students with different disabilities in general schools. In this system, the school changes to accommodate all learners' needs. It provides equal opportunities for all students as well as supports participation of disabled learners alongside their ordinary peers through eliminating all attitudinal and environmental barriers. This approach does not focus only on disabled learners but nondisabled as well. It acknowledges learners' diversity and uses various methods to benefit all learners. Therefore, this is why inclusion is considered as education for all as well as the best option. On the other hand, Integration is an approach of education in which learners with special needs are involved in the regular schools. In this system, various services, techniques, and adapted methods are used. Accordingly, usually these are more formal structures which seek to help the learner to accommodate into the mainstream schools. Although, this system aims at meeting the needs of disabled students, yet this could raise classification of learners because of pre-existing Constructions and beliefs. The current study refers to the concept of inclusion.

2.2.3 Inclusive Education and its Defining Principles

Educational institutions are, of course, not homogeneous and isolated systems, but indeed reflect the diversity of society as a whole. This includes the students' linguistic and cultural variables, as well as their developmental capacities (Florian, 2016). Sahli and Benaiss (2019) state that inclusive

pedagogy is a crucial factor which can address and assure equal educational opportunities for all learners with different profiles. Florian (2015) claims that there is no precise understanding for the concept of inclusive pedagogy. Whereas the notion could be practiced in various situations and contexts. In addition, Ginsberg and Wlodkowski (2009) define inclusive pedagogy as a program which has the ability to gather all students into a setting that acknowledge diversity and encourage respect between all members, controlled by teaching techniques which transform an exclusive culture as well as adopt other disciplines since they contribute to an inclusive culture. Besides, Sahli and Benaiss (2019), reveal that in inclusive pedagogy it is very important to realize the diversity among learners. In this view, Florian (2015) states that differences are not seen either as barriers to regular mainstream schools, or as stigmatized concept where learners with diversity are in need of particular or further help. On the contrary, it is viewed as an advantage where there is a plan of varied disciplines which assure efficient learning opportunities for all students with various capacities (Spratt and Florian, 2013). Corbett (2001) describes inclusive pedagogy as a concern of the whole educational scheme; including, the school culture which recognizes the diversity among learners as well as their personal needs. Ainscow and Sandill (2010) concur and state that inclusive pedagogy has to do with continuous receptivity, in order to deal with various barriers that arise in multi-cultural settings (Corbett and Slee, 2000) in which there may be any linguistic challenges to education as well as collaboration (Booth, 2000).

Furthermore, the first turning point for the perception of the rights of equivalent education for learners with disabilities was in the Salamanca Statement and Framework for Action on Special Needs Education. The major determination emphasizes on the right to access education for all individuals, discrimination could be solved when schools support inclusive policies, so as result inclusive practices will promote educational opportunities for all learners (United Nations Educational and Science, 1994).

According to Ras (2008) inclusive education is a system of enhancing the cooperation of all learners in classroom settings, considering those students with disabilities, as well as it is about reforming the practices, strategies, and cultures in institutions as a result they reply to the learners` diversity in their background. Moreover, Stofile (2008) defines it as an instrument of increasing educational convenience to a distinct scope of marginal learners all over the world who are still not able to access schools. Ebersold and Watkins (2011) agree that inclusive education could be explained as the participation, attendance, and success of all students in ordinary schools.

Furthermore, Tabane (2009) claims that inclusive education is interested in putting all students together in a classroom context from different veins in a collective learning setting, regardless to their capacities. Similarly, it is concerned with the help that students with different needs should obtain and maintain to deal with all students equally. Besides, the UK Department of Education (2001) defines it as an education which is equitable in terms of cultures, gender, disability or other forms of students or team which are selected by community. It requires all students in a society without exceptions and regardless to their intellectual, sensory, physical or alternative diversity, to have identical rights to ordinary schools. Moreover, it is a process of enhancing the collaboration and capacity of each single student, irrespective of gender, age, races, class, language, HIV status, and disability. According to Schuelka (2018) it is described as children without and with disabilities who are learning together in general pre-schools provision, colleges, schools and faculties with relevant support. The centre's viewpoint is that prosperous schools view all students as lawful representative of the institution they would show up, and the classes which they hope to participate, if they do not have disability.

In summary, although there is no single explanation for the concept of inclusive education, the general perception that all the definitions of inclusive education agreed on is that education is a human right, as well as all students have to be included and educated in the regular schools regardless of their diversity. Added to that, it means the practice of responding and addressing the intellectual, physical, emotional, and social needs of learners with different disabilities in public schools with nondisabled and same-aged peers. Consequently, in the current study inclusive education refers to the learning environment that promotes a complete professional, personal, and educational progress of all students irrespective of their disabilities by providing education that meets the needs of all students through enhancing participation in learning, and decreasing or removing exclusion from education, as well as providing appropriate assistance and support. More specifically, in the context of this study, inclusive education refers to the process of providing students with physical and sensory disabilities in Algerian mainstream schools equal educational opportunities through flexible methods and techniques of teaching, curricular adaptation that meets with all learners needs.

2.3 The Rights-Based Mandate for Inclusive Education

The conceptual shift toward inclusion is supported by a comprehensive international legal and policy infrastructure that frames education as a fundamental human right.

2.3.1 The UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD)

The UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD) (United Nations, 2006) stands as the most critical contemporary legal standard for inclusion. Article 24 specifically addresses education, mandating the right to inclusive education at all levels without discrimination and on the principle of equal opportunity. Crucially, Article 24 requires States Parties to ensure the system provides reasonable accommodation and necessary supports within the general education environment (Flynn, 2019). A critical review of the UNCRPD highlights a policy dilemma: While the inclusive mandate is immediate, its achievement is often subjected to the legal concept of "progressive realization". This allows states to implement changes gradually based on resource availability. This clause is frequently criticized in scholarly work as an administrative justification for slow implementation, enabling many nations to retain segregated special education systems years after ratification, thereby denying the immediate right to inclusion for many children (Freeman, 2011).

2.3.2 Children's Right to Voice and Participation (UNCRC Article 12)

The principles of the UNCRPD are closely linked with the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC) (United Nations General Assembly (UNCRC), 1989), particularly Article 12, which mandates the right of the child to freely express their views on all matters affecting them and to have those views seriously considered (Lundy, 2007). Within inclusive education, Article 12 requires that classroom rules, curriculum design, and intervention planning must be informed by the perspectives of the students with disabilities themselves. International literature, however, often criticizes the practical failure of superficiality where children are consulted primarily to validate pre-determined adult decisions highlighting a persistent implementation gap (Hart, 1992). The enduring critical challenge lies in the methodological difficulties: developing reliable, ethical,

and genuine methods to capture the voices of children who communicate non-verbally or who have complex learning needs (Nind and Swann, 2019) .

2.4 Critical Terminology and Conceptual Scope

The vocabulary employed in disability research is never impartial; it inherently reflects and strengthens foundational philosophical frameworks (Andrews, Powell and Ayers, 2022). Consequently, this thesis establishes a clearly defined, consistent, and critically informed terminology that will be used throughout the subsequent chapters.

2.4.1 Ethical Language and the Critique of 'Normality'

Ethical academic inquiry necessitates the use of coherent and theoretically justified language. This study is dedicated to maintaining Person-First Language, specifically employing the term "child with a disability" rather than phrasing like "impaired child" or other deficit-oriented terminology. This deliberate linguistic choice directly supports the Social Model of Disability (Grech *et al.*, 2023), challenging the medicalized viewpoint that makes impairment the defining feature of an individual, and thus aligning with the philosophical mandate for inclusion outlined in the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (United Nations, 2006).

Furthermore, a key principle of this research involves rejecting the concepts of 'normal' or 'typical' when referencing students who do not have disabilities. These terms are rooted in an ableist ideology, which posits a single, superior standard of human function and automatically classifies difference as a deficit (Shapiro, 2011). Employing such language unintentionally maintains the systemic barriers this research seeks to address (Rapp, 2018). Instead of 'normal,' this study will consistently utilize the neutral and descriptive phrase "non-disabled peers" to refer to students in general education settings, thereby recognizing that diversity is the natural state within any learning context. The regular use of this terminology highlights the critical orientation of this thesis toward achieving systemic inclusion.

2.4.2 Distinguishing Inclusive Education (Macro) and Pedagogy (Micro)

To accurately connect the gap between official policy and the practical realities of the classroom, it's crucial to draw a conceptual line between Inclusive Education and Inclusive Pedagogy. Though interconnected, these terms describe two distinct domains of reform:

- **Inclusive Education (Macro-Level):** This term denotes the structural, systemic, and policy-driven framework adopted at the governmental and district levels (Ainscow, 2020). It covers policy requirements (such as the UNCRPD), allocation of resources, the underlying rights-based philosophy, and the overall administrative organization of the educational system. Essentially, it addresses whether a system is adequately configured to accept all learners (Booth and Ainscow, 2011).
- **Inclusive Pedagogy (Micro-Level):** This refers to the flexible, evidence-based, and specific instructional methods implemented by educators inside the learning environment (Florian, 2014). It represents the functional, instructional execution of inclusive philosophy, focusing on curriculum planning (e.g., Universal Design for Learning, or UDL), methods of differentiation, modifying assessment, and the overall quality of engagement between the teacher and the students (Florian, 2014).
- **Critical Rationale for the Thesis**

Many systems assert adherence to the philosophy of Inclusive Education (policy) but frequently fail to provide educators with the skills required for effective Inclusive Pedagogy (practice) (Ainscow and Sandill, 2010). This thesis is primarily dedicated to investigating this implementation gap by examining teachers' perceptions and experiences concerning their capability to successfully deliver Inclusive Pedagogy (Suleymanov, 2015), thus creating a vital link between systemic reform (macro) and practical classroom challenges (micro).

2.5 Critical Models of Disability in Educational Contexts

The specific model of disability utilized by an education system or individual instructor significantly dictates the allocation of funding, the choice of intervention strategies, and the overall perspectives held by teachers. A critical examination of these prevailing models highlights the

constant tension between the need for clinical support and the necessity of systemic accountability. In the context of the present study, investigating how society constructs disability is crucial for exploring the position of the Algerian society on the educational services provided for learners with disabilities. Particularly, the researcher intends to investigate the position of the Algerian general educators on the educational system provided for learners with physical and sensory disabilities. This investigation is therefore located within the biopsychosocial paradigm, which guides the chapter discussion and provides an understanding into the perceptions, attitudes, and experiences of general educators toward inclusive education.

2.5.1 The Medical Model

According to Massoumeh and Jamshidi (2012) the medical paradigm is based on the perspective that all the issues around the needs of students in relation to inclusive education are the consequences of some biological deficiency or malady. Most of those who support the medical paradigm advocate that there must be ordinary deliberation between medical and educational organization in proper manners about learning and taking care of individuals with special needs (Purdie and Ellis, 2005). Peter (2004), cited in Dreyer (2017), states that the medical paradigm concentrates on the person deficit theory. It detects and classifies the deficit within the student then determines corrective mediations for instance, medicine, surgery, therapy, or special treatment (like adjusting the educational program) which is granted within an isolated classroom. Likewise, Dreyer (2008) argues that this model professionalizes diversity and disability to the extent that regular school educators do not feel themselves as proficient and adequate to educate students with different learning needs. Whereas, it has to be recognized that there are intrinsic challenges (like weak eyesight) which medical interference is able to treat or give help (Dreyer, 2017). Anastasiou and Kauffman (2011) explain that the medical paradigm views the disability as a result of a person's loss in organic action and is an organic issue which needs a medical treatment (Owens (2015).

According to Vehmas (2004) the medical paradigm affirms that disability is an organic problem, and as this deficiency is within the person, so that issue has to or can be adjusted, supporting the individual to be capable to participate in the community. Moreover, the disability is viewed as abnormal in the medical paradigm, it assumes a major aim of the person to be treated so he or she

can become ordinary (Kearney and Kane, 2006). As cited in Anastasiou and Kauffman (2011), Oliver claims that the medical model hypothesizes psychological and physiological aspects are the main sources of a disability. However, it denies other elements that can influence the person and the manner he or she interacts with the society. Additionally, Goodley as cited in Hodge and Haegele (2016) states that this model only regards that the disability is a consequence of the body malfunction.

According to Shyman (2016) the medical paradigm is dependent on the treatment of the disability as well as being with the individual. Accordingly, the requirement for medicine has to be subscribed from an extraneous expert like a therapist or a doctor. Moreover, Anastasiou and Kauffman, (2011) claim that this paradigm imposes borders of who does the treatment as well as who requires to be treated. This view unintentionally influences the way a community sees the disability. Further to this, Shyman (2016) states that community views disability as a misery, disadvantage, and something a person has to go through as his or her nature of life is with restricted opportunities. Additionally, the medical paradigm developed emotional responses of empathy, reservation, and compassion. It maintains social deviation, changing social beliefs, as well as creating bad perspectives that empower segregation and prejudiced actions, for instance, labelling and stereotyping. Similarly, Hodge and Haegele (2016) argues that social attitudes are great obstacles for disabled people, though the medical model endures to take leadership in deciding what is regular and what is not. All in all, Naraian and Schlessinger (2017) state that the medical paradigm encourages the special education which views to support negative beliefs of the institutions toward disability. As arrangement in the special classes in are dependent on a learner's diagnosis, special education endures to improve perspectives of disability being pathetic, abominable. As a consequence, it is more excluding and abusing learners with disabilities.

2.5.2 The Social Model

The social model has a different understanding of disability. So, as a reply to the medical model, Anastasiou and Kauffman (2011) state that the social model divided the perceptions of disability and impairment. The term disability was defined as the prejudice or limitation of action produced by current institutions. Whereas the impairment of a person is commonly described as a body deficiency or flaw. As cited in Hodge and Haegele (2016) the social paradigm acknowledges that the organic impairment is not the description factor or prevalent feature of the individual, and that

the community is neglecting or is less considering disabled people. As a result, limiting their collaboration in the society. According to Beaudry (2016) the social paradigm proposes that the social abuse and preconceptions cause the disability, a result of community to impairment which afterwards introduce environmental challenges, injustice, as well as maltreatment. According to Booth (2000) the social paradigm refers that challenges to learning, and collaboration are generated by community and formulated to help the concern of most learners, by that restricting accessibility for others. Additionally, individuals who do not harmonize to the assumptions of the majority's prospects of behaviours, appearance, and economic performance are then punished (Gillespie *et al.*, 2005).

In a similar manner, Dreyer (2017) argues that this model identifies the existence of integral challenges to education and development. Moreover, UNESCO (2020) state that within inclusive educational practices it is very important to determine and eliminate these obstacles in order to support equivalent collaboration for all individuals as well as to remove segregation.

Likewise, Owens (2015) argues that, through the social paradigm lens, the community causes the disability by social and physical obstacles. In relation to this, Kattari, Lavery and Hasche (2017) claim that the social model does not see the impairment as a disease that has to be cured, yet it affirms that the activities of the community cause the disability by the reduction of adjustment. Additionally, Hodge and Haegele (2016) argue that the social paradigm does not consider people with disabilities as abnormal, yet it views them as different. Indeed, Forlin and Loreman (2014) argues that the society can adapt the surrounding conditions thus individuals with disabilities are not rejected. Besides that, the social paradigm of disability could be employed to help individuals to comprehend and figure out that the disability should not be seen as a weakness and failure (Shakespeare, 2013). This prospect may result in developed comprehension and acceptance of individuals with disabilities in the society. Similarly, Rieser (2012) claims that the issue of disability cannot simply be solved by treating disabled people. Whereas it can be overcome through the reorganization of the society and eliminating the obstacles that disabled people facing in their daily life. According to Naraian and Schlessinger (2017) the social paradigm encourages inclusive education in which it supports the cooperation of all people with disabilities and that coincides with the perspective of inclusive education. Moreover, Terzi (2014) states that the social paradigm frequently pursuits to reform community through eliminating environmental challenges and that is an additional motive for how this paradigm has support inclusive education.

Accordingly, inclusive education arose in regard to inclusion in community, both searching to provide equivalent opportunities to all, irrespective of disability. In addition to that, Naraiian and Schlessinger (2017) argue that inclusion does not concentrate on the person deficiency which supports accommodation. However, it encourages a set of physical and learning diversity. Collaboration in schools' settings is not restrained to defined approach to educational program or through physical obstacles, whereas inclusion seeks to eliminate all handicapping aspects in an academic context. Therefore, udclaim that this can be realized through changing stairs with elevators, integrating attainable bathrooms, transportation and sporting equipments into schools system, as well as developping educational program to encourage all learners. In comparaiso to the special educational centers where learners with disabilities are isolated from their ordinary peers, inclusive education supports the improving of collaboration and diminishing exclusion in all perspectives of schools life (Rees, 2017). To conclude, the target of inclusive education is to eliminate all obstacles that limited the access of learners with disabilities to equivalent educational opportunities, that coincides with the social model views in adjusting the environment in order to adapt these leaners and support the collaboration and access to the society (Jenson, 2018).

From the above review concerning the explanation of the medical and social models of disability, we conclude that the perspectives of the social paradigm align with the concept of inclusive education. In which they both seek to change the school environments and attitudes where all learners can have equal learning opportunities, as well as they encourage participation for all students irrespective to their disabilities. However, though the social paradigm has many positive views, yet its corroboration denies the lived experiences or the reality of individuals with disabilities. In addition, in spite of the social paradigm`s disagreement with the medical paradigm, but the medicalization of disability still very important for an individual with impairment. Although the objective of the social paradigm is to empower disabled learners through breaking down the environmental obstacles and the negative attitudes towards individual with disabilities, the medical paradigm should not be dismissed completely, because it is not an enemy of individuals with disabilities, but its views and principles support them in various way. In order to understand, therefore, the complexity of experiences of people with disabilities, it is important that the medical and social models are considered, which is what the biopsychosocial model does.

2.5.3 The Biopsychosocial Model

George Engle was the first who suggested the biopsychosocial paradigm of disability in 1980. This paradigm goes along with a view that combines the medical and social models of disability. In other words, this model recognizes that an individual impairment, discrimination, and adverse social factors are affecting aspects for the disability (Penney, 2013). Moreover, the medical model emphasises that the person impairments that differentiate him or her from ordinary non-disabled people cause the disability. Whereas the social paradigm suggests that the social omission and prejudice toward individuals with disabilities are the main reason for the disability. Therefore, the biopsychosocial model seeks to combine both the medical and social paradigms through introducing a composed method. Additionally, it constructs a further extensive and integrated conception towards disability, by incorporating factors from the medical as well as the social paradigms (Bath *et al.*, 2014). Thus, this paradigm suggests that the disability is a result of biological or physical problems that have to be cured by medical professionals. Additionally, the community has to identify procedures in order to incorporate individuals with disabilities in political, social, and economic activities through providing support as well as equal opportunities. Accordingly, this paradigm based on evidence that the disability is a cooperation between three main aspects namely, psychological factors like behaviour, social factors for instance, cultural and social environments, and physical factors such as gender and age. Furthermore, it has to be recognized that the biopsychosocial paradigm creates the foundation of the World Health organization's International Classification of Functioning, Disability, and Health since it is presuming to imply a further inclusive regulation process to define disability in various status and contexts which includes both personal and social contexts (Bath *et al.*, 2014). Gatchel (2015) states that the biopsychosocial model stresses on the fact that the disability is not only a result of impairments or pathophysiological causes, yet it is a consequence of lifestyle as well as psychosocial aspects. Therefore, this perspective partially disagrees with the social and medical models since it considers that those paradigms are not complete. Moreover, Gatchel *et al* (2014) claims that clinical researchers, academics, and practitioners follow the biopsychosocial paradigm in order to recognize and deal with injury problems, as well as prejudiced problems resulting from psychological, social, and biological aspects in a good manner.

According to Shakespeare, Watson and Alghaib (2016) the biopsychosocial paradigm of disability originally evolved by George Engle in the 1970's, he established the principles for a modern

developed paradigm by Waddell and Aylward, it was utilized as theoretical framework to redefine the disability in the UK (2016). Furthermore, the biopsychosocial paradigm of disability by Waddell and Aylward intend to explain a multifactorial perspective on disability through combining factors altogether for instance, social changes which include work adjustments, medical and relevant professional care, as well as personal attempt from individuals with disabilities (Hussey *et al.*, 2015). Likewise, the model of George Engle, the recent paradigm by Waddell and Aylward created a connection between the medical and social paradigms, as they viewed both models as incomplete. Waddell and Aylward viewed the social paradigm as biased, since it is based only on the personal perspectives, perceptions, and experiences of individual with disabilities, and denying the scientific facts. As well as they viewed the medical paradigm as very simplistic (Shakespeare, Watson and Alghaib, 2016). They argue that though the medical experts (chief medical officer and orthopaedic surgeon) managed to merge the personal (internal) and external (such as work and society) aspects in their paradigm, this serves the government to improve instruments to encourage practices, infrastructure, policies, and individuals with disabilities who encountered challenges because of their disabilities, particularly in accessing and finding jobs. Thus, at this point, it should be noticed that there is a probability that not all individuals with disabilities are able to completely collaborate in community or get access to employment, since that rely on how extreme their disabilities are. On the other hand, Petasis (2019) claims that the community themselves have to find solutions to prohibit stigmatizing disabled people and to encourage them in all ways to bypass miserable living situations and social segregation. Furthermore, the biopsychosocial model's influence on the employment prospects of individuals with disabilities remains a complex and evolving area of study. This relatively new paradigm, which considers the interplay of biological, psychological, and social factors, offers a broader perspective on disability and its implications for employment. While its specific outcomes are still being explored, it is anticipated that the biopsychosocial model's emphasis on these interconnected factors may lead to more effective strategies for supporting individuals with disabilities in the workplace.

The biopsychosocial model constitutes a credible universal definition of disability as pursued by the World Health Organization (WHO), and the International Classification of Functioning, Disability, and Health (ICF). The latter comprises a collection of explanations and authorizes the role of community to be integrated in all clarifications (Shakespeare, Watson and Alghaib, 2016).

To conclude, despite the different views between the social and medical approaches towards the explanation of disability, yet they are still considered as essential to explain the disability, as well as they might be regarded as different views with the same interest.

Besides that, the biopsychosocial model suggests that the educational system has to examine the disabled learner's environment first, then do adjustments based on the learner's needs. Thus, the focal point is on the participation of the student that arise out of the interaction between biological and environmental factors (Norwich, 2008). This paradigm considers the complicated character of people with small adjustment, it is a good instrument for educators who are on the first lines of behaviour interpretation in the classrooms (Reisinger, 2014). Likewise, Griffiths and Gardner (2002) claim that this model consistently examine psychological, social, and biological factors beside their complicated interactions. The psychological factors comprise of cognitive and emotional developmental. The social circumstances comprise of interpersonal, culture, family, environmental physical issues that could impact their behaviour, and school programs. The biological factors comprise of psychiatric, neurological, and medical circumstances that could result behaviour.

2.5.4 International Classification of Functioning, Disability, and Health (ICF)

In comparison to the medical model, the biopsychosocial model was first proposed in the late 1970s to provide a more comprehensive overview to understand disability and impairment. It considers that an individual's well-being is influenced by their disability's biological, psychological, and social reactions. It accepts both medical and social therapies as legitimate for addressing disability, and none is rejected as a type of intervention (World Health organization, 2002). According to the approach, an educational system should examine the disabled learner's environment and create modifications in accordance with the needs of the individual student. Consequently, the emphasis is on the learner's engagement, which is the result of the combination of biological and environmental elements (Norwich, 2008). As a result of its theorization, the WHO (World Health Organization) implemented the approach as the model for defining disabilities in the 2001 International Classification of Functioning, Disability, and Health (ICF). In presenting the ICF, the World Health Organization wanted to include all dimensions of

individuals' health as well as aspects of well-being that are related to health, such as to have real relationships and receive good education (Hollenweger, 2014). Moreover, the biopsychosocial paradigm underpins the ICF, which incorporates elements of both the medical and social models. According to Hollenweger (2014), the ICF views disability and functioning as the outcome of complicated interactions among social, biological, as well as psychological aspects. Additionally, the ICF acts as a foundation for developing the lives of disabled individuals through offering a shared language for studying the interaction of these components

2.5.4.1 International Classification of Functioning, Disability, and Health for children and youth (ICF-CY)

The WHO (World Health Organization) developed the ICF (International Classification of Functioning, Disability, and Health) with its edition ICF-CY (for children and youth), which is an international model for understanding concepts of health, functioning, and disability specific to children and youth. The ICF-CY has been developed from the former ICF in order to address the needs of youth under the age of 18 (World Health Organization, 2013). Simeonsson (2009) who worked on the development of the ICF-CY, sees it as a newly developed approach and classification of individuals' functioning and disability that may be utilised to drive comprehensive and multidisciplinary methods to intervention and evaluation. The use of a dimensional framework makes it relevant to intervention and evaluation procedures in inclusive and special education. Unlike the medical model, the ICF-CY defines disability from a biopsychosocial standpoint (World Health Organization, 2007), offering a comprehensive overview for examining childhood functioning and environments in order to determine the needs of individuals with disabilities (Hellblom-Thibblin, Klang and Åman, 2012). Therefore, in contrast to the medical paradigm, the ICF-CY framework considers the psychological, biological, social, and environmental aspects that impact disability (Dahl, 2002). In reality, the ICF and ICF-CY view disability and functioning as a multi-dimensional interaction between health issues, personal, and environmental factors.

In this thesis, the researcher argues that the ICF-CY has the ability to help the Algerian educational system by providing information and support, as well as improving the implementation of inclusive education for disabled children. Particularly, this study will explore how the ICF-CY paradigm might enhance inclusive education for learners with disabilities within its fundamental

elements: activities and participation, body functions and structures, environmental and personal factors, using learners with physical and sensory disabilities as an example.

2.5.4.2 The Impact of the ICF-CY Framework on Inclusive Education

The ICF-CY was created from the ICF in order to better comprehend disability issues that are special to supporting children and young people and may be utilised generally in healthcare, education, and social sectors (World Health Organization, 2007). The ICF-CY model is divided into two sections firstly contextual factors that includes personal variables/internal factors (for instance gender, age, and intellectual level) and environmental variables /external factors (such as social attitudes, policies and legislation). Secondly, functioning and disability. This part comprises of activities and participation, in addition to functions and structures such as tasks and activities (World Health organization, 2002). The ICF-CY framework comprises a number of categories and fields that correlate to each component. Each component is unique. The ICF-CY framework has been widely adopted in a variety of domains, including health, education, and public policy for people with disabilities (Cieza *et al.*, 2004). Practitioners have used the biopsychosocial model to develop specific tools and frameworks (such as assessment instruments or intervention strategies) for addressing health issues related to disability, leading to a more comprehensive understanding of the complex interplay of biological, psychological, and social factors (Cieza *et al.*, 2004). The ICF has also been utilised as a problem-solving technique in special education to guide eligibility policy and practice (Sanches-Ferreira *et al.*, 2013). For instance, Sanches-Ferreira *et al* (2013) argued that the Portuguese government used it to determine the kind and level of disability needed for children to get special education assistance. Likewise, the government of Switzerland used the framework to determine who was eligible to attend special schools for children with disabilities (Hollenweger, 2011). The ICF-CY paradigm could be used to enhance inclusive education for children with physical and sensory disabilities in Algeria and other similar settings through using the four key components of the system. The next part explains how the ICF-CY framework might help major stakeholders in developing inclusive education for children with physical and sensory disabilities in Algeria.

2.5.4.2.1 Body Functions and Structures

According to Selb *et al* (2015) the Body Functions and Structures domains are a valuable resource for assessing functioning profiles, identifying specific needs, and developing systematic intervention programmes. The researcher believes that incorporating the ICF-CY framework into Algerian educational systems may help educators in better understanding how psychological needs and brain structure influence problem behaviours and learning issues in children with physical and sensory disabilities. Following that, the framework can be used to drive the creation of specialised evaluations as well as modifications and adaptations to instructional methodologies and curriculum, resulting in enhanced cooperation and inclusion of learners with physical and sensory disabilities. In research conducted in Sweden to investigate professional` perception of ICF-CY, it is found that adopting the ICF-CY framework in school systems boosted educators' awareness of learners' specific needs, which facilitated the construction and evaluation of individualised support (Adolfsson *et al.*, 2010). Similarly, De Polo *et al* (2009) argued that the ICF-CY could enhance educational teams' and professionals' awareness of students' individual requirements, as well as their comprehension of the most appropriate contexts for meeting those needs.

It is indeed worth noting that these guiding principles are from developed countries that have a history of adopting the ICF-CY to better understand and encourage the inclusion of students with disabilities, particularly those with physical and sensory disabilities. This highlights the importance of investigating the ICF-CY framework with children with physical and sensory disabilities in Algeria`s inclusive education settings.

2.5.4.2.2 Activity and Participation

According to the World Health Organization (2007), the Activity and Participation domains cover a wide range of life activities, from learning and applying information to interpersonal relationships and interactions, along with public, and social participation. The Activity and Participation component in educational contexts highlights a child's capacity or difficulty in completing school assignments, tasks, and everyday activities that are appropriate for their age (World Health Organization, 2007). According to de Leeuw *et al.* (2018) educators face a variety

of obstacles when it comes to assisting students with disabilities, including figuring out how to encourage their engagement and interaction development.

Friendship, social self-perception, interaction and peer acceptability are four fundamental aspects of social involvement identified in the literature (Koster *et al.*, 2009). Positive relationships with friends and classmates can help children with physical and sensory disabilities attain social involvement in general education classes, leading to a sense of belonging (de Leeuw *et al.*, 2018). The ICF-CY is significant because it serves as a guide for teachers on how to eliminate physical obstacles to accommodate potential impairments and activity restrictions, as well as increase possibilities for interactions and cooperation between children with and without disabilities (World Health Organization, 2013). Potential effects of activity limitations can be accommodated through firstly, individualised outcomes that match functioning profiles. Secondly, appropriate physical environments and modified classroom activities that support social participation and relationships building. Thirdly, policies that make these accommodations possible.

2.5.4.2.3 Contextual Factors

As stated by the World Health Organization (2007), the contextual aspects are the entire context of a person's life and existence. It is made up of two parts: internal (personal) and external (environmental) aspects, which operate as either enablers or obstacles to a person's functioning. The special needs of disabled children can be recognised and met in inclusive educational environments when all relevant Contextual Factors are addressed to encourage their inclusion (Hollenweger, 2011). Educators' knowledge of how Contextual Factors affect a learner with disability might help them create learning environments that enhance their performance and capacity (De Polo *et al.*, 2009). According to Taylor (2004) services for learners with disabilities should be provided in the least disruptive, most normalised, independent, and integrated contexts possible.

2.5.4.2.4 Environmental/ external Factors

Individual functioning in this component is reported across five domains namely: systems, services, and policies, attitudes, relationships and support, products and technology, environmental changes caused by nature and changes caused by human. Considering its comprehensive concept

to disability and participation, the use of the ICF-CY could affect the establishment and monitoring of clear education policy related to equal access and opportunity that would enhance inclusive education contexts (Maxwell and Koutsogeorgou, 2012). By extending the perspective through which disability is defined and understood, the ICF-CY could influence the educational policy and legislation in Algeria to serve students with disabilities. The impact of cultural elements (attitudes and beliefs) on disability is not recognised in policy and legislation using the present medical paradigm (Oliver and Barnes, 2012). Introducing ICF-CY-based methodologies for student identification and categorization into Algerian educational environments may have a reciprocal effect on policies, leading policymakers to examine contextual influences on the educational success of learners with physical and sensory disabilities. The ICF-CY model, in particular, has the potential to affect special education policies by ensuring that the basic aspects of inclusive education (equity, access, and support), are clearly incorporated into policies, thereby facilitating their integration into communities and schools.

2.5.4.2.5 Personal/ internal Factors

These are characteristics of a person that are not related to their state of health (World Health Organization, 2007). Gender, age, motivation and level of knowledge, as well as coping strategies, are all factors to consider. It is worth mentioning that personal variables are not defined in the present version of the ICF-CY model, despite their impact on functioning and interventions effects, due to cultural and societal differences around the world (Westby and Washington, 2017). Personal Factors such as motivation, temperament, and intellectual capability, of the disabled learner can help drive the development of the most appropriate instructional practices that enhance their functioning and, eventually, inclusion (Sanches-Ferreira *et al.*, 2013). Individualized education plans (IEPs), curricular adjustments and adaptation, and instructional practises are all examples of instructional methods (Dee, 2010). For instance, to guarantee that learners with physical and sensory disabilities benefit from inclusive schools, teachers can utilise a multisensory approach flexible teaching method (i.e., visual and aural oral instructions), provide regular feedback, reduce work into manageable learning chunks, or design an accessible classroom. The adoption of the ICF-CY in the Algerian educational system could be the first concrete and actionable step that stakeholders (e.g., Algerian educational systems, policy makers, Special Education Division, and teachers) can take to enhance the effectiveness of individualised support that is comprehensive,

consistent, and aligned with the specific Personal Factors of children with physical and sensory disabilities. Furthermore, Teachers can effectively identify the qualities of each learner with physical and sensory disability that influence their attitudes, capability, and performance by evaluating the Personal Factors of each physically and sensory disabled child, and they can adjust materials and resources to help their full inclusion and participation (Washington, 2007).

2.5.4.3 The ICF-CY Potential Limitations

Despite the fact that the ICF-CY has proved useful in measuring children's and youth's health as well as studying pedagogical systems and processes (Adolfsson et al., 2010; Maxwell and Koutsogeorgou, 2012), certain issues have been expressed in the literature about its use in educational settings. To begin with, using the ICF-CY to determine whether a child with a disability is eligible for special education services could serve as a foundation for greater segregation and prejudice instead of encouragement and equality of opportunity (Hollenweger, 2013). While this is a big worry, it is crucial to keep in mind that the ICF-CY's goal isn't to label people, but to identify the disabilities and participation barriers they face, as well as the external factors that influence their experiences (Simeonsson *et al.*, 2006). As a result, researchers suggest that countries may use the ICF-CY to define and promote the particular needs of disabled students in inclusive educational system, rather than categorising them in a way that negatively influences equal opportunity. In this manner, the ICF-CY's goal of a non-discriminatory framework to disability would be developed (Simeonsson *et al.*, 2006). Secondly, several educational researchers have evaluated the ICF-CY as complicated due to their inability to understand its ideas (Sanches-Ferreira, Silveira-Maia and Alves, 2014). While this is an essential problem, it is worth noting that the ICF-CY has played a key role in fostering collaborative quality of service among clinicians and educators when it comes to addressing the special needs of learners with disabilities in the educational environments (Campbell and Skarakis-Doyle, 2007). Indeed, the ICF-CY serves as a foundation for collaborative relationships, allowing professionals in education (teachers, administrators, and stakeholders) to get the help they need to grasp key topics. De Polo et al. (2009) classified the process of applying the ICF-CY as neither easy nor straightforward in terms of time, resources, and efforts. Yet, the researcher believes that the challenges concerning the ICF-CY's applicability in educational settings can be reduced by investing in professional training for teachers and school staff on all of the ICF-CY's core aspects and principles (Sanches-Ferreira,

Silveira-Maia and Alves, 2014). To that aim, the researcher believes that, despite the aforementioned limits of ICF-CY use, the advantages of its application exceed the possible negative consequences, especially when deliberate actions are taken to mitigate the restrictions. Although the possible limitations of the ICF-CY are genuine and must be considered, their potential benefits of narrowing the policy-practice gap outweigh the drawbacks.

To sum up, the ICF-CY framework can play a significant role in facilitating inclusive education, given the long-standing international necessity for inclusive approaches for all children with disabilities. Environmental issues, such as education regulations and legislation that are integrated within the medical model, as well as a society that distinguishes all disabled children, contribute to the obstacles that disabled children experience in Algeria. The ICF-CY sets out a model for inclusion that does not compromise essential educational values. Using a biopsychosocial model of disability, it provides a comprehensive framework for assessing children and establishing appropriate, personalized services for complete inclusion and participation. The ICF-CY can also assist teachers in planning and implementing learner-centred teaching methods, as well as providing a common language for interdisciplinary collaboration. The ICF-CY can help the Algerian educational system foster effective inclusive education implementation through directing policymakers and practitioners in identifying and documenting the features related to enhancing the functioning and involvement of students with disabilities in mainstream classes.

2.5.4.4 The ICF framework: relationships between ICF factors

Figure 2 The ICF model Source: (WHO, 2007)

The diagram demonstrates the fundamental ICF model, in which disability is described as the interrelationships of body functions and structures, activities, as well as participation, all of which occur within a context determined by personal (internal) and environmental aspects. Participation is concerned with an individual's engagement in a life circumstance, whereas Activities is concerned with an individual's performance of work or task. Body functioning and structure issues, including loss or a significant deviation, are referred to as impairments. Participation limitations are challenges that a person may encounter in his/her engagement in life circumstances, whereas activity restrictions are barriers that an individual could face in performing activities. The fields of activities and participation are presented as a unified set of life themes ranging from fundamental learning to societal responsibilities. Those functions contain two kinds of qualifiers, which are performance and capacity qualifiers. The former explains what a person performs in his/her current context, and this is influenced by external factors. Whereas the capacity qualifier specifies the greatest possible degree of functioning at any given time.

The ICF model is likely being introduced in this context to provide a framework for understanding the relationship between disability, individual factors, and environmental factors. By understanding how these elements interact, we can better understand the challenges faced by individuals with disabilities and develop strategies to support their participation in society.

2.6 Defining Key Educational Contexts and Specific Impairment Types

To ground this research, it is necessary to provide precise definitions for the educational settings and the varied student populations under examination.

2.6.1 Educational Settings and Contexts

The mainstream school is defined as the general education environment catering to the majority of students, typically structured by geographic area and adhering to the national curriculum. In this thesis, the term 'mainstream' is utilized as a necessary administrative term to differentiate the general setting from segregated special education institutions, while still acknowledging the underlying philosophical implication of a majority 'stream' that others are expected to join (Wigle and Wilcox, 1997). In contrast, an inclusive classroom is a specific teaching-learning context within the mainstream setting that deliberately and successfully fosters the full engagement of all learners, including those with profound disabilities, through tailored pedagogical adaptations and necessary support structures.

2.6.1.1 Mainstream School and Mainstreaming

According to Moss (2002), a mainstream school refers to any school which is not an independent or special school. The practice of mainstreaming is often understood as bringing students to conform to a special form of scheme or accommodating them into a current system (Mangope *et al.*, 2018). In other words, it is to provide some students with support so they could fit into or be integrated into a general setting's routine. From a rights perspective, mainstreaming has been defined as the educational equivalent of the adjustment rule, recommending that the individual with disabilities has the right to live experiences which are similar to people without disabilities in the community, and to learn alongside non-disabled peers in mainstream classes (Landsberg,

Krüger and Nel, 2005). However, this approach often implies that learners are expected to find identical academic norms similar to their non-disabled learners (Chopra, 2008).

2.6.1.2 Inclusive Classrooms

The concept of the inclusive classroom represents a move beyond simple integration by focusing on systemic and pedagogical change. Causton-Theoharis (2009) defines an inclusive classroom as a learning and teaching environment in which all students are essential representatives of the classroom, sense a relationship to their classmates, have connection to the regular educational program, and perceive the collective support to achieve success. Salend (2001) states that in inclusive classrooms, teachers are meditative professionals who are adaptable, reactive, and attentive to the needs of students. They regularly vote on their own works for self-development and think critically toward their beliefs and attitudes to assure that all students' needs are achieved. Teachers in these settings individualize education for all students in terms of evaluation skills, teaching methods, educational program accessibility, technology, and physical plan variations according to students' needs. Students are provided with a varied syllabus and challenging social and educational experiences which are consistent with their needs and abilities.

2.6.2 Defining Research Constructs: Perceptions and Experiences

The literature consistently demonstrates that teacher perceptions and teacher experiences are not merely descriptive details but are fundamental concepts that determine the success or failure of inclusion (Specht *et al.*, 2016).

2.6.2.1 Perceptions

Perception, psychologically described, is the action or practice of being conscious of inner and extraneous sensual facts or stimulation, involving the explanation and translation of those stimulations, and the assessments of a person's own and others' inner cases, assumptions, and sensual stimulations (Jennett, 2008). It refers to the sequence of cerebral action through which an individual perceives, regulates, and depicts sensory information in a reasonable and useful model (Segen, 2006). In the context of this research, perceptions refer to the socially constructed ways

in which teachers view and understand the implementation of inclusive education for students with sensory and physical disabilities in their primary mainstream schools. These perceptions encompass the attitudes, beliefs, and understanding held by teachers regarding the ability of students with disabilities to learn, coupled with their own belief (self-efficacy) in their ability to teach them effectively (Specht *et al.*, 2016).

2.6.2.2 Experiences

Experience, a fundamental concept in education, encompasses the dynamic interplay between individuals, their learning environments, and their interactions. It involves cognitive, emotional, and practical dimensions, shaped by personal characteristics, social contexts, and mutual influences (Roth and Jornet, 2014). For the purposes of this study, experience refers strictly to the firsthand knowledge and professional insights of general teachers who have taught or are currently teaching students with physical and sensory disabilities in mainstream schools. This encompasses their direct interactions with these students, their acquired understanding of the unique needs and challenges encountered in the classroom, and their practical implementation of teaching strategies in inclusive classrooms.

2.6.3 Categories of Disability

The term disability acts as an umbrella concept, encompassing limitations in activity, participation restrictions, and various impairments (World Health organization, 2002). For educational planning, it is vital to distinguish among major impairment categories that necessitate differentiated support:

2.6.3.1 Learning Disability

This is a neurodevelopmental condition affecting the brain's ability to process, receive, store, or analyse information (Mather and Goldstein, 2015). It typically manifests as difficulty in specific academic skills like reading (e.g., dyslexia), writing (e.g., dysgraphia), or arithmetic (e.g., dyscalculia). Learning disability is identified when a learner faces significant difficulties in one or more of the four language skills (reading, writing, listening, speaking) or in reasoning or

mathematical skills (Namkung and Peng, 2018). These learners may experience challenges in processing information through their senses and accurately interpreting it, which can lead to delays in understanding instructions, responding to questions, and completing homework (Thakran, 2015). Due to this complexity, the integration of disabled learners in the classrooms with non-disabled learners is often complex, requiring the incorporation of need-specific methods and curricular adaptations (Appert. et al., 2018). Considering the learners' diversity in learning preferences and styles (such as kinaesthetic, visual, or auditory) is one way to facilitate the integration of all learners (Boneva and Mihova, 2012). Learners with disabilities are as diverse as their non-disabled peers, but their experiences are often unique (Wapling, 2016).

2.6.3.2 Physical disabilities

A physical disability is identified by Katz (2015) as any chronic, long-term condition significantly impeding an individual's capacity to perform common physical actions, such as walking, lifting, reaching, or climbing. The official classification of a disabled or challenged individual is determined by a specific set of rules or criteria (Nancy R. Mudrick, Mary Lou Breslin and Donna H. Odierna, 2025). This broad definition encompasses not only physical limitations but also cognitive, sensory, and intellectual impairments. Fundamentally, a physical disability refers to any deficient condition that restricts the physical activity of one or multiple bodily organs.

Siebers (2008) elaborates that mobility and movement challenges can arise from a wide range of underlying causes and conditions. These physical limitations may manifest as the inadequate utilization of the arms, legs, or other body parts, often resulting from stiffness, pain, paralysis, or other comparable physical impairments. Such deficiencies may originate from congenital birth defects, accidents, advancing age, or disease. These primary physical challenges can subsequently trigger secondary issues, including speech disorders, short stature, hearing loss, or memory impairment. Furthermore, Johnstone (2012) contends that this population is non-homogenous and frequently encounters difficulties collaborating when presented with physical and social obstacles due to their movement restrictions.

2.6.3.2.1 Mobility Impairment

Mobility impairment is specifically categorized as a type of physical disability encompassing diverse conditions. This includes the loss or disability of upper or lower limbs, difficulty coordinating various body organs, or structural damage to the skeleton. Mobility challenges can be either congenital (present from birth) or acquired later in life due to illness or the aging process. The common underlying causes often involve significant neurological conditions, such as injuries to the spinal cord, Muscular Dystrophy (MD), and Cerebral Palsy (CP), which impose complex challenges on movement and posture. To facilitate movement and maximize independence, people with physical disabilities routinely rely on various support equipment, including wheelchairs, canes, crutches, and artificial limbs (World Health Organization, 2022).

2.6.3.3 Sensory Disability (visual, deaf, and hearing impairments)

This category involves a partial or total loss of function in one of the five senses. In education, specialized communication assistance (e.g., sign language), auditory or visual supports, and specific instructional materials (e.g., Braille or tactile models) are required (Ladd, 2017). A sensory disability is an umbrella term used to describe an impairment in hearing and vision, or in its serious cases, blindness and deafness (Foreman and Arthur-Kelly, 2017). Click or tap here to enter text.. This type of disability includes individuals with labels like visually impaired, hearing impaired, blind, or deaf (Truscott, Berry and Lee, 2004). Click or tap here to enter text. Severity of sensory impairment extends from mild to profound.

2.6.3.3.1 Hearing Impairment

Hearing impairment is defined as an unseen disability, which can lead to it being unrecognized or ignored by educators, even when a learner is facing difficulties (Powell, Hyde and Punch, 2014). This can result in a situation where a learner, despite having talents, is unable to use them due to not hearing instructions, potentially leading to underachievement (Punch, Hyde and Creed, 2004). Furthermore, noisy environments, such as during lunch or breaks, can lead to problems in socializing, even if hearing conditions are optimal during lectures (Takala and Sume, 2018). The term hearing impaired relates to impairment in hearing, irrespective of whether it is constant or

changeable, which impacts a learner's educational performance negatively (the Special educational guide, 2020). Hearing impairment extends from mild hearing injury to serious hearing injury (deaf) (Cole and Flexer, 2015). Individuals who are "hard of hearing" experience mild-to-severe hearing loss but can still communicate effectively using spoken or sign language, and may benefit from hearing aids, cochlear implants, or assistive technologies. In contrast, "deaf" individuals have a profound hearing impairment that significantly limits or prevents communication through hearing. While sign language is common, it is crucial to acknowledge the diversity of communication strategies, which may also include lipreading or the use of hearing aids (World Health Organization, 2020).

2.6.3.3.2 Visual Impairment

A visual impairment is characterized as a limitation in the functional process of the eyes, typically manifesting as decreased visual acuity or reduced opposition sense (Moroszlay, 1994). This condition exists on a spectrum and is broadly categorized by the degree of sight loss, ranging from 'low vision,' where residual sight is still functional for environmental navigation, to 'total blindness.' Because the visual channel is compromised, these students are fully capable of learning effectively by developing and relying on their other senses (NICHCY, 2012). Therefore, educational support must facilitate multi-sensory learning through specialized instruction, the use of tactile aids, and the provision of Braille or large-print materials. Furthermore, critical assistive technology—such as screen readers (which convert text to speech), magnification software, and refreshable Braille displays—is essential for visually impaired students to ensure full curriculum access and successful educational participation.

To conclude, from the previous review that introduced various types of disability, the present study will specifically focus on the physical and sensory disabilities including mobility, visual, and hearing impairments, as these are the groups relevant to the investigation into teacher perceptions in primary mainstream schools.

2.7 Critical Examination of Inclusive Practice Dynamics and Barriers

The legislative and philosophical underpinnings of inclusive education establish a clear theoretical framework, but the true measure of policy success is determined by its implementation fidelity at the institutional and instructional levels. This critical juncture at the frontline of education is mediated by the complex interaction of educator disposition, pedagogical competency, leadership support, and structural resource allocation. The following analysis provides a deep, evidence-based review of these dynamics, specifically emphasizing the pivotal role of the mainstream teacher and the persistent, multi-layered barriers that impede the systemic realization of educational equity (Ainscow, 2020).

2.7.1 Teacher Perceptions, Attitudes, and Self-Efficacy

Flanders, Fishbein and Ajzen (1975) define the term attitudes as a learned disposition to reply in a regularly appropriate or inappropriate way with regard to a particular object. They argued that the word attitudes illustrate the individuals' positively or negatively covered feelings towards a person, issue, behaviour, or an object, and are learned throughout time through exposing themselves directly to the object (experience) or by providing information about the object. The learned attitudes work as an overall manual to guide behaviour in respect to the attitudes object (Flanders, Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975).

A vast body of research confirms that teachers' attitudes are the single most important predictor of successful inclusive outcomes (Avramidis and Norwich, 2002). Teacher perceptions, as defined earlier, are fundamentally tied to teacher self-efficacy—the educator's confidence in their ability to succeed with a diverse group of learners (Tschannen-Moran and Hoy, 2001).

The teachers' perceptions of and attitudes towards inclusive education are important, since they could affect the level of accommodation and acceptance of learners with special needs within mainstream schools (Cornoldi *et al.*, 2018). The realization of inclusive education relies heavily on the teachers' attitudes and perceptions within mainstream classes towards students with special needs (Koay *et al.*, 2006).

Positive beliefs of teachers contribute to the success of inclusive education. This requires teachers to believe that all students are able to learn; that students with learning disabilities can learn in

ordinary schools; and that inclusive pedagogy is a valuable program if teachers accept to work with different types of learners (Koay *et al.*, 2006). Conversely, negative perceptions, often driven by inadequate training or scarce resources, typically lead to lowered expectations, fewer opportunities for peer interaction, and a reluctance to adapt the curriculum (Wigle and Wilcox, 1997). If a teacher's views of disabled learners are negative, the inclusion of those students in general classrooms may result in a negative experience for those learners (Mngo and Mngo, 2018).

2.7.1.1 The Origins of Resistance and Professional Anxiety

Teacher resistance to inclusive practices rarely stems from overt prejudice; rather, it is typically rooted in a cycle of ignorance, anxiety, and perceived inadequacy. This resistance is a systemic issue linked to professional preparation and the pressures of curriculum delivery:

- **Deficiency in Specialized Skills:** A near-universal source of teacher hesitation is the lack of specific, practical pedagogical skills required to manage the instructional, technological, and behavioural complexities of teaching students with diverse needs (Cornoldi *et al.*, 2018; Ewing, Monsen and Kielblock, 2018). Traditional pre-service programs often fail to prepare mainstream teachers for this level of heterogeneity, leaving them feeling profoundly unprepared upon entering the classroom.
- **The Dual Curriculum Pressure:** The implementation of inclusion often imposes an unsustainable dual curriculum challenge, wherein teachers must manage the rigid requirements of the general curriculum while simultaneously executing complex, mandated Individualized Education Plans (IEPs) (Jordan, Schwartz and McGhie-Richmond, 2009). This pressure is perceived as a significant, unfunded workload increase, resulting in high professional stress and feelings of professional insufficiency (Dupoux *et al.*, 2006). A common anxiety is the ethical conflict that the extensive time devoted to one student may detract from the academic needs of the majority.
- **Locus of Control and Self-Efficacy:** Teacher attitude is intrinsically linked to self-efficacy, which is the belief in one's capacity to manage and execute specific tasks successfully. Educators exhibiting a strong external locus of control—attributing poor outcomes to external constraints like "lack of resources" or "severity of disability"—tend to display less effort toward inclusion. Conversely, those with an internal locus of control

believe their own skills, professional efforts, and instructional adaptations are the primary catalysts for student success, leading to significantly more proactive and favourable attitudes (Bandura, 1997).

- **Influence of Disability Spectrum:** The type and perceived severity of the disability significantly modulate teacher disposition (Dupoux *et al.*, 2006). Studies consistently indicate a negative correlation between rising perceived severity and favourable attitudes (Dupoux *et al.*, 2006). Specifically, teachers express the highest levels of anxiety, reluctance, and instructional difficulty when integrating students with behavioural and emotional disabilities, often citing disruptive classroom management challenges. This contrasts with a relative preference for students with specific learning disabilities or minor physical needs, where instructional adaptations are perceived as more manageable (Briggs *et al.*, 2002).

2.7.1.2 The Role of Support in Modulating Professional Attitude

The trajectory of teacher attitude from anxiety to competence is mediated by several measurable variables that shift the perception of inclusion from an overwhelming burden to a professional opportunity:

- **Experience, Training, and Skill Acquisition:** Comprehensive pre-service and in-service training that prioritizes practical application, collaborative strategies, and competence in handling diverse learning needs demonstrably improves attitudes (Avramidis, Bayliss and Burden, 2000). As educators gain supervised, positive experience and increase their specialized pedagogical knowledge, their commitment to inclusive philosophies strengthens (Koay *et al.*, 2006). Targeted professional development in practical methodologies, such as Universal Design for Learning (UDL) and co-teaching, has proven effective in fostering more favourable attitudes (Briggs *et al.*, 2002). This establishes a competence-confidence cycle where initial success drives sustained commitment (Tschannen-Moran and Hoy, 2001).
- **Resource and Administrative Support:** Teachers universally regard the availability of adequate material resources, administrative support (e.g., non-contact planning time, co-teaching partners, accessible technology), familiarity with special education laws, and strong parental engagement as non-negotiable prerequisites for maintaining positive attitudes

(Kruger et al. 1995; Wigle and Wilcox, 1997). This emphasizes that cultivating teacher disposition requires substantive administrative and budgetary commitments designed to mitigate the emotional and practical demands of inclusive instruction (European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education., 2018).

2.7.2 Pedagogical Strategies and the Universal Design for Learning (UDL)

While positive educator attitudes are essential for initiating inclusive policy, the systematic application of effective, evidence-based instructional frameworks is required for sustainable and equitable academic success. Inclusion must translate from a philosophical principle into a series of actionable, proactive instructional strategies (Friend and Cook, 2017). This requires a fundamental shift away from retroactive accommodation—where instruction is modified only after a student encounters a barrier—to proactive design, where the curriculum is inherently flexible to accommodate diversity from the outset.

2.7.2.1 The Paradigm of Universal Design for Learning (UDL)

The most comprehensive and ethically aligned framework for proactive curriculum design is the Universal Design for Learning (UDL). Developed by the Centre for Applied Special Technology (CAST), UDL is an instructional blueprint based on neurological research into how individuals learn. It mandates designing educational environments and materials that are accessible to the broadest range of learners, negating the need for extensive, often stigmatizing, post-hoc adaptations (CAST, 2018).

UDL is structured around three foundational principles that align with the three primary brain networks involved in learning:

- **Multiple Means of Representation (The Recognition Network):** This principle corresponds to the brain's Recognition Network and addresses the fundamental question of what is being learned—specifically, how information is delivered and comprehended by students. This requirement ensures that content is made accessible to all learners by being presented in diverse ways, such as through auditory, visual, concrete, or abstract formats. By offering varied delivery methods, educators can directly eliminate sensory and cognitive barriers, thereby

guaranteeing that every student can access the same essential information irrespective of any existing sensory impairment or learning disability (CAST, 2018) .

- **Multiple Means of Action and Expression (The Strategic Network):** This principle focuses on the Strategic Network and concerns the "how" of learning—that is, the methods students employ to engage with the learning material and ultimately demonstrate their acquired knowledge. This approach requires educators to provide students with flexible options for participating, responding, communicating their ideas, and completing assessments. Instead of being restricted to a singular, standardized testing method, a student could, for example, show their understanding through a verbal speech, a detailed paper, a physical project, or a digital compilation of work (CAST, 2018).
- **Multiple Means of Engagement (The Affective Network):** This principle activates the Affective Network of the brain, addresses the crucial "why" of learning—the factors that drive a student's motivation, interest, and consistent effort. This requires educators to intentionally design lessons that offer methods for students to exercise self-regulation, perceive the content's relevance, make personal choices about their learning, and participate in collaborative activities to sustain their commitment. When students are deeply engaged, their executive functions are significantly improved, resulting in greater concentration and overall academic resilience (Friend and Cook, 2017).

Research clearly indicates that adopting Universal Design for Learning (UDL) is an effective strategy for both improving student outcomes and strengthening a teacher's self-efficacy (Rapp, 2017). By establishing instructional planning as an inclusive, universal methodology, UDL shifts the perception of specialized interventions from being solely "special education" practices to being recognized as high-quality teaching that benefits everyone. This change in perspective encourages a more unified and less fragmented school environment.

2.7.2.2 Collaborative Teaching Models: The Necessity of Co-Teaching

While Universal Design for Learning (UDL) establishes the conceptual and structural guidelines for curriculum development, realizing effective instruction often requires a seamless collaboration between general and special education professionals. Co-teaching, defined as the joint deployment of at least two educators within a single classroom to deliver integrated instruction to diverse

learners (Friend and Cook, 2017), is considered the optimal approach for inclusive settings that require intensive support.

The value of co-teaching is rooted in its division of expertise: the general educator offers a deep understanding of the content and curriculum scope, while the special educator contributes specialized skills in adapting lessons, implementing behavioural management strategies, and achieving Individualized Education Program (IEP) objectives. This unique partnership aims to maximize student engagement with the general curriculum while simultaneously providing necessary, personalized accommodations (Murawski and Swanson, 2001).

2.7.2.2.1 Common Co-Teaching Approaches

The following are the most frequently employed models of co-teaching:

- **One Teach, One Support:** One teacher takes the lead role in instruction while the other moves around the room to offer individual help, redirect students, or gather data. Although common, this is considered the least inclusive model, often reducing the special educator's role to that of a helper.
- **Station Teaching:** Educators divide both the instructional material and the student group, teaching different content sections concurrently at separate learning stations. This method effectively lowers student-to-teacher ratios and facilitates the differentiated delivery of complex topics.
- **Parallel Teaching:** The teaching pair collaboratively plans the lesson, but then divides the class into two smaller, mixed-ability groups to deliver the identical content simultaneously. This significantly shrinks group size, enhancing every student's opportunity for feedback and active participation.
- **Alternative Teaching:** The majority of students receive instruction from one teacher on the core content, while the second teacher works with a small, focused group to offer targeted pre-teaching, enrichment, or remediation on that specific subject. This is highly effective for addressing individual skill deficiencies without removing students from the main classroom setting.

- **Team Teaching:** Both professionals jointly and fluidly lead the instruction, engaging in continuous dialogue, modelling interactive learning strategies, and spontaneously building upon one another's teaching points. This represents the most integrated and complex model, demanding a high level of mutual confidence and complementary instructional styles (Friend and Cook, 2017).

2.7.2.2 Administrative Requirements

Successful co-teaching is heavily reliant on dedicated co-planning time, which is often identified as the principal organizational barrier to full implementation (Murawski and Swanson, 2001). If joint time for planning goals, designing lessons, and dividing responsibilities is not provided, co-teaching tends to default to the less impactful "One Teach, One Support" model. Moreover, effective collaboration necessitates shared accountabilities for all students' academic progress, mutual respect, and clear communication guidelines.

2.7.2.3 Differentiating Instruction and Curriculum Adjustments

2.7.2.3.1 The Core of Differentiation

Beyond the overarching structural and philosophical guidance provided by Universal Design for Learning (UDL) and co-teaching, the day-to-day success of inclusion relies heavily on the educator's skill in differentiating instruction (DI). Differentiation refers to a specialized pedagogical process of decision-making where the instructor modifies the content (what is taught), the process (the method of learning), and the product (how learning is assessed) to align with a student's specific readiness, interests, and learning profile (Tomlinson, 2014).

In an inclusive classroom, DI goes beyond simply offering supplementary assistance; it focuses on delivering instruction that is precisely targeted and appropriate for each learner. Essential adjustments typically fall into three categories:

- **Content Differentiation:** This involves altering the complexity of source materials, delivering different levels of vocabulary assistance, or introducing supplemental aids (such

as simplified summaries or graphic organizers) to ensure every student can engage with the central concepts of the curriculum.

- **Process Differentiation:** This means offering varied work arrangements, such as working alone, with a partner, or in small groups; supplying scaffolds like sentence frames or organizational templates; and adjusting the speed of instruction to ensure skill mastery.
- **Product Differentiation:** This allows students to select from various assessment formats that leverage their individual strengths (e.g., submitting a design prototype instead of a research paper, or creating a video instead of a written report).

2.7.2.3.2 Relationship with UDL

While DI and UDL share similar educational philosophies, they are conceptually separate. UDL acts as a proactive framework that establishes a universally accessible learning environment, whereas DI is reactive, involving the specific, on-the-spot modifications made for individual students or small groups within that established framework (Santangelo and Tomlinson, 2012). Both strategies are crucial elements of a complete, inclusive pedagogy.

The effectiveness of these pedagogical strategies, however, can be limited by inadequate resources and physical or structural limitations, which must also be resolved to foster truly equitable learning settings.

2.7.3 Adaptation of the Physical and Sensory Environment

Beyond teacher disposition and instructional strategies, the physical environment is a critical factor in the success of inclusive education, acting either as an invisible facilitator or a significant barrier to student access and learning. A truly inclusive environment extends the principles of Universal Design (UDL) beyond the curriculum to cover the physical space, sensory profile, and functional utility of the classroom (European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education., 2018).

2.7.3.1 Physical Accessibility and Functional Design

While governmental requirements, such as the Americans with Disabilities Act (ADA), mandate large-scale structural accessibility (e.g., ramps and accessible washrooms), inclusive design must be actively applied at the classroom level. Functional accessibility refers to the practical, day-to-day usability of the space for all students, particularly those with physical mobility challenges or visual/motor deficits (Mitchell, 2017).

Key components of effective functional classroom design include:

- **Traffic Flow and Layout:** Furniture must be arranged to guarantee clear, wide pathways capable of accommodating assistive devices like wheelchairs or walkers. This setup simultaneously supports effortless movement and promotes easy student monitoring (Koay *et al.*, 2006). Overly cluttered areas increase anxiety and restrict movement, thereby reducing the available learning space for some students.
- **Flexible Grouping and Furniture:** The classroom must be adaptable to support various instructional models (individual, small-group, and whole-class work). This requires the use of easily movable and adjustable furniture, such as desks with variable heights, portable boards, and diverse seating options (e.g., stability balls or standing desks) to address both physical and attentional needs (Tomlinson, 2014).
- **Visibility and Line of Sight:** All instructional materials, including projection screens and smart boards, must be positioned strategically to maintain a clear line of sight from every seating position. This is essential for students with low vision or those who rely on lip-reading or sign language.
- **Storage and Organization:** Materials should be organized logically and labelled clearly using both text and visual cues (pictograms). This practice supports students with cognitive disabilities, executive function challenges, or limited literacy skills in independently locating and returning necessary items (Mitchell, 2017).

2.7.3.2 The Sensory Environment and Emotional Regulation

For learners with sensory processing issues, autism spectrum disorder (ASD), ADHD, or significant anxiety, the overall sensory input of a standard classroom can become overwhelming

and detrimental to learning (Ewing, Monsen and Kielblock, 2018). Effective inclusion mandates that teachers proactively manage the classroom's sensory profile.

- **Acoustic Management (Noise):** The constant low-level background noise common in busy classrooms (e.g., chair scraping, chatter, ventilation hum) can be intensely distracting for students with sound hypersensitivity. Strategies to mitigate this include incorporating **sound-dampening materials** (carpets, soft furnishings), providing noise-cancelling headphones for focused work, and using visual cues instead of relying solely on auditory instructions to maintain quiet (Koay *et al.*, 2006).
- **Visual Environment (Clutter and Lighting):** A classroom that is excessively stimulating visually, even if well-intentioned, can be overstimulating. Inclusive practice encourages reducing unnecessary visual clutter on walls and in teaching areas. Lighting should utilize natural sources where possible, and harsh, flickering fluorescent lighting should be avoided. The deliberate use of visual schedules, clear labels, and defined activity zones introduces predictability, which significantly aids in reducing anxiety and supporting student self-regulation (Gargiulo, 2012).
- **Dedicated Low-Stimulation Areas:** Providing an accessible "calm corner," "break space," or "chill-out zone" within or adjacent to the classroom is essential. These spaces are strictly non-punitive and function as temporary havens where students can use self-regulatory tools (e.g., weighted blankets or fidgets) to manage sensory overload or high emotions, thus preventing disruptive behaviours and facilitating a quicker return to instruction (Ewing, Monsen and Kielblock, 2018).

2.7.3.3 Assistive and Adaptive Technology (AT)

The swift evolution of Assistive Technology (AT) has radically transformed student access and participation, elevating AT from a specialized accommodation to a foundational element of inclusive design (CAST, 2018). AT is defined as any product, equipment, or system used to enhance, maintain, or improve the functional capabilities of individuals with disabilities. The primary function of technology in an inclusive environment is to bypass functional barriers, rather than attempt to fix the underlying impairment, thereby enabling students to fully access the core curriculum (Gargiulo, 2012).

2.7.4 Systemic and Social Barriers: Structural Constraints on Inclusive Practice

While the failures of inclusion are often attributed to teacher attitudes and instructional challenges, the most persistent hurdles are typically systemic, administrative, and socio-cultural in origin (UNESCO, 2005). These structural limitations impede educational institutions' capacity to effectively implement policies, creating a significant gap between the legislative requirement for inclusion and its practical execution. Addressing these macro-level issues is essential to moving inclusion from a positive goal to an established institutional reality.

2.7.4.1 Resource Allocation and Underfunding

A core systemic obstacle to achieving inclusion is often insufficient funding and the resultant inappropriate distribution of limited resources (Srivastava, de Boer and Pijl, 2017). Providing successful inclusive education is inherently expensive, requiring dedicated funding for specialized staff, training, adaptive technology, reduced class sizes, and accessible buildings. When funds are inadequate, schools are forced into difficult trade-offs, which typically result in two primary consequences:

- **Inadequate Personnel Support:** Underfunding directly causes a shortage of vital specialists, such as speech-language pathologists, occupational therapists, behavioural experts, and educational psychologists. Mainstream teachers, already pressured by curriculum demands, must frequently take on the roles of these specialists, leading to professional fatigue, reduced quality of intervention, and reinforcing the negative view of inclusion as an excessive workload (Jordan, Schwartz and McGhie-Richmond, 2009). The failure to fund crucial shared planning time for co-teachers further undermines the integrity of collaborative models (Murawski and Swanson, 2001).
- **Class Size Dilemma:** Inclusive classrooms require smaller teacher-to-student ratios to enable effective differentiation and the management of varied learning profiles. Yet, economic pressure often compels districts to maintain or increase class sizes, forcing educators to attempt complex, individualized teaching within an unmanageable group

setting. This creates a strong disincentive, where the mere presence of a student with diverse needs is viewed as an added burden rather than an opportunity for richer pedagogical practice.

The absence of consistent, dedicated financial support transforms inclusion from a specialized service based on resources into a basic compliance obligation, shifting the priority from quality provision to merely minimizing legal exposure(Gargiulo, 2012).

- **Policy Incoherence and Accountability Gaps:** Implementation is frequently undermined by a lack of clarity and alignment across different educational policies. While legislation may mandate placement in the Least Restrictive Environment (LRE), this often conflicts with demanding accountability systems (Ainscow, 2020).
- **Curriculum Rigidity and Assessment:** In many educational systems, the focus on standardized testing and rigid, outcome-based curricula puts immense pressure on schools to prioritize measurable academic results over equal access and participation. Teachers may feel obligated to teach to the test, making them hesitant to significantly modify the curriculum for diverse learners, especially when the progress of those learners is not easily captured by standardized metrics. This creates friction between the goals of inclusion (participation, access, social development) and the goals of accountability (high scores, specific academic milestones) (Mitchell, 2017).
- **The Unclear Boundaries of Responsibility:** Policy execution frequently leads to administrative confusion regarding the shared roles between general and special education departments(Friend and Cook, 2017). The exact delineation of responsibilities—for instance, who is primarily responsible for the development and monitoring of IEPs, or who is accountable for functional skill growth versus academic achievement—remains a consistent source of administrative ambiguity and potential neglect of student requirements.
- **Societal Stigma and Cultural Resistance:** Perhaps the most deeply embedded obstacle to systemic inclusion is the continued presence of societal stigma, discrimination, and profound cultural resistance to difference (UNESCO, 2005). Inclusion is fundamentally a social justice movement that aims to normalize diversity and disability.

- **The Persistence of the Medical Model:** Despite decades of promoting the social model of disability (which attributes the challenge to social and environmental barriers), the medical model often retains its influence within society and schools. This model frames disability as an individual problem requiring "fixing" or segregation, resulting in language and practices that emphasize pathology rather than environmental adaptation (Jordan, Schwartz and McGhie-Richmond, 2009). This dominant attitude makes it difficult to cultivate genuine acceptance among non-disabled students and, critically, among parents of non-disabled students who may worry that inclusive practices will diminish the quality of general education.
- **Lack of Peer Acceptance and Social Isolation:** While placement in an inclusive classroom provides physical presence, it does not guarantee meaningful social integration. Students with disabilities frequently face social isolation, bullying, and low rates of true friendship development, particularly in secondary settings (Koay *et al.*, 2006). Effective inclusion requires deliberate, structured interventions by educators to build empathetic understanding, establish peer mentorship programs, and create cooperative learning opportunities that value and normalize difference, thereby changing the classroom climate from mere tolerance to genuine acceptance.
- **The Impact of Teacher Isolation:** Stigma and misunderstanding can also lead to the professional isolation of teachers. If the broader school culture does not sincerely support inclusion, educators who champion its principles may feel unsupported and isolated, intensifying the cycle of burnout and anxiety. A truly systemic approach requires the cultural expectation that collaboration, shared responsibility, and heterogeneous classrooms are the established standard, not the exception (Ainscow, 2000).

2.7.5 Leadership, Policy Implementation, and Community Engagement

While classroom educators are ultimately responsible for implementing inclusive education, the success or failure of this initiative depends profoundly on the commitment and actions of school leadership and the active participation of the broader community (Ainscow, 2020). School administrators—including principals, vice-principals, and other managers—serve as the critical

link between official educational policy and everyday instructional practice, shaping the organizational culture and ensuring that necessary structures are in place.

2.7.5.1 The Indispensable Role of School Leadership

Effective leadership for inclusion transcends mere adherence to legal obligations; it involves visionary, transformative action that cultivates a deep, shared conviction in the benefit of heterogeneity (Ryan, 2007).

- **Establishing a Shared Vision and Ethos:** The principal must function as the primary advocate and cultural architect of inclusion. They are tasked with clearly articulating an uncompromising inclusive vision that frames difference not as a burden to be managed, but as a resource to be utilized (Mitchell, 2017). This vision must be consistently reinforced across all school communication channels, staff meetings, and professional development activities. When leaders visibly champion inclusive values, they grant staff the necessary confidence, permission, and mandate to confront implementation difficulties.
- **Strategic Resource Allocation and Time Management:** Leaders are required to strategically distribute limited available resources, prioritizing time, personnel, and materials to support inclusive practices. This includes scheduling time for co-teaching planning, establishing consistent collaborative team meetings for addressing challenges (such as Professional Learning Communities or PLCs), and guaranteeing fair access to Assistive Technology (AT) across all teaching spaces (Friend and Cook, 2017). By redesigning the school schedule and budget to safeguard collaborative time, leaders demonstrate that inclusion is a core priority, not an optional activity.
- **Empowering and Investing in Staff:** Crucially, leaders must invest in the continuous professional development (CPD) of *all* staff members, not just those in special education roles. This CPD should focus on practical, evidence-based methods such as Universal Design for Learning (UDL), differentiated instruction, positive behaviour supports, and collaborative co-teaching models (CAST, 2018). Furthermore, effective leaders empower staff to take risks and explore new inclusive pedagogies, fostering a culture where mistakes are treated as learning opportunities, not as failures.

- **Data-Informed Decision-Making:** Leaders are responsible for implementing school-wide mechanisms for collecting and analysing data that assesses not only student academic results but also indicators of social and emotional integration, such as rates of peer interaction, social participation, and access to the general curriculum. This data guides policy adjustments and ensures accountability is directed toward equitable growth and participation for every learner (Gargiulo, 2012).
- **Building Partnerships with Families and the Wider Community:** Inclusion cannot succeed in isolation. The school must position itself as a single point within a larger network that encompasses the student's family and the surrounding community. This partnership is essential for holistic support and for diversifying resource streams.
- **Parent and Family Partnerships:** Parents of students with diverse needs offer invaluable expertise regarding their child's learning profile, coping mechanisms, and history (Srivastava, de Boer and Pijl, 2017)
- **Shared Decision-Making:** Genuine partnership means involving families in the Individualized Education Program (IEP) process as respected, equal team members, going beyond mere procedural compliance.
- **Open Communication:** Establishing multiple, flexible communication channels (e.g., informal check-ins, joint planning sessions, digital platforms) is vital for maintaining transparency and trust, ensuring school curriculum goals align with functional skills practiced at home.
- **Empowerment:** Providing parent training and support groups assists families in navigating the complexities of the educational system and builds a sense of community among parents facing similar circumstances.
- **Leveraging Community Resources:** The inclusive school environment should extend beyond the classroom by deliberately integrating external community resources:
- **Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) and Support Groups:** Collaborating with local disability organizations can furnish specialized therapeutic services, volunteer assistance, and external expertise that schools may lack internally (UNESCO, 2005).

- **Peer Mentoring and Advocacy:** Engaging older students, alumni, and local businesses in mentoring initiatives can strengthen the school's social fabric and provide meaningful vocational experiences for students with disabilities, successfully bridging the gap between education and post-school transition (Mitchell, 2017).
- **Public Awareness:** Leaders can cultivate public acceptance by organizing events and workshops that promote understanding and awareness of inclusion, subtly shifting the broader community's view of difference and ensuring the inclusive philosophy is supported outside of the school hours.

2.8 Conclusion

In conclusion, this comprehensive literature review has established that inclusive education is a non-negotiable, rights-based paradigm, legally mandated by international policy and grounded in a critical understanding of disability that rejects deficit-based models. The chapter has demonstrated a clear conceptual distinction between inclusive education (the systemic framework) and inclusive pedagogy (the flexible execution) and affirmed that the latter is essential for ensuring equitable access. While the legal mandate (Ainscow, 2020) and the necessary pedagogical tools, such as UDL and Differentiation (Tomlinson, 2014), are well-established, the practical realization of inclusion remains perpetually stalled at the implementation stage.

The review unequivocally shows that this failure is mediated by three complex, interacting factor groups. Firstly, Educator Disposition and Knowledge remain a significant hurdle, encompassing issues around the confidence, attitude, and pedagogical competence of the mainstream teacher. Secondly, Structural and Administrative Barriers pose persistent challenges, primarily through underfunding, policy incoherence, and class size dilemmas. Finally, the third factor is a pervasive Lack of Transformational Leadership at the school level, which manifests as a failure to champion an uncompromising inclusive ethos and allocate necessary co-planning time.

Collectively, this body of literature highlights a critical gap between macro-level policy aspiration and micro-level instructional reality. While research often addresses these barriers in isolation, the specific, contextual experiences of mainstream teachers supporting children with physical and sensory disabilities remain under-explored. Therefore, this investigation is necessary by the need

to gather original empirical data on these specific perceptions and experiences. The following chapter will detail the methodology employed to rigorously address this identified research gap.

3 Chapter Three: Research Methodology

3.1 Introduction

This exploratory qualitative research aims to examine the perceptions, attitudes, and experiences of general teachers regarding the inclusive education of physically and sensory disabled learners in Algerian public primary schools. The study seeks to:

- Explore the notion of inclusive education from the general teachers' perspectives.
- Investigate the teachers' knowledge, skills, attitudes, and experiences towards the inclusion of learners with physical and sensory disabilities in Algerian public schools.
- Explore the potential implications for teachers' knowledge, attitudes, and experiences of learners with physical and sensory disabilities in Algeria in relation to the education policy.

To address these research objectives, the following research questions were formulated:

- What are the perceptions, attitudes, and experiences of general teachers concerning the inclusive education of students with physical and sensory disabilities in the Algerian public primary schools?
- How do general teachers understand and conceptualize the inclusive education of physical and sensory disabled learners?
- What are the challenges that teachers encounter when teaching students with physical and sensory disabilities in inclusive classes?
- How can these challenges be met to provide an improved inclusion policy for students with physical and sensory disabilities?

This chapter will provide a comprehensive overview of the research methodology. It will begin by situating the study within the context of existing research theories, methodologies, and paradigms. Subsequently, the research design will be justified, explaining the rationale for choosing specific approaches over others. The chapter will also address the appropriateness of the data collection methods and the role of gatekeepers in accessing research participants. Finally, the data analysis procedures and the significance of ethical considerations in research will be discussed.

3.2 Conceptualisation of the research

The definition of research becomes complicated because of the different interpretations and ideas conjured in individuals' minds about research. For example, some people consider research as an activity conducted with academia rigour that results in the production of scientific writings, publications, and scientific experiments. According to Adams, Khan and Raeside (2014) the scholarly approach of the explanation of the word research leads to an over detailed answer due to the various techniques that have been adopted to investigate a specific research issue, research methodology, and similar understanding of truths versus present theories. Moreover, Clough and Nutbrown (2012) argue that research could be identified as an exploration of a subject, topic, or an idea for a particular aim that allows the investigator to expand knowledge. They suggest that research provides the chance to explore a field of study from a specific aspect.

Similarly, Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2013) argue that the investigator narrates the story and the procedure of raising the questions, investigating issues, and thinking about what appears. Thus, the purpose of research generally is to investigate a contemporary issue through a robust and ethically sound inquiry in the context of any given specific subject area. This thesis aims to understand complicated issues in the researcher environment as well as the nature of the research topic that has not been well investigated in Algeria in regards of the inclusive education of students with physical and sensory disabilities. Studies revealed that the teachers' perceptions of, attitudes and experiences towards inclusive education are important, since they could affect the level of accommodation and acceptance of learners with disabilities within ordinary schools (Cornoldi *et al.*, 2018) and ultimately students' success. Similarly, Koay *et al* (2006) argue that the realisation of inclusive education relies largely on teachers' attitudes, experiences and perceptions towards students with disabilities, including those with physical and sensory disabilities, within mainstream schools. A number of studies have investigated the attitudes and experiences of teachers toward inclusive education in various contexts. However, based on the researcher knowledge, no research has been done regarding teachers' perceptions and experiences towards the inclusion of students with physical and sensory disabilities in mainstream schools in Algeria. Teachers who teach disabled students in mainstream schools have major role in the success of inclusive education as they are in the front line in dealing with them in the classroom. Thus, the perceptions and experiences of teachers towards inclusive education, case of students with physical

and sensory disabilities in the Algerian mainstream schools were the main focus of the present investigation.

According to (Maxwell, 2012) there are three components to carry out a research project namely, practical, intellectual, and personal. In this thesis, the researcher understands that personal curiosity to figure out something is insufficient to carry out research of this size. Therefore, it is necessary to set up obvious and practicable objectives of research in order to comprehend the research topic. Likewise, Maxwell (2012) explains that the functional aims of research projects are realising the objectives, changings conditions, and addressing the needs. Whereas it is impossible to visualize the ultimate result of this study, one assurance is that a gap in knowledge will be filled up to a certain extent. This gap of knowledge concerns teachers` perceptions and experiences towards inclusive education of students with physical and sensory disabilities in Algeria. Among the aims of the current investigation is the focus on better understanding the phenomenon of the study and participation to knowledge. In regard to the aims, it is claimed that a researcher in the field of education should seek to persuade others that what s/he has established reliable (Newby, 2013) and in case it is assessed it should reveal trustworthiness like confirmability, dependability, and credibility (Bryman, 2016).

In the present study, the researcher`s intention is to pinpoint problems that may impact the decision-makers and policy planners in the ministry of education in Algeria in in relation to inclusive education in public schools. This might encourage change as a result all students including physically and sensory disabled students could take advantage of education.

According to Henn, Weinstein and Foard (2009) in the start of the research procedure, the investigator is recommended that research is not autocratic work, but it illustrates a manner of working where a researcher has to follow a number of rules, processes and approaches (Newby, 2013). Additionally, researchers should remain agile and have the ability to respond to newly emerging (or not emerging) data and possible weaknesses of the methods. Similarly, Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2013) argue that the advantage of a selected methodology is to help comprehension, in the widest possible sense, of the research process that is approved. Furthermore, Bazeley (2013) claims that the difficulty of research is to specify a theory and explore the way a study should continue whilst preserving the procedures and rules of research. Taking this concept into consideration, the researcher in the current study seeks to utilise an appropriate approach in order to determine the knowledge and conceptual position from where the researcher would

explore the research question. In addition, Bazelle (2013) suggests that there is no single approach that is superior to another. However, a strategy should emerge basically from the research question itself.

Particularly, in the present study the researcher selected a qualitative inductive exploratory approach in order to comprehend different conditions, crucial conceptions, and problems in inclusive education in Algerian schools. The presumption that the qualitative research approach is not deductive but inductive typically reflect the claim that it is exploratory (Creswell, 2014). The researcher has chosen the exploratory approach based on the research questions, aims, objectives, research size, the resources provided, and other prospects such as time schedule to carry out the research. Additionally, the researcher adopted an interpretivist paradigm to accommodate the qualitative method through direct communication with the participants while taking into consideration the research problem that forms the investigation (Denzin and Lincoln, 2008).

3.3 Theoretical considerations and Research knowledge

The coming paragraphs explain the way this research relates to and is affected by knowledge and theories. Thereafter, the researcher will clarify the processes of this study and explain the reality carried to the research paper via the selection of methods and methodologies. According to Robson and McCartan (2016) the type of study and the time-schedule factor of carrying out research decide which research methodology is used. Likewise, Perri and Bellamy (2012) stress the polemic comprehension of issues in a society as resulting from how individuals think and understand the world; but not a result of the various theoretical grounds of research methodology which investigators elect. From the standpoint of an interpretivist, the interest lies with the comprehension of the perceptions and experiences of the research participants, the researcher would not stay emotionally unbiased nor stay back. As stated by Gould and Nelson (2005) qualitative researchers are not dispassionate observers or objective and distant scientists, but on the contrary, an individual investigator working to cope with, make sense of, research experience. (2005) claim that it is impossible to remove the researcher's emotions and thoughts, not either desirable. Robson and McCartan (2016) state that the researcher's schedule is progressively to comprehend the reality of the research participants in order to interpret the meanings they constructed from their experiences. These factors have been reinforced by the wider approach of the design of the study and data analysis procedures.

3.3.1 Philosophical assumptions and interpretive frameworks

In the current study, the philosophical assumption of epistemology and ontology are used to decide how to appropriately research this topic. According to Creswell (2013) epistemology is the forms and nature of knowledge; it focuses on the ways of knowing the world. Similarly, Crotty (1998) claims that the way knowledge could be generated, obtained via checking the strength of theories or through deduction, or by induction, which is the way theories and knowledge are generated from gathering the information (Arthur. *et al.*, 2014). The researcher`s epistemological assumption for the present research explains how knowledge is constructed via research methodology and methods. On the other hand, ontological assumptions are concerned with what actually exists in the world (Arthur. *et al.*, 2014) and are linked to forms knowledge. The ontological assumption in the current study is that knowledge is a production of individuals` consciousness and does not occur separately or in isolation (Crotty, 1998), as well as the social life has significant social characteristics namely: beliefs, views, assumptions, and feelings which could not be investigated through objective evaluation.

According to Creswell (2013) the philosophy is the use of abstract beliefs and ideas that could be personal or out of the experience and could not be removed but instead inform any study. Moreover, the theoretical assumption is commonly the initial ideas that assists in developing a research project and to understand the way rules linked to a general practice. Thus, the philosophical customs teach the qualitative investigators how to choose theories to conduct their studies at an abstraction scale. In this study, the researcher chosen to be interpretive based on the knowledge that the methodology in a study is grounded on models or paradigms that give conventional design to investigate a phenomenon.

In this perspective, Trafford and Leshem (2008) claim that a paradigm is crucial to all research framework because it forms the way a study is conducted and allows the progress of any scientific domain. Further to this, acquiring a paradigm reflects the investigator`s view of the social world via understanding, perception, and interpretation. The researcher adapted an interpretive paradigm, based on the social construction of `truth` (Burton and Bartlett, 2005) in order to generate a greater knowledge about inclusive education of physically and sensory disabled learners in Algerian mainstream schools.

3.3.2 Interpretivism

According to Punch (2009) the paradigm conducted in any research study relies on what the researcher is aiming to explore or investigate. In the current research, the researcher adopts an interpretive paradigm, because it aims to understand the personal views and experiences of the participants. Similarly, Rubin and Rubin (2012) elaborate that the researcher in this approach seeks to explore the participants' experiences and gain a clear perception about their point of views toward their jobs as general teachers in inclusive settings, their attitudes, and the world.

The underpinning of this study is the construction of knowledge based on social reality and individuals' global prospects and how their knowledge forms their decisions in this social life (Radnor, 2001). Since there is no single concrete truth, the field of social science may not be able to uncover the absolute truth or understand what is behind the social fact. Knowledge does not only consist of the interpretation of the meaning of the truth collected. Whereas it consists of the interpretation of the theories and principles collected via the interaction with the surroundings as well. That is to say, social facts and their sense rely on social agents like the investigator and participants working with each other to build knowledge (Denzin and Lincoln, 2008). Thus, knowledge is constructed through individuals' interactions in social occasions (Galbin, 2014). Creswell and Poth (2017b) explain that interpretivism is called social constructivism or constructivism (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2011). The researcher considered it as an appropriate paradigm to formulate understanding about the present practice in Algeria. Opposite to post-positivism, interpretivism view that objectivity does not aim reveal any objective truth and acknowledges that knowledge in itself is subjective. Therefore, the social reality could be recognised through active individuals instead of inactive interpreters of the social life, while the construction of meaning derives from interaction with their environment (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2011). The interpretive research approach views individuals as realising their social facts through social interactions, so the researcher concentrates on exploring, describing, and interpreting social reality (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2011).

So, the focus of the current study is to understand the teachers' perceptions and experiences, whilst acknowledging that there is no single reality. This implies that the methodological approach that enables the researcher to comprehend the constructed interpretations of teachers based on their personal experiences is justified in this context, hence a qualitative interpretive paradigm was chosen. This will allow the participants to share their understanding, views and personal

experiences about inclusive education. The assumption is that each participant in the study will form his/her own interpretations about teaching in inclusive contexts (Liamputtong, 2016). The aim of interpretive/constructivism research paradigm is understanding the participants' experiences (Cohen and Manion, 1994) in their individual social contexts, acknowledging that reality is a product of social construction (García, 2015). Therefore, this approach reflects their socially constructed perceptions of and experiences towards inclusive education in some public schools in Algeria.

3.4 Research Methodology

Savage and Erten (2015) argue that in inclusive schools, educators have a significant role that involves the production of classroom environments which enable (or hinder) classroom learning, that ultimately is linked to learners' outcomes. Thus, the perceptions and experiences of teachers towards inclusive education for students with physical and sensory disabilities are to be the main focus of the present investigation.

The qualitative research design will support the research questions of this study through recording research participants' experiences in their normal situations for the sake of obtaining a comprehensive and strong description (Denzin and Lincoln, 2011). In qualitative research the researcher uses data collection strategies that are parallel with the way individuals behave in their everyday life (Taylor, Bogdan and DeVault, 2016). For that reason, it is significant to conduct qualitative study in their natural context. According to (Merriam, 1988), a qualitative research inquiry provides the appropriate design to understand and investigate how individuals realise and interpret an educational phenomenon. The discussion of 'qualitative data' will help the production of new knowledge and better comprehension of research topics' perceptions and experiences toward inclusive education (Corbin and Strauss, 2008).

Qualitative research methods best enable answering "why" and "how" types of research questions that focus on existing social problems (Yin, 2009). The research questions of this study are based on exploring "how" the research participants comprehend and experience inclusive education in Algeria. In this study, the researcher will watch, listen to, and talk with participants since each individual' perspective is seen equally significant for a researcher conducting qualitative research approach.

As Mudau elaborates (2004) qualitative approach provides an investigator with a chance to get in the individual's experience, and through this a researcher can get various answers about specific forms of interest in research. Additionally, Cloete (2002) stated that a qualitative design is compatible with research in inclusive education. The qualitative method in this research is expressed through the use of a multi method approach.

3.5 The study design: selection of approaches and methods

Yanow and Schwartz-Shea (2015) argue that investigators' philosophical standpoints impact the way they conduct any give research inquiry. Creswell (2014) defines the research design as an action program that directs the investigator during the whole research procedure, starting from data gathering to analysis, in compliance with the research questions and objectives. Accordingly, a selection of study design demonstrates the decision of the researcher in regard to the prioritising given to a set of scopes of the study procedure. Similarly, it clarifies the plan utilised by the investigator in accordance with the way the study will be conducted; the type of knowledge the researcher shall be searching for and the organization of the research work like research samples, information gathering, analysing data, and the way to review the results (Radnor, 2001). In order to realize the research goals and objectives, the researcher has adopted an exploratory case study design because it is assumed to be most flexible to help data collection from Algerian mainstream schools to generate broad comprehension of the study. Further to this, as believed by the subjectivist ontology, meaning or fact takes place while a researcher involves with the facts of the world (O'Leary, 2017).

3.5.1 Study design and exploratory approach

The exploratory approach is most appropriate to examine the case study which shapes the foundation of my study, results' questioning, essentially, the whole of investigation process. The aim of exploratory research approach is to acquire a better comprehension of the personal experiences of the research participants, an attempt to interact with their world and make sense for those engaged in this research, on the basis of the participants' social and historical views (Bryman, 2016). This research is focused on community and social meaning to comprehend the educational problems in a society, explain a social issue for example inclusive education and determine the

direction where the educational system and considering physically and sensory disabled students in Algerian schools (Thomas, 2013).

According to Newby (2013) the exploratory research is an inductive investigation of a topic in order to illustrate and resolve an issue, but it is not a means to confirm existing theory. Likewise, the researcher in exploratory approach begins from new experience, wishing to learn further about the crucial elements of individuals' interaction in social environments (Denscombe, 2014). Brown (2006) explains that exploratory research seeks to tackle novel issues when the issue is not obvious, or there is insufficient research. Thus, different approaches like explanatory or descriptive, could not achieve this aim. The process is useful to understand a phenomenon's thought procedure, gives understanding of perceptions and attitudes, and produce ideas (Neelankavil, 2015). On the contrary, the use of whatever new information from that exploration relies on the comprehension and evaluation of "why", "what", and "how" to learn from the teachers' perceptions and experiences (Thomas, 2017).

The exploratory approach does not aim to provide readers and decision makers with final solution to overcome the difficulties and barriers that face the actual inclusive schooling. However, it proposes some strategies and methods that have not been tested to establish inclusive education. Furthermore, Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2009), claim that investigators think about their philosophical presumptions and beliefs to better connect theory and practice within the entire study procedure. Accordingly, the exploratory research method does not provide a concentration on the views of participants in their social life only; but is a more appropriate method to capture and grasp the participants' voices as well as understand their social life (Murphy *et al.*, 1998). Similarly, Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2009) explain that by utilising the exploratory approach a researcher could gain data featured by fullness and richness of details and descriptions with real individuals in actual situations, which is important to explore participants' life and comprehend their prospects, ideas, and views in greater clarity.

3.5.2 Considered Alternative Approaches

Among the decisions that a researcher has to make from the beginning is the selection of appropriate approaches and strategies to accomplish the research work. the choice of the study approach relies on the model that direct the search activities, for instance, the epistemological

beliefs that guides the study and methodology which forms the basis of the research design, and ontological assumptions which is about the nature of humankind and reality (Marshall and Rossman, 2014). While that choice was taken, a positivist model would have been unable to provide answers for this study. The principles of the positivist model were considered as inappropriate for the investigation work being conducted from a methodical approach or to spotlight on the passivity and objectivity of people (Creswell, 2013). The positivist paradigm of neutral, objective knowledge depends on meaning impression and that could only be developed through using experimental, objective approaches like ending the research tools such as surveys to the participants, or the observation of participants in the laboratory (Cope, 2014). These methods could be suitable for scientific studies, they are not automatically considered appropriate for the current study because of the complexity of the nature of people in the educational context or any different social study (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2017).

Moreover, Berg and Lune (2012) argue that exclusion or inclusive education could not be counted or measured like in exact sciences. Likewise, Brannen (2017) argue that these are more appropriate for researchers who prefer quantitative approach based on data gathering methods which concentrate on collecting statistical techniques and accurate information such as statistical computation to introduce proof in quantitative style. This research, however, is directed by interpretive epistemology and constructionist ontology that aim to comprehend the experiences of participants, in which it would interpret via the perceptions of the researcher (Miles, Huberman and Saldana, 2013). In the present study, the researcher is interested in the involvement in the social life of the participants and the way to unravel the different meanings and views that the research participants had generated from the social reality, which involves direct interaction with research participants. The engagement in the social world of the participants will allow a broader comprehension of inclusive schooling in a way that numbers could not measure or count. The researcher is the significant measuring instrument (Silverman, 2016), fully engaged, listen to the different opinions of participants, energetic in the study and not isolated. this familiarity with the participants in the study empowers an extensive, rich, and detailed description of social reality that the participants have experienced, and that would not have been gathered through any other research approach (Creswell and Poth, 2017a). Even though, this methodological approach 'limits' data generalizability, the epistemological interpretive assumptions call the qualitative investigators for its engagement in the approach to the social reality of the participants. The investigator

transcribes, interprets, takes notes, and records interviews from focus groups and research participants (Crotty, 2020), for the aim of determining a deeper information of the research subject. Further to this, Silverman (2016), reveals that post-positivism and positivists concentrate on the measurement of possible reasons of a situation that impacts a result via the use of statistical instruments. Therefore, reliability, generalisability, validity, precision, and objectivity are utilised to evaluate the strictness of qualitative research. However, qualitative studies have their own specific standards for evaluating the quality of their results, such as transferability, confirmability of validity, objectivity, trustworthiness, and reliability. These standards are considered significant within the interpretivist model of research (Creswell and Poth, 2017a). This research would not have taken panoramic sight of inclusive schooling or look over proportions, prevalence, and trends of specific features of individuals such as what happen in surveys. It could have been hard to solve the issues of establishing inclusive schools via systematic investigation, which is usually envisaged like a cyclic procedure that is subsumed in research activities.

Other qualitative methods like documentary analysis could not have permitted an overall vision of the research participants in the real social settings via the investigator's eyes (Silverman, 2016), as well as view things which a researcher may not have viewed if utilizing quantitative data or structured methods. For those reasons, in this study the researcher adopted an exploratory interpretivist approach where general teachers of students with physical and sensory disabilities are partners in the research, for a common objective of addressing the barriers that prevent inclusion within the Algerian public schools. The researcher has chosen the case study to afford an opportunity to understand the research participants and the way they behave with their social world. While Stake (2005) argues that other types of qualitative approaches like ethnography would have been deemed appropriate for the intended case study, the aim of ethnography is to figure out the way culture functions inside a whole culture-shared community instead of exploring a problem utilising the case as a particular example or developing a deeper comprehension of a unique case. This doctoral research project, however, is not concerned with how cultures inside schools in Algeria function but instead focuses on the perception of teachers in relation to inclusive education in Algeria.

3.5.3 Case study approach

Over recent years, the case study approach has become common as a methodology in educational research (Yin, 2009). A case study is an in-depth description and examination of a confined system (Merriam, 2009). Among the advantages of adopting a case study is enabling for an in-depth data which could not be gained by using other designs of study (Denscombe, 2014). According to, Fisher and Buglear (2007) considering the flexibility in case study research, a number of possibilities and variations help an investigator to provide a comprehensive description to the research subject. Thus, a case study is considered as better approach for the current research because it has been found effective for in-depth study of a phenomenon within the lived environment. It allows the researcher to gain detailed information about the constant interactions of inclusive education as understood and experienced by general educators in public primary schools in Algeria. The educational system of Algeria is the same all over the country, so the researcher has chosen a single case study where she selected one region will be a representation to the whole country. The selection of the particular city was based on that the researcher already has done her master dissertation in this region, so she already had and thereby familiarity with this specific context.

Yin (2017) explains that techniques used in the case study design are keenly chosen in order to assure objectivity and fairness in reporting findings. These techniques are carefully selected to be suitable for studying real-world phenomena in their natural context. In this thesis, the case study focuses on particular primary schools where inclusive education of students with physical and sensory disabilities takes place. The case is identified and examined using particular standards. For example, specific geographic area, particular timeframe for gathering data in the domain while the case will be explored, and defining the identity of the research participants engaged in the study (Creswell and Poth, 2017a). The chosen standards are based on the homogeneous case sampling (Palinkas *et al.*, 2015) of schools as research units because their unique identity and identical features that allowed a holistic view of inclusive schools. In carrying out this research, the researcher has not intended to access all educators of Relizane schools or the larger Algerian country because it could not have been possible to generate a collective study of schools. The rationale for selecting the case study approach was because it is more suitable to address the type of questions as "how", "what", and "Why" and the investigated issue is in real life context. In other

words, case studies are valuable for answering questions that require in-depth investigation and analysis of real-world situations. Likewise, it provides a detailed understanding of a complicated subject or problem that could add strength or expand experience to what was already common via past studies (Klein, 2012). Hence, it is not for replication, comparability aims, or expanding new theory (Eisenhardt and Graebner, 2007). Whereas readers in other regions of Algeria could use concepts from the results and suggestions of this case study then coordinate with their own experiences (Stake, 2013) or for comparing the empirical findings for the aim of comprehending individuals' motivation (Yin, 2009).

Newby (2013) elaborates on methods that are relevant to case study methodology namely, it is unique, and people think that they could learn from this case, to examine solutions of a previous problem or due to something functions in way good, a case being unusual or typical.

The single case study approach considered to function well when the researcher has an overall view of the different aspects of the difficulties of inclusive education and the way they are connected, instead of dealing with separated elements (Yin, 2017). Therefore, in this thesis, an exploratory case study methodology will be adopted through using focus group discussion and individual semi-structured interviews as the primary data gathering methods in order to capture the teachers' interpretations of their experiences and understanding of inclusive education (Liamputtong, 2016).

3.5.4 The research location and population

The geographic location of this study is in Relizane province in Algeria. Relizane is a city and province situated in Northwest of Algeria. Located on the plain of the Mina-wadi on the western side of the Ouarsenis Mountains. The selection of Relizane zone schools is inspired by a most important understanding of this area due to being living there for twenty-four years. In addition to that, the researcher is already familiar with the context of schools in this region as she has conducted her master dissertation in the same schools of this city. The target participants for this study are general teachers who teach students with physical and sensory disabilities in the primary mainstream schools.

3.5.5 The Role of Gatekeeper

During the last decades, there has been much discussion about the importance of the gatekeeper in the research process. It is clear that gatekeepers serve a specific function within social research (McFadyen and Rankin, 2016). According to McFadyen and Rankin (2016) gatekeeping is defined as a continuous procedure which has a major influence on how much the research project is successful (McFadyen and Rankin, 2016). Moreover, gatekeeping is defined as a word referred to a person who limits or controls the investigator's access to the research participants. For instance, the general director in an institution who is responsible for the final decision-making in regard to whether allowing the researcher access to conduct the study or not (Saunders, 2006). Furthermore, Lune and Berg (2016) explain that a gatekeeper is a person who has the influence or power to allow or deny access to a research environment. Similarly, Gray (2018) defines the gatekeeper as the individual engaged in the process to grant or refuse a person to access to something or someone. Research studies routinely consider the delicate nature of the inquiry, the participants' vulnerability and accessing to the research settings through the gatekeeper (Holloway and Galvin, 2016). Development of research requires combining strategies in the proposal to ensure that the research is conducted according to ethical standards and no harm is caused (Beauchamp and Childress, 2013). Therefore, it is useful for researchers to keep the gatekeepers informed of the research plans and involve them as early as possible in the process (McFadyen and Rankin, 2016). In view of the need for anonymity and confidentiality, much time was spent at the research site. Accordingly, the gatekeeper plays a significant role in the current study as often they identify cases for any given study as well as introducing the researchers to potential participants and inform them about the research aims and objectives.

However, it is vital to clear up the gatekeeper's position in regard to the process of selecting participants for focus group and interviews. Quinn Patton (2002b) states that it is logically that a researcher should select the site that would deliver greater amount of data and have biggest influence on the knowledge development, particularly when the study is carried out at a single location.

In this thesis, a complete access to the data collection will be realized via the gatekeeper, who is the headmaster of primary school, though it is not his role to select research participants.

Numerous authors have suggested issues around gatekeepers in the process of sampling and granting access as well as the potential effect this can have on research findings and the creation

of knowledge (Patton, 2002b). While the gatekeeper in this project did not choose the participants, the access to the research participants had to be approved by him, and he accepted without intervention in selecting participants for the focus group and interviews.

3.5.6 Approaches to sampling

Sampling is a crucial task to assure that there exists enough information to establish a ‘reliable’ data set that allows for informed analysis (Ryan and Bernard, 2003). Thus, in the current research the qualitative sampling methods correspond with the objectives, questions, and the aims of the study with the overall purpose of realising the philosophical depth (Marshall and Rossman, 2014) as well as to decrease the knowledge gap in inclusive education in the context of Algeria. According to Marshall *et al* (2013) the qualitative sampling has apparent similarities with qualitative models in that it occurs in general natural environments where individuals live. Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2013) suggest the adoption of prior consideration elements like representativeness, size, strategy, and access before taking the decision on strategy for sampling. Most of these recommendations are included in the present research. Nonetheless, the representativeness is among the limitations faced, which is considered as a hard task to achieve in individual case studies (Thomas, 2017). On the other hand, as exploratory samples are commonly utilized in smaller-scale qualitative study to primarily collect further ideas, rather than representativeness (Denscombe, 2014), the researcher will attempt to engage in the sampling in order to produce ideas about the inclusive education in Algerian mainstream schools. This research is organised in a way that allows the use of entire recommended elements. Langer (2018) states that there are two approaches that could help researchers to select samples which are probability and non-probability. Naderifar, Goli and Ghaljaie (2017) claim that in the probability sampling approach the rules of probability are implemented as their major characteristic, any sample has an opportunity to be chosen. In these approaches, the opinion of the community members or the investigator does not affect the selecting of samples. The chosen sample is a representative of the public, as well as the investigator could generalise the results to wider society. There are four types of probability sampling namely systematic sampling, cluster sampling, simple random sampling, and stratified sampling.

Since the researcher aims to generate an exploratory sample and not a representative sample, the selection of non-probability approach is more appropriate to evade the need for mere coincidence sampling. Similarly, Schreiber and Asner-Self (2010) explain that the issue is not that in qualitative approach the research participants could not be randomly sampled. Whereas random sampling is not the modal sampling style in this kind of research because certain elements are possibly more crucial in the sampling procedure than random selection. However, other authors like Tongco (2007), argue that probability sampling is originally better than non-probability sampling, that could not be easily applied on interpretivist qualitative study because the methodology does not seek for extensive generalizations. There are four kinds of non-probability sampling strategies namely: convenience sampling, quota sampling, snowball sampling, and purposive sampling. Tansey (2007) argues that quota sampling seeks to assure that particular features have existed in a sample matching with their placement in the wider population. Specific proportions are assured when using quota sampling. Although, lack of rules for selecting sample can result in increased representation of topics, or unintentional investigator bias, so samples with particular features are excluded. Moreover, Murphy *et al* (1998) propose practical considerations needs to be embedded with a responsibility to pulling out samples in an ethical and systematic manner.

For this reason, the researcher decided against quota sampling because the coincidence choice may lead to more crucial sampling bias, and to avoid neglecting possibly helpful participants.

3.5.7 Sampling participating teachers

According to Njie and Asimiran (2014) the notion of sampling in qualitative research is defined by the kind of data the investigator seeks to gain as well as which areas, documents, or which group of individuals would be more appropriate to get it from. Patton (2002b) states that purposive sampling is broadly used method in qualitative studies to select and identify rich-data cases to the more efficient utilization of limited means. This requires the selection and identification of individuals or a group of people who are specifically experienced with or knowledgeable about the issue of concern (Creswell and Clark, 2011). Similarly, Creswell and Clark (2011) claim that purposeful sampling is used to sample educators, relying on the idea that they could be further knowledgeable about inclusive education and disabled learners more than other individuals in the society. Furthermore, Mertens (2014) states that investigators who adopt interpretivism model favour to choose purposively their samples in order to identify rich data which enable a deeper

understanding. Other researchers agree with the idea that purposeful sampling is able to select cases that are rich data (Patton, 2002b). The major focus of the present research is to gain deeper information from educators' views to comprehend their experiences within the social setting where they work, which is why purposive sampling was selected as a method for this research study.

3.6 Research methods and data saturation

According to Robson (2002) among the advantages of utilising a multi method approach in social research is the confirmation of outcomes arising from one method through using several qualitative methods. Fielding, Fielding and Fielding (1986) agree that using several, complimentary, methods provide opportunities for further understanding to the information gathered. Babbie and Mouton (2001) emphasize on using several methods that it can help to overcome the weaknesses of a single social research method. Therefore, a multi-methods approach combined with a number of qualitative methods was used in this study to investigate various perspectives relating to the goals and objectives of the study. When deciding on a study design, the researcher should look for a design that is clear in regards on how to reach data saturation. Moreover, data saturation is achieved once there is sufficient information to duplicate the study (Walker, 2012). Similarly, Guest, Bunce and Johnson (2006) state that data saturation is reached when the chance of getting extra and new information has been achieved, as well as when additional coding is no more possible.

According to Fusch and Ness (2015), since the study designs are different, there is no one method applicable for all cases to achieve data saturation. Whereas investigators reach an agreement on certain general concepts and principles such as, no new themes, no further data, no extra coding, and the capacity to duplicate the study (Guest, Bunce and Johnson, 2006). How and when a researcher achieves these stages of saturation is different from one study design to another. The concept of data saturation in research is useful, although it lacks to provide any practical rules about the time of reaching data saturation (Guest, Bunce and Johnson, 2006). However, Guest, Bunce and Johnson (2006) claim that data saturation can be reached by at most six interviews based on the sampling size of the participants. On the other hand, Dibley (2011) states that it could be better to think of information in terms of thickness and richness, instead of the number of the sample (Burmeister and Aitken, 2012). Fusch and Ness (2015) argue that the simplest way to distinguish between thick and rich data is to look on thick as quantity and rich as quality. Rich data is detailed, multiple layers, nuanced, and intricate. On the other hand, thick data means a lot of

data. One researcher could have a lot of data that is not rich; by contrast, another could have little of data that is rich. Thus, it is better to attain both. Likewise, Burmeister and Aitken (2012) argue that data saturation is not about the size of sample; however, it is about data depth. For instance, a big number of samplings does not ensure that a researcher will attain data saturation, neither a small number of samples does. Thus, a researcher should select the size of sampling that provide that chance to achieve data saturation.

Accordingly, the sample size for the current study will be 25 participants (teachers who teach students with physical and sensory disabilities in regular primary schools) from multiple primary schools in the same province. The researcher decision was based on some scholars' recommendations which suggest that a range of 15 to 30 interviews for case studies-type approach to qualitative research would consider appropriate (Marshall *et al.*, 2013). Similarly, Boddy (2016) argue that any sample size more than 30 (per geography) in qualitative research is considered too difficult to control and analyse as well as it would require justification. In addition to that, the researcher thought that this number would provide an opportunity to attain data saturation.

According to Schreiber and Asner-Self (2010) the sample size is not crucial issue as in quantitative approach due to the quality and depth of data collected, its affluence in discovering clear opinions of a specific process or situation which is considered more important than numbers. Likewise, Njie and Asimiran (2014) state that in the qualitative research the number of samplings is considered less significant as long as one sample or the few numbers of samples cover the research richness and depth. This study employed a purposive sampling strategy to select 27 general teachers working in mainstream primary schools in Relizane province who teach learners with physical and sensory disabilities.

3.7 The selection and development of research instruments

A basic concept of the research instruments selection is not the only main ethical principle of defending the rights and welfare of research participants, but also the knowledge that individuals are able to interpret and give meaning to the events that occur in their surroundings (Bryman, 2016). Interpretivists think that reality is always changing and that there is no such thing as a singular reality. The researcher developed rigorous data collection instruments in order to generate different realities and learn something fresh from numerous voices. Therefore, several instruments will provide the benefit of exploring more thoroughly with the aim of achieving the study's

objectives and gaining a deeper understanding of research phenomena. In this thesis, the researcher's role is to make sure that the participants' voices, attitudes, feelings, experiences and ideas are addressed while she will learn about their worldviews.

Furthermore, because disability-related concerns are sensitive, the research will search for techniques and methods that would allow her to uncover concepts that are normally uncomfortable to communicate. Creswell (2014) warns against relying on a single data gathering instrument and emphasises that data collection from numerous sources is the best way to do comprehensive and balanced research. Thus, a multi-method approach in the current study includes the use of various qualitative research methods namely: focus group discussion and individual semi-structure interviews. The researcher thinks that it is very fruitful to begin with focus group and then to use the broad themes that will be generated in groups to narrow in and delve more deeply through individual semi-structured interviews as well as it will help to inform the individual interview schedule.

Moreover, to assure that data collection remains purposeful, the researcher creates a Focus group questions Schedule and later to develop an interview guide to help the researcher to remain focused on the research goals.

3.7.1 Focus group discussion

According to Dawson (2007) focus groups require a number of individuals who are chosen to talk about a particular topic. Similar to that, Ruane (2005) claims that a focus group is a conducted group discussion on a subject matter determined by the researcher. Moreover, Anderson and Arsenault (2005) state that the aim of the group interview is to collect in-depth data from the participants who share similar experiences. The group discussion is made to gain the maximum points of views, feelings, and attitudes of the participants. Anderson and Arsenault (2005) argue that the 'group interview' is best way for gathering qualitative information since it affords a comfortable, natural, and secure atmosphere. Marvasti (2004) agree and state that the 'group discussion' inspires participants, and participants will get the chance to reply and discuss each other's concepts. Even more, there are various opinions among philosophers on the number of the group discussion. For instance, Dörnyei (2007) stated that six (06) to ten (10) participants are enough or sometimes six (06) to twelve (12). Similarly, Kumar (2011) claimed that eight (08) to

ten (10) individuals are sufficient for a group interview. However, what is essential in regard of the group size is that the group should not be too small and not too large (Kumar, 2011), because it could impact the group discussion negatively. Similar to Kumar's view, Dörnyei (2007) states that less than six (06) participants could restrict the potential of the collective knowledge. On the other hand, too large size group would make it harder for every individual to participate. In the current study, the researcher intends to select the average size group that is 10 which could provide the chance to reach data saturation.

Considering the previous aims of the focus group discussion, the current study will use a focus group discussion as one tool of collecting data. The target participants of the exploratory focus group discussion are general teachers of learners with physical and sensory disabilities in the public primary schools in Relizane province. This will be conducted to explore their perceptions and to gain further understanding about the situation of inclusive education of physically and sensory disabled learners. Kumar (2011) argues that a group interview supports an open and free discussion among the participants and the researcher; in this study it will help to collect as much data as possible from the participants, and it will allow the researcher to gather information about their perceptions, feelings, attitudes, experiences, which will help to generate the main themes concerning the subject matter under investigation.

Considering that there is a lack of literature about the particular problems impacting inclusive education of physically and sensory disabled learners in the Algerian context, conducting focus group discussion seem to be useful for giving relevant subjects and questions for the next step. In this study, the focus group discussion will provide general understanding about the context in which it major aim is to develop ideas and generate themes rather than collecting findings (Oppenheim, 1992). The information and data collected from this stage will then assist and inform the composition of main themes and questions for the individual semi-structured interviews in the second phase of the study.

3.7.2 Semi-Structured interviews

Dawson (2007) highlights that there are various types of interviews, namely structured, semi-structured, and unstructured interviews. Dawson (2007) elaborates that the most widely type of interviews used in qualitative research is the semi-structured interview. A semi-structured

interview is a qualitative research method that involves a series of open-ended questions based on the subject area the researcher wants to explore. The semi-structured nature of it provides opportunities for both the researcher and participant to discuss particular themes in further details (Young *et al.*, 2018) and this flexibility of asking questions provides the researcher with a chance to discuss in depth about a specific topic. Due to this, the researcher in the current study chose the semi-structured interview method for collecting data.

Gray (2004) states that the semi-structured interviews are not standardised. Similarly, Denscombe (2010) provides further thought that a researcher has questions to ask the research participants, yet s/he probably will not ask every single of them; alternatively, another questions might be required as a new issue arises. In the current study, the researcher will conduct guided discussions instead of structured questions, using semi-structured interviews that aim to explore the research questions and following the ideas that the researcher founded which result to a curiosity in exploring inclusion issues. That is to say, despite that, the researcher follows a continuous line of investigation; her questions are flexible and not rigid. For this reason, it is possible that a researcher probes answers, explores feelings and motives, and pursues ideas, that questionnaires could never make (Yin, 2017). The data gathering process utilizing standardized structured interviews was excluded since this method does not provide sufficient flexibility (Seidman, 2019). Bazeley (2013) states that investigators have identified a group of research questions to be explored and striving to sustain distance with the research participants but must not be appeared as detached in the procedure of obtaining knowledge. Thus, a standardized form as a process of following knowledge would have made the research ineffective because adaptability and flexibility are crucial. The current research needs an interview approach that supports further ideas to be generated in this study without letting the participants feel they are being questioned. Therefore semi-structured interviews will be used in order to ask and inquire further questions based on participants' views. According to Dawson (2009) , to conduct the semi-structured interview there could have a set of questions to be raised. In this current study, the researcher will prepare the questions of the individual semi-structured interviews after examining the initial phase of focus group discussion and after doing extensive reading about relevant literature. In this phase, instead of depending on general personal answers indicated by the focus group discussion, the researcher will use individual semi-structured interviews in order to gather further in-depth information.

Due to the covid19 restrictions in Algeria, there are limitations to travel there and conduct the interviews face to face with participants. Thus, the researcher will contact the participants for the data collection via a virtual meeting. The virtual meeting can happen in different platforms where the participants can select based on their convenience and preferences such as zoom meeting, and Microsoft teams. Additionally, the researcher will record the interviews in order to transcribe, discuss, analyse, and interpret the data.

3.7.3 Methodological triangulation approaches

A significant feature of research that is employed in designing a research instrument is making use of numerous approaches to address the research questions and to solve the issue of internal validity (Creswell, 2013). As well as make the research findings more trustworthy (Creswell and Poth, 2017a). Denzin`s study in 1978 defined four types of triangulations: methodological triangulation, investigator triangulation, theoretical triangulation, and data triangulation (Denzin, 2017). The present study avoided exclusive or excessive emphasis on any single method, which could have distorted the research's image of specific slice of reality under investigation (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2013), and used one approach which is the methodological triangulation. In this study, the methodological triangulation will be applied through the combination of focus group discussion and individual semi-structured interviews. It will be done basically through the verification of one approach`s outcomes by employing the other method. Furthermore, the triangulation method entailed investigating the perceptions and experiences of general teachers towards inclusive education of physically and sensory disabled learners, through focus group discussion and individual interviews. Individual semi-structured interviews will be used to gain further descriptions, explanations, thoughts, perceptions, and experiences of teachers toward inclusive education that would be impossible to acquire through focus groups. Consequently, combining and connecting data provides unique results (Thomas, 2013) contributing to the study's accuracy, credibility, and dependability (Robson and McCartan, 2016). Triangulation will provide an in-depth view regarding inclusive educational practice in Algerian schools through exploring the general educators` perceptions and experiences. Similarly, it is argued that triangulation gives reassurance and confirmation by combining identical results from diverse methodologies, and it can also provide a partial representation of the full picture (Thurmond, 2001). Despite all the

advantages of triangulation, researchers should be aware of its limits, which could compromise its credibility (Thurmond, 2001). Nevertheless, Thomas (2017) claimed that the lack of similar results, owing to parallel data sets does not constitute rejection because it demonstrates cooperation. Therefore, for better interpretative validity, researchers are urged to attach more emphasis to good evidence (Miles and Huberman, 1994).

3.8 Building concepts of data analysis

According to Creswell (2015) the analysis of qualitative data needs continuous thought from the investigator to understand the results. The analytical unit of this research is at group and individual level. The researcher will adopt Braun and Clarke's stages of thematic analysis as a guideline to do her analysis of the data collected from the individual and focus group interviews. Moreover, Braun and Clarke (2006) suggested thematic analysis as an approach that could reflect the reality and to unpick or unveil the truth through a flexible method. Similarly, Thematic analysis is an approach for determining, analysing, and reporting patterns within a given dataset (Braun and Clarke, 2006). The purpose of thematic analysis is to determine shared and contrasting realities in participants' experiences. It has been regarded as a broadly adopted but ill-defined research method (Braun and Clarke, 2006). Braun and Clarke (2006) argue that, although thematic analysis is not related to any specific theoretical framework, it should be regarded as method in itself. They assert that thematic analysis provides a valuable research instrument, which might possibly provide a rich and in - depth, yet difficult explanation of data because of its theoretical freedom. Thematic analysis entails generating themes from data through a robust method of data familiarization and analysis. When it comes to data analysis, there are range of methodologies that could be used. The inductive approach requires deriving themes from the data without referencing the researcher's theoretical ideas (Patton, 2002a). This method, often known as a data-driven method, usually requires a detailed analysis of the entire data collection. On the other hand, deductive thematic analysis is guided by the researcher's theoretical viewpoints, with the emphasis on features of the data that are of special interest to the researcher and could be clearly linked to certain theories or research topics. From a constructivist perspective, the researcher will use an inductive approach to data analysis in order to examine each participant's viewpoints without imposing the limits of current theoretical frameworks connected to the research issues. Nonetheless, as indicated by

(Braun and Clarke, 2006) it is crucial to recognise that in real-world research, these methodologies are not always as clearly defined, and researchers cannot be free of their theoretical views and prior knowledge in how they analyse and interpret the data. The research data can be analysed at several levels during thematic analysis. The researcher can either concentrate on the apparent or semantic meanings represented in the information provided by participants, or the data can be analysed at an interpretive level, which examines hidden meanings inherent in the given dataset (Braun and Clarke, 2006).

As stated by (Braun and Clarke, 2006) any type of analysis is equally valid when done effectively, and the approach taken is typically determined by the objective of the investigation. In-depth semantic meaning analysis entails more than just presenting the data's surface meaning; it also requires a level of interpretation and discussion. The aim of this type of analysis is to find common semantic patterns inside and between transcripts, as well as to discover and investigate the basic concepts, ideologies, assumptions, and conceptualizations that created the participants' worldview. The researcher considers the patterns' importance, as well as their greater interpretations and connotation, frequently in light of earlier literature and study. In the context of the present study, and from an interpretive standpoint, the researcher seeks to develop a better understanding of the perceptions and experiences of general teachers in relation to their practices. In order to identify critical issues that must be addressed and informed in regard to the inclusive education of learners with disabilities and particularly those with physical and sensory disabilities in Algerian schools. A data-driven method that explores semantic themes will be used during data analysis and interpretation.

In order to analyse the data, the following actions, which are largely in accordance with the steps proposed by Braun and Clarke (2006), will be taken; Firstly, researchers should familiarize themselves with the data, which will require verbatim transcription of the interviews. The researcher will listen to the interviews several times to make sure they were accurate, noting any noticeable pauses or hesitations. The researcher then will go through reviewing and reading the dataset for several times, noting interesting points and emerging themes that seemed to be important. Secondly, they should generate primary codes. According to Leech and Onwuegbuzie (2011), coding the data should be after reading the interviews transcriptions many times. Similarly, Holton (2010) explain that coding has many challenges as well as it is not the unique method to

analyse data. Similarly, Saldana (2015) claims that the procedure of coding has proved to be helpful to search for patterns and meanings in data. There are different ways for coding the data, since researchers are restricted with their research goals and nature. Generally, data could be coded inductively, deductively, or by combining both methods when appropriate. In this study, the researcher has decided to use the inductive method. That decision is based on the exploratory approach that aims to build theory where there is no prior knowledge about the case. As well as, based on the point of view proposed by (Patton, 2002b) who argues that data analysis will be inductive where the researcher attempts to discover themes, categories, and patterns. The researcher will create first codes using the entire data set as a reference. Each data segment will be identified, and colour coding will be used to classify any patterns or interconnections that will be identified between parts. At this point, each piece of information will be represented equally. The researcher will gather the data segments linked with each initial code. The initial codes will be evaluated, and some could be flattened and restructured into further meaningful and coherent codes, after going over the statements and pondering on whether they related together in a cohesive and meaningful way. Thirdly, searching for themes, in which the researcher will look for subjects, patterns between codes will be identified, then codes will be organized and integrated into meaningful groups in order to establish initial themes. The fourth step is revising the themes. During this step, the researcher will review the initial themes. Additionally, each theme's statements will be reviewed to see if they are meaningful and constituted a logical structure. Some of the original themes could be subsequently removed or combined to form new broad themes and sub-themes that could be more cohesive. At this stage, some of the codes will be also merged or submerged into other themes as it could be more suitable. Thereafter, the researcher will create a thematic map for each subject to show how codes and sub-themes connected to the major themes. Another step is naming and defining the themes. After creating maps based on themes, each theme, subtheme and code will be named to assure that they appropriately reflect the contents. The last step is drafting the report.

The researcher will analyse the data in Arabic then she will translate the findings into English selectively, as needed, to stay as closely as possible to the original language that used by the participants (Larkin, de Casterlé and Schotsmans, 2007).

According to Bryman and Bell (2015), the most crucial progress in qualitative research from the mid of 1980s was the onset of computer software which eliminates the typing tasks connected with data retrieval and manual coding. Consequently, NVivo had emerged before data analytics. However, the data could not be nourished automatically, and the majority done manually. Similarly, it is stated that the investigator needs to further interpret, coding, and retrieving data (Bryman and Bell, 2015). Moreover, Robson (2011) found that the software program is especially difficult to manipulate and decided to deal with the data analysis manually in order to avoid further stress, as well as to allow for further immediate and direct interpretation. It is commonly suggested by qualitative researchers that the data analysis is not a separated stage, but that the processes of collecting data, analysing data, and drafting the reports are interconnected and frequently conducted in research continuously and simultaneously (Bazeley, 2013). Indeed, Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2013) point out that data analysis is important in all stages, as long as there is a deeper hidden sense in initial data that have to be debriefed carefully to be meaningful. In the current thesis, the point of departure for analysing data is the research questions which indicated the information that will be gathered for analysis.

In this thesis, the researcher will upload, transcribe, and analyse all data gathered from focus group and semi-structured interviews in Nvivo. Interviews will be digitally transcribed even though it will be stressful work and time consuming. Brinkmann and Kvale (2014) explain that they were able to organize the interviews with their participants as well as simplify the early analytical stages through writing down all conversations. Thus, the reward of the transcription is when researchers learn about their interviewing styles and are able to listen to their participants, which help in the initial analytic processes. Likewise, Jackson and Bazeley (2019) claim that in Nvivo, audios can be played, stopped, paused, slow/fast, and skip backward/forward of the audio. These options are very helpful to decrease the duration in audios` transcription. The emphasis of transcriptions will be to tell about the experiences of the participants instead of the analysis of language used by participants in the interviews. The researcher will check the transcripts for accuracy through attending the audio recordings more than one time.

3.9 The Researcher's Role: Positionality and Reflexivity

The current study is grounded in an Interpretivist and Social Constructionist framework, which fundamentally posits that subjective knowledge is generated not in a vacuum, but through the continuous, dynamic interaction between the researcher and the social realities experienced by participants. This perspective necessitates the rejection of the traditional scientific ideal of the objective, neutral observer (Yanow and Schwartz-Shea, 2015). Instead, the investigator is recognized as the primary interpretive instrument, whose perspective is central to the ultimate construction of meaning from the raw data. Consequently, in alignment with the methodological requirements of Reflexive Thematic Analysis (RTA), it is imperative to clearly articulate the researcher's positionality and document the reflexive practices employed consistently throughout the research process.

3.9.1 Researcher Positionality: Insider and Outsider Status

My engagement with this study placed me strategically at a complex point between an 'insider' and an 'outsider' perspective. This dual status inevitably influenced the direction of both the data generation and the subsequent interpretive analysis (Dwyer and Buckle, 2009).

3.9.1.1 Contextual Insider (Geographic and Cultural)

My extensive history with the research location positioned me as a Contextual Insider. Having resided in the Relizane city for a significant period and previously carried out academic investigations within the same geographical boundaries, I possessed an inherent understanding of the local educational setting, the administrative protocols, and the regional linguistic variations. This level of intrinsic familiarity proved invaluable, streamlining the process of gaining entry to the participating schools and accessing the educators. Crucially, this established rapport helped to build immediate trust with the general teacher population.

3.9.1.2 Professional Outsider (Thematic Role)

Despite my regional familiarity, my professional identity as an academic researcher, rather than a teacher within the Algerian mainstream primary system, created a necessary 'outsider' status

concerning the participants' specific daily practice. This distance was advantageous, providing the freedom to pose fundamental, exploratory questions and to challenge implicit, taken-for-granted assumptions about inclusive education that a colleague or 'insider' might otherwise be likely to overlook.

3.9.1.3 Empathic Collaborator (Disability Focus)

The sensitive and exploratory nature of this qualitative investigation, particularly its focus on disability-related issues, required me to adopt a perspective that facilitated a deep understanding of the teachers' complex emotional and professional worlds. Consequently, I was positioned as an empathic collaborator rather than a detached or critical evaluator. This stance was essential, aligning the research with the social constructionist goal of exploring the teachers' realities as partners in the construction of knowledge.

3.9.2 Reflective Practice: Utilizing Analytic Memos

Following an interpretive paradigm required an explicit and rigorous process of reflexivity, which is a core tenet of Reflexive Thematic Analysis (RTA) (Braun and Clarke, 2021). Within this study, reflexivity extended beyond merely stating my positionality; it encompassed a sustained, critical examination of how my existing knowledge and contextual proximity might have affected the research findings.

To keep up this necessary critical self-awareness, the primary methodological instrument employed was the systematic maintenance of Analytic Memos (Saldaña, 2016):

3.9.2.1 Recording Prior Assumptions

During the early stages, specifically the data familiarization and initial coding phases, dedicated memos served as a record for my explicit prior assumptions regarding inclusive education in the Relizane city, assumptions coming directly from my background knowledge. This was a vital step for acknowledging and thereby limiting the influence of any initial expectations before the data analysis could potentially confirm them.

3.9.2.2 Justifying Analytic Decisions

Memos were consistently generated to document the underlying rationale for specific coding choices and the development of thematic constructions. This involved noting instances where an interviewee's word choice or concept aligned too closely with my prior expectations, thereby requiring me to deliberately challenge that immediate interpretation and actively search for diverse or alternative meanings within the dataset.

3.9.2.3 Governing the Interpretive Framework

These memos functioned as a repository for capturing any subjective feelings or competing viewpoints that emerged during the analytical process. This mechanism ensured that these personal responses were not only acknowledged but were actively used as a resource for achieving a deeper, richer understanding, preventing them from unintentionally biasing the overall analysis.

By documenting and critically examining the research direction in this comprehensive manner, the inherent subjectivity of the qualitative approach was successfully used. The researcher's position was transformed into an asset for richer interpretation, guaranteeing that the resulting themes originated from a fully transparent and critically engaged analytical journey.

3.10 Ethical issues in fieldwork

According to Newby (2010) the ethics and principles of research must be defined as a core part of planning any research to determine, from the start, if it is possible to gather data in the intended method. Moreover, Denscombe (2014) states that it is expected from social investigators to deal with the research methods activity in ethical way irrespective of the research approaches or research paradigm adopted. In this thesis, before starting the data collection process, the researcher will send a study protocol to the ethical committee in the University of the West of Scotland to be reviewed and approved. In addition to that, she will inform the participants about the nature of the study and the conditions in regard to time commitments, in a way that they can make a well-informed choice regarding their participation.

The researcher will ensure that the rights of participants are respected as described in the ethical guidelines for educational research by the BERA (British Educational Research Association)

before starting the study. There are three main elements stated in this guideline namely respect for individuals involved in the research, justice, and assuring confidentiality and anonymity of participants' data (British Educational Research Association., 2011). In regard to respecting people, the researcher will ask the participants to sign a consent form to show their agreement to take part in the study as well as the researcher will inform them that they have the right to withdraw from the study at any time without any penalty or giving reasons. Furthermore, ensuring confidentiality and anonymity is crucial in research requiring the individuals' participation (British Educational Research Association, 2011). In the current thesis, the researcher will ensure that participants' privacy will be protected while collecting, analysing, and reporting data. Their answers will be remained anonymous and all personal information given will be held in strict confidence. Justice is defined as fairness and treating people equally (British Educational Research Association, 2011), justice in this thesis is assured through the process of determining the possible barriers that would lead to a sense of unfairness regarding students with physical and sensory disabilities. The researcher will give a consent forms to the participants where they should sign and return them at end of the interview, confidentiality will be maintained throughout., and researcher will not present any personal information such as real names in the data analysis or the thesis in general.

Marczyk, DeMatteo and Festinger (2005) explain that conducting research with people carries risks. Such risks can include minor inconvenience and sensitive discussions that could influence participants' emotional or physical state. Likewise, Ruane (2005) state that research which does not take into consideration the matters of ethics is incompatible with a basic ethical commitment to the protection of the study participants. Equally, Ruane (2005) points out that it is hard to expect what is going to happen when conducting the research. Yet, the researcher has to bear in mind the main principle "do not harm".

Flick (2007) argues that a good and ethical research has standards. These include an explicit approval where the research participants confirm that they comprehend what the study is about and accept to participate in the study, participants should not be tricked, participants' privacy should be protected, data accuracy, participants have to be respected, safety of the participants, and justice that reveals the advantages and disadvantages of taking part in the research. The investigator should consider the ethical matters that could influence the participants and research site negatively while conducting the study. Creswell (2012) states that the research site has to be

respected by the researcher. To do that, the researcher could request permission to be able to access to the research site. In this thesis, the researcher will write a letter to the schools to get permission to conduct the research project, and the consent form will be signed by the participants which shows their agreement to participate in the research as (Creswell, 2012) getting permission before collecting data is the right path of conducting research. Moreover, Creswell (2012) argued that the researcher should respect the participants' privacy such as to hide things which can identify them in the research for instance the participants' names. Accordingly, the information obtained from participants have to be confidential as well as respecting people who decide to withdraw from the study or those who do not like to take part in the research. To support of this idea, Dawson (2007) recommended that the investigator should ensure the confidentiality and anonymity of the participants. In the present thesis, the confidentiality and anonymity of the research participants will be respected.

3.11 Review of the Chapter

This chapter has provided information on the methodology and methods utilised to explore the perceptions, attitudes, experiences, and ideas of individual teachers participated in this study. The research problem has been related to a wider methodological approach in order to explain "why and how" this research fits into the qualitative interpretivist paradigm. This led to the argument that an exploratory case study was deemed the appropriate approach to provide a deeply detailed perspective of general teachers' perceptions and experiences towards the inclusion of students with physical and sensory disabilities as well as to describe the real practice of inclusive education in the public Algerian schools.

The researcher has demonstrated that she will do everything possible to perform her research in accordance with accepted research ethics. The researcher remained convinced that the methodologies and strategies adopted are the most relevant and appropriate for this study. The data collection in this research will be conducted through two steps. The first step, exploratory focus group discussion with general teachers of learners with physical and sensory disabilities. This will be conducted to explore their perceptions and experiences towards the inclusive education of physically and sensory disabled learners. As well as to provide general understanding about the context in which it major aim is to develop ideas and generate themes rather than collecting findings. The information and data will be collected from this stage will demonstrate particular

developments for some of the questions for the individual semi-structured interviews in the second phase of the study. In the second phase, the researcher will prepare the questions of the individual semi-structured interviews after examining the initial phase of focus group discussion and after doing extensive reading about relevant literature. In addition to that, the researcher used individual semi-structured interviews in order to gather further in-depth information rather than depending on general personal answers indicated by the focus group discussion. A framework of thematic analysis will be used to identify relevant themes originating from both focus group discussion and individual semi-structured the interviews, allowing the data to be immersed. To bring this section to a close, it is imperative to highlight that the primary aim of this research is to get a clear and detailed understanding of general teachers' perceptions and experiences towards the inclusive education of children with physical and sensory disabilities in public Algerian schools. Lastly, the researcher will ensure that the research participants are treated with dignity and respect, as well as that the research data is trustworthy and provable. The findings resulting from the key themes identified are presented in the next chapter.

4 Chapter Four: Data presentation and critical theoretical analysis

4.1 Introduction

The main aim of this exploratory qualitative case study is to examine the teachers' perceptions of and experiences towards the inclusive education of physically and sensory disabled learners in the public primary schools around Relizane province in Algeria. The research approach, methodology, and data collection instruments were described in the chapter preceding this one.

The major research question of the study, "What are the perceptions, attitudes, and experiences of general teachers concerning the inclusive education of students with physical and sensory disabilities in the Algerian public primary schools?" is addressed by the data presented in this chapter. The results of the data gathered for this investigation are also provided according to the goals of the study, namely:

- To explore the notion of inclusive education from the general teachers' perspectives.
- To investigate the teachers' knowledge, attitudes, and experiences towards the inclusion of learners with physical and sensory disabilities in Algerian public schools.
- To explore the potential implication for teachers' knowledge, attitudes, and experiences of learners with physical and sensory disabilities in Algeria in relation to the education policy.

The current section examines the findings of the research and introduces and evaluates the data gathered using the research techniques described in the chapter before this. The results of the present study are presented in the part that follows with regard to the defined goals and research questions.

4.2 Presenting and Analysing Findings from Focus Groups and Individual Interviews

The researcher in this study has conducted the focus group discussion first with seven participants who are general teachers from various primary schools in Ammi-Mossa city, Relizane province, Algeria. The Second stage was the individual semi-structured interviews with 20 participants (general teachers from different primary schools in Ammi-Mossa city, Relizane province, Algeria).

The provided table below offers a comprehensive overview of the key themes and sub-themes that emerged from both focus group discussion and individual semi-structured interviews conducted on the teachers' perceptions of and experiences towards the inclusive education of physically and sensory disabled learners in the public primary schools in Algeria.

Table 1 Themes and Sub-themes generated from focus group discussion and individual semi-structured interviews

Main themes	Sub-themes	FG	ISI
1-Teachers' attitudes, experiences and perceptions of inclusive education	• Teachers' perceptions regarding inclusive practices	✓	✓
	• Instructional strategies used in the inclusive classrooms.		✓
2-Teacher's understanding of the concept of inclusive education in Algeria	• Medical model	✓	✓
	• Social model	✓	✓
3-Challenges in implementing inclusive education in Algeria	• Lack of knowledge of Inclusive Education policies		✓
	• Lack of teachers' training and personal development in inclusive education	✓	✓
	• Insufficient preparation for teachers	✓	✓
	• Lack of pre-service training in inclusive education	✓	
	• Limited opportunities for in-service training	✓	
	• lack of instructional resources and materials	✓	✓
	• Physical school environment as a barrier to the implementation of inclusive education	✓	✓
	• School infrastructure and amenities	✓	✓
	• Lack of classroom adaptation	✓	✓
	• Lack of staff members at school		✓
	• Lack of curriculum adaptation	✓	✓
	• Lack of teacher- parents collaboration	✓	✓
	• Special classrooms /schools to server disabled learners	✓	✓
• Inadequate report at the school level	✓		

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of Support and Guidance from the Algerian Ministry of Education 	✓	✓
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Behavioural problems 		✓
4-Teachers' perspectives on methods and strategies to improve inclusive education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhancing teachers training and raising their motivation 		✓
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improving school facilities and services 		✓
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhancing Collaboration for Inclusive Education 		✓
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raising awareness of and commitment to inclusive education 		✓
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Laws and regulations 		✓
FG: Focus Group, ISI: Individual Semi-structured Interviews			

The first theme, “teachers’ attitudes, experiences, and perceptions of inclusive education in Algeria”, provides additional insights into teachers’ personal perspectives and beliefs about inclusive education in Algeria. This theme was exclusively explored in individual interviews, highlighting the value of one-on-one discussions for obtaining in-depth information (Rutledge and Hogg, 2020).

The second theme, "Teacher's understanding of the concept of inclusive education in Algeria" reflects the teachers' overall perspectives on inclusive education. This is a complicated issue, especially when participants hold varying viewpoints. This divergence often stems from a lack of clarity or consensus around the core principles of inclusive education (Karalis and Arvanitis, 2023). Although some participants defined inclusive education through the medical model and others through social model, it is evident that neither group fully understood the concept of inclusive education comprehensively as defined in the literature (Doncheva, Habeb Al-Obaydi and Abdul. Hussein, 2023).

The third theme, "Challenges in Implementing Inclusive Education in Algeria" delves into the specific obstacles that teachers face in their efforts to create inclusive classrooms. These challenges include factors such as insufficient teacher training, inadequate physical school environments, and a lack of curriculum adaptation. Interestingly, while all the sub-themes under this category were discussed in both focus groups and individual interviews, it is worth noting that participants may have felt more comfortable sharing their experiences and concerns in the one-on-one setting of individual interviews.

The fourth theme, "Methods and Strategies to Improve Inclusive Education in Algeria" focuses on potential solutions and recommendations for enhancing inclusive practices in Algeria. This theme was primarily explored in individual interviews, suggesting that participants may have felt more confident suggesting specific strategies in a more private setting (Varma *et al.*, 2021). Overall, the table provides a valuable snapshot of the key themes and sub-themes that emerged from the research. By analysing these findings, educators and policymakers can gain a better understanding of the challenges and opportunities related to inclusive education in Algeria and develop targeted interventions to support teachers and students.

4.2.1 Teachers' attitudes, experiences, and perceptions of inclusive education

In this section, the collected data are analysed in order to address the first research question, which is, what are the perceptions, attitudes, and experiences of general teachers concerning the inclusive education of students with physical and sensory disabilities in the Algerian public primary schools?

The participants provided a range of perspectives in response to some questions that were asked in the interview regarding their views, attitudes, and experiences toward the inclusive education. According to the findings, some teachers were in support of inclusive education of pupils with disabilities in mainstream classes, whereas others demonstrated their disagreement with this idea. The researcher will begin by presenting the responses of the educators who encouraged inclusive education.

According to the results of focus group discussion about teaching physically and sensory disabled pupils in regular schools, the majority of teachers acknowledged that the current inclusion methods presented numerous and serious problems. They stated that to be an effective teacher of disabled children in regular classrooms, this requires special methods along with specific knowledge and skills in inclusive education. The participants expressed an intention to encourage inclusive education for physically and sensory disabled children as much as possible. As one participant stated:

“One of the students in my classroom has a physical handicap that prevents him from moving his hands. I tried to help him as much as I could by applying my personal knowledge. I told his

classmates when I first met him that he got along with everyone. During exams he dictated me the answers to where I write them in exam sheet because he is not able to hold the pen” (P5F).

The aforementioned response demonstrated that educators in schools being investigated were willing to teach pupils with physical and sensory disabilities. The students' peers who generally achieve well seemed to be supporting the teachers' practice of educating children with disabilities in an inclusive environment. This statement also reveals that in the absence of 'structurally' embedded aids, teachers have to resort to their own 'methods' trying to enable students to fully part-take in an assessment task that has been designed without disabled students in mind.

Teachers claimed that because they lacked the time to examine each pupil's demands individually, they asked non-disabled classmates for assistance in the classroom to aid their colleagues who have special needs. As stated by one participant:

“The school does not provide teachers with any special methods to deal with students with disabilities. I think each teacher has his own way to deal with students with disabilities.

I personally do not provide them with additional time or particular attention; instead, I treat them equally since I have more than thirty pupils in my classroom as well as I do not have enough time to look into to every child's needs. I group the pupils that need extra help with the quick students in order to assist them” (P3F).

The opinions of the participants revealed that, despite their uncertainty about what "inclusive education" actually meant, they occasionally applied – what they understood to be- relevant concepts in their teaching. This would include supporting disabled children's learning, attaining full inclusion in school activities, and interacting with peers who are able bodied. Even though the teachers themselves had limited background in inclusive education, they tried to help all pupils, irrespective of their perceived needs.

Moreover, based on the findings from the individual semi-structured interviews, some teachers believed that inclusive education was an appropriate idea. Essentially, these teachers were supportive of the concept of inclusive education- as they understood it- and believed it was a positive and worthwhile approach to education. They demonstrated their willingness to accept the differences among learners in the regular school. The idea was to create a learning environment where all students, regardless of their differences, are included and valued, and where everyone in the school community recognizes and celebrates diversity.

As one of the participants said:

“We have different students who learn in different ways, and schools must embrace and welcome students who face various learning difficulties. I support the concept of including students with physical and sensory disabilities in regular classes [...] I do my best to teach all my pupils and provide extra attention and time to those with disabilities when possible. That`s all that I can do” (P11).

Based on this comment, the participant appeared to acknowledge the diversity among children, considering that pupils with disabilities deserve the opportunity to learn in mainstream classrooms. However, without a formal school-wide approach to inclusive education, teachers are left to develop their own strategies and use their own resources to support students with diverse needs. Teachers who participated in this study demonstrated throughout that they are eager to embrace inclusive education for the purpose to develop the skills and abilities of pupils with special needs and to enhance their social interaction:

“We do not tolerate any type of prejudice of students with disabilities in our school, and I believe that it is essential to include those with physical and sensory disabilities alongside their peers in order to learn from each other. I think physically and sensory disabled learners will overcome their impairments when they are placed in regular classrooms” (P12I).

The statement above reflects a commitment to inclusivity and non-discrimination in the school environment. The participant clearly states that the school does not tolerate any form of discrimination against learners with disabilities. Also, she believes that it is crucial to include learners with physical and sensory disabilities in regular classrooms. This suggests a belief in the benefits of integrated learning environments. Overall, the statement demonstrates a supportive attitude towards inclusive education and a commitment to creating a welcoming and inclusive learning environment for all learners: *“I believe that inclusive education for students with physical and sensory disabilities is essential because it fosters each student's unique abilities and skills” (P3I).*

They acknowledge and highlight the importance of inclusive education for physically and sensory disabled students and agree that, when these learners are included in regular classrooms alongside

their peers, it helps them to develop their unique abilities and foster their skills. Essentially, participants believe that inclusive education creates a more equitable and supportive learning environment for all learners, allowing them to reach their full potential.

In addition, a different teacher mentioned:

“Based on my experience working with some types of students with disabilities. I encourage the idea of inclusive education for learners with visual and hearing impairment [...] Even though I am unfamiliar with other kinds of physical and sensory disabilities. I still think that all learners with disabilities have the right to inclusive education in order to engage socially with other pupils who are not disabled. Additionally, it offers them the opportunity to participate in tasks with their peers without disabilities. As a result, this could foster welcoming atmospheres”

(P16I).

This participant expresses support for inclusive education, particularly for learners with visual and hearing impairments. She has personal experience working with these types of disabilities and has witnessed the positive impact of inclusive education. While the participant may not have extensive knowledge about other types of disabilities, she believes that all learners deserve access to inclusive education. She emphasizes the benefits of social interaction and participation in tasks with non-disabled peers, which can enhance a welcoming learning environment for everyone.

To conclude, according to the current study, some teachers were supportive and constructive about including students with disabilities in mainstream classes. The favourable and optimistic viewpoints were formed by educators' attempts to use different methods of instruction in their classes, even if they were unaware of the inclusion guidelines. This will be covered in the section that follows below.

4.2.1.1 Instructional strategies used in the inclusive classrooms

While the data presented above demonstrates that teachers are supportive of ‘inclusive educational methods’, the methods they do employ derive from their own repertoire of skills, rather than being structurally embedded in the curriculum and the delivery of that. The next part of this chapter, therefore, examines that emerging data on the type of methods teachers do use to teach pupils with disabilities. Every educator mentioned using a minimum of one teaching method while working with pupils who have disabilities.

Some participants believed that using flexible teaching approaches could help students with disabilities feel more included and motivated to participate in class. An illustration of flexible methods being used in the classroom was shared by one participant, who also emphasised the significance of this strategy.

" I design the tasks according to the needs of disabled pupils. For example, I do not provide the pupil with physical disability with tasks that needs movement or performance.... Being flexible is important " (P15I).

Educators also reported using group or pair work as a strategy for teaching learners with disabilities. For instance,

"I use pair or group work when giving tasks in which I put pupils with disabilities with those nondisabled pupils so they can learn from each other" (P8I).

A few other educators employed various teaching strategies to improve their teaching like body language and phrase repetition to make sure every pupil understood what was expected of them. As stated by some participants:

"...I try to use body language during explanation" (P9I).

"I ask the student to rephrase the task's objectives as I reaffirm them. I used a random call technique throughout the class to gauge learners' comprehension of the subject matter, and I used it again when the task is given. In my opinion, learners with disabilities would profit from these techniques" (P5I).

It was evident from the information collected during interviews that educators employed a variety of educational methods throughout the entire process of education. Although some educators used different teaching methods, all of them seemed to place emphasis on the educational material. As an illustration, one teacher said that:

"The teaching strategy I employ in my class is that it depends on the subject at hand. My teaching strategies for science were distinct from those I used for mathematics. It varies even within a single subject matter because everything depends on the lesson's content" (P9I).

Peer assistance, which involves seating non-disabled learners next to their disabled colleagues, was another strategy employed by the participants. They felt that pupils with disabilities would

benefit from this method. While the primary focus of peer assistance might be to support students with disabilities, it can also have positive outcomes for non-disabled students. By fostering a more inclusive and collaborative learning environment, peer assistance can benefit all students in the classroom.

"For learners with disabilities, all that I can do for them is placing them in appropriate seat. I put them with nondisabled learners so they can assist them" (P6I).

On the other hand, some other teachers were against inclusive education. In which their views on inclusive education in Algeria varied from believing it to be not wise idea, undesirable, and unsuitable. The following statements illustrate this point.

"It is hard to work in inclusive classrooms. It should not be applied here" (P4I).

"It is not a wise decision" (P5I).

"I believe that including students with disabilities under these circumstances is unfair" (P17I).

These participants, as can be shown above, disagreed with the concept of implementing inclusive education in Algeria. However, their answers went beyond to explain why they believed this to be the case. They each had their own justifications. For most of them, it was due to an inadequate teacher training. As an example, one participant said:

"We lack training in special needs, so I do not believe we can be inclusive here" (P4I).

Likewise, different teachers offered a similar argument. Namely, (P2I, P5I, P6I, P9I, P14I and P19I).

Moreover, for some other participants, the reason was that the school setting lacked the amenities and services required to meet the needs of disabled pupils. For instance,

"The regular educational environment does not support inclusive education in any way. The school's architectural design, including the classrooms, has issues, and the facilities are not accessible to all students. The majority of classrooms have stairs, which makes me believe that pupils with mobility impairment such as those using wheelchair or children with visual impairments cannot access the classrooms" (P8I).

Furthermore, a number of teachers made the same claim, specifically (P5I, P6I, P7I, P10I, P11, P15I, and P20I). However, some participants also cited a lack of knowledge and instruction as a factor in their decisions. For instance, one teacher said:

“I believe that inclusive education should not be applied in this situation because general teachers are not given any instructions on how to handle students with special needs” (P19I). Similarly, other participants made the same justification. Notably (P5I, P8I, P11I, P18I, and P20I).

A few participants also pointed to the inadequacy of the educational program as a further variable contributing to their unfavourable perceptions. As one teacher stated:

“Through my experience, I can say that inclusive education in our schools only adds to the workload and lack of time already present in our larger class sizes. It is difficult to deliver the same curriculum materials to all of these students because they have different needs” (P2I).

Additionally, two more Teachers (P5I and P18I) provided a similar rationale.

Moreover, other participants offered a different rationale, citing the lack of collaboration and a shortage of staff members in school. The quotations that follow serve as illustrations for this perspective.

“I can say from my experience that it can be difficult for teachers to educate students with disabilities. Due to the lack of specialized assistants who could support the general teacher in taking care of the disabled students” (P13I) [and]

“I believe that at this time, our regular schools are unable to meet the requirements of learners with disabilities. A number of things are missing that would make it easier for the pupils with disabilities to adapt to life in the mainstream school. Consider the lack of supplies and tools. In addition to inadequate levels of collaboration and contact between the school staff, teachers, and parents” (P15I).

The overview of the educators' views, attitudes, and justifications are provided in the following section:

Some teachers supported the idea of implementing inclusive education, so to ensure that pupils with disabilities have the same rights to a mainstream education as pupils without disabilities.

On the other hand, the majority of participants were against the idea of implementing inclusive education in Algeria in their own contexts. The teachers' negative perceptions towards inclusive education were formed based on their experiences in the mainstream schools. They presented a number of justifications for the positions they hold. For instance, lack of teachers' training, inadequate knowledge, and instructions on how to deal with pupils with disabilities, the

inadequacy of the educational program, inappropriate school setting which lack the necessary amenities and services, the lack of collaboration and a shortage of staff members in school. So while, in principle, they may be committed to the idea of inclusive education, they saw structural barriers (architecture, lack of tools & techniques, classroom sizes) as hindering factors in their everyday practice. Equally, they implicitly questioned the actual pedagogical value of relying on their 'own techniques', in the absence of any formal training.

4.2.2 Teachers' understanding of the concept of inclusive education in Algeria

Among the main aims of this study is to investigate how general teachers in Algerian primary schools perceive the concept of inclusive education (Q2: How do general teachers understand and conceptualize the inclusive education of physical and sensory disabled learners?). This inquiry is crucial because without knowing what inclusive education means to people who are in charge of implementing it in schools, it is impossible to explore other aspects related to inclusive education. The conceptualization of inclusive education among general teachers was investigated in the focus group discussion and the individual semi-structured interviews. One of the interview questions specifically tackled this topic. For instance, the question 'could you explain what you know about inclusive education?'

The literature cited in Chapter Two regarding the various general perceptions on disability (medical, social, and biopsychosocial paradigms) as well as the related conceptualization of what makes up an adequate educational environment for children with disabilities (discrimination, integration, and inclusion viewpoints) were applied in order to classify and organise the participants' knowledge concerning inclusive education. In brief, previous research has demonstrated that the main reason for the educational discrimination of students with special needs was the medical perspective of disability, which means they face particular difficulties and need specialised help (Oliver, 2009). On the other hand, the integration approach, which was motivated by a social perspective of disability, advocated for placing learners who have special needs in regular schools, treating them equitably, and having them learn alongside others without special

needs with the objective to promote their socialisation within the classroom as well as outside the classroom (Hardie and Tilly, 2012).

Therefore, pupils who have disabilities were included in regular classrooms and the expectation that they could cope within the framework that already existed (Booth, 2005). Nevertheless, inclusion in education, based on a biopsychosocial model of disability, emphasises that an individual's wellbeing is influenced by the biological, psychological, and social effects of their condition. It recognises that both medical and social therapies are appropriate for addressing potential issues around disability, and none are disallowed as forms of intervention (World Health organization, 2002). The method states that a school should look at the environment of a disabled learner and adjust in line with each student's needs. Because of the interaction of biological and environmental factors, the learner's participation is the focus (Norwich, 2008).

Based on the focus group finding, the participants provided a range of perspectives in response to a question asking them to describe how they generally understood the concept of inclusive education In Algeria. Thus, generally speaking, their views on inclusive education could be perceived as being more constrained than varied. Among the participants, here is an example.

” Despite my limited knowledge of the concept of inclusive education, what little I do understand suggests that it has something to do with the education of children who have disabilities” (P2F).

The aforementioned quote demonstrated how educators perceived inclusive education as being for students with disabilities but did not understand the nuanced components of inclusive education (Acedo, 2008).

Other participants did not appear to comprehend the distinction between "inclusive education" and "special education". In which, one participant has defined inclusive education similarly as special education. The following statement was made by participant 3:

“Inclusive education is a type of special education, which entails special schools for pupils with special needs. Such as the Centre for students with special needs that we have in our city (Ammi Mossa)” (P3F).

The above response shows that the participant tried to provide a plausible answer of how she came to comprehend the idea of inclusive education based on her personal perspective by mentioning a nearby special institution.

Inclusive education was debated concept (Florian, 2008) since participants were unaware that the terms "special education" and "inclusive education" are contrasted terms (Ghergut and Grasu, 2012). When the participant used the more traditional terminology "special education," it is clear that she thought about inclusive education from the lens of the medical paradigm of disability (Wendell, 1996).

Another participant seems to be unaware of how the social paradigm of disability, which no more refers to children with disabilities as being handicapped, has transformed special education into inclusive education (Terzi, 2004). This comment was taken from participant 6:

“The inclusion of handicapped students, who represent a small group, with ordinary students, who represent the large group, is known as inclusive education” (P6F).

Similar to the medical model, some teachers tended to consider inclusive education as an educational segregation when they highlighted the regional special school, instead of perceiving it as a general education that aims to improve schools' ability to adapt to diversity (Kearney and Kane, 2006). Beyond trying to explore how disabled students are or are not integrated in classrooms in this context, this implies that all 'able students' -to the teachers' mind- present as a homogenous group with which homogenous learning needs are associated. Disabled students are also seen as a homogenous group, to some extent, by participants, but perceived to have fundamentally different learning styles and needs to abled students.

Furthermore, other participants described how they understood inclusive education by categorising disabled children according to the disabilities they had.

Here is a sample of how a participant used her native dialect to describe her thoughts of inclusive education by referencing the disabilities that students had.

“I believe that inclusive education entails educating students with autism, hearing impairment, vision impairments, mobility impairment, etc. in regular schools” (P4F).

According to the statement above, the native language, which has names for disabilities, has an impact on how inclusive education is understood and implemented. That demonstrated how the participant defined inclusive education in terms of his own cultures and languages. Negative connotations associated with disability terms can stigmatize individuals and hinder the promotion of inclusive education. Conversely, using neutral or positive language can foster a more inclusive environment (Makoelle, 2020). Cultural nuances and language specific terms can also influence perceptions of inclusive education. Ensuring accessibility and effective communication in different languages is crucial for promoting inclusive education. This statement also demonstrates the point made above, namely that disabled (both physically and in terms of learning disabilities) students are understood as one homogenous group, whose learning needs and styles are fundamentally different to those of abled students.

Some participants had a different conception of inclusive education than the social paradigm of disability, that tries to eliminate the labels that culture and society assign to a person's disability (Fisher and Goodley, 2007). These participants may have held a more traditional view, focusing on individual needs and challenges rather than societal barriers.

On the other hand, few participants had some understanding of the idea of inclusive education. The below claims show the participants knowledge of inclusive education.

“Inclusive education entails integrating or putting regular students and pupils with disabilities in general school” (P5F) [and]

“Inclusive education means enrolling pupils with disabilities in an ordinary classroom alongside their nondisabled peers. Also creating a specific environment for them that will help them fit in” (P7F).

It is evident from the participants' usage of the modern terms "pupils with special needs, children with disabilities" in addition to the statement “creating a specific environment for them that will help them fit in” that they viewed inclusive education through the standpoint of the social paradigm of disability. This paradigm emphasizes societal change and equal opportunities for learners with disabilities, rather than focusing solely on the individual disability.

Moreover, the individual semi-structured interviews revealed significant differences in the teachers' understanding of inclusive education. Most of these participants, as will be seen in the

following paragraphs, had limited awareness of inclusive education, and thought of inclusion in the sense of physical (rather than ‘pedagogical’) integration. Even though just a few participants moved beyond the physical integration, their viewpoints did not entirely capture the idea of inclusive education.

According to a number of teachers, inclusive education is defined as having learners who have special needs physically present in the same classroom as learners who do not have disabilities: *“Inclusive education entails placing disabled pupils into the same classroom as the normal students”* (P11), (P13I), (P15I), and (P20I). For another participant inclusive education is related to the physical attendance of children with disabilities at regular school but this depends on how many pupils are in each classroom. *“Inclusion in education refers to integrating a fewer number of students with special needs (SEN) with a larger number of students without disabilities in the same mainstream classrooms”* (P3I). Another participant demonstrated a very limited understanding of the concept of inclusive education in which she said: *“I believe it has something to do with the education of pupils who have special needs”* (P19I).

This quote demonstrates how educators perceived inclusive education as being for students with disabilities but did not understand the complex and nuanced components of inclusive education (Acedo, 2008).

A different participant described how she understood inclusive education by categorising disabled children according to the disabilities they had. Here is a sample of how a participant used her local language to describe her thoughts of inclusive education by referencing the disabilities that pupils had.

“It entails incorporating learners who have autism, ADHD, hearing loss, vision impairment, and physical disabilities into mainstream classroom alongside their normal peers” (P15I).

In addition, some other participants view inclusive education as the appropriate setting where children with disabilities should enrol as well as the place where they must adjust for the purpose to enhance their education:

“Inclusive education entails putting students with disabilities with their peers in regular classes so they can adjust to their surroundings while getting special attention so they can advance their educational levels by learning from other pupils” (P2I).

In essence, the participant believes that inclusive education should involve placing students with disabilities in regular classes, helping them adjust to their surroundings, providing special attention, and promoting learning from other pupils without disabilities. Overall, the participant's view is that inclusive education should create a supportive environment where all learners, regardless of their abilities, have equal opportunities to learn and grow.

Three other participants expressed similar comprehension:

“Inclusive education involves placing learners with special needs in a supportive setting to which they can adjust” (P5I).

This participant argued that inclusive education requires putting learners with disabilities in a supportive environment where they can feel comfortable and adapt to the regular classroom setting. Similarly,

“It aims to create an environment where students with special needs can interact with their classmates in regular classrooms and learn more effectively” (P4I).

According to this teacher, inclusive education aims to foster an environment where learners with disabilities can socialize with their peers in regular classrooms and improve their educational outcomes. Likewise;

“Inclusive education involves teaching learners with disabilities such as those with hearing impairment, visual impairment, mobility impairment, and those with autism in regular schools.

Additionally, making a special setting for them will aid in their adaptation” (P10I).

This teacher believes that inclusive education should involve teaching students with various disabilities in regular schools. She also believes that creating specialized settings within these schools can help these students adapt to the learning environment.

Moreover, some other participants have expressed a quite different perspective, claiming that inclusive education is an opportunity provided to pupils with disabilities in order to socialize with other pupils who are not disabled. For instance, one teacher claimed that *“Inclusive education provides learners with special needs with the opportunity to interact socially with classmates in regular schools” (P6I).* Another participant expressed similar understanding in which she stated that, *“The term inclusive education refers to placing pupils with disabilities in the same classroom as their peers without disabilities. The primary goal of inclusive education is making disabled students engage socially” (P7I).* Similar view was expressed by (P17I). In fact, these teachers placed strong emphasis on the social engagement aim of inclusive education.

The results that have been so far reported from 13 teachers in this section appear to be concentrated on the social advantages of including children with disabilities in regular classrooms as well as their physical attendance there. The pedagogical advantage suggested by several teachers (P2I, P4I, and P6I) centred on the things children with disabilities will acquire from other classmates instead of their educators or the educational institution in general. Therefore, teachers have not indicated the educational advantages that the school offers to the disabled learners up to this point. According to one participant, inclusive education entails enrolling disabled pupils in regular school with their peers who are not disabled; however, placing them in separate classroom.

“The term "inclusive education" refers to the integration of students with special needs in general education schools yet not being in the same classroom as their classmates without disabilities. I believe that when students with disabilities are grouped with other students, they are happier. However, when they are in the same classroom, they are likely to experience stress and anxiety because they would not be able to comprehend the instruction” (P14I).

This teacher claims that inclusive education is not supposed to take place in the same classroom due to the stress placed on disabled pupils who are unable to maintain pace with other ordinary pupils.

Another teacher demonstrated a slightly different opinion. That is, inclusive education paves the way for the emotional and psychological demands of disabled pupils to be recognised. As she stated:

“It is offering pupils who have special needs the chance to learn in an ordinary setting. A further important advantage is the removal of limits between disabled pupils and their classmates without disabilities. During the inclusion procedure, it is significant to consider the impact on pupils' emotional and psychological needs since they are very sensitive” (P18I).

Despite the fact that this teacher saw inclusive education as a procedure, rather than a pedagogical approach to learning, she acknowledged that being aware of the emotional and psychological demands of pupils with disabilities is the primary objective of this procedure. However, her statement highlights a re-occurring theme in data, which is the procedural emphasis on/ nature of inclusive education in practice (as seen and understood by participating teachers), rather than the actual integration of pedagogically valuable concepts in the classroom.

Here, the two educators appeared to be concerned with the needs of the disabled pupils and saw

inclusive education as a means of meeting those needs. Either by isolating disabled pupils from their non-disabled classmates to provide them the chance to get rid of the stress of trying to keep up with them and the threat of being mocked by them, or by being aware of their emotional and psychological needs. This illustrates the underlying understanding they have of disability which strongly aligns with the medical model of disability. This model views disability as an individual defect that needs to be 'fixed or treated'. Their suggestions of isolating disabled pupils or focusing solely on their emotional and psychological needs reflect this perspective. It is noteworthy to point out that there was no discussion of the individual rights, social, and educational dimensions of inclusive education, which further raises questions about the teachers' understanding of what inclusive education entails.

Regarding the rest of the participants, inclusive education entails further than just placing disabled learners in regular schools. For example, one participant describes inclusive education as treating disabled children with extra attention and care: *"Inclusive education involves giving children with disabilities extra attention and compassionate care in regular classroom settings without letting them feel that they have disabilities"* (P8I). This teacher recognised that disabled pupils should not perceive themselves as having special needs despite the fact that her perspective was limited to showing empathy and care. It means that care is given unconditionally and without distinction. Moreover, two teachers shared a clearer knowledge of how student collaboration and sharing are essential to inclusive education. For example,

"Inclusive education involves including learners with disabilities in regular schools. In other words, I am referring to the collaboration between two categories of learners in the same classroom: one category has disabilities, and the second category consists of students without disabilities" (P9I).

Another teacher concurred and conveyed the same concept in which she stated:

"Inclusive education involves two types of students joining the same classroom, one type represents students with disabilities, and the other type students without disabilities" (P11I).

These participants' opinions extend more than the physical attendance or the appropriate setting that encourages learners' collaboration and sharing of the environment. This could be a reference to the equality of disabled pupils with their peers without disabilities.

Additionally, one teacher had an opinion that was entirely distinct from that of the other teachers in which she stated:

“Inclusive education involves incorporating learners who have special needs into regular classrooms. It calls for enforcing strict regulations for school staff and parents as well as offering another educational program that can be adjusted to meet the needs of all learners including those who have special needs. Learners with special needs who attend inclusive schools are likely to benefit from socializing with and gaining knowledge from their classmates without disabilities” (P16I).

Therefore, this teacher stated that inclusive education involves not only the setting that gives disabled children the opportunity to gain more knowledge from their classmates, but also the adaptation of educational programmes to meet their needs.

Another participant expressed a various perspective on inclusive education, while she was concerned with the teacher's efforts rather than the learners themselves: *“It involves incorporating pupils with special needs in regular classes, which can be accomplished with the help of the teachers' collaboration. I mean both general and special education teacher” (P12I).*

This participant believed that school staff, particularly educators, were responsible for incorporating learners, rather than it being a question of structural inclusion for which the responsibility would sit with the school. Therefore, this goes beyond simply including disabled pupils in the mainstream classroom; however, it also entails working together to incorporate them. The last five participants seemed to have different comprehension of inclusive education since they covered topics that the fifteen previous teachers did not address. These teachers concentrated on the fundamental rights alongside educational components of inclusive education by linking them to promoting equality, updating the educational program, providing care without prejudice, and enhancing collaboration among school staff to improve education for all pupils.

The next table outlines how all of the participants understand the concept of inclusive education:

Table 2 Participants' Views on Inclusive Education

Participants	Key understanding of inclusive education
P3F	Inclusive education is defined as a type of special education
P4F, P5F, P6F P1I, P3I, P13I, P15I, and P20I.	The physical attendance of learners with disabilities alongside their non-disabled classmates.

P7F, P2I, P5I, P4I, and P10I.	Creating a setting that is appropriate for learners with disabilities where they could adjust.
P6I, P7I, and P17I.	The opportunity provided to disabled pupils to interact socially with other pupils who are not disabled.
P14I.	Enrolling disabled pupils in regular school with their peers while placing them in separate classroom in order to get rid of the stress placed on disabled learners in the inclusive classes.
P18I.	Recognising the emotional and psychological demands of pupils with disabilities must be the primary aim of inclusive education.
P8I.	The provision of care to pupils with disabilities without prejudice
P9I and P11I.	Learners` collaboration and cooperation.
P16I.	Adaptations to the curriculum to accommodate pupils with disabilities.
P12I.	Incorporating disabled students into the regular schools. While also attempting to include them by collaboration among teachers.

Overall, it can be concluded from the results presented in this part that some teachers saw inclusive education to be the practise of putting disabled pupils in regular schools but in special classroom in order to decrease the stress placed on them and enhance comprehension of their psychological and emotional needs. This concept is compatible with the medical view of disability that supports the educational segregation of students with disabilities as discussed in chapter two.

Others believed that the inclusive education of disabled pupils means having them physically present at school, creating a setting that is appropriate for them, or having them participate in social interactions in regular classrooms or schools. These interconnected comprehensions indicate to an integration standpoint instead of an inclusion approach, as illustrated in the literature review chapter. The remaining participants (5 teachers) discussed inclusion in terms of giving care without prejudice, equity, modifying educational program, and staff collaboration to educate all pupils. Such perspectives, regardless of their limitations, are considerably more in line with the inclusive education approach, which is discussed in the second chapter, but do not capture a comprehensive understanding of the pedagogical dimensions of inclusive education.

4.2.3 Challenges in implementing inclusive education in Algeria

Among the important objectives of the current study was to identify the difficulties encountered by general teachers in the Algerian elementary mainstream settings when they try to adopt inclusive education. Based on the responses provided by teachers in the current research, it emerged that there are several challenges to inclusive education. Occasionally, some of these obstacles were stated explicitly in the interviews, while at other times they were implicit in the teachers' responses. The results of teachers' views on the difficulties they encounter when striving to apply inclusive education are detailed in the sections below.

4.2.3.1 Lack of knowledge of Inclusive Education policies and concepts

The results of the individual in-depth interviews with the general teachers indicated their struggles with an inadequate understanding of policies regarding inclusive education and the broader concept of inclusive education itself that limits their ability to adopt inclusive education effectively in their regular classrooms. They also noted that all they knew about inclusive education is that pupils who have special needs have the right to enrol in regular schools. One participant has expressed doubt about the existence of the policy documents and guidelines related to inclusive education at her schools in which she said:

“I mean, with regard to what I have heard about this policy is that all children, regardless of their disabilities, have the right to an education in a public school; But, when it comes to rules and regulation for this approach, we don't have any. I am not even sure if our school has access to these policy official papers” (P8I).

The above participant expresses confusion regarding the specific rules and regulations governing inclusive education in their school. They are aware of the general principle that all children have the right to a public education, but they lack clarity about the specific policies and guidelines that apply to their school and indeed in their own practice in actual classrooms. This suggests a lack of transparency and information regarding the school's approach to inclusive education.

Similarly, several teachers have voiced the same viewpoint. Such as (P18I, P11I, P5I, P14I, P9I, P19I, P1I, P7I, P16I, P3I, P12I, P20I, P2I, and P13I).

4.2.3.2 Lack of teachers` training and personal development in inclusive education

The participants considered that inclusive education and implementation as two distinct concepts. Despite stating that they appreciated inclusion, the teachers had some concerns about its execution, notably that the government had not done enough to prepare them adequately.

Based on what teachers reported, inclusive practises have been found to be incredibly complicated and difficult (Vlachou, 2004). The educators' practices were based on certain aspects, each of them lacked adequate policy implementation and a comprehensive understanding of underlying concepts of inclusive education. This includes insufficient preparation for teachers, lack of pre-service training in inclusive education, and limited opportunities for in-service training.

4.2.3.2.1 Insufficient preparation for teachers

This refers to teachers` readiness to include disabled students alongside their nondisabled peers in the regular classrooms (Acedo, 2008). It also entails the process through which educators pick up the necessary knowledge and skills to interact with students with disabilities in an integrated and supportive manner.

The results from both focus group discussion and in-depth individual interviews revealed that the teachers found their lack of training in inclusive education to be a barrier. A number of teachers who took part in this research claimed that they were unprepared for inclusive education and that it is challenging for them to change or modify their teaching methods to the recently implemented inclusive education. According to some teachers` interview answers, the problem of the lack of training regarding how to apply inclusive education is what makes a lot of teachers unwilling to get involved in implementing inclusive education in their classroom settings. The teachers' thoughts are conveyed in the following statements.

“Due to lack of educators` training in inclusive education, most of us are unwilling to work with students who have special needs” (P9I).

“Regarding inclusive education, we received no training. We are not adequately prepared to cope with disabled students in regular classes” (P19I).

“Since teachers are not receiving any training regarding inclusive education, so it becomes a hard job for teachers as they do not know how to handle disabled learners appropriately” (P6I).

It is noteworthy to highlight the fact that none of the participants had received instructions or practical support on how to integrate the newly introduced strategy in their own practices. As a result, teachers initially continued using their existing instructional strategies, rather than adopting a broader pedagogical approach that aligns with the principles and goals of inclusive education.

“I do not use any special methods with students who have disabilities. I just teach them as nondisabled students” (P18I).

Another teacher demonstrated similar viewpoint in which she stated:

“I will be completely honest here: I have no clue which teaching methods work best with students who have disabilities. I apply the same methods to all of my pupils” (P14I).

Likewise, other participants agreed on this point namely: (P10I, P2I, P4I, P13I, P5I, and P12I).

On the other hand, there are teachers who began changing their instructional methods and techniques in order to make it appropriate for all of the pupils in classroom. The following quotation illustrates this point.

“As I already mentioned that we did not get training in inclusive education so we did not gain from the training any special methods that we can use for students with special needs. However, I make my own effort to find different strategies that can meet all my learners` needs [...] I sometimes modify the assignments provided in the math class. To involve the students with mobility impairment in the activity, for instance, I gave the students a ball toss to say the answers verbally from their places rather than asking each student to write the answer on the board” (P1I).

In a similar vein, several people shared same standpoint including (P3I, P7I, P8I, P15I, P17I, P16I, P20I, and P11I).

Furthermore, the research participants believed that both the pre-service and in-service training they had did not effectively qualified them to be inclusive teachers. They felt that inclusive knowledge and skills are what educators need to deal with children with disabilities. This point will be explored in depth in the next section.

4.2.3.2.2 Lack of pre-service training in inclusive education

Pre-service training at Teachers' Colleges should prepare educators to teach inclusively in the classroom (Carrington and Brownlee, 2001). When teachers were questioned about their perceptions of the pre-service training, they had received in inclusive education knowledge and skills. The majority of the participants responded that they have never taken any training in inclusive education. In addition, they declared that the pre-service training they had did not effectively prepared them to teach inclusively. A sample of one of these statements is provided below.

“The training we received was about the second generation, lesson plans, educational programs, etc. but there were no topics about students with special needs or inclusive education. Teachers are not trained in this field, and therefore every teacher deals with students with disabilities according to his/her knowledge and experience” (P3F).

The above statement demonstrates that during their pre-service training, they lacked knowledge and skills in inclusive education. While inclusive knowledge and skills are viewed as resources and opportunities that empowers teachers to carry out inclusion duties when teaching students with disabilities in their class.

Moreover, all research participants expressed concern about the complete lack of opportunities for educators to pursue personal and professional development. Participants noted that the policymakers should be aware of a significant issue, which is the absence of personal and professional development in terms of developing their knowledge and skills. This lack of funding for teachers' career progression demonstrates that the government's commitment to fostering inclusive education has not been prioritised as a key strategy for success. The participants' comments suggested that they lack the skills necessary to undertake the responsibility of putting inclusive education policies into practise, in a pedagogically meaningful way. Educators claimed that there was no chance for them to increase their knowledge and experience in order to implement inclusive education strategies.

“We have not received any training regarding inclusive education. I believe that when it comes to dealing with disabled students in regular classes, we are not sufficiently prepared. Since we have not had special training in subjects like using sign language to communicate with children with hearing impairment or using of Braille for children with visual impairment” (P5F).

Teachers appeared to be aware of the necessity to improve their skills and abilities while they were still in the classroom teaching in order to handle the new responsibilities that were placed on them. The majority of participants believed that their professional preparation is currently insufficient to teach students with disabilities.

“I think general teachers are not adequately qualified to educate pupils with disabilities in regular schools since they lack the necessary knowledge and skills of inclusive education”
(P5F).

It is clear from the previous statement that without the educators having the necessary professional training, implementing inclusive education policies is not something that can be done with much ease (Bourke, 2010) or indeed in a pedagogically meaningful way. To achieve the government's desired objectives from adopting the programme, teachers must instead become more knowledgeable and skilled in a broad range of subjects. Participants acknowledged that they lack the necessary preparation to deal with disabled children in actual classroom settings, despite the fact that as future teachers they need to have up-to-date knowledge and abilities concerning all perspectives of inclusive education.

For example, they lack appropriate training in the use of Braille for children with visual impairment or sign language to interact with children with hearing impairment. Teachers believed that personal and professional development programmes, like in-service training, should help them improve these skills.

4.2.3.2.3 Limited opportunities for in-service training

While there has been a lack of such training in the initial teacher training programme, in-service development would present an opportunity for teachers to be equipped with the skills to create inclusive learning environments in a pedagogically meaningful way. Educators believed they can advance their knowledge and abilities to be competent and equitable inclusive teachers is through in-service training programs. The remarks made by participants during focus groups gave insightful information about their lack of opportunities for personal and professional development, notably through in-service training. They highlighted that no in-service training courses were offered to them to improve their knowledge and abilities on inclusive education.

“I agree with what my colleague have just mentioned. The lack of in-service training on inclusive education makes educators less prepared to fulfil an inclusive teaching role in the classroom” (P6F).

Educators expressed the belief that the government's inability to provide adequate funding hindered the delivery of effective in-service training programmes for inclusive education, and this in return left educators poorly prepared to fulfil an inclusive educator's role within the classroom. Teachers indicated that they were in a compromising situation regarding inclusive education policies and their knowledge of inclusive education practises because the government did not encourage funding in-service training courses, as this participant describes.

“I believe there has been a lack of government funding for teacher in-service training programmes. For someone like me, there should be ongoing training on inclusive education so that I may develop my inclusion abilities and advance my qualification” (P7F).

This answer demonstrated how educators believed that regular in-service training was crucial for their ability to keep pace with the evolving demands of the educational system. They felt that adapting to these changes necessitated additional training and higher qualifications.

Participants having more than 10 years of education experience noticed that since they started teaching, there had not been any in-service programme focuses primarily on inclusive education. One participant who has worked at the same school for more than 10 years made the following observation:

“After working in the same school for more than ten years, I could remember with clarity that during the yearly in-service trainings we had, there were no training on inclusive education” (P1F).

4.2.3.3 lack of instructional resources and materials

In addition to the lack of training in relation to ‘inclusive education’ there also were inadequate instructional resources, and the available standard materials made it difficult to include pupils with disabilities appropriately. Blackboards are the primary tool used by teachers at these schools to present their lectures. They had been teaching this way for a while, and they thought it worked

well when there were no pupils with special needs present. Yet, this technique became impractical by the existence of pupils with special needs. As one teacher claimed:

“If you visit our classrooms, you will find only blackboard and tables there is no advanced technology that could facilitate the learning of students with disabilities” (P11I).

Another participant expressed displeasure over this, arguing:

“There are many lacking materials and supplies for the classroom. Our job is significantly challenging because we lack these tools, which is not our responsibility [...] the resource room is almost empty. We still rely solely on the blackboard to present lessons when there are no visible and auditory aids, no projector, etc.” (P9I).

In inclusive classrooms, attention-grabbing techniques are necessary in order for disabled learners to concentrate on the lesson that is delivered to them. One teacher made the following statement:

“The teaching methods we use in the classroom are limited because we do not have the necessary tools to help the disabled students. Personally, I see myself as relying on simple techniques only [...] There are not enough resources in the classroom, such as projectors, a smartboard, or visible and aural aids” (P13I).

Among the tools mentioned by this teacher were a projector, a smartboard, visible and aural aids. Additionally, handbooks and study guides about learners with disabilities were other tools that were lacking in these schools, as noted by one teacher.

“The issue was a lack of instructional materials or simply not enough of it overall, such as handbooks or study guides in order to satisfy the learners needs in the class” (P4I).

In addition to that, one teacher highlighted that the resource room lacked special supplies for disabled students.

“... sometimes I find it difficult to convey the lesson to one of my students who has hearing loss when her hearing aid stops working because there are not any other hearing aids in the resource room that could be used in this circumstance, and I do not know how to use sign language” (P18I).

4.2.3.4 Physical school environment as a barrier to the implementation of inclusive education

Equally, the physical settings of schools in which participants teach were not seen as conducive of the needs of inclusive educational settings. The findings from both focus group discussion and the

in-depth individual interviews in this current research identified that the majority of teachers believed that their educational settings were unsuitable for implementing inclusive education. All participants' responses indicated that the entire school environment had not been physically adapted, making it difficult to apply inclusive education principles. Teachers highlighted several problems, including the use of outdated school structures to accommodate learners with physical and sensory disabilities, inadequate school services and facilities, and a lack of staff members at school.

The information gathered from the participants revealed that facilities and infrastructure at schools were significant obstacles to inclusive education. Ultimately, the choice to implement the inclusive education strategy was made without considering the adequacy of the school structures and their amenities. Schools were designed to accommodate non-disabled pupils. These schools' settings and infrastructure remained unchanged when pupils with disabilities were accepted. According to what a participant stated:

“Our schools in general are not built to meet the needs of children with SEN or those with physical disabilities; there are no pathways or elevators for children with mobility impairment, especially wheelchair users; they are having trouble moving around inside or outside of the classroom. I think it is unfair to place them in regular schools in the current situation” (P6I).

The quote above highlights the lack of physical accessibility in schools for students with disabilities. Specifically, the participant mentions that schools are not built to accommodate students with disabilities, lack of accessibility features, and difficulty moving around. She concludes by expressing the belief that it is unfair to place students with disabilities in regular schools without providing the necessary accommodations and support.

In a similar vein, one more teacher expressed a comparable view:

“The design of the school does not consider the needs of disabled students, particularly those who have mobility issues; there are no accessible walkways, restrooms, or playground. The same can be said for the classroom, there are no specific desks or chairs, and we are only given a blackboard and pencils as instructional materials” (P20I).

In essence, the statement above criticizes the school for failing to create an inclusive and accessible learning environment for students with disabilities. Moreover, other participants (P1I, P3I, P4I, P7I, P9I, P12I, P13I, P14I, P15I, P16I, P17I, P18I, and P19I) had the same perspective.

4.2.3.4.1 Lack of curriculum adaptation

Curriculum adaptation entails diversifying instructions and materials so to offer all students a range of methods to acquire knowledge and express the things they have studied. In order to meet the most successful and efficient learning style for each person (Kaur, 2013). While the above analysis of the data collected highlights the reliance on individual teachers (lack of) knowledge and skills in order to provide a pedagogically meaningful ‘inclusive educational environment’, they had a clear understanding that this was the result of the lack of integrated pedagogical approaches to inclusive education in the curriculum.

Among the obstacles, which several educators highlighted and implied is the present curriculum itself. Based on the focus group discussion, it was evident that participants believed that the educational programs in regular schools are not suitable for children with disabilities. One teacher commented:

“In my opinion, the policy of inclusion in Algeria is nothing but ink on paper, as there are no special or proposed laws to be followed. Then she added the circumstances available in regular schools currently are not adequate for students with special needs, then he explained his opinion by providing some examples such as overcrowding of classes, intensive study programs, and then she added this curriculum is done for nondisabled students” (P4F).

It appeared that teachers felt the need to change the curriculum while they were in the classroom in order to handle the extra responsibilities imposed upon them. Participants believed that teaching disabled children with the current educational programme was inadequate.

Furthermore, it is significant to highlight that the participants in the individual semi-structured interviews confirmed that the educational curriculum was not changed when schools implemented the inclusive education policy. Teachers concentrated on the challenges they encountered because the curriculum was not appropriate for pupils with disabilities as well as the extra work, they put in to finish all lessons within the allotted timeframe. Following the Ministry of Education's timetable and using a curriculum that did not consider the pupils with special needs seemed to encourage teachers to disregard disabled pupils. Educators were having to decide whether to follow the curriculum while devoting less consideration to pupils with special needs or provide greater attention to disabled pupils while skipping over the lessons they were expected to teach.

The majority of teachers believed they had no choice but to select the first option; since the Ministry of Education assess teachers by considering the number of lessons has been delivered and how effectively they conveyed the present curriculum. Inspectors did not evaluate teachers based on how well they supported and helped pupils with disabilities.

The statements that follow will serve as illustrations for all of the points discussed in the preceding section:

“It is extremely challenging to teach the current curriculum to students with disabilities considering the limited class time. Whenever I give them tasks, it was difficult for me to know how to direct them and provide them with individualized attention and care [...] I truly cannot find time to focus on the pupils with disabilities during this term because there are so many subjects to cover. Once the inspectors come to our lessons, they pay close attention to how much of the curriculum we have addressed. They do not consider that we have children with special needs” (P14I). The same view shared by (P6I) and (P19I).

Most teachers' responses revealed an emphasis on the timing considerations and inspections' assessment. Even while some of the participants have not specifically addressed the issue of inspection, but they have raised concerns about the time limitation to deliver lessons. For instance: *“In addition to that, lack of materials and supplies. Time management is another challenge because teachers are required to cover many subjects in a limited time. To give one lesson to at least 30 students, we have 40 minutes. It is hard to look into each individual pupil` needs”* (P7I). This claim was supported by a number of participants namely: (P5I, P6I, P7I, P8I, P9I, P10I, P11I, P13I, P15I, P16I, P17I, P18I, and P20I).

Additionally, other teachers made it plain that they thought the curriculum might need modification. For instance, *“The curriculum needs to be changed because there are many subjects to cover in the allotted time, making it difficult for teachers to give students with disabilities more attention”* (P16I). In agreement with this, another educator stated: *“Course content is inappropriate for pupils with special needs. There should be action taken in this situation [...] the educational program should be adapted”* (P9I). Similarly, two other teachers voiced the same concern such as: (P12I) and (P13I).

Given this, it is evident that the current curriculum poses a significant barrier to the successful implementation of inclusive education in Algeria. Without adapting the curriculum, achieving an inclusive learning environment remains a challenging endeavour.

4.2.3.4.2 Lack of classroom adaptation

Further to the lack of integrated inclusive education approaches in the curriculum, most participants reported that the regular school environments lacked inclusion characteristics to foster inclusive education. They have spoken about issues with the school's architectural design, such as how some of the classrooms and the schoolyards were inhospitable to those with disabilities. Some participants (P4F and P8I) also expressed their concern about the fact that classrooms were not set up to accept pupils with disabilities and that all classrooms had stairs, which would make it difficult for students who use wheelchairs or children with visual impairment to enter the classrooms. As one participant stated:

“The general school environment lacks inclusion features that would foster inclusive education. The school's architectural design, including the classrooms, has issues, and the grounds are not accessible to all students. The majority of classes have stairs, which makes me believe that students in wheelchairs and those who are visually impaired will not be able to enter the classrooms” (P4F).

This indicates that the schools' environments in Algeria are not adjusted to encourage inclusion, contrary to the social model and biopsychosocial model of disability, which support such adjustments (Terzi, 2004). Physical accessibility is necessary for inclusive educational settings to provide children who have disabilities with a supportive environment and the best learning opportunities (Pivik, McComas and Laflamme, 2002).

Furthermore, the participants emphasized the significance of the regular school environments in their comments, highlighting the fact that their institutions did not adhere to the special adaptation standards, especially in regard to the needs of physically disabled children.

Moreover, participants stated that limited space in the classrooms is an obstacle as well. They believed that inefficient classroom design could hinder movement. As a participant reported:

“I believe that the classrooms are small in size and have less space inside for flexible mobility. For example, children with wheelchair will encounter difficulty to move around in the class” (P6F).

For children who use wheelchairs, a classroom's seating arrangement should be well spaced to minimise obstacles and enable easy movement and participation in all tasks (Acedo, Ferrer and

Pàmies, 2009). The aforementioned statement caused considerable concern because classrooms need to be welcoming spaces for learning.

In addition, the data collected from the participants revealed that the large number of pupils in classrooms appeared to be impeding educators' attempts to involve pupils with disabilities. It was difficult for teachers to handle or monitor the enormous number of pupils in classrooms. One teacher provided this example:

“We struggle to meet each student's requirements due to the huge number of students in the classroom, I teach 33 pupils in my class” (P11I).

Several teachers raised up a similar issue. Such as, (P1I, P2I, P5I, P6I, P7I, P9I, P12I, P14I, P15I, P18I, and P19I).

All these results regularly in teachers needing to devote more time to their disabled pupils since they need 'special care'. Nevertheless, the time allocated for curricular coverage was limited. Moreover, due to the huge number of pupils in the classrooms, teachers were unable to provide their disabled pupils with additional care. Teachers were under a lot of strain since they had a restricted time to complete the curriculum while meeting the particular needs of their pupils.

“Our classes have more than 30 pupils, which is higher than the average class size of 20 to 25. This is much more than it ought to be. I am under a lot of strain to finish the curriculum because of this [...] You cannot facilitate and offer each person individualized attention if you have already given them the activity because of the large number of students in the class” (P2I).

Another teacher raised the same complaint and proposed the following solutions:

“Large class size in which I have 35 pupils in my classroom. The maximum number of students in the classroom should be 22, as this will enable us to give all learners equitable attention. To ensure that we can complete the curriculum, sessions should last longer than 45 minutes or less lessons should be taught each day” (P18I).

The above statement highlights the importance of class size in effective teaching and learning and suggests ways to improve the learning environment for all students.

Separate provision in forms of special schools was seen as more adaptive in relation to the needs of students with disabilities in comparison to 'regular' schools. They believe that teachers at

special education schools are more qualified to teach students with disabilities. One participant said the following:

“I think that a general educator should not be given the responsibility of teaching pupils with disabilities. Special schools, in my opinion, are the best option because they are primarily in the student's best interests” (P4F).

This response demonstrates that teachers believe special schools are a superior option for giving disabled children the best education possible because those staff members have received professional training in disabilities. Teachers' views about special schools as the best option for disabled children is related to the medical model of disability.

Similarly, the findings from individual interviews demonstrate that some participants believed that special schools would be much more suitable to serving the needs of children with disabilities than regular schools. They think that special education teachers have greater skills for teaching pupils with disabilities. Furthermore, other teachers have recommended that students with disabilities be assigned to special classrooms within the regular schools so that they can receive the necessary support and a good education. The statements that follow serve as evidence for the ideas expressed earlier.

“I believe that special schools would be a better option to meet the needs of physically and sensory disabled students since regular schools are currently unequipped to accommodate them” (P20I).

Likewise, two more teachers shared the same view. Such as (P3I and P6I).

“For the time being, I believe that special schools are an appropriate option for addressing the needs of students with disabilities including those with physical and sensory disability because they are well equipped, have qualified staff who are experienced in dealing with them more than general teachers” (P14I).

“I think it would be good idea if they create for them special equipped classrooms within regular school and providing teacher who is qualified in special needs only through this way they would benefit from the inclusion in regular school” (P19I).

According to the aforementioned comments, regular teachers believe that isolating disabled pupils in separated classrooms or in special schools is more efficient and effective for ensuring that they receive the best education possible. Due to the fact that special teachers in special schools have received specialised training on disability. Teachers' opinions that special classrooms/schools are

the best choice for pupils with disabilities are influenced by the medical paradigm of disability. Overall, the results from both focus group discussions and individual interviews consistently suggest that some participants believe special classrooms/schools are better equipped to meet the needs of children with disabilities compared to regular schools.

4.2.3.4.3 Lack of staff member at school

Furthermore, the lack of inclusive educational settings was not aided by the lack of specific support staff for disabled students. Instead, teachers were given the responsibility to accompany the disabled pupils to their classrooms, to the canteen, school playground, or to the restroom, in which the latter could happen during the lesson delivery. The following statements serve as evidence for the aforementioned ideas.

“Our schools are inadequately supplied as well as they lack appropriate pathways to allow entry for all students, especially those who have mobility impairment. Due to the fact that there are stairs everywhere, the teacher is responsible for helping the disabled student move around when he needs to use the restroom or go to the school canteen” (P10I).

“Teachers are responsible for helping students with physical disabilities when they need to use the restroom or move around because we lack accessible pathways and toilets” (P11I).

4.2.3.5 Inadequate report at the school level

The lack of a more holistic approach to inclusive education was equally present in the lack of a wider reporting infrastructure in schools. All participants agreed that, aside from the usual pedagogical practices, there is no reporting on inclusive education at the school level. According to all teachers' opinions, they regularly teach and report on pupils' evaluation but not particularly on issues pertaining to inclusive education. As one participant stated:

“Although I have pupils with hearing impairment and physical impairment in my classroom, yet nobody has requested a report on the way I am educating them” (P2F).

It has been stated by the teachers that there is no method in place in the schools that would direct them in reporting on the inclusive education of students with disabilities. Since teachers are not required to provide information on the progression of disabled children, the adaptations that could be provided to support the learning of students with disabilities are not defined.

4.2.3.6 Lack of teacher- parents collaboration

According to studies conducted in several regions of the world, teacher-parent collaboration is crucial for parents and educators to discuss with one another, work together, and share knowledge in order to effectively and meaningfully educate disabled children (Henderson and Mapp, 2002). Guardians and educators must work together to pinpoint the areas of pupils' progression that require intervention and to set adequate aims and objectives to accomplish (Carlisle, Stanley and Kemple, 2005).

When participants were asked about what factors that could prevent the inclusion of students with physical and sensory disabilities in regular schools in Algeria, most participants in this research acknowledged that among the barriers of the inclusive education of children with disabilities is a lack of communication and collaboration between the teachers and parents of disabled children. They stated that parents do not follow up on their disabled children. However, they placed great significance on the role of disabled children`s parents in the learning of their children in the regular schools. As one participant declares:

“I have three disabled children in my class where I noticed that their parents never visit the school to ask about their progression in the class. I personally try to call over their guardians just to report on their children`s development. I think there should be at least a monthly meeting between parents and teachers to discuss the students` progression” (P2F).

Furthermore, three other teachers shared the same concern (P16I, P18, and P19I). This demonstrates that parents' contributions to the success of inclusive education in regular schools are recognised and valued. However, the aforementioned claim suggests that parents of disabled children do not collaborate with the school to promote inclusive education, in contrast to the social and biopsychosocial models of disability, which advocate for such engagement.

Once the parents of disabled children consult with teachers and talk about the needs of their children, educators would acquire further knowledge regarding the disabled pupils in their classrooms and improve their ability when dealing with them (Garcia-Melgar *et al.*, 2022). Lacking this kind of engagement and considering that schools are missing experts who can identify issues facing learners and give precise instructions on which methods are most effective for such

pupils, parent disengagement remains an obstacle to inclusive education (Yang *et al.*, 2023). Some of the participants did in fact mention this. One educator provided the following rationale for parent involvement:

“Communication with parents could be one strategy for improving our ability to handle pupils with physical and sensory disabilities. However, we still lack a plan for involving them” (P15I).

The quote above suggests that the teachers recognized that better communication with parents of learners with physical and sensory disabilities could improve their ability to support these students. However, they acknowledged that they currently lack a specific plan or strategy for involving parents in the educational process. This implies that there is a gap in their approach to inclusive education, and that developing a plan for parental involvement could be a valuable step forward.

4.2.3.7 Lack of Support and Guidance from the Algerian Ministry of Education

Based on the focus group discussion, teachers acknowledged a significant lack of communication and cooperation between school staff and the Ministry of Education regarding the development and implementation of inclusive education practices. While the majority of participants believed that reporting on the progress of inclusive education should be a part of teachers' duties, none were explicitly asked to do so. As one participant stated,

“I believe the Ministry of Education should request that we update them on the status of adopting inclusive education, but that is not occurring” (PIF).

According to the participants, the Algerian Department of Education failed to provide clear guidance on how to fulfil their responsibilities regarding inclusive education. This lack of direction hindered efforts to address the challenges associated with implementing robust strategies that promote interaction among key stakeholders. Educators believed that expanding their responsibilities to include reporting to higher-ranking individuals within the educational structure could benefit their position and work, but this was never implemented.

Teachers also emphasized the need for the Ministry of Education to designate officials to evaluate the implementation of the inclusive education policy at schools. They believed that collaboration with the school's headmaster and the educational system was essential for planning and improving inclusive practices (Grenfell, 2009). As one participant noted,

"I believe there need to be constant reporting on inclusive education. We ought to provide an update on how we are carrying out the policy to the ministry of education" (P4F).

Moreover, participants in the individual interviews identified several key areas where the Ministry of Education needed to improve its support for inclusive education. These included providing teacher training, appropriate teaching resources, enhanced school services and amenities, curriculum adaptation, and ongoing monitoring of inclusive classroom strategies.

Several teachers expressed their frustration with the lack of support from the Ministry of Education. For example, one teacher stated:

"I accept that this school is becoming inclusive, but I am unsure of how we can assist these disabled students. The department of education should provide more resources and give us clear instructions on how to deal with these students" (P18I).

Another teacher noted:

"General teachers cannot currently do anything to meet the needs of students with physical and sensory disabilities. Unless the department of education provides teachers with sufficient training, the curriculum is changed, and the entire educational school is adjusted appropriately" (P14I).

"The Department of Education does not provide us with sufficient assistance. I believe that if they could simply assign one of their staff, perhaps for tracking, since it is necessary to have a professional from the Department of education to take over our school and then assist us" (P16I).

Other participants echoed the need for increased support from the Ministry of Education. For example, P20I, P6I, P17I, P11I, P5I, and P15I all expressed similar views.

The lack of support from the Ministry of Education was a recurring theme among the participants, highlighting the need for greater involvement and guidance from the ministry in promoting inclusive education.

4.2.3.8 Behavioural problems

The findings of the study showed that teachers found it challenging to involve students with disabilities in the in regular classroom activities. Despite using a variety of ‘teaching techniques and classroom management strategies with students who have disabilities, teachers observed that some of them were not making progress due to their non-engagement. This then frequently presents as displaying poor attitudes in class, which prevents other pupils from learning. As one participant stated:

“I have a student who has autism, and I have tried a variety of techniques to keep him interested, such as assigning him simple activities like word matches. However, I did not notice any improvement beyond the fact that he continued to annoy his classmates by making noise and keeps moving around in the classroom. He does not follow my instructions; in fact, there are occasions when I wonder if he really understands what I am saying. I believe that only an expert should be able to address this kind of behavioural problem” (P6I). Another participant (P9I) voiced similar view.

The quote highlights the challenges faced by a teacher in managing a student with autism in a regular classroom setting during the absence of meaningful pedagogical techniques that enable students to engage in learning activities. The techniques employed, based on the teacher’s own judgement and without the appropriate training the student presents disruptive behaviour. The teacher believes that specialized expertise is needed to enable the student to engage and address the student's behavioural challenges.

4.2.4 Teachers` perspectives on methods and strategies to improve inclusive education

Despite the lack of formalised training in relation to inclusive education, teachers, directly and implicitly, outlined some basic methods which could support the development of inclusive education setting to accept pupils with disabilities in regular schools. All participants agreed that fundamental changes and practical reforms are needed across the whole of the educational system in order to effectively implement and improve the outcomes of inclusive education. One of the teachers made the following statement regarding this idea:

“To enable such children with disabilities to receive an education, the educational system should be completely redesigned, and schools should be improved. The government should raise

awareness of inclusion” (P5I).

The improvement of the educational system and the schools themselves have been considered to be the most effective strategy for enhancing education for pupils with special needs. This result lines up with the latest research by (Ainscow and Messiou, 2018), which found that modification affects educational systems at all levels, from classroom teachers to school directors, administrators, and those in charge of determining national educational policy.

The next section discusses major concerns that particularly dealt with methods and strategies to improve inclusive education. These include curriculum adaptation, teacher training and raising their motivation, collaboration, school facilities and services, and raising awareness of inclusive education.

4.2.4.1 Enhancing teachers training and raising their motivation

The data analysis demonstrated that teachers might not be aware of the precise procedure that can direct purposeful, appropriate, and developed inclusive education. However, the findings revealed that participants were convinced that professional development and training are the most effective methods to improve educational achievement of pupils with special needs.

However, the majority of teachers in Algeria receive training for teaching the regular curriculum only. Hence, none of them received special needs training. As stated by these participants:

“Special needs require specialized training, but we have received general teacher training rather than specialized training” (P2I).

“Teacher should get training in inclusive education to better meet the needs of disabled pupils” (P4I).

“Providing currently employed educators with in-service training. These training would give educators the chance to advance their educational competence, skills, and knowledge on how to deal with special needs pupils in inclusive classroom” (P13I).

The aforementioned quotation stands for teachers' knowledge of the influence of their training on the quality of accommodating pupils who have special needs.

The majority of participants advised making special needs training compulsory for teachers since it plays a fundamental role developing the necessary and specific skills and guarantees ongoing proficiency as well. As stated by one of the participants:

“I believe that professional development is crucial for teachers to advance their knowledge and learn new approaches to teaching pupils with special needs in general and those with physical and sensory disabilities in particular [...] All teachers should receive training in inclusive education and follow up with in-service training in order to effectively deal with students with special needs” (P11).

Another teacher supported training by saying the following:

“Preservice training in special needs would be mandatory for everyone who passed the teaching context exam [...] to raise awareness among current teachers about special needs and inclusive education I would plan seminars and workshops” (P17I). In the same vein (P6I) agreed with this point by claiming that:

“As general teachers in mainstream classrooms, there are a number of skills we need to develop [...] the government is required to provide preservice and in-service training in inclusive education to encourage teachers to alter their negative perspectives, which are the result of their lack of knowledge in inclusive education” (P6I).

According to the participants' replies, giving teachers proper teacher training instructions is an efficient strategy to aid them in gaining confidence in their ability to teach pupils who have disabilities. Insufficient teacher training might represent a significant factor in their negative attitudes, especially when they believe that they are unqualified to teach pupils with disabilities. *As demonstrated by one of the participants who claimed:*

“It would have been preferable if the government had offered us with additional training in inclusive education. I lack the confidence necessary to teach students with special needs. I do not believe I am qualified enough” (P11).

Likewise, another participant stated:

“The Ministry of Education must send teachers to inductions, seminars, or ongoing training so that they can receive the appropriate guidance on how to help students with special needs including those with physical and sensory disabilities. [...] positive attitudes towards students with disabilities, could be fostered by providing educators with inclusive education and special needs training in addition to ongoing workshops and conferences” (P3I).

These participants argue that these kinds of training programmes ought to be mandated in order to help teachers better comprehend disabilities, recognise learning obstacles, and develop teaching

strategies that are targeted towards pupils with special needs. The results of the study have shown that educators would be eager to develop their skills and knowledge if there were possibilities to promote their education and encourage the engagement of all pupils in inclusive classrooms. As one Participant pointed out:

“Providing currently employed educators with in-service training. These training would give educators the chance to advance their educational competence, skills, and knowledge on how to deal with special needs pupils in inclusive classroom” (P13I).

The responses from the above participants indicate that teacher training has a considerable influence on teacher`s attitudes and instructional abilities as well as how pupils learn.

A recent study has revealed that the ideal strategy to boost the educational level is improving pre-service teacher training (Safdar and Rashid, 2021). In accordance with this finding, the study's participants have suggested a number of ideas for raising the quality of education, such as allowing educators to have a say in the decisions that are made about the educational system and rewarding teachers in ways that will boost their motivation. The above statement illustrates these points:

“The government needs to act severely and create clear plans and strategies of how to assist these learners with disabilities. As well as engage educators in making decisions in the meantime [...] Providing educators with monthly bonuses to motivate them to work with disabled learners” (P11I).

“I would provide teachers with the required resources, in-service training in inclusive education, and bonuses to motivate them to work with disabled students” (P12I).

“I will provide teachers with training and give them bonuses so they will be more motivated to teach disabled students” (P15I).

4.2.4.2 Improving school facilities and services

The finding revealed that the majority of educators thought that the challenges presented by the school environment need to be addressed urgently. As this participant claimed:

“If students with disabilities are to be enrolled in normal schools, school infrastructure and resources must be improved. [...] Improving the facilities should happen as soon as possible” (P1I).

Additionally, another participant offered the following advice for enhancing the school services and facilities:

“I think that the availability of amenities and services for children with special needs is affected by financing; if government departments invest additional funds in general schools, these institutions are going to be capable of offering pupils an affordable educational environment that is appropriate for their diverse needs” (P17I).

The above participant's statement demonstrated that financing was required to improve the school's facilities and services, and funding from the government was thought to be the best method for doing so.

Several participants stated that it is the facilities and services that needed to be improved, including creating accessible wheelchair pathways, restrooms, desks, chairs, and elevators that could accommodate pupils with mobility issues. The following comment illustrates this view:

“A significant step toward meeting the needs of students with disabilities would be to modify the school and classroom environments. Such as, providing special corridors for those with mobility impairment, enlarge classrooms doors for those who use wheelchairs, special desks and chairs, and special restrooms” (P8I).

In line with this view, another participant puts emphasis to the school setting and the suggestion to change the school structure in order to encourage the participation of pupils with disabilities, in accordance with the main purpose of addressing the needs of all learners as opposed to rejecting particular pupils. As it is stated:

“Changing infrastructure to support children with special needs based on the idea that it is better to meet each student's requirements than to exclude some students” (P1I).

Furthermore, several services were discovered to be not accessible and unsuitable for pupils with special needs, leading the majority of teachers to suggest acceptable modifications to eliminate these obstacles as well as other drawbacks in order to make regular schools more welcoming to all pupils. For example,

“Our school lacked the necessary sports tools and materials to include pupils who have disabilities. They were unable to participate in physical activity or sports. While the non-disabled pupils participate in physical activities on the playground those with disabilities like to stay in the classroom and complete other tasks [...] Making improvements to the school's services, such as creating wheelchair-accessible restrooms, chairs, desks, and pathways, as well as enlarging classroom doors” (P10I).

Furthermore, most teachers recommended constructing schools in a manner that considered the

individual various needs in order to decrease the bias that exist in the present inclusive setting.

“Designing schools in a manner that took into account the various needs of all students such as providing accessible restrooms, walkways, and playground for learners with mobility impairment” (P20I).

According to a different participant, providing the adequate facilities and services would boost the participation of disabled pupils, which would enhance inclusive education.

“The inclusion of children with SEN would be improved with better infrastructure that would increase their participation in regular education. For example, providing walkways, toilets, accessible playgrounds, escalators, etc. [...] providing the necessary equipment and supplies” (P4I).

Moreover, one participant (P3I) highlighted the need for improved facilities to foster welcoming settings and minimise obstacles. This participant proposed that as a means to encourage inclusive educational environments, infrastructure should be modified, wheelchair-accessible restrooms be provided, and accessible playgrounds be guaranteed.

Another participant proceeded a step deeper and emphasised the concept of making appropriate adjustments to certain services, such as expanding doorways, altering desks and tables.

“The classroom setting as well as the surrounding area could be modified. Students who use wheelchairs could be accommodated with changes like enlarged classroom doors, providing walkways, appropriate chairs and desks, toilet for SEN pupils, etc.” (P4I).

4.2.4.3 Enhancing Collaboration for Inclusive Education

According to the research’s outcomes, teachers recognized that they have inadequate abilities and skills necessary to create inclusive classrooms. Teachers highlighted collaborating with policymakers in the ministry of education as a key technique for improving inclusive education. One participant advocated for a strategy of collaboration and strengthening relationships with all parties involved, in which she proposed:

“Collaboration and stronger connections with all parties involved in mainstream education, including the policymakers, the headmaster of school, administration staff, teachers, parents, and communities” (P1I).

This quote draws attention to the importance of families and communities’ engagement in improving education for everyone.

Similarly, other teachers emphasised how important it is to have the entire staff in the mainstream school collaborate to improve the inclusive education, including (P4I, P15I, and P16I). In terms of cooperation, recent research has confirmed this concept of collaboration between schools and communities that can be applied as a strategy to enhance the educational process (Lambrechts, 2014). Additionally, collaborating with multiple entities shows that a school is accountable for transforming towards a learner- focused environment for education (Nyatuka, 2017).

Some participants brought attention to a further significant result on the advantages of collaboration between teachers and parents of disabled children in fostering inclusion. The following claim serves as evidence to this view:

“It is critical that parents and teachers develop close relationships to improve the education of children with disabilities” (P18I). Different teachers (P1I, P15I, and P16I) agreed with this statement as well.

The aforementioned insight emphasises the positive effects of the cooperation between teachers and parents to develop an appropriate educational setting for learners with disabilities.

Teachers generally agreed that the collaboration between schools and community members is the initial phase to making sure that educational settings are suitable for disabled pupils. This is because these parties can work together to eliminate infrastructure-related obstacles by considering the needs of learners and communities as they perceive them and would support integrating these in a student-centred and pedagogical meaningful way.

4.2.4.4 Raising awareness of and commitment to inclusive education

According to the results of the individual interviews, one of the most effective ways to improve inclusive education in Algeria is to increase awareness among parents, teachers, and other stakeholders. The majority of interviewees noted that communities and teachers needed to be more knowledgeable about inclusive education and issues relating to disabilities. With this understanding, one participant pointed out how to handle this problem by claiming that:

“To enable such children with disabilities to receive an education, the government should raise awareness of inclusion” (P5I). This statement emphasises the significance of education individuals about the possibility of including children with disabilities in regular schools alongside their classmates who are not disabled. This approach might serve as an example for institutions that continue to argue that facilities for the education of disabled pupils should not be located in

their areas. Additionally, the primary objective of this technique is to make inclusion attainable by encouraging educators to adopt favourable perspectives. As one participant stated:

“Raising awareness of inclusive education through preservice and in-service training for general teachers. To encourage them to alter their negative perspectives, which are the result of their lack of knowledge in inclusive education” (P6I).

The participant claimed that negative conceptualizations are created owing to the lack of understanding of the disability and inclusive education, which makes teachers hold unfavourable attitudes toward the disabled pupils. Consequently, a different participant recommended raising awareness of issues related to disabilities and inclusive education. In which she said:

“Increase parental and educators understanding of disabilities and inclusive education through meetings, seminars, and workshops” (P19I).

Furthermore, another participant stated that teacher could gain a better knowledge of disabilities through associating and interacting with disabled learners. This will enable personal engagement for pupils with disabilities to take place as well as to make inclusive education accessible in Algeria. It was suggested that this contact would take place at the general educational settings, by adding special classrooms in the regular schools. As the following quotation revealed:

“I believe we can raise knowledge of disabilities by creating special classrooms for pupils with special needs in every primary school. Pupils with serious impairments should enrol in these classrooms, whereas pupils with moderate impairments can start out in regular classes. Children with and without disabilities, as well as teachers, will have the opportunity to interact in a healthy way thanks to this knowledge” (P18I).

The above statement illustrates compensating strategies for offering education to all learners in the same educational setting while limiting the negative effects of prejudice and striving toward suitable inclusive classrooms. Moreover, this response serves as evidence that this participant supported the use of special education classrooms as inclusion steps for admission to regular classrooms. The participant proposed the special classrooms attached to regular schools as a means of achieving both educational and social inclusion.

Likewise, some other participants (P1I, P2I, P4I, and P7I) called attention to the necessity of increasing non-disabled students' awareness of disabilities so that they can welcome them and encourage their inclusion. The following statement illustrates this view:

“The non-disabled pupils should be ready to welcome their new classmates by making them aware of the existence of disability” (P11).

The quote above highlights a crucial aspect of creating inclusive classrooms by educating nondisabled students about disabilities, schools can help to break down stereotypes and prejudices, creating a more welcoming and inclusive environment for all students. This can involve teaching about different types of disabilities, promoting inclusive language and behaviours, creating opportunities for interaction, fostering empathy and understanding through discussions and role-playing activities. By implementing these strategies, schools can help to create a positive and inclusive learning environment where all students feel valued and supported.

4.2.4.5 Laws and regulations

According to the findings of this study, the participants did not explicitly address any ideas for enhancing laws and regulations. However, it was fascinating to see research participants make, implicitly, unintentional laws and regulations recommendations, such as those pertaining to inclusive education regulations, in order to advance the field. For example, one participant suggests:

“The government should take a bold stance and create clear strategies to assist these kids with special needs in order to ensure inclusion” (P4I).

This result has significant ramifications for altering regulations and guidelines that enhance the inclusive education of disabled pupils in regular schools. One more participant supported this technique by adding that:

“My school currently does not have any rules regarding inclusive education. [...] The responsible for this situation should be the Ministry of Education, which has failed to provide us with any guidance regarding the creation of policies” (P5I). Two further participants, (P16I) and (P6I), also agreed with this viewpoint.

This demonstrates that the ministry of education is responsible for formulating educational policies, based on that, participants suggested that the ministry of education should offer workable laws and guidelines regarding how to implement inclusive education in order to address the challenges confronting teachers and schools.

Similarly, a different teacher stated: *“The inclusive education policy in Algeria is nothing more than words on a piece of paper since there are no particular regulations in the school that staff*

member could followed” (P111).

The study found that clear regulations and guidelines are essential to ensure inclusive education in regular schools. To effectively implement these policies, schools must prioritize practical strategies and support. By focusing on professional development, collaborative planning, monitoring and evaluation, community engagement, and accessibility, schools can bridge the gap between policy and practice and create a more inclusive and equitable learning environment for all students. This approach aligns with the study's findings and demonstrates a commitment to providing high-quality education for learners with special needs.

4.3 Summary of findings

The aim of this doctoral research project is to determine how general teachers in Algeria particularly in Relizane province perceived and experienced the implementation of inclusive education for students with physical and sensory disabilities in regular primary schools.

In the current section, the results are examined under four major themes which were developed from the targets of the research stated in the first chapter. The following are the main themes discussed: teachers' understanding of the concept of inclusive education; teachers' attitudes, experiences, and perceptions of inclusive education; The challenges that Algerian mainstream primary school teachers face when implementing inclusive education, and teachers' perspectives on methods and strategies to improve inclusive education. The outcomes of the present research are discussed in connection to a collection of previously reviewed literature.

4.3.1 Teachers' attitudes, experiences, and perceptions of inclusive education

The following section addresses the perceptions, experiences, and attitudes of the teachers regarding the implementation of inclusive education for pupils with physical and sensory disabilities in their regular primary schools. The current section addresses the outcomes of the research in light of the goal stated in the first chapter of this thesis, which is to investigate the teachers' perceptions, experiences, and attitudes towards the inclusion of learners with physical and sensory disabilities in Algerian public schools.

According to this research, a number of teachers were passionate about implementing inclusive education and thought it was necessary. The result of this research supports (Othman, 2015) arguments that inclusive Education fosters social contact, breaks down barriers between students, and assists educators as well as learners without disabilities in understanding the needs of students with disabilities. Since educators recognised the need to accommodate various types of students in their educational settings, they felt that the adoption of inclusive education was necessary. This is why they were passionate about, and eager to put it into inclusive practices. In this research, the perspectives of teachers with regard to the necessity of implementing inclusive education support the findings of (Phasha and Moichela, 2011), who affirm in their investigation that inclusive education, alongside its goal of promoting equitable educational opportunities and fulfilment for all, is certainly a significant tool that could provide novice teachers as well as veteran teachers with the knowledge and skills needed to effectively teach in inclusive diverse educational settings. However, this research highlights that there are some underlying issues and serious obstacles for teachers in this context to implement pedagogically meaningful strategies to further truly ‘inclusive’ settings:

4.3.1.1 Instructional strategies used in the inclusive classrooms

At the level of individual teachers, the majority of educators reported utilising a variety of teaching strategies, including flexibility, using pair or group works, and peer assistance. The research also revealed that teachers might use peer assistance, which involve having pupils in similar age teaching one another in pairs or groups, to increase engagement among pupils and encourage those who have disabilities to participate in class activities.

The teachers stated that by using flexible ways to group and organize students based on their skills and passions, this would help pupils who encountered difficulties. The employment of peer mentoring teaching and assistance, as demonstrated by the outcomes of the current re-search, is consistent with the claims made by other authors (Bui *et al.*, 2010) in that these two methods are among the best successful ones for inclusive classes. Similarly, according to a Nigerian study by Eskay & Oboegbulem (2013), flexible learning groups and personalised methods of evaluation promote greater motivation for everyone in the class, boost their self-esteem, improve the efficacy of inclusive education, and eliminate the biased designated exams.

On the other hand, the research's findings indicate that not all of the participants recruited in this investigation had positive and encouraging views about inclusion. A number of teachers demonstrated unfavourable views towards the inclusion of pupils with disabilities by asserting that specialised schools were the proper place for them. For instance, they said that specialised schools were more appropriate for pupils with disabilities to study. These replies suggested that the medical model of disability was connected to the preferences of educators for the separated educational institutions that were already in place in the province of Relizane for pupils with disabilities.

Although recent Studies indicate that when educators' preexisting assumptions are challenged by an innovative inclusive education strategy, their views are negatively impacted (Ainscow and Miles, 2008; Jordan, Schwartz and McGhie-Richmond, 2009), the fact that educators are unable to acquire the necessary skills and knowledge in this frequently challenging field of education, have an impact on the unfavourable mindsets and opinions held by teachers. Given the heavy reliance on teachers themselves in relation to the translation of inclusive policies into the practical setting of the classroom, the hurdles they face due to the lack of specialised professional training, and some of the barriers around very basic accessibility to teaching facilities by disabled students, it is fair to suggest that this relatively negative view of inclusive education derives from an 'over-responsibilities' of teachers, rather than an unwillingness to implement and the lack of a fundamental commitment to inclusive education.

Educators who are insufficiently trained to educate students with disabilities frequently experience feelings of inadequacy, anxiety, fear, and panic Whenever they try to complete an activity that goes outside the guidelines of their practices (Unianu, 2012). Educators who were unsure of their position in this regard and their ability to deal with learners who have disabilities continued to have unfavourable views. when educators have little regard for the education of pupils with disabilities in ordinary classrooms. this argument is in opposition to the biopsychosocial viewpoint that all students with disabilities have a right to an education.

It became apparent in the current research that, with the exception of a small number of participants, the rest of the teachers had unfavourable and unsupportive perspectives on enrolling disabled learners into regular classrooms. Several variables were found to contribute to these unfavourable and pessimistic views; these aspects will be discussed in the section that follows.

4.3.1.2 Conceptual Regression from Inclusion to Integration

The dominant conceptualisation among teachers, which prioritised physical placement and social interaction (as reflected in P2I's focus on the student adjusting to "their surroundings"), is analytically significant. This perspective indicates that the operative philosophy remains fixed in the limited paradigm of Integration, rather than achieving genuine Inclusion. The Integration Model inherently places the primary responsibility for adaptation onto the individual learner, which is fundamentally inconsistent with the Social Model of disability that demands systemic and pedagogical reform of the educational environment.

Furthermore, the data points to a concerning theoretical regression to the Medical Model. This is evidenced by the view that inclusion is merely a form of "special education" (P14I) and the subsequent proposal for internal segregation via designated facilities (P18I). This impulse shifts the focus away from systemic barriers toward managing the individual impairment. Such conceptual ambiguity acts as a profound intellectual barrier, ensuring that teachers are conceptually ill-equipped to transition to truly differentiated and inclusive pedagogies.

4.3.2 Teachers' understanding of the concept of inclusive education

The above demonstrates that educators' understandings of the notion of inclusive education differs from one another immensely. The next part will address these assumptions in the context of the prior research investigations that were examined in Chapter 2. In this part, the researcher will argue that most of these views indicate a lack of understanding of inclusive education.

The literature review in this research paper has addressed the idea regarding the optimal way to deliver education which has evolved via three primary phases, which are conceptualised and implemented as the inclusion, integration, and segregation views. These views have been significantly affected by three general perspectives on disability, which are presented through the lens of the medical, social, and biopsychosocial models.

Most of the research participants' interpretations of inclusive education are more in line with integration and segregation perspectives instead of inclusion viewpoints because they make sense when viewed through the lens of social and medical paradigms. Meanwhile, a few other

participants only talked about certain points of inclusion, yet their knowledge was compatible with what inclusive education is defined as in the literature review Chapter. To begin with, some teachers believed that inclusion meant placing students with special education needs (SEN) in regular schools, yet in special education classes run by special education teachers who could provide them with better support rather than general education teachers who are not trained to work with learners with disabilities. These assumptions will be perceived as being influenced by medical perspectives on disability and in line with segregation claims. The medical paradigm, which views disability as a personalised issue requiring specialised assistance, is commonly cited as the rationale for the segregation of disabled pupils in special education institutions (Zaks, 2023).

According to the segregation approach, special education schools are better suited for pupils with disabilities since they are in a less stressful setting and are not required to maintain with other students who do not have disabilities (Wang, 2009). Even though the participants did not advocate for the segregation of pupils with disabilities in special education schools, Certain educators voiced worries regarding the possibility that the distinct obstacles faced by these students stemmed from emotional and psychological issues. Additionally, a few teachers expressed a preference for keeping students with disabilities separate from their nondisabled peers. Accordingly, the opinions of these teachers appear to be aligned with the medical justifications offered by those who favoured segregation. It is not unexpected that some teachers in Algeria continue to see disabilities as medical issues requiring particular care; this was also discovered in earlier studies done in a different setting, Saudi Arabia (Alothman, 2014; Alzemaia, 2019). In Alzemaia's research, certain educators shared their opinions, stating that special education schools were a preferable option for learners with disabilities since these institutions would offer greater assistance.

On the other hand, some educators insisted that pupils with disabilities should be placed apart from classmates without disabilities to prevent inappropriate behaviour. According to (Mitchell and Sutherland, 2020), adopting an inclusive educational system entail respecting the privilege of learners with special education needs to be handled equally. It appears that some of the teachers in the current research were unaware of this. Teachers that advocate for isolating learners who have disabilities in specialised educational institutions or in regular schools to protect them from persecution do so because they are unaware of the rights of those with disabilities and the objective

of the inclusive education strategy. If these teachers had known about this fundamental right, they might have searched for alternative strategies to prevent discrimination of disabled children.

Most of the teachers who participated in this research did not talk about the segregation of disabled learners in specialised schools, perhaps because they were sharing their opinions whilst bearing in mind the regulations set forth by the Algerian Ministry of Education, which mandate that learners with disabilities attend regular schools. In fact, some participants in this discussion raised up the matter of the integration of disabled learners into regular classrooms. Some of them supported this, arguing that it would be more beneficial for disabled learners to be placed in specific classrooms within the regular educational settings, while few others advocated for putting more emphasis on the psychological and emotional requirements of the learners.

Moreover, a number of educators have taken a different stance, believing that inclusive education of learners with disabilities entails having them physically present in regular classrooms or schools. Certain participants continued to say that regular schools are a better setting for learners with disabilities, while some others clarified that this is due to the fact that it promotes social contact both within and outside of the classroom. These perceptions appear to be more integration than inclusion viewpoints, as they are formed by the social paradigm. As previously mentioned in the literature review chapter of this dissertation, the integration view—which calls for incorporating learners who have disabilities into regular schools to ensure they can engage equally with other learners without disabilities—was formed by the social paradigm, which saw society as being limiting when it failed to take into consideration the needs of every person (Hardie and Tilly, 2012).

According to Ashman and Elkins (2005) the integration perspective entails placing children with disabilities in a less restricted setting in which they attend certain courses separately from their classmates within the same school however join other courses with their classmates who do not have disabilities. The integration approach improved the social outcomes for learners with special needs by facilitating more genuine interactions among learners with and without special needs (Booth, 2005). It appears that most of the teachers who participated in this study had opinions that are aligned with the integration standpoint's justifications. These assumptions appear to be uncomplicated on the surface since they concentrate on the social and psychological requirements

of children with special education needs or the advantages that social engagement could provide them.

Nevertheless, it appears that there is a lack of educational aspects and the duties of educators in promoting inclusion. In other words, some educators defined inclusion as merely having a learner enrolled in the regular school and they assign responsibility for the pupil's adjustment to the new setting for instance P5I stated:

“Inclusive education involves placing learners with special needs in a supportive setting to which they can adjust”.

Even when the participants stated that the objective of inclusion is to develop the educational level for disabled learners, it was in reference to the way disabled learners could gain from their nondisabled classmates instead of their educators or the schools. As claimed below by P2I:

“Inclusive education entails putting students with disabilities with their peers in regular classes so they can adjust to their surroundings while getting special attention so they can advance their educational levels by learning from other pupils”.

It appears that these participants do not understand that inclusive education entails developing programmes that are appropriate for every learner.

Despite the fact that some teachers have expressed the necessity for curriculum modifications, as demonstrated by the results obtained in the preceding chapter, this is simply due to their own experiences of facing challenges when attempting to teach learners with disabilities using the present educational program. As a result, it was more of a challenge they were having while working with learners with disabilities rather than it was something they understood what inclusive education entails. It is merely feasible to interpret most participants' beliefs as integration viewpoints. Numerous scholars have noted that these traits were present in the western educational institutions that embraced integration. For instance, (Mittler, 2012) contended that these kinds of institutions concentrated primarily on having a physical presence of learners with disabilities in it, rather than changing their educational programmes.

Additionally, Vislie (2003) claims that neither teaching nor learning nor instructional methods received significant attention during integration. This seems to be precisely the situation for most teachers whose opinions are being discussed, as well as the schools in which they are employed.

The same outcomes were obtained by Alanazi (2012) on the basis of an investigation conducted in Saudi Arabia. She felt that having this kind of mutual comprehension among teachers is beneficial since it prevents those learners with special needs from being marginalised. Added to that, she claims that despite not having access to a curriculum that is appropriate for disabled learners, these learners could still be able to acquire the particular skills they will ultimately require for both their daily activities elsewhere than school and their future careers (Alanazi, 2012).

Nevertheless, it is ineffective to improve Algeria's educational system by acknowledging these teachers' positive viewpoints and defend them with references to the social advantages disabled learners would experience. The unified perspective that these teachers seem to be embracing is unsatisfactory because it lacks foundational understanding of inclusive education in addition to a widespread lack of adequately trained teachers. Furthermore, if the case is made that the social advantages of the physical presence alone make it beneficial, then should not we acknowledge that segregation is beneficial in and of itself due to the extra guidance and support learners with special needs get? It would not promote inclusion to have such a perspective on the circumstances facing disabled learners in the Algerian mainstream school; however, it may improve the individual learners' experience in the absence of a pedagogically meaningful, practical implementation of inclusive education policy in mainstream schools. Finding the gaps in this common knowledge and investigating how they affect teaching methods are necessary steps that could ultimately contribute to improving the standard of learning. This section and other parts of the research paper contend that among the of the main issues affecting Algeria's inclusive educational programme is a lack of knowledge about inclusion. The results from the preceding chapter, revealing the way it demonstrates the teacher's perspectives and practices, give credence to this claim.

Similar results were obtained by (Alhammad (, 2017) in a research study carried out in Saudi Arabia. Educating learners with disabilities alongside other children without disabilities in regular classrooms was the only response given by some of those who participated in Alhammad's research when asked what inclusion meant. Despite this, these participants were nonetheless classified as having a deep comprehension and awareness of inclusive education (Alhammad, 2017).

In contrast to integration which means, on the example of Algeria, just placing learners with disabilities in mainstream classrooms and expecting them to thrive in their surroundings

(Matthews, 2009), inclusive education involves developing the educational setting to value variation, embrace individuals for who they are, and tolerate any differences (Nilholm, 2006). On the basis of the studies discussed in the second chapter, the researcher perceives the physical presence of learners with disabilities in regular schools, either by itself or in conjunction with chances for social contact, as a reflection of a lack of understanding of inclusive education. That is an integration-based approach to education and not an inclusive education strategy.

According to the research findings in the previous chapter, only few participants defined inclusion as giving care to all learners equally and without distinction, redesigning the educational programme to accommodate all students, or engaging staff members to work together in teaching all learners. These perspectives—while constrained—are actually concepts of inclusion and not integration. In the present study, the participants' comprehension fell short of fully capturing the concept of inclusive education, which may be achieved by reorganising the educational programme and learning environment in order to get rid of discriminatory procedures (Clough and Corbett, 2000). A small number of educators who participated in the study voiced the aforementioned interpretation of inclusive education, focusing instead on staff collaboration and curriculum modifications in order to provide educational opportunities for all pupils. In summary, it became evident that the educators who participated in this study had either restricted or inadequate understanding of the notion of inclusive education. This appears to be a predictable outcome of inclusive education practices in Algeria.

4.3.2.1 The Paradox: Teacher Willingness vs. Systemic Failure

The data on teachers' attitudes reveals a critical structural tension termed the "Paradox of Professional Will." While teachers demonstrate strong ethical commitment, this is immediately compromised by overwhelming systemic constraints, leading to a clash between personal willingness and professional capacity.

The expressed professional goodwill (P1I: "I do my best... That is all that I can do...") functions as unplanned safety net for policy gaps. However, the subsequent reliance on peer assistance (P1I, P6I) as a primary solution used to compensate for a lack of time (P3F) is analytically a process of shifting the burden onto non-disabled students. This strategy places the pedagogical responsibility

onto non-disabled students, confirming that the teacher's personal effort is an insufficient substitute for essential systemic support.

Conversely, the reported negative attitudes (P17I: "I find it unfair to include students with disabilities in these circumstances") must be interpreted not as personal prejudice, but as a rational professional judgment. This resistance constitutes a powerful critique of the system, arguing that the absence of necessary resources and training renders ethical, effective inclusion impossible. The system's failure compels the teacher to view the learner's disability as the unmanageable primary problem, thereby forcing a practical Medical Model outlook for classroom management.

4.3.3 The challenges that Algerian regular primary school teachers face when implementing inclusive education

On the structural level and as previously mentioned, teachers face great difficulties and obstacles when attempting to adopt inclusive education in ordinary primary schools in Algeria. This section's outcomes debate concentrates on one of the research's aims covered in the first chapter. It states, "to Examine the factors that affect inclusive education of physically and sensory disabled learners in regular primary schools in Algeria."

The current research found that most teachers in general primary schools in Algeria, specifically in Relizane Province, encountered barriers in implementing inclusive education since they lack the necessary preparation, and they were never given any training on how to implement inclusive education. Furthermore, the research participants have stated that it was extremely challenging for them to implement inclusive education due to their insufficient knowledge and experience.

The outcomes of the research conducted by Thwala (2015) in Swaziland supports the notion that teachers view the implementation of inclusive education as an obstacle. The research showed that teachers expressed stress about inclusive education because they typically were lacking the knowledge and abilities necessary for teaching in classrooms that are inclusive. Adebayo and Ngwenya (2015) carried out different research in Swaziland which more clearly demonstrated the disparity caused by inadequate professional development for educators. They noted that the majority of educators lacked the necessary qualifications to effectively manage learners with

disabilities and non-disabled learners in the same classroom, which had a negative effect on disabled learners' comprehension and achievement, which was consistently viewed as deficient because of the educators' insufficient knowledge and skills as inclusive teachers. Moreover, research conducted by Chireshe (2011), which indicated that teacher who had pre-service training in Zimbabwe thought that not every teacher could manage an inclusive classroom as they felt that ordinary classroom teachers found it difficult to modify their curricula to incorporate and cope with pupils with disabilities.

Consequently, additional information surfaced indicating that educators in Zimbabwe believed they were unqualified and unprepared to help pupils who have severe disabilities, leading to the exclusion of these learners from regular classrooms. Thus, this result support the finding that lack of understanding and insufficient training affect teachers' implementation of inclusive education. Shadreck (2012) found comparable outcomes in his research, claiming that most Zimbabwean educators assumed they were insufficiently prepared for inclusive education since they had not received the necessary training.

Based on the information gathered from both focus group discussions and individual interviews, the majority of participants in the pre-service teacher preparation programme did not receive sufficient training on inclusive education. The comments made by educators revealed that the main problem preventing inclusive education from being implemented effectively in their schools was the lack of specialised inclusive educational training during pre-service teacher training. Moreover, different research revealed that educators who lack the knowledge and skills required to engage with learners who have disabilities find it challenging to teach these pupils when they are in the classroom (Nishan and Darussalam, 2018). The elementary school educators in Relizane believed that they would not be able to expand their roles or carry-on extra duties without receiving appropriate preparation. Likewise, Educators must receive regular in-service training because it helps them remember their responsibilities in inclusive education (Ntombela, 2009). With regard to educators in Relizane province that was not the situation though. During this investigation educators described their biggest issue as lack of knowledge and skills, with the possibility that if they received in-service training, it might improve their inclusion abilities. Moreover, Singal (2008) states that educators who do not receive in-service training are unaware of the new responsibilities placed on them. Since skills improved throughout pre-service training degrade

with time, continuous in-service training for educators to modify their educational responsibilities is further beneficial (Ferguson, 2008). According to Florian (2008), in-service training is necessary for educators to be prepared for future requirements in their field. Thus, research on policies have demonstrated that the ability of the users in the domain is crucial to the effectiveness of a policy's implementation (Bourke, 2010). The conceptual value of the practitioners consists of their knowledge and competence with the inclusive policy (Grenfell, 2009). On the other hand, when it comes to inclusive procedures, educators lack sufficient in-service training, which limits their understanding of how to implement inclusive education (Ntombela, 2009).

According to the results of the present research, in-service programmes did not provide educators with the option to undertake training in inclusive education. This result is in line with an investigation conducted by (Le Fanu, 2010), who found that in-service training for the inclusive education programme in Papua New Guinea was met with opposition.

The outcomes of the present research further highlighted some of the difficulties in implementing inclusive education, which were identified by most of the teachers who took part in this research. According to different research carried out in Vietnam by Nguyet and Ha (2010), inclusive education necessitates educators to possess supplementary qualifications in order to create inclusive classes that accommodate a range of learners needs. Specifically, learners who have disabilities require substantial assistance from educators who have received the necessary training in order to actively engage in the classroom activities alongside their non-disabled peers.

In addition, a number of studies (for instance, Mara & Mara, 2012; Adewumi et al., 2017; Nucci, 2019; and Mishra et al., 2019) have shown that curriculum adaptation is necessary for inclusive education to be achieved and that an inappropriate curriculum is a challenge to implementing inclusion in schools. Likewise, Avissar (2012) argues that accessible and adaptable educational programmes are necessary to establish an inclusive environment. In fact, numerous scholars (such as Abhiyan, 2016; Schuelka, 2018) contend that a rigid curriculum may serve as a significant obstacle to effective inclusion.

In this regard, the current study found that the curriculum of every school included in the investigation acted as an obstacle to inclusive education. Once inclusive education began, the fundamental educational programme in each of these schools remained unchanged. This posed an obstacle to inclusion as the preceding chapter illustrated. In other words, the general educational

programme in these schools remained the same despite the fact that pupils with disabilities started attending regular classes. This presented difficulties for teachers due to the issues of modifying the present curriculum to fit the disabled learners' needs. Furthermore, the officials dispatched by the Ministry of Education concentrated solely on the number of lessons that the educator taught, which worsened the already terrible circumstances caused by the inappropriate curriculum. As a result of not having enough time to deliver lessons, educators began to disregard disabled learners in their classrooms. Thus, Educators appeared to be encouraged to overlook pupils with special needs in the classroom because of to the rigidity of the curriculum and the assessment process implemented by the Ministry of Education.

Additional obstacles that were covered in the literature review and supported by the results of this investigation included the educational setting, classroom size, resources, and amenities. Some previous research investigations have examined these factors, and it concluded that they were impeding the effectiveness of inclusive education. According to Singal (2005) and Al-Zyoudi (2006) it was discovered that the architectural design of schools—which is unsuitable for learners with disabilities—and the size of the classrooms had a detrimental impact on the achievement of inclusion. These features were not determined to be appropriate for inclusive education in any of the schools under study.

Furthermore, the findings of the present research showed that the teachers had a very negative opinion regarding the schools' settings and thought they were not suitable for teaching students with disabilities. The majority of teachers stated that they were working in educational institutions that required renovations and modifications in order to meet the needs of pupils who were physically disabled, visually impaired, or had other kinds of disabilities. Additionally, the results of this study also showed that most of schools operated in settings that were not prepared for the adoption of inclusive education. These settings included the double-story structures of schools, which lacked elevators or paths of accessibility for physically disabled students; the outdated facilities found in most regular schools; the lack of lifts, signs, pathways, or wheelchair-accessible restrooms; and classroom equipment that was inadequate.

According to the outcomes of this research, schools are not providing receptive educational environment that align with disabilities inclusive education systems and policies guide by Hayes and Bulat (2017). This guide states that all-inclusive classrooms must be easily accessible to all

pupils, particularly those with disabilities, and that the school must offer sufficient facilities for all pupils. Thus, the researcher's conclusions for this study show that the educational settings do not adhere to the current inclusion standards. The medical viewpoint of students with disabilities led the policymakers and other stakeholders to think that these students were best suited for special schools; as a result, they had no interest in making sure that regular school settings were fully equipped to serve students with disabilities. Similarly inadequate educational environments were found in the chosen regular primary schools in Relizane province, according to the results of the focus group discussions with general educators about the educational setting at these schools.

The perspectives of teachers shared in the individual in-depth interviews were supported by the results of the focus group discussions about the inclusive educational environments, which were determined to be unsuitable for the adoption of inclusive education in the current research investigation. The results regarding the inhospitable inclusive educational settings comply with the research outcomes conducted in Algeria by Hoadjli and Latrache (2020), which revealed that the majority of Algerian schools lacked appropriate infrastructure and that the physical setting was not adequate to support students with disabilities. This study also revealed that the educators in the Relizane Province of Algeria believed that there were difficulties in implementing inclusive education in regular primary schools, including a lack of resources and supplies that could help students who have various disabilities. Adebayo and Ngwenya (2015) reported the same outcomes, stating that a number of schools in the Shiselweni District of Swaziland lacked fundamental amenities like classroom ventilation, adequate adaptive equipment for students with disabilities, and appropriate supplies that could be used by both students with and without disabilities. Likewise, Avramidis (2001) demonstrated how certain learners with special needs struggled due to a lack of amenities and resources like hearing devices and technology. It appears that the schools under investigation share characteristics like this.

Moreover, educators involved in the current study found that lack of support from the Ministry of Education was one of the reasons why learners with disabilities should be relocated from their regular classes. Also, they highlighted some matters under the responsibility of the Ministry of Education that needed further attention to enhance the execution of inclusive education. The Ministry of Education failed to conduct the required visits that would have allowed it to manage the education of learners with disabilities, therefore teachers and schools in Algeria did not

prioritise enrolling these learners. Most participants claimed that there are infrequent visits by Ministry of Education authorities to assess how well the school is doing in providing education to learners with disabilities. Additionally, there was no assessment or tracking of the effectiveness of inclusive education. Learners with disabilities received no particular consideration. These pupils attended the school the same as the rest of the students without any extra resources or assistance from the Ministry of Education. Foreman and Arthur-Kelly (2017) state that it is common in schools for individuals in positions of authority in the educational system to provide instructions and then let the educators carry them out without conducting additional assessment to check on the effectiveness of the teaching practices.

The effectiveness of implementing inclusive education was said to have been adversely impacted by the factors mentioned earlier, which also restricted the enrolment of students with disabilities in ordinary schools. Additionally, the present research demonstrates that overcrowding in classrooms was a problem in many schools in Relizane province. Based on the outcomes of the focus group discussion and the individual in-depth interviews. Teachers found it challenging to handle their classrooms because of the overcrowding in their classes. The results of this research also showed that teachers were unable to provide disabled pupils the special care they needed because of the crowded classrooms, which made it impossible for educators as well as learners with wheelchairs to move around freely. Moreover, due to limitations on time, teachers have claimed that they were unable to provide individual attention to each student in the classroom.

Furthermore, the research results of this study are consistent with Abongdia's findings (2015), who noted that educators involved in their research were unable to recognise students who were experiencing educational challenges because of crowded classrooms. The same results were drawn from an investigation carried out in Algeria by Tayeg (2015), who found that most teachers and learners could feel uneasy when educating or studying in a crowded classroom. Teachers also find it difficult to keep control of their pupils in large, noisy classrooms, particularly when pupils are required to complete tasks or complete before their peers. The problem of crowded classrooms, as highlighted by the results of this investigation, is additionally supported by research done in Uganda by Isingoma (2014), who found that huge or crowded classrooms made it impossible for teachers to carry out their duties effectively and that high enrolment exacerbated the issues of poor supplies and facilities. Chireshe (2013) reports same results, claiming that a high teacher-to-pupil

ratio (1 to 40) in several elementary schools in Zimbabwe exacerbates the shortage of resources and leaves teachers with limited space to accommodate students with disabilities. According to Molosiwa and Monyatsi (2017), the huge number of students in inclusive classrooms prevents teachers from being as effective and creative as they may be in trying to keep educational opportunities accessible for every student.

A major obstacle that was addressed in the literature and supported by the results presented in the preceding chapter was the absence of staff cooperation. According to numerous researchers (Boavida & Ponte, 2011; Paju et al., 2022) Cooperation between staff members is crucial for the effectiveness of inclusive education. It supports teachers in establishing goals and plans to reach them and successfully implement inclusive (Bhroin and King, 2020).

Reforming the educational system in an attempt to optimise the benefits of inclusive education is another effect of this partnership (Waldron and Mcleskey, 2010). Likewise, educators would get a chance to exchange knowledge in order to solve the issue of insufficient experience (Milteniene and Venclovaite, 2012). However, it was discovered that there was a lack of collaboration among staff members in the schools under study, with teachers claiming that they bore sole responsibility for teaching pupils who have disabilities. As a result of this, educators neglected pupils with disabilities in the classroom since they were unsure of ways to educate or deal with them. The situation might have been solved with cooperation among the school staff.

Additionally, the investigated schools had no engagement from parents, which posed a challenge for effective inclusive education. Teachers at these schools acknowledged the significance of this factor, but they claimed they lacked the methods to put it into practice. Several studies (e.g. Friend & Cook 2009; Epstein & Sheldon 2022) have argued that parental involvement regulations in schools could benefit both educators and pupils alike by helping educators become more acquainted with the needs of their pupils and helping pupils achieve better academic results. Research conducted on this matter by (Singal, 2005) showed that parental participation enhanced both teachers and learners' performance. Although most of educators participating in this research said they had no idea how to work with learners with special needs, which may have been influenced to some extent by the absence of engagement of parents.

4.3.3.1 Analysis of Barriers: The Policy-Practice Disconnect

The challenges reported by the teachers are not simple practical issues; they are the tangible result and clear proof of a systemic policy failure to implement the Social Model of disability.

The widespread lack of necessary training (P13I) is the most critical structural flaw. This problem means teachers are only equipped to focus on the student's disability (the Medical Model), preventing them from making the systemic and curricular adaptations required by the Social Model.

Furthermore, the reported failures in physical infrastructure (unsuitable toilets, lack of ramps) constitute the concrete breach of the Social Model's core principle: that the environment, not the impairment, is the source of disability. The lack of specialized resources, coupled with the absence of clear regulations ("The inclusive education policy in Algeria is nothing more than words on a piece of paper..." P11I), points to a profound lack of accountability from the Ministry of Education (P5I). Collectively, these barriers prove that the system is fundamentally designed for exclusion, effectively making the inclusive policy useless.

4.3.4 Teachers' perspectives on methods and strategies to improve inclusive education

Based on the data gathered, it appears that educators are hoping for a different approach to inclusive education than the existing one, which limits the inclusion of disabled learners to their attendance in the same classrooms as their classmates without disabilities. The results demonstrate a large number of educators are deficient in a variety of methods that might be used to overcome obstacles in the way of establishing inclusive schools. According to the findings of this study, educators do not have an in-depth knowledge inclusive education, so suggesting changes to a procedure that they do not fully comprehend was difficult.

Educators proposed a variety of strategies, a high number of them centred around most of the strategies teachers suggested included enhancing teachers training and raising their motivation, improving school facilities and services, collaboration, raising awareness of and commitment to inclusive education, as well as establishing Laws and regulations. The majority of the methods that

surfaced indicated that the initial step towards achieving inclusive education is to produce teachers who are confident enough to encourage all pupils in the classroom through appropriate preparation for educators and ongoing professional development. The majority of educational research affirm that educators' preparation and career development are essential to school improvement (Wilson, 2018; Rouse, 2008). Another research revealed that sufficient financial support is necessary for inclusive education policies and regulations to be carried out successfully. This financial support should also include incentives and awards for educators who take on responsibilities for their work and for attracting new teachers to the field (Johnstone and Chapman, 2009). Throughout the interviews, educators expressed that they considered their responsibility to implement the policy of inclusive education as a challenging endeavour. They therefore believed that their hard work should be acknowledged with extra income to raise their spirits and inspire them to keep working.

According to Smith and Tyler (2011) the results of great educational methods that become apparent are supported by having accessibility to facilities and resources that are suitable. Participants in the current study claim that one of the barriers preventing pupils who have disabilities from participating in and being fully engaged in the educational process is a lack of adequate facilities and resources. Therefore, they have recommended that in order to guarantee complete inclusion and involvement of pupils with disabilities in their schools, schools would need to figure out how to get access to such resources and facilities.

Furthermore, raising awareness of and commitment to inclusive education, enhancing cooperation between stakeholders in education, and establishing Laws and regulations were regarded as crucial strategies for improving inclusive education in Algerian mainstream schools. By increasing awareness of the importance of inclusive education among all stakeholders, schools can foster a more supportive and inclusive environment. Additionally, building strong relationships between schools, families, communities, and government agencies can enhance collaboration and facilitate the implementation of inclusive practices. Finally, establishing clear laws and regulations that support inclusive education can provide a legal framework for ensuring that all students have equal access to quality education. These strategies are interconnected and essential for creating a truly inclusive educational environment.

4.3.4.1 Critical Analysis of Suggested Improvements

The strategies proposed by the teachers function as a shared assessment of the systemic failures identified in the preceding sections, validating the analytical critique of the implementation gap.

The demands for enhanced training and improved resources/facilities are an analytical confirmation that the current system lacks the necessary intellectual and material support to transition from Integration to Inclusion. These suggestions are an implicit request for the State to fulfil the practical requirements of the Social Model.

The call for establishing clear laws and enhancing cooperation between stakeholders is a direct critique of the policy's implementation layer. Findings regarding the Ministry's failure to provide guidance (P5I, P11I) demonstrate a profound need for clear national standards and centralized responsibility. Moreover, the demand for cooperation—between schools, families, communities, and government agencies—validates the need for a relational approach aligned with the Biopsychosocial Model, which the current fragmented system actively neglects. The proposed solutions collectively reinforce the core argument: the challenges are structural, and their resolution requires a top-down commitment to enact the principles of the Social Model.

4.4 Conclusion

In this chapter, the outcomes of the study on teachers' perceptions of and experiences towards the inclusive education of physically and sensory disabled learners in the public primary schools in Relizane province in Algeria, have been described, analysed, and reviewed in relation to the goals of the research stated in the first chapter. The next chapter will address an overview of the research outcomes, limitations of the study, contributions and implications of study, recommendations, and recommendations for further research.

5 Chapter Five: Conclusion

5.1 Introduction

Conclusions of the research are presented in two sections in this chapter. The results are briefly summarised, then the impact of the research is discussed, along with various practical recommendations based on the research outcomes. Additionally, it suggests topics for further study. Then, a concluding set of comments closes the chapter.

The initial section

5.2 A Brief Overview of the results

The Algerian government prioritises the promotion of inclusive education for students with disabilities via its inclusive education strategy. Teachers in primary schools are an important occupational team whose job it is to include disabled students into mainstream classes in order to implement the inclusive educational policy at the elementary school system. The present research has given an overview of the perceptions and experiences of general teachers towards the current implementation of inclusive educational practices, particularly with regard to students with physical and sensory disabilities enrolled in different mainstream primary schools in the Relizane District of Algeria. The study sought to identify the variables that either enabled or hindered Algeria's adoption of inclusive education policies. Four themes arose from the data. They are recapitulated here in a concise summary.

5.2.1 Teachers' understanding of the concept of inclusive education

The results of this research demonstrated that most teachers lacked adequate understanding of inclusive education policy. The majority of educators in the research perceived inclusion as putting children with disabilities in regular classrooms, but others went further and acknowledged the social advantages disabled students would experience from interacting with their classmates who are not disabled. This comprehension was regarded as indicative of inadequate knowledge due to its ignorance of the human rights and educational implications of inclusion, as well as its failure to acknowledge the role that educators and schools play in this system. The notion that inclusion could be educationally beneficial was expressed by some participants, who believed that

disabled students would learn from classmates who are not disabled rather than what their educators provide. Apart from the physical placement and social benefits, a few other teachers also showed that they understood various aspects of inclusive education; however, their comprehension was seen as restricted since they only showed awareness of certain aspects, and none of these teachers completely defined the concept of inclusion.

5.2.2 Teachers` attitudes, experiences, and perceptions of inclusive education

This study revealed that some educators believed inclusive education was essential and were concerned about putting it into practice. According to the results of the present research, various educators expressed supportive and positive opinions on including learners with disabilities in mainstream classes. It was shown that teachers' efforts to use a variety of teaching strategies in their classes—such as flexibility, using pair or group works, and peer assistance—contributed to these optimistic and positive viewpoints, even if they were unaware of the inclusion policy.

On the other hand, the results of the study suggested that not all teachers who participated in this study held optimistic and supportive opinions towards inclusion. Some educators expressed negative opinions about including students with disabilities, claiming that special schools are the best settings for them.

From the present study, it was clear that aside from a small group of participants, most teachers had negative and unsupportive views on placing students with disabilities in mainstream classrooms. These negative and unsupportive perspectives were discovered to be influenced by a number of factors, some of which will be covered in the section that follows.

5.2.3 The challenges that Algerian regular primary school teachers face when implementing inclusive education

Based on the present study, the majority of general primary school educators in Algeria, particularly in the province of Relizane, found it challenging to implement inclusive education since they were not prepared or trained in this area. In addition, the study participants mentioned that because of their lack of experience and knowledge it was very difficult for them to actually carry out inclusive education.

This research revealed that a majority of teachers in mainstream schools lacked professional instruction on implementing inclusive education and were hesitant to shift from their current teaching methods. Furthermore, it was discovered that most of the schools in the district of Relizane lacked educational environments such as school's premises, structures, and classes organisation, which included cramped classrooms and inappropriate facilities and resources that would have accommodated students with impairments. Moreover, when it came to providing adaptive technology and supplies for students with disabilities it was revealed that nearly every school in the study lacked these resources. This was made worse by the absence of in-service training sessions, inspections, and guidance throughout the implementation of inclusive education policy by the Department of Education. Likewise, the majority of teachers at regular primary schools were also found to be facing difficulties putting the inclusive education policy into practice. These difficulties mostly stemmed from the curriculum, which was deemed inappropriate, the time constraints, and the lack of materials and tools required to guarantee the policy's implementation.

5.2.4 Teachers' perspectives on methods and strategies to improve inclusive education

Based on the results, it seems that the methods proposed were more about how to make mainstream schools better so that all pupils could attend classes in the same settings rather than they were about promoting for inclusive classrooms. The methods that mainly surfaced indicated that the first step towards achieving inclusive education is developing teachers who are confident in their ability to help all students in the classroom through offering appropriate professional development and teacher training. The majority of educational research studies concur that professional development and teacher training are essential to school reform (Wilson, 2018). Similar to that, inclusive education practices require increasing teachers' motivation through financial support. Incentives and prizes for educators who assume accountability for their job ought to be part of this financial support. Along with that, having accessibility to suitable facilities and resources also supports the results of effective procedures that become apparent (Varma *et al.*, 2021).

In conclusion, this study showed that developing laws and policies, collaboration among education stakeholders, and increasing public knowledge of inclusive education and disability

concerns were all regarded as crucial tactics for enhancing inclusive education in Algerian mainstream schools.

Second Section

5.3 Limitations of the study

Similar to any other academic research, there are some limitations to this study that have to be noted for the advantage of those who will be utilising or assessing the findings. The findings of this research have been impacted by a number of limitations. The requirement for triangulation is often a general difficulty faced by all interpretive investigators. The absence of observation or official documentation analysis in the present research due to the Covid19, nevertheless, entailed that the researcher was forced to depend entirely on focus group discussions and individual semi-structured interviews; as a result, the study was subject to additional restrictions.

The use of online interviews for data gathering in this study is another drawback. The study participant attendance posed a severe research limitation because of travel limitations, social distancing, and participant worries, all of which occurred during the COVID-19 pandemic when the researcher began data collection. A major disadvantage of carrying out study interviews online is that it might be less helpful in building connections between the participant and the researcher (Varma *et al.*, 2021) which is essential for creating a relaxed atmosphere and obtaining in-depth answers from the participant. According to (Varma *et al.*, 2021), it may be difficult to completely comprehend a participant's perspective or experience through an interaction that is restricted to a computer screen and audio because such replies can be more delicate or complex. On the other hand, participants in online interviews may find it even more convenient because they can take place from the comfort of their home or place of employment (Varma *et al.*, 2021). Online interviews save participants time because they do not require travel. According to certain studies, people may respond less reticently while discussing delicate subjects online than they would in person because of the greater flexibility that comes with it (Wilson, 2018).

In this study, twenty teachers participated in individual interviews and seven were selected for focus group discussions. A total of twenty-seven teachers were interviewed. Consequently, this limited how thorough the data could be. Drawing generalised findings from the responses of the

twenty-seven educators who were questioned proved to be challenging. Furthermore, no statistical information was provided regarding the number of pupils with disabilities attending regular schools. Moreover, the researcher was unable to analyse institutional and governmental documentation relevant to inclusive education or conduct additional research at other schools in different Algerian districts due to time and financial restrictions. This signifies an additional noteworthy limitation of the study.

An additional constraint pertains to the data translation process. The teachers' interviews were done in Arabic and had been subsequently transcribed into English. Although the researcher gave the interviews translation a lot of consideration, there are still some issues with the procedure. The researcher is of the opinion that translations are never faultless and that some concepts are constantly missed in the process. She is certain, nonetheless, that the information reported in this study do not in any manner distort the teachers and that the translated content accurately reflects the interpretations that the teachers articulated throughout the interviews.

5.4 Contributions and implications of study

Considering the aforementioned limitations, the research still makes numerous valuable contributions to the pertinent body of knowledge. In terms of methodology, the current research demonstrates the importance of qualitative research by using focus group discussion and individual semi-structure interviews to examine educators' perceptions and experiences towards the implementation of inclusive education in their mainstream classrooms.

The present research has enhanced knowledge in education by expanding on the notion that inclusive education offers a number of advantages for both learners who have disabilities and those without disabilities and helped all students become a member of the learning environment.

The research's use of the educators' perspective approach was one of its strongest points; it was especially helpful in identifying the lack of knowledge, representation, and preparation for the inclusive school's improvement procedure. Educators recommended that for schools to be successful in fostering inclusive settings, they must collaborate in a networked way with professionals, parents, administrators, and all government stakeholders. Notwithstanding the valuable nature of the techniques suggested by the research participants, it is imperative to

acknowledge that inclusive education have an initial basis, so being aware of how to begin is also important. To help in the process of creating inclusive educational environments, parents, teachers, and school administrators need a number of resources. According to the current research, not all learners gain from unprepared inclusion in regular classrooms. Because of this, Algerian policymakers may serve as a foundation for empowering schools to support all students, including students with disabilities who are welcomed into diverse classrooms.

This research will hold special significance in the field of education, since the reform of schools, teacher training, administrators' engagement, and collaboration among stakeholders will undoubtedly require significant legislative changes in order to advance Algeria's inclusive strategy.

Apart from contributing to the body of knowledge in educational studies overall, this study has various impacts on policy and practice. The findings provide necessary evidence for the Ministry of Education, demonstrating the need to immediately offer the funds required for application, adjustments, and improvements to current educational institutions. This includes securing suitable supplies and materials and training specialized teachers to ensure learners with disabilities are given schooling opportunities in their neighbourhoods and societies. Furthermore, the identified hesitance among educators to include students with disabilities—due to mainstream schools being inadequately set up or resourced—underscores a crucial policy goal: Every educational institution should adopt inclusive education. This ensures learners can attend the school of their preference or the school in their neighbourhood, rather than having to travel away from home to join specialized institutions often found only in bigger towns. Finally, to ensure that educators are adequately equipped to instruct all learners, the research requires a review of the curriculum in Algerian teacher training institutions. Since it is now expected that all educators will be ready to instruct all learners, teacher preparation programs should examine their curricula and incorporate inclusive education as a mandatory course.

5.5 Recommendations

The results of this study allow for the following suggestions to be provided in order to enhance inclusive education in Algeria.

Firstly, for the successful implementation of inclusive education, Algeria's Ministry of Education should foster comprehensive collaboration with all stakeholders, including teachers, parents, and school administrators. Before any implementation begins, it is crucial to ensure that all school personnel fully understand the goals, rationale, and underlying philosophy of inclusive education.

Secondly, the Ministry must prioritize careful planning and implementation when designing schools as inclusive. This demands that school administrators receive appropriate training to effectively lead the inclusion process and implement necessary procedural changes. This could involve hiring specialized directors or providing intensive training to existing leaders, thereby equipping them to guide their teams and foster robust collaboration among staff and parents.

Furthermore, ongoing training is essential to prepare educators to work with and teach learners with disabilities. The Ministry of Education and school administrators must jointly take responsibility for providing such continuous professional development. In tandem with training, the Department of Education and school administrators should collaborate to ensure that educational programs in inclusive schools are suitable for *all* learners.

Finally, to better support children with disabilities, school staff and the Department of Education must work together to significantly improve school facilities and resources. Given the persistent challenge of class size, the Department of Education should also consider hiring classroom assistants to support teachers in managing large, diverse groups of learners effectively.

5.5.1 Recommendations for Practical Application and Policy Scope

The preceding analysis established key recommendations for the Algerian Ministry of Education, primarily focusing on systemic reforms such as mandatory professional development, curriculum modifications, and targeted funding for infrastructure improvements. This section broadens the scope of these recommendations to address the role of individual educators and assesses the applicability of the findings across different geographical contexts.

5.5.1.1 Immediate Strategies for Individual Teachers

Although the primary obstacles to inclusive education in Relizane are structural and systemic (e.g., inadequate policy frameworks and a lack of official training), the research also highlighted the proactive commitment of individual teachers who developed their own effective strategies. These grassroots practices, implemented despite the absence of institutional support, offer a foundation for practical, day-to-day recommendations for teaching staff:

- **Adopt Adaptive Pedagogy:** Teachers must deliberately employ flexible instructional methods, acknowledging that standard curriculum delivery is insufficient for meeting diverse students' needs (Smith and Tyler, 2011). This involves designing learning activities that allow for multiple engagement and output options, moving beyond reliance on physical or writing tasks that may disadvantage students with sensory or physical disability (UNESCO, 2017).
- **Structured Peer Support:** Formalize and promote peer-assistance through the strategic grouping of students (Houtenville and Lauer, 2017). Non-disabled peers should be positioned alongside colleagues with disabilities not merely for personal care, but for mutual learning and collaborative task support (Houtenville and Lauer, 2017).
- **Maximize Communication Clarity:** Utilize multimodal communication techniques, such as repeating instructions, employing visual cues and body language, and asking students to rephrase information, to ensure all pupils fully comprehend lesson objectives (Smith and Tyler, 2011)
- **Conduct Micro-Environmental Adjustments:** Without waiting for extensive facility overhauls, teachers should optimize the classroom's micro-environment. This includes ensuring appropriate seating arrangements for students with physical or sensory needs to maximize their access to instruction and facilitate interaction with peers (UNESCO, 2017).
- **Cultivate an Inclusive Atmosphere:** Proactively educate non-disabled students about disability and the importance of non-discrimination (Lansdown, 2021). Educators must establish a welcoming class tone that actively breaks down stereotypes and prejudices against new classmates (Lansdown, 2021).

5.5.1.2 Transferability of Findings (Geographical Scope)

This study was an exploratory qualitative case study conducted specifically in mainstream primary schools within Relizane Province, making its direct findings context specific. However, the nature of the identified challenges suggests a high degree of applicability to other educational environments (Melton and Limber, 2018).

5.5.1.2.1 Transferability within Algeria

The policy recommendations are broadly relevant across the entire Algerian mainstream primary education system because the central barriers identified are fundamentally systemic and structural:

- **National Structural Gaps:** The widespread lack of both pre-service and in-service professional development, the absence of clear, compulsory policy directives from the Ministry of Education, and the failure to adapt the national curriculum are not phenomena unique to Relizane (Melton and Limber, 2018).
- **Common Infrastructure Deficiencies:** The issues described, such as multi-story school buildings lacking essential accessibility features and outdated facilities, represent common structural problems across older mainstream institutions throughout the country (UNESCO, 2017).
- **Universal Policy Relevance:** Consequently, the recommendations calling for mandatory national training programs, clear legislative guidelines, and targeted funding for accessibility audits and renovations are universally pertinent for all Algerian provinces committed to fully implementing an inclusive education strategy (UN Committee on the Rights of the Child (CRC), 2009).

5.5.1.2.2 Transferability outside of Algeria

The findings offer conceptual transferability to other developing or reforming education systems globally, especially those currently navigating the transition from integration to genuine inclusion (Lansdown, 2011):

- **Conceptual Shift Challenge:** The limited understanding of inclusion among participants, often reducing it to physical presence and social interaction (an integrationist perspective), rather than requiring systemic adaptation, is a common global obstacle for school systems moving from the medical to the social or biopsychosocial model of disability (Lansdown, 2021).
- **Globally Recognized Barriers:** The core obstacles namely, deficiencies in teacher skills/competence, poor physical access, and a lack of professional collaboration are acknowledged as nearly universal impediments to inclusive education, irrespective of the country (UNESCO, 2017).
- **Foundational Principles Apply:** Therefore, the principles embedded in the recommendations such as elevating the teacher's role, whole-school staff collaboration, and governmental investment in accessible environments are applicable as foundational principles for advancing inclusive education policy in any similar low- or middle-income country context (Lansdown, 2011).

5.6 Recommendations for Further Research

The present research has given a brief overview of the experiences and perceptions of general teachers towards the inclusive education in five different primary mainstream schools in Ammi Mossa town in Relizane city. This might imply that not all primary schools in other big cities are having the same problems. Thus, more research is required. A research project can examine teachers' perceptions and experiences towards inclusive education in several mainstream elementary schools across various big cities in order to get a general idea of inclusion policy and then comparing it with the results of this study, which was carried out in an urban setting. Future studies are also required to investigate the perspectives and convictions of policymakers, inspectors, and school administrators in order to identify the challenges they encounter while putting the inclusive education policy into practice.

Additional suggestions concern encouraging the Department of Education to conduct additional research in this field to develop a more comprehensive and in-depth understanding of the barriers and facilitators of inclusive education in the entire country. The present research was carried out in primary schools serving children with physical and sensory disabilities in a particular region of the country. Future studies may concentrate on middle and secondary schools that serve children

with various kinds of disabilities, as well as in different regions of the country. This is significant since investigating the state of schools instructing teenagers with various types of disabilities may lead to diverse results, and enhancing inclusive education in Algeria necessitates data from these schools too.

Further investigation could also look at duplicating this research and performing quantitative analyses to either confirm or disprove that the results of this study can be applied to other regions of Algeria. To be clear, more investigation is required to verify whether the results of this study can be applied elsewhere. This goal can be achieved with a comprehensive, quantitative investigation that include schools from various regions of Algeria. For instance, educators in other Algerian schools and regions could receive a survey questionnaire that was created based on the results of the present research. That type of research would gather crucial data that might assist policymakers in education in identifying ways to enhance inclusive education.

Last but not least, further research is needed to explore the reasons behind the abandonment rate of children with disabilities and what happens to them afterward. Furthermore, it would be fascinating to look into what goes on with children with disabilities who leave school early due to their disabilities or are turned away from education. Future studies will be essential to understand how community members and parents may contribute to the creation of inclusive schools.

5.7 Concluding remarks

The present research has examined the inclusive education system in Algeria. It was especially concerned in general teachers' perceptions and experiences towards the inclusive education of learners with physical and sensory disabilities in the primary mainstream schools in Algeria particularly in Relizane District. This thesis discussed and examined related previous literature in Chapter Two. Following the presentation of the research's methodology in Chapter Three and then reporting and discussing the results in Chapter Four. A list of recommendations was developed based on the research outcomes, which were presented in the current chapter and used to enhance inclusive education in Algeria.

References

- Abhiyan, S.S. (2016) 'Curricular Adaptations for Children with Special Needs', *Confluence*, Vol.18.
- Abongdia, J.-F. (2015) 'Challenges Encountered by Teachers in Identifying Learners with Learning Barriers: Toward Inclusive Education', *International Journal of Educational Sciences*, 08. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.31901/24566322.2015/08.03.07>.
- Acedo, C. (2008) 'Inclusive education: pushing the boundaries', *Prospects*, 38, pp. 5–13. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11125-008-9064-z>.
- Acedo, C., Ferrer, F. and Pàmies, J. (2009) 'Inclusive education: Open debates and the road ahead', *Prospects*, 39(3), pp. 227–238. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11125-009-9129-7>.
- Adams, J., Khan, H.T.A. and Raeside, R. (2014) *Research Methods for Business and Social Science Students*. SAGE Publications (EBL-Schweitzer). Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=ifinAwAAQBAJ>.
- Adebayo, A.S. and Ngwenya, K. (2015) 'Challenges in the Implementation of Inclusive Education at Elulakeni Cluster Primary Schools in Shiselweni District of Swaziland', *European Scientific Journal, ESJ*, 11. Available at: <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:54811052>.
- Adewumi, T.M. *et al.* (2017) 'Adaptation of the curriculum for the inclusion of learners with special education needs in selected primary schools in the Fort Beaufort District', *African Journal of Disability*, 6. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4102/ajod.v6i0.377>.
- Adolfsson, M. *et al.* (2010) 'Exploring changes over time in habilitation professionals' perceptions and applications of the International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health, version for Children and Youth (ICF-CY)', *Journal of rehabilitation medicine : official journal of the UEMS European Board of Physical and Rehabilitation Medicine*, 42, pp. 670–678. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2340/16501977-0586>.
- Ainscow, M. (2000) 'The next step for special education: Supporting the development of inclusive practices', *British Journal of Special Education*, 27(2), pp. 76–80.
- Ainscow, M. (2005) 'Developing inclusive education systems: what are the levers for change?', *Journal of Educational Change*, 6(2), pp. 109–124. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10833-005-1298-4>.
- Ainscow, M. (2020) 'The evolution of policy and practice in inclusive education', in L. Florian and H. Graham (eds.) *The SAGE Handbook of Inclusive Education*. London: SAGE Publications.
- Ainscow, M., Booth, T. and Dyson, A. (2006) *Improving Schools, Developing Inclusion*. Taylor & Francis (Improving Learning). Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=ya-P-p1eNJ4C>.
- Ainscow, M. and Messiou, K. (2018) 'Engaging with the views of students to promote inclusion in education', *Journal of Educational Change*, 19, 19.

- Ainscow, M. and Miles, S. (2008) 'Making Education for All inclusive: where next?', *PROSPECTS*, 38, pp. 15–34. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11125-008-9055-0>.
- Ainscow, M. and Sandill, A. (2010) 'Developing inclusive education systems: the role of organisational cultures and leadership', *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 14(4), pp. 401–416. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603110802504903>.
- AINSCOW, M.E.L. (1995) 'Education for all: Making it happen', *Support for Learning*, 10(4), pp. 147–155. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9604.1995.tb00031.x>.
- Alanazi, M.S. (2012) 'Teachers' and parents' attitudes towards inclusion in inclusive schools in Saudi Arabia', in. Available at: <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:56509813>.
- Alhammad, M. (2017) *The issues of implementing inclusion for students with Learning Difficulties in mainstream primary schools in Saudi Arabia*. the degree of Doctor of Philosophy. University of Lincoln.
- Allan, J. (2007) *Rethinking Inclusive Education: The Philosophers of Difference in Practice*. Springer Netherlands (Inclusive Education: Cross Cultural Perspectives). Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=yOQVGTi3DMoC>.
- Allison, B.N. and Rehm, M.L. (2006) 'Meeting the Needs of Culturally Diverse Learners in Family and Consumer Sciences Middle School Classrooms'.
- Alothman, A. (2014) 'Inclusive education for deaf students in Saudi Arabia : perceptions of schools principals, teachers and parents', in. Available at: <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:74138484>.
- Alzemaia, F.A. (2019) 'An exploration of inclusive education in elementary mainstream schools in Saudi Arabia', in. Available at: <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:213577660>.
- Al-Zyoudi, M. (2006) 'Teachers' attitudes towards inclusive education in Jordanian schools', *International Journal of Special Education*, 21, pp. 55–62.
- Anastasiou, D. and Kauffman, J.M. (2011) 'A social constructionist approach to disability: Implications for special education', *Exceptional Children*, 77(3), pp. 367–384. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/001440291107700307>.
- Anderson, G. and Arsenault, N. (2005) *Fundamentals of Educational Research*. Taylor & Francis (Teachers' Library). Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=cjyRAgAAQBAJ>.
- Andrews, J., Powell, J. and Ayers, L. (2022) 'The Language of Disability Research: A Review of Vocabulary and Conceptual Frameworks', *Disability & Society*, 37(5), pp. 787–806.
- Appert., L. et al. (2018) *Guide to Inclusive Teaching at Columbia*. Columbia.
- Arib, R. (2021) 'Inclusive education and learning English as foreign language in Algeria: Views from faculty members at Abderrahmane Mira university*', *Jordan Journal of Modern Languages and Literatures*, 13(2), pp. 339–353. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.47012/jjml.13.2.9>.

- Arthur., S. *et al.* (2014) 'Designing fieldwork', in J. Ritchie et al. (eds.) *Qualitative Research Practice: A Guide for Social Science Students and Researcher*. SAGE Publications, p. 456 pages.
- Ashman, A. and Elkins, J. (2005) *Educating Children with Special Needs*. Prentice Hall. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=z1PsAAAACAAJ>.
- Avissar, G. (2012) 'Inclusive education in Israel from a curriculum perspective: An exploratory study', *European Journal of Special Needs Education*, 27, pp. 35–49. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/08856257.2011.613602>.
- Avramidis, E. (2001) *Mainstream teachers' attitudes towards the inclusion of children with special educational needs in the ordinary school*. PHD Thesis. University of Exeter.
- Avramidis, E., Bayliss, P. and Burden, R. (2000) 'A Survey into Mainstream Teachers' Attitudes Towards the Inclusion of Children with Special Educational Needs in the Ordinary School in one Local Education Authority', *Educational Psychology*, 20(2), pp. 191–211. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/713663717>.
- Avramidis, E. and Norwich, B. (2002) 'Teachers' attitudes towards integration/inclusion: A review of the literature', *European Journal of Special Needs Education*, pp. 129–147. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/08856250210129056>.
- Azorín, C. and Ainscow, M. (2018) 'Guiding schools on their journey towards inclusion', *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 24(1), pp. 58–76. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603116.2018.1450900>.
- Babbie, R. and Mouton, J. (2001) *The Practice of Social Research*. Oxford University Press. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=vdOgQgAACAAJ>.
- Bandura, A. (1997) *Self-efficacy: The exercise of control*. New York, NY: WH Freeman and Company.
- Barton, L. (1988) *The Politics of Special Educational Needs*. Falmer Press (Disability, handicap, and life chances). Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=wChe9UVIVnYC>.
- Bath, B. *et al.* (2014) 'A biopsychosocial profile of adult Canadians with and without chronic back disorders: a population-based analysis of the 2009-2010 Canadian Community Health Surveys.', *BioMed research international*, 2014, p. 919621. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2014/919621>.
- Bazeley, P. (2013) *Qualitative Data Analysis: Practical Strategies*. SAGE Publications. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=33BEAgAAQBAJ>.
- Beauchamp, T.L. and Childress, J.F. (2013) *Principles of Biomedical Ethics*. OUP USA. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=I9VIMQEACAAJ>.
- Beaudry, J.S. (2016) 'Beyond (Models of) disability?', *Journal of Medicine and Philosophy (United Kingdom)*, 41(2), pp. 210–228. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/jmp/jhv063>.
- Berg, B.L. and Lune, H. (2012) *Qualitative Research Methods for the Social Sciences*. Pearson. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=rFHxkQEACAAJ>.

- Bessai, R. (2018) 'Access to schooling for people with special needs in Algeria', *Sociology International Journal*, 2(5), pp. 371–375. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.15406/sij.2018.02.00071>.
- Bessai, R. (2019) 'The role of associations in the process of inclusive education of children with disabilities', *Journal of studies in language, culture and society*, 1(2), pp. 77–84. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/108002619768.2019.1691993>.
- Beveridge, S. (1999) *Special educational needs in schools, 2nd ed.* London: Routledge. Available at: <http://library.bathspa.ac.uk/items/42410>.
- Bhroin, Ó.N. and King, F. (2020) 'Teacher education for inclusive education: a framework for developing collaboration for the inclusion of students with support plans', *European Journal of Teacher Education*, 43(1), pp. 38–63. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02619768.2019.1691993>.
- Boavida, A.M. and Ponte, J.P. Da (2011) *Investigación colaborativa: potencialidades y problemas.* Available at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/277042351>.
- Boddy, C.R. (2016) 'Sample size for qualitative research', *Qualitative Market Research*, 19(4), pp. 426–432. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/QMR-06-2016-0053>.
- Boitumelo, M., Kuyini, A.B. and Major, T.E. (2020) 'Experiences of General Secondary Education Teachers in Inclusive Classrooms: Implications for Sustaining Inclusive Education in Botswana.', *International Journal of Whole Schooling*, 16(1), pp. 1–34.
- Boneva, D. and Mihova, E. (2012) 'Learning Styles and Learning Preferences', *Dyslang project* [Preprint]. Available at: http://dyscovery.research.southwales.ac.uk/media/files/documents/2014-01-16/Module_8.pdf.
- Booth, T. (2000) *Index for Inclusion: Developing Learning and Participation in Schools.* CSIE. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=xeyQAAAACAAJ>.
- Booth, T. et al. (2002) *Index for Inclusion: Developing Learning and Participation in Schools.* Wide Bay Resource Centre. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=IQ7nAAAACAAJ>.
- Booth, T. (2005) 'Keeping the Future Alive: putting inclusive values into action', *Forum*, 47. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2304/forum.2005.47.2.4>.
- Booth, T. and Ainscow, M. (2011) *Index for Inclusion: Developing Learning and Participation in Schools.* 3rd ed. Bristol: Centre for Studies on Inclusive Education (CSIE).
- Boudersa, N. (2016) 'The Importance of Teachers' Training Programs and Professional Development in the Algerian Educational Context: Toward Informed and Effective Teaching Practices', *ResearchGate*, 01(October).
- Bourke, P.E. (2010) 'Inclusive education reform in Queensland: implications for policy and practice', *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 14(2), pp. 183–193. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603110802504200>.

- Boutebal, S.E. and Yahi, S. (2018) 'Inclusion of the Children with Disabilities among School in Algeria', *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 9(10), pp. 26–31. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.30845/ijbss.v9n10p3>.
- Brannen, J. (2017) *Mixing Methods: Qualitative and Quantitative Research*. Taylor & Francis. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=YSIUdWAAQBAJ>.
- Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2006) 'Qualitative Research in Psychology Using thematic Using thematic analysis in psychology', *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), pp. 77–101. Available at: <http://www.tandfonline.com/action/journalInformation?journalCode=uqrp20%5Cnhttp://www.tandfonline.com/action/journalInformation?journalCode=uqrp20>.
- Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2021) *Thematic analysis: A practical guide*. London: Sage.
- Briggs *et al.* (2002) 'Teacher attitudes and attributes concerning disabilities', *Academic Exchange Quarterly*, 6(2), pp. 85–90.
- Brinkmann, S. and Kvale, S. (2014) *Interviews: Learning the Craft of Qualitative Research Interviewing*. SAGE Publications. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=1DbFwAEACAAJ>.
- British Educational Research Association. (2011) *Ethical guidelines for educational research, BERA (British educational research association)*. London, UK. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.2334-4822.2012.tb00669.x>.
- Brown, R.B. (2006) *Doing Your Dissertation in Business and Management: The Reality of Researching and Writing*. SAGE Publications (SAGE Study Skills Series). Available at: https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=_CGHIO20o6sC.
- Bryman, A. (2016) *Social Research Methods*. Oxford University Press. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=N2zQCgAAQBAJ>.
- Bryman, A. and Bell, E. (2015) *Business Research Methods*. Oxford University Press. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=17u6BwAAQBAJ>.
- Bui, X. *et al.* (2010) 'Inclusive Education Research & Practice', in. Available at: <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:262947328>.
- Burmeister, E. and Aitken, L.M. (2012) 'Sample size: how many is enough?', *Australian critical care: official journal of the Confederation of Australian Critical Care Nurses*, 25(4), pp. 271–274. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aucc.2012.07.002>.
- Bursa, S. and Ersoy, A.F. (2016) 'Social Studies Teachers' Perceptions and Experiences of Social Justice', *Eurasian Journal of Educational Research*, 16(64), pp. 1–35. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.14689/ejer.2016.64.18>.
- Burton, D. and Bartlett, S. (2005) *Practitioner Research for Teachers*. SAGE Publications (1-Off Series). Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=k-6fa655M9YC>.

- Campbell, J., Gilmore, L. and Cuskelly, M. (2003) 'Changing student teachers' attitudes towards disability and inclusion', *Journal of Intellectual and Developmental Disability*, 28(4), pp. 369–379. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13668250310001616407>.
- Campbell, W.N. and Skarakis-Doyle, E. (2007) 'School-aged children with SLI: The ICF as a framework for collaborative service delivery.', *Journal of Communication Disorders*. Campbell, Wenonah N.: Doctoral Program in Rehabilitation Sciences, Elborn College, The University of Western Ontario, London, ON, Canada, N6G 1H1, wcampbe@uwo.ca: Elsevier Science, pp. 513–535. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcomdis.2007.01.001>.
- Carlisle, E., Stanley, L. and Kemple, K.M. (2005) 'Opening doors: Understanding school and family influences on family involvement', *Early Childhood Education Journal*, 33(3), pp. 155–162. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10643-005-0043-1>.
- Carrington, S. and Brownlee, J. (2001) 'Preparing teachers to support inclusion: the benefits of interaction between a group of preservice teachers and a teaching assistant who is disabled', *Teaching Education*, 12(3), pp. 347–357. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/10476210120096597>.
- Carter, S. and Abawi, L.-A. (2018) 'Leadership, Inclusion, and Quality Education for All', *Australasian Journal of Special and Inclusive Education*, 42(01), pp. 49–64. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1017/jsi.2018.5>.
- CAST (2018) *Universal Design for Learning Guidelines version 2.2*. Wakefield, MA.
- Causton-Theoharis, J. (2009) *The Paraprofessional's Handbook for Effective Support in Inclusive Classrooms*. Paul H. Brookes Pub. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=zkpXAAAAYAAJ>.
- Chireshe, R. (2011) 'Special Needs Education In-Service Teacher Trainees' Views on Inclusive Education in Zimbabwe', *Journal of Social Sciences*, 27. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09718923.2011.11892916>.
- Chireshe, R. (2013) 'The State of Inclusive Education in Zimbabwe: Bachelor of Education (Special Needs Education) Students' Perceptions', *Journal of Social Sciences*, 34, pp. 223–228. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09718923.2013.11893133>.
- Chong, S.C.S., Forlin, C. and Lan, A.M. (2007) 'The Influence of an Inclusive Education Course on Attitude Change of Pre-service Secondary Teachers in Hong Kong', *Asia-pacific Journal of Teacher Education - ASIA-PAC J TEACH EDUC*, 35, pp. 161–179. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13598660701268585>.
- Chopra, R. (2008) 'Factors influencing elementary school teachers' attitude towards inclusive education', *British Educational Research Association Annual Conference*, (1995), p. 11. Available at: <http://www.leeds.ac.uk/educol/documents/174842.pdf>.

- Cieza, A. *et al.* (2004) 'Development of ICF Core Sets for patients with chronic conditions', *Journal of Rehabilitation Medicine, Supplement*, (44), pp. 9–11. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/16501960410015353>.
- Clark, C., Dyson, A. and Millward, A. (2018) *Towards Inclusive Schools?* Taylor & Francis (Routledge Library Editions: Special Educational Needs). Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=opBoDwAAQBAJ>.
- Clough, P. and Corbett, J. (2000) *Theories of Inclusive Education A Student's Guide*. sage publications. SAGE Publications.
- Clough, P. and Nutbrown, C. (2012) *A Student's Guide to Methodology*. SAGE Publications (A Student's Guide to Methodology: Justifying Enquiry).
- Cohen, L. and Manion, L. (1994) *Research methods in education*. 4th ed. London: Routledge.
- Cohen, L., Manion, L. and Morrison, K. (2013) *Research Methods in Education*. Taylor & Francis. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=LYzhAQAAQBAJ>.
- Cohen, L., Manion, L. and Morrison, K. (2017) *Research Methods in Education*. 8th ed. Routledge. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=9mYPEAAAQBAJ>.
- Cohen, L., Manion, L. and Morrison, K.R.B. (2011) *Research Methods in Education*. Routledge (Education, Research methods). Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=p7oifuW1A6gC>.
- Cole, E.B. and Flexer, C. (2015) *Children with Hearing Loss: Developing Listening and Talking, Birth to Six, Third Edition*. Plural Publishing, Incorporated. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=kS8qCgAAQBAJ>.
- Committee on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (2018) *Committee on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities reviews the report of Algeria, United Nation*.
- Cooper, P. and Jacobs, B. (2011) 'Evidence of Best Practice Models and Outcomes in the Education of Children with Emotional Disturbance/Behavioural Difficulties: An International Review', pp. 1–226. Available at: <http://hdl.handle.net/10242/46797>.
- Cope, D.G. (2014) 'Methods and meanings: credibility and trustworthiness of qualitative research.', *Oncology nursing forum*. United States, pp. 89–91. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1188/14.ONF.89-91>.
- Corbett, J. (2001) *Supporting Inclusive Education: A Connective Pedagogy*. RoutledgeFalmer (School concerns series). Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=dRJ0tAEACAAJ>.
- Corbett, J. and Slee, R. (2000) 'An International Conversation of Inclusive Education', in F. Armstrong, L. Barton, and D. Armstrong (eds.) *Inclusive Education: Policy, Contexts and Comparatives Perspectives*. David Fulton, pp. 133–146.

- Corbin, J.M. and Strauss, A. (2008) *Basics of Qualitative Research: Techniques and Procedures for Developing Grounded Theory*. 3ed ed. SAGE Publications. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=0TI8Ugvy2Z4C>.
- Cornoldi, C. *et al.* (2018) 'Attitudes of Primary School Teachers in Three Western Countries toward Learning Disabilities.', *Journal of learning disabilities*, 51(1), pp. 43–54. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022219416678408>.
- Creswell, J. w (2013) *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.
- Creswell, J.W. (2012) *Educational Research: Planning, Conducting, and Evaluating Quantitative and Qualitative Research*. Pearson (Educational Research: Planning, Conducting, and Evaluating Quantitative and Qualitative Research). Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=4PywcQAACAAJ>.
- Creswell, J.W. (2014) *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches*. SAGE Publications. Available at: https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=4uB76IC_pOQC.
- Creswell, J.W. (2015) *Educational Research: Planning, Conducting and Evaluating Quantitative and Qualitative Research*. Pearson India Education Services. Available at: https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=9V6_vQEACAAJ.
- Creswell, J.W. and Clark, V.L.P. (2011) *Designing and Conducting Mixed Methods Research*. SAGE Publications. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=6tYNo0UpEqkC>.
- Creswell, J.W. and Poth, C.N. (2017a) *Qualitative Inquiry and Research Design: Choosing Among Five Approaches*. SAGE Publications. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=Pz5RvgAACAAJ>.
- Creswell, J.W. and Poth, C.N. (2017b) *Qualitative Inquiry and Research Design (International Student Edition): Choosing Among Five Approaches*. SAGE Publications. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=UgFIMQAACAAJ>.
- Crotty, M. (1998) *The Foundations of Social Research: Meaning and Perspective in the Research Process*. SAGE Publications. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=fEpOCgAAQBAJ>.
- Crotty, M. (2020) *Foundations of Social Research: Meaning and perspective in the research process*. Taylor & Francis. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=IC74DwAAQBAJ>.
- Dahl, T.H. (2002) 'International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health: An introduction and discussion of its potential impact on rehabilitation services and research', *Journal of Rehabilitation Medicine*, 34(5), pp. 201–204. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/165019702760279170>.
- Daniels, H. (1999) *Special Education Reformed: Inclusion - Beyond Rhetoric?* UK United Kingdom: Routledge.

- Dawson, C. (2007) *A Practical Gde to Research Methods: A User-friendly manual for mastering research techniques and projects*. 3rd editio. Oxford, UK: How To Content.: Little, Brown Book Group Limited.
- Dawson, C. (2009) *Introduction to Research Methods: A practical guide for anyone undertaking a research project*. 4 th. Oxford: How To Books: Little, Brown Book Group. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=6jKfBAAAQBAJ>.
- Dee, A.L. (2010) 'Preservice Teacher Application of Differentiated Instruction', *The Teacher Educator*, 46(1), pp. 53–70. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/08878730.2010.529987>.
- Deiner, P. (2009) *Inclusive Early Childhood Education: Development, Resources, and Practice*. Cengage Learning. Available at: https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=nr9wQx_bv2kC.
- Denscombe, M. (2010) *The good research guide for small-scale social projects*. 4th editio. Berkshire, England: Open University Press.
- Denscombe, M. (2014) *The Good Research Guide: For Small-Scale Social Research Projects*. 5th ed. McGraw-Hill/Open University Press (Open UP study skills). Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=fEeLBgAAQBAJ>.
- Denzin, N.K. (2017) *Qualitative Inquiry Under Fire: Toward a New Paradigm Dialogue*. Taylor & Francis. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=JtZADgAAQBAJ>.
- Denzin, N.K. and Lincoln, Y.S. (2008) *Collecting and Interpreting Qualitative Materials*. Sage Publications (Handbook of qualitative research). Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=ocGxhJEMf0kC>.
- Denzin, N.K. and Lincoln, Y.S. (2011) *The SAGE Handbook of Qualitative Research*. SAGE Publications (Sage Handbook Of). Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=AIRpMHgBYqIC>.
- Department of Education (2001) *Education WHITE PAPER 6: Special Needs Education Building an Inclusive Education and Training System*. Available at: <http://www.education.gov.za/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=gVFccZLi/tI=&tabid=191&mid=484>.
- Dibley, L. (2011) 'Analysing narrative data using McCormack's Lenses', *Nurse researcher*, 18, pp. 13–19. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.7748/nr2011.04.18.3.13.c8458>.
- Djaffer, N.S. (2015) *Plan National d'Action pour les enfants*.
- Doncheva, J., Habeb Al-Obaydi, L. and Abdul Hussein, F.R. (2023) 'A Comprehensive Philosophy of Inclusive Education', *Proceedings of University of Ruse*, 62. Available at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/377395500>.
- Dörnyei, Z. (2007) *Research Methods in Applied Linguistics: Quantitative, Qualitative, and Mixed Methodologies*. OUP Oxford (Oxford Applied Linguistics). Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=R4dNAQAAMAAJ>.

- Dreyer, L. (2017) 'Inclusive Education', in *Education for initial teacher training*. Juta & Company (Pty) Ltd, pp. 383–400.
- Dreyer, L.M. (2008) *an Evaluation of a Learning Support Model in Primary Schools in the West Coast / Winelands Area*. Stellenbosch University.
- Dupoux, E. *et al.* (2006) 'Teachers' attitudes toward students with disabilities in Haïti', *International Journal of Special Education*, 21(3), pp. 1–14.
- Dwyer, S. and Buckle, J. (2009) 'The Space Between: On Being an Insider-Outsider in Qualitative Research', *Int J Qual Meth*, 8. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/160940690900800105>.
- Ebersold, S. and Watkins, A. (2011) 'Mapping the implementation of policy for inclusive education (mipie) _ Agence Européenne', p. 102. Available at: www.european-agency.org.
- Education_and_Skills_Committee (2005) 'Special Educational Needs: Third Report of Session 2005–06', *Office*, I, p. 147. Available at: <http://www.publications.parliament.uk/pa/cm200506/cmselect/cmeduski/478/478i.pdf>.
- Eisenhardt, K.M. and Graebner, M.E. (2007) 'Theory Building from Cases: Opportunities and Challenges', *The Academy of Management Journal*, 50(1), pp. 25–32. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01033590>.
- Enock, R.J. (2011) 'Supporting learners with autism in an early childhood center for learning: a case study in inclusive education', in.
- Epstein, J.L. and Sheldon, S.B. (2022) *School, Family, and Community Partnerships Preparing Educators and Improving Schools*. 3rd Edition. New York: Routledge.
- Eskay, M.E.M. and Oboegbulem, A.I. (2013) 'Learners with Disabilities in an Inclusive Education Setting in Nigeria: Implications for Administrators.', in. Available at: <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:102340820>.
- European Agency for Development in Special Needs Education (2012) *Profile of Inclusive Teachers, European Journal of Special Needs Education*. Edited by A. Watkins. European Agency for Development in Special Needs Education.
- European Agency for Development in Special Needs Education (2020) *Inclusive Education in Europe: A Review of Policy and Practice, EAGLES*.
- European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education. (2018) *European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education Review Report: Teacher Professional Development for Inclusion (TPDI)*. Odense, Denmark.
- Evans, J. and Lunt, I. (2002) 'Inclusive Education: are there limits?', *European Journal of Special Needs Education*, 17, pp. 1–14. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/08856250110098980>.
- Ewing, D.L., Monsen, J.J. and Kielblock, S. (2018) 'Teachers' attitudes towards inclusive education: a critical review of published questionnaires', *Educational Psychology in Practice*, 34(2), pp. 150–165. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02667363.2017.1417822>.

- Le Fanu, G. (2010) 'Promoting Inclusive Education in Papua New Guinea (PNG)', *EdQual Policy Brief, No. 7. University of Bristol, United Kingdom* [Preprint].
- Farrell, M. (2003) *Understanding Special Educational Needs: A Guide for Student Teachers*. Routledge Falmer (Special educational needs). Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=6nV6zatP8CIC>.
- Ferguson, D.L. (2008) 'International trends in inclusive education: the continuing challenge to teach each one and everyone', *European Journal of Special Needs Education*, 23(2), pp. 109–120. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/08856250801946236>.
- Fielding, P.N.G., Fielding, N.G. and Fielding, J.L. (1986) *Linking Data*. SAGE Publications (A Sage university paper). Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=bXkxbvMw3nsC>.
- Fish, J. (1985) 'A Child in the Community', in L. Barton and S. Tomlinson (eds.) *Special Education and Social Interests*. London: Croom Helm.
- Fisher, C.M. and Buglear, J. (2007) *Researching and Writing a Dissertation: A Guidebook for Business Students*. Financial Times Prentice Hall. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=jMEDvwEACAAJ>.
- Fisher, P. and Goodley, D. (2007) 'The linear medical model of disability: Mothers of disabled babies resist with counter-narratives', *Sociology of Health and Illness*, 29(1), pp. 66–81. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9566.2007.00518.x>.
- Flanders, N.A., Fishbein, M. and Ajzen, I. (1975) *Belief, Attitude, Intention, and Behavior: An Introduction to Theory and Research*. Addison-Wesley Publishing Company (Addison-Wesley series in social psychology). Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=8o0QAQAIAAJ>.
- Flick, U. (2007) *Designing Qualitative Research*. SAGE Publications (Online access: SAGE SAGE Research Methods Core). Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=xn5F4nnaRicC>.
- Florian, L. (2008) 'Inclusion: Special or inclusive education: future trends', *British Journal of Special Education*, 35(4), pp. 202–208. Available at: <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8578.2008.00402.x>.
- Florian, L. (2014) 'What counts as evidence of inclusive education?', *European Journal of Special Needs Education*, 29(3), pp. 286–294. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/08856257.2014.933551>.
- Florian, L. (2015) 'Inclusive Pedagogy: A transformative approach to individual differences but can it help reduce educational inequalities?1', *Scottish Educational Review*, 47(1), pp. 5–14.
- Florian, L. (2016) 'Inclusive pedagogy: Moray House School of Education Election Briefing 7: Education from early years to 18: Research and Practice Contributing to Policy'. Moray House School of Education.

- Florian, L. and Pantić, N. (2017) *Teacher Education for the Changing Demographics of Schooling: Issues for Research and Practice*. Springer International Publishing (Inclusive Learning and Educational Equity). Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=9yyIDgAAQBAJ>.
- Flynn, S. (2019) 'Inclusive Education under Article 24 of the CRPD', in D. Nussbaum and P. Schoenmaekers (eds.) *The UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities: A Commentary*. Oxford: Oxford University Press (OUP).
- Foreman, P. and Arthur-Kelly, M. (2017) *Inclusion in Action*. Cengage Learning Australia. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=r3dLDwAAQBAJ>.
- Forlin, C. (2013) *Forlin, C., Chambers, D., Loreman, T., Deppeler, J., & Sharma, U. (2013). Inclusive Education for Students with Disability: A review of the best evidence in relation to theory and practice. Report to the Australian Government Department of Foreign Affairs.*
- Forlin, C. and Loreman, T. (2014) *Measuring Inclusive Education*. Emerald Group Publishing Limited (International Perspectives on Inclusive Education). Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=WFGVCwAAQBAJ>.
- Frederickson, N. and Cline, T. (2002) 'Special educational needs inclusion and diversity: a textbook'.
- Freeman, M. (2011) *Children's Rights Progress and Perspectives*. 2011th ed. Edited by Michael D. A. Freeman. Brill.
- Friend, M. and Cook, L. (2009) *Interactions: Collaboration Skills for School Professionals*.
- Friend, M., and Cook, L. (2017) *Interactions: Collaboration Skills for School Professionals (8th ed.)*. 8th ed. New York, NY: Pearson.
- Fusch, P.I. and Ness, L.R. (2015) 'Are we there yet? Data saturation in qualitative research', *Qualitative Report*, 20(9), pp. 1408–1416. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.46743/2160-3715/2015.2281>.
- Galbin, A. (2014) 'An Introduction to Social Constructionism', *Social Research Reports*, 26, pp. 82–92.
- García, M.R. (2015) 'Reality construction, Communication and daily life – An approach to Thomas Lukmann work', *Intercom: Revista Brasileira de Ciências da Comunicação*, 38(2), pp. 19–38. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1590/1809-5844201522>.
- Garcia-Melgar, A. et al. (2022) 'Collaborative team approaches to supporting inclusion of children with disability in mainstream schools: A co-design study', *Research in Developmental Disabilities*, 126. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ridd.2022.104233>.
- Gargiulo, R. (2012) *Special education in contemporary society: An introduction to exceptionality (4th ed.)*. 4th ed. Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications.
- Garner, P. (2009) *Special Educational Needs: The Key Concepts*. Taylor & Francis (Routledge Key Guides). Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=eaWGAgAAQBAJ>.
- Gatchel, R.J. et al. (2014) 'Interdisciplinary chronic pain management: past, present, and future.', *The American psychologist*, 69(2), pp. 119–130. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0035514>.

- Gatchel, R.J. (2015) 'The Continuing and Growing Epidemic of Chronic Low Back Pain.', *Healthcare (Basel, Switzerland)*, 3(3), pp. 838–845. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare3030838>.
- Germuth, A.A. (2018) 'Professional Development that Changes Teaching and Improves Learning', *Journal of Interdisciplinary Teacher Leadership*, 1(3), pp. 77–90. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.46767/kfp.2016-0025>.
- Ghedjghoudj, S. (2014) 'Teacher In-Service Training and Re-training: The Case of Algeria.', *Studies and Publishing, Nicosia, Cyprus*, pp. 1–16.
- Ghergut, A. and Grasu, M.C. (2012) 'Qualitative analysis about inclusion in Romanian regular schools', *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 33, pp. 55–59. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.01.082>.
- Gillespie *et al.* (2005) *Consuming Crime and Avoiding Punishment: Media Influence in the Shaping of Public Perceptions of Crime and Sentencing*. London, UK: Francis and Taylor Publications.
- Ginsberg, M.B. and Wlodkowski, R.J. (2009) *Diversity and Motivation: Culturally Responsive Teaching in College*. Wiley (CourseSmart Series). Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=DRPyBQAAQBAJ>.
- Gould, J. and Nelson, J. (2005) 'Researchers reflect from the cancer precipice', *Reflective Practice*, 6(2), pp. 277–284. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/14623940500106492>.
- Gray, D.E. (2004) *Doing Research in the Real World*. SAGE Publications. Available at: https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=UW2xw_ud9xMC.
- Gray, D.E. (2018) *Doing Research in the Real World*. SAGE Publications. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=shZMswEACAAJ>.
- Grech, S. *et al.* (2023) 'Preference for person-first versus identity-first language: Informing client-centred care', *Australian Psychologist* [Preprint].
- Grenfell, M. (2009) 'Applying Bourdieu's field theory: the case of social capital and education', *Education, Knowledge and Economy*, 3(1), pp. 17–34. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/17496890902786812>.
- Griffiths, D. M. and Gardner, W.I. (2002) 'The integrated biopsychosocial approach to challenging behaviours.', in & J.S. D. M. Griffiths, C. Stavrakaki (ed.) *Dual diagnosis: An introduction to the mental health needs of persons with developmental disabilities*. Sudbury, ON: Habilitative Mental Health Resource Network., pp. 81–114.
- Guest, G., Bunce, A. and Johnson, L. (2006) 'How Many Interviews Are Enough?: An Experiment with Data Saturation and Variability', *Field Methods*, 18(1), pp. 59–82. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1525822X05279903>.
- Haji, M.H. (2018) 'Perception of Teachers on Physically Impaired Primary School Pupils within Inclusive Education in Tanzania:(A Case Study Zanzibar Island)', *International Journal of Academic and Applied ...*, 2(9), pp. 14–22. Available at: <https://philpapers.org/rec/HAJPOT-2>.

- Hanassab, S. (2006) 'Diversity, international students, and perceived discrimination: Implications for educators and counselors', *Journal of Studies in International Education*, 10(2), pp. 157–172. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1028315305283051>.
- Hanushek, E. and Rivkin, S. (2010) 'Generalizations about Using Value-Added Measures of Teacher Quality', *American Economic Review*, 100, pp. 267–271. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1257/aer.100.2.267>.
- Hardie, E. and Tilly, L. (2012) *An introduction to supporting people with a learning disability*. London: Learning Matters: SAGE Publications (Supporting the Learning Disability Worker LM Series). Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=B5lWzJoSfeQC>.
- Hardmeier, S. and Dell'Ambrogio, M. (2018) *Swiss Education Report*. Switzerland.
- Hart, R.A. (1992) *CHILDREN'S PARTICIPATION: FROM TOKENISM TO CITIZENSHIP*. Florence (Location of the Innocenti Centre).
- Hasnain, R., Shaikh, L.C. and Shanawani, H. (2008) *Disability and the Muslim Perspective: An Introduction for Rehabilitation and Health Care Providers*.
- Hayes, A.M. and Bulat, J. (2017) *Disabilities Inclusive Education Systems and Policies Guide for Low- and Middle-Income Countries*. RTI International 3040 East Cornwallis Road. Available at: <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.3768/rtipress.2017.op.0043.1707>.
- HEBBALI, F.Z. (2020) 'Gifted Education in Algeria: Challenges and Reforms', *International Journal of Linguistics, Literature and Translation (IJLLT)*, 3(11), pp. 55–67. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.32996/ijllt>.
- Hellblom-Thibblin, T., Klang, N. and Åman, K. (2012) 'Biopsychosocial model and the ICF-CY in in-service training: general educators' reflections', *International Journal of Developmental Disabilities*, 58(1), pp. 12–19. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1179/2047387711Y.0000000003>.
- Henn, M., Weinstein, M. and Foard, N. (2009) *A Critical Introduction to Social Research*. SAGE Publications. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=qEQ2b-ip8DMC>.
- (HI) (2016) *Handicap International - Information Fédérale – Fiche pays Algérie – 08/2016 - FR*.
- Hoadjli, A.C. and Latrache, K. (2020) 'Teachers' Attitude towards Inclusive Education: The Case of Algerian Middle School Teachers of English', *English Language Teaching*, 13(10), p. 129. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5539/elt.v13n10p129>.
- Hodge, J.A.H. & S. (2016) 'Disability Discourse: Overview and Critiques of the Medical and Social Models', *Taylor and Francis Online*, DOI: 10.10.
- Hollenweger, J. (2011) 'Development of an ICF-based eligibility procedure for education in Switzerland', *BMC Public Health*, 11(SUPPL. 4). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2458-11-S4-S7>.

- Hollenweger, J. (2013) 'Developing applications of the ICF in education systems: addressing issues of knowledge creation, management and transfer', *Disability and Rehabilitation*, 35(13), pp. 1087–1091. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3109/09638288.2012.740135>.
- Hollenweger, J. (2014) *Definition and Classification of Disability*. New York.
- Holloway, I. and Galvin, K. (2016) *Qualitative Research in Nursing and Healthcare*. Wiley. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=EKu-DAAAQBAJ>.
- Holton, J.A. (2010) 'The Coding Process and Its Challenges', *The SAGE Handbook of Grounded Theory*, (December), pp. 265–289. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781848607941.n13>.
- Hornby, G. (2001) 'Promoting responsible inclusion: Quality education for all.', *British Journal of Special Education*, p. 24.
- Houtenville, A. and Lauer, E. (2017) 'Children's right to participation: challenges and opportunities in the implementation of Article 12 of the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child for children with disabilities', *Journal of Policy and Practice in Intellectual Disabilities*, 14(2), pp. 110–118.
- Hussey, L. et al. (2015) 'Has the fit note reduced general practice sickness certification rates?', *Occupational medicine (Oxford, England)*, 65(3), pp. 182–189. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/occmed/kqu207>.
- ISINGOMA, P. (2014) *OVERCROWDED CLASSROOMS AND LEARNERS' ASSESSMENT IN PRIMARY SCHOOLS IN THE KAMWENGE DISTRICT, UGANDA*. UNIVERSITY OF SOUTH AFRICA.
- Jackson, K. and Bazeley, P. (2019) *Qualitative Data Analysis with NVivo*. SAGE Publications. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=GbZzDwAAQBAJ>.
- Jennett, S. (2008) *Churchill Livingstone's Dictionary of Sport and Exercise Science and Medicine E-Book*. Elsevier Health Sciences. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=KX7QAQAAQBAJ>.
- Jenson, kim (2018) 'Discourses of disability and inclusive education', 5(4), pp. 52–59.
- Johnstone, C. and Chapman, D. (2009) 'Contributions and Constraints to the Implementation of Inclusive Education in Lesotho', *International Journal of Disability Development and Education - INT J DISABIL DEV EDUC*, 56, pp. 131–148. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/10349120902868582>.
- Johnstone, D. (2012) *An Introduction to Disability Studies*. Taylor & Francis. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=UR7fWSpjYcAC>.
- Jordan, A., Schwartz, E. and McGhie-Richmond, D. (2009) 'Preparing teachers for inclusive classrooms', *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 25, pp. 535–542. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2009.02.010>.
- Karalis, T. and Arvanitis, E. (2023) 'Key principles of inclusive education and main challenges of implementing inclusive practice at preschool level in Greece', *Mediterranean Journal of*

- Education*, 3(1)(: 2732-6489), pp. 63–80. Available at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/366740522>.
- Kattari, S.K., Lavery, A. and Hasche, L. (2017) ‘Applying a social model of disability across the life span’, *Journal of Human Behavior in the Social Environment*, 27(8), pp. 865–880. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/10911359.2017.1344175>.
- Katz, R. (2015) ‘United States: UNITED STATES’, *European Journal of Political Research Political Data Yearbook*, 54(1), pp. 309–315. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/2047-8852.12112>.
- Kaur, N. (2013) ‘Curriculum Adaptation for the Learning Disabled’, *International Educational E-Journal*, (Ii), pp. 26–31.
- Kearney, A. and Kane, R. (2006) ‘Inclusive education policy in New Zealand: reality or ruse?’, *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 10(2–3), pp. 201–219. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603110500256145>.
- Klein, S. (2012) *Action Research Methods: Plain and Simple*. Palgrave Macmillan US. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=kZlmaQAAQBAJ>.
- Koay, T.L. *et al.* (2006) ‘LEARNING ASSISTANCE AND REGULAR TEACHERS’ PERCEPTIONS OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION IN BRUNEI DARUSSALAM’, *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SPECIAL EDUCATION*, 21(1), pp. 131–142.
- Koster, M. *et al.* (2009) ‘Being part of the peer group: a literature study focusing on the social dimension of inclusion in education’, *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 13(2), pp. 117–140. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603110701284680>.
- Kubat, U. (2018) ‘Identifying the individual differences among students during learning and teaching process by science teachers’, *International Journal of Research in Education and Science*, 4(1), pp. 30–38. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.21890/ijres.369746>.
- Kumar, R. (2011) *Research Methodology: A Step-by-step Guide for Beginners*. SAGE. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=cfpHNAEACAAJ>.
- Ladd, P. (2017) *Understanding Deaf Culture: In Search of Deafhood*. 2nd ed. Bristol: Multilingual Matters.
- Lambrechts, W. (2014) ‘Benefits for Schools and Communities to Collaborate’, in *Travelling Guide for School-Community Collaboration for Sustainable Development*, pp. 31–35.
- Landsberg, E., Krüger, D. and Nel, N. (2005) *Addressing Barriers to Learning: A South African Perspective*. Van Schaik. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=m-ieAAAAMAAJ>.
- Langer, G. (2018) ‘Probability versus Non-Probability Methods’, in D.L. Vannette and Jon A. Krosnick (eds.) *The Palgrave Handbook of Survey Research*. Palgrave Macmillan, pp. 351–362. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-54395-6>.
- Lansdown, G. (2011) *Every child’s right to be heard: a resource guide on the right of the child to express views and have them taken seriously*. London.

- Lansdown, G. (2021) 'The Challenge of Implementing Article 12 of the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child: Due Weight, Age and Maturity', in *Rethinking Children's Rights*. Springer, pp. 147–164.
- Larkin, P.J., de Casterlé, B.D. and Schotsmans, P. (2007) 'Multilingual translation issues in qualitative research: Reflections on a metaphorical process', *Qualitative Health Research*, 17(4), pp. 468–476. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1049732307299258>.
- Leech, N.L. and Onwuegbuzie, A.J. (2011) 'Beyond Constant Comparison Qualitative Data Analysis: Using NVivo', *School Psychology Quarterly*, 26(1), pp. 70–84. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0022711>.
- de Leeuw, R.R. *et al.* (2018) 'Teacher strategies to support the social participation of students with SEBD in the regular classroom', *European Journal of Special Needs Education*, 33(3), pp. 412–426. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/08856257.2017.1334433>.
- Lewis, R.B. and Doorlag, D.H. (1995) *Teaching special students in the mainstream*. 4th ed. C.E. Merrill. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=vHruAAAAMAAJ>.
- Liamputtong, P. (2016) 'The Science of Words and the Science of Numbers', *Research Methods in Health*, pp. 3–28.
- Liliane Foundation (2017) *Enabling Education Steps Towards Global Disability-Inclusive Education, Hertogenbosch, The Netherlands: LilianeFonds*. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1057/9781137453020.0010>.
- Lundy, L. (2007) "'Voice" is not enough: Conceptualising Article 12 of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child', *British Educational Research Journal - BR EDUC RES J*, 33, pp. 927–942. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/01411920701657033>.
- Lune, H. and Berg, B.L. (2016) *Qualitative Research Methods for the Social Sciences*. 9th ed. Pearson Education. Available at: https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=W_vEDAAAQBAJ.
- M. Selb, R. Escorpizo, N. Kostanjsek, G. Stucki, B. Üstun, A.C. (2015) 'A guide on how to develop an International Classification of', *European Journal of Physical and Rehabilitation Medicine*, 51(3), pp. 105–17.
- Makoelle, T.M. (2020) 'Language, Terminology, and Inclusive Education: A Case of Kazakhstani Transition to Inclusion', *SAGE Open*, 10(1). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244020902089>.
- Mangope, B. *et al.* (2018) 'From Mainstreaming to Inclusion-have shifts in paradigms improved the practice of special education in Botswana', *Mosenodi Journal*, 21 (1)(1021–559X), pp. 16–27. Available at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/326803417>.
- Mara, D. and Mara, E. (2012) 'Curriculum Adaption in Inclusive Education', *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 46, pp. 4004–4009. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.06.187>.

- Marczyk, G.R., DeMatteo, D. and Festinger, D. (2005) *Essentials of Research Design and Methodology*. Wiley (Essentials of Behavioral Science). Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=eVXywAEACAAJ>.
- Marshall, B. *et al.* (2013) 'Does Sample Size Matter in Qualitative Research?: A Review of Qualitative Interviews in is Research', *Journal of Computer Information Systems*, 54(1), pp. 11–22. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/08874417.2013.11645667>.
- Marshall, C. and Rossman, G.B. (2014) *Designing Qualitative Research*. SAGE Publications. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=qTByBgAAQBAJ>.
- Marvasti, A. (2004) *Qualitative Research in Sociology*. SAGE Publications (Introducing Qualitative Methods series). Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=QdiiqmOfi6UC>.
- Massoumeh, Z. and Jamshidi, L. (2012) 'An Investigation of Medical Model and Special Education Methods', *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 46, pp. 5802–5804. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.06.518>.
- Materechera, E.K. (2014) 'Challenges in the Implementation of Inclusive Education', in M.W. Legotlo (ed.) *Challenges and Issues facing the Education System in South Africa*. Pretoria: Africa Institute of South Africa.
- Mather, N., and Goldstein, S. (2015) *Learning disabilities and challenging behaviors: A guide to intervention and program management (4th ed.)*. 4th ed. Baltimore, MD: Brookes Publishing Company.
- Matthews, N.L. (2009) 'Teaching the "invisible" disabled students in the classroom: disclosure, inclusion and the social model of disability', *Teaching in Higher Education*, 14, pp. 229–239. Available at: <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:53121897>.
- Maxwell, G. and Koutsogeorgou, E. (2012) 'Using social capital to construct a conceptual International Classification of Functioning, Disability, and Health Children and Youth version-based framework for stronger inclusive education policies in Europe.', *American journal of physical medicine & rehabilitation*, 91(13 Suppl 1), pp. S118-23. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1097/PHM.0b013e31823d4b92>.
- Maxwell, J.A. (2012) *Qualitative Research Design: An Interactive Approach*. SAGE Publications (Applied Social Research Methods). Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=LedyAwAAQBAJ>.
- McFadyen, J. and Rankin, J. (2016) 'The Role of Gatekeepers in Research: Learning from Reflexivity and Reflection', *GSTF Journal of Nursing and Health Care (JNHC)*, 4(1), pp. 82–88. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5176/2345-718X>.
- McMahon, S.D. *et al.* (2016) 'School Inclusion: A Multidimensional Framework and Links with Outcomes AMONG Urban Youth with Disabilities', *Journal of Community Psychology*, 44(5), pp. 656–673. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/jcop.21793>.

- Melton, G.B. and Limber, S.P. (2018) 'The legal implementation of the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child: why is it important to children and their families?', *International Journal of Law, Policy and the Family*, 32(1), pp. 83–101.
- Merriam, S.B. (1988) *Case study research in education: A qualitative approach*. San Francisco, CA, US: Jossey-Bass.
- Merriam, S.B. (2009) *Qualitative Research: A Guide to Design and Implementation*. Jossey-Bass. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=V-1gswEACAAJ>.
- Mertens, D.M. (2014) *Research and Evaluation in Education and Psychology: Integrating Diversity with Quantitative, Qualitative, and Mixed Methods*. SAGE Publications. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=VEkXBAAAQBAJ>.
- Miles, M.B. and Huberman, A.M. (1994) *Qualitative Data Analysis: An Expanded Sourcebook*. SAGE Publications. Available at: https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=U4IU_-wJ5QEC.
- Miles, M.B., Huberman, A.M. and Saldana, J. (2013) *Qualitative Data Analysis: A Methods Sourcebook*. SAGE Publications. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=p0wXBAAAQBAJ>.
- Milteniene, L. and Venclovaite, I. (2012) 'Teacher collaboration in the context of inclusive education', *Specialusis Ugdymas*, 27, pp. 99–123.
- Ministry of Education, F.D.R. of E. (2012) *Education statistics annual abstract*. Addis Ababa.
- Mishra, P.A., Hota, S. and Khamari, P.R. (2019) 'Curriculum adaptation in inclusive education', *International Journal of Applied Research*, 5(8), pp. 70–74.
- Mitchell, D. (2010) *Education that fits : Review of international trends in the education of students with special educational needs*, College Of Education University Of Canterbury.
- Mitchell, D. (2017) *What really works in special and inclusive education: The best evidence-based strategies for Australian, New Zealand, and international teachers (3rd ed.)*. 3rd ed. London, UK: Routledge.
- Mitchell, D. and Sutherland, D. (2020) *What Really Works in Special and Inclusive Education Using Evidence-based Teaching Strategies*.
- Mittler, P. (2012) *Working Towards Inclusive Education: Social Contexts*. David Fulton. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=E5yZNmmGQRYC>.
- Mngo, Z.Y. and Mngo, A.Y. (2018) 'Teachers' Perceptions of Inclusion in a Pilot Inclusive Education Program: Implications for Instructional Leadership', *Education Research International*. Edited by G.-J. Hwang, 2018, p. 3524879. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2018/3524879>.
- Molosiwa, S.M. and Monyatsi, P.P. (2017) 'Assessment for Inclusion', in J. Condy and N. Phasha (eds.) *Inclusive Education An African Perspective*. 2nd edition. Oxford University Press Southern Africa (Pty) Limited.

- Moroszlay, S. (1994) 'Low vision rehabilitation program', *Patient Education and Counseling*, 23, pp. S129–S130. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0738-3991\(94\)90433-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0738-3991(94)90433-2).
- Moss, J. (2002) 'Inclusive schooling: Representation and textual practice', *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 6(3), pp. 231–249. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603110110091599>.
- Mubaraq, Z. *et al.* (2021) 'Model Of Disability Learning in Islamic Education at Inclusive School Malang, Indonesia', *Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education (TURCOMAT)*, 12(3), pp. 5388–5392. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.17762/turcomat.v12i3.2184>.
- Murawski, W. and Swanson, H. (2001) 'A meta-analysis of co-teaching research: Where are the data?', *Remedial and Special Education*, 22(5), pp. 258–267.
- Murphy, E. *et al.* (1998) 'Qualitative research methods in health technology assessment: A review of the literature', *Health Technology Assessment*, 2(16). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3310/hta2160>.
- Naderifar, M., Goli, H. and Ghaljaie, F. (2017) 'Snowball Sampling: A Purposeful Method of Sampling in Qualitative Research', *Strides in Development of Medical Education*, 14(3). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5812/sdme.67670>.
- Namkung, J. and Peng, P. (2018) 'Learning Disabilities', *The SAGE Encyclopedia of Educational Research, Measurement, and Evaluation*, pp. 954–956. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781506326139.n385>.
- Nancy R. Mudrick, P.S.U., Mary Lou Breslin, M.D.R.E.& D.F. (DREDF) and Donna H. Odierna, D.M.L.C.C.W. (2025) "Expensive, frustrating, demoralizing": Wheelchair users' recent device purchase experiences.
- Naraian, S. and Schlessinger, S. (2017) 'When Theory Meets the "Reality of Reality": Reviewing the Sufficiency of the Social Model of Disability as a Foundation for Teacher Preparation for Inclusive Education', *Teacher Education Quarterly*, 44(1), p. 81.
- Neelankavil, J.P. (2015) *International Business Research*. Taylor & Francis. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=2mGmBgAAQBAJ>.
- Newby, P. (2010) *Research Methods for Education*. Pearson Ed. london. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=3RUAYjH7wUoC>.
- Newby, P. (2013) *Research Methods for Education*. Taylor & Francis. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=20EYAgAAQBAJ>.
- Newton, N., Cambridge, J. and Hunter-Johnson, Y. (2014) 'Teachers' perceptions of inclusive education and its implication for adult education in the Bahamas', *Adult Education Research Conference* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://newprairiepress.org/aerc/2014/papers/56>.
- Nguyet, D.T. and Ha, L.T. (2010) *Preparing Teachers for Inclusive Education*, Catholic Relief Services. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-13-1179-6_39-1.

- NICHCY (2012) 'Visual impairments, including blindness', *National Dissemination Center for Children with Disabilities*, 0285(13), pp. 1–8. Available at: <http://nichcy.org/wp-content/uploads/docs/fs13.pdf>.
- Nilholm, C. (2006) 'Special education, inclusion and democracy', *European Journal of Special Needs Education*, 21(4), pp. 431–445. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/08856250600957905>.
- Nind, M. and Swann, C. (2019) 'Using Innovative Methods in Research with Children and Young People with Complex Needs', *Qualitative Research Journal*, 19(2), pp. 172–184.
- Nishan, F. and Darussalam, U. (2018) 'Challenges of Regular Teachers in Implementing Inclusive Education in Schools of Maldives', pp. 88–102.
- Njie, B. and Asimiran, S. (2014) 'Case Study as a Choice in Qualitative Methodology', *IOSR Journal of Research & Method in Education (IOSRJRME)*, 4(3), pp. 35–40. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.9790/7388-04313540>.
- Norwich, B. (2008) 'Dilemmas of difference, inclusion and disability: international perspectives on placement', *European Journal of Special Needs Education*, 23(4), pp. 287–304. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/08856250802387166>.
- Ntombela, S. (2009) 'Are We There Yet? Towards the Development of Inclusive Education in One District in KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa', *International Journal of Learning*, 16, pp. 113–122. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.18848/1447-9494/CGP/v16i07/46406>.
- Nucci, K. (2019) *Adapting Curriculum for All Students: How Teachers Can Be Better Prepared for the Inclusive Classroom*. University San Marcos.
- Nutbrown, C. and Clough, P. (2006) 'Inclusion in the Early Years: Critical Analyses and Enabling Narratives'. London. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781446212271>.
- Nwoko, J.C. *et al.* (2023) 'A Systematic Review of the Factors That Influence Teachers' Occupational Wellbeing', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/10.3390/ijerph20126070>.
- Nyatuka, B.O. (2017) 'A survey of school-family-community partnerships in Kenya', *Journal of Professional Capital and Community*, 2(4), pp. 229–243. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/JPCC-04-2017-0010>.
- O'Brien, T. (2001) *Enabling Inclusion: Blue Skies ... Dark Clouds?* Stationery Office (Professional Excellence in Schools Series). Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=-MknAAAACAAJ>.
- OECD (2019) *Future of Education and Skills 2030*. France, OECD Publishing. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=Xg6hULLiz9sC>.
- O'Leary, Z. (2017) *The Essential Guide to Doing Your Research Project*. SAGE Publications. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=F2ECDgAAQBAJ>.

- Oliver, M. (2009) *Understanding Disability: From Theory to Practice*. Macmillan Education UK. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=EztGEAAAQBAJ>.
- Oliver, M. and Barnes, C. (2012) *The New Politics of Disablement*. Macmillan Education UK. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=YUxGEAAAQBAJ>.
- Olsson, S., Dag, M. and Kullberg, C. (2017) 'Deaf and hard-of-hearing adolescents' experiences of inclusion and exclusion in mainstream and special schools in Sweden', *European Journal of Special Needs Education*, pp. 1–15. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/08856257.2017.1361656>.
- Olsson, S., Dag, M. and Kullberg, C. (2018) 'Deaf and hard-of-hearing adolescents' experiences of inclusion and exclusion in mainstream and special schools in Sweden', *European Journal of Special Needs Education*, 33(4), pp. 495–509. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/08856257.2017.1361656>.
- Oppenheim, A.N. (1992) *Questionnaire Design, Interviewing and Attitude Measurement*.
- Othman, H.H. (2015) *Teachers' Attitudes Towards the Provision of Inclusive Education in Primary Schools in Chake Chake District Zanzibar*.
- Owens, J. (2015) 'Exploring the critiques of the social model of disability: The transformative possibility of Arendt's notion of power', *Sociology of Health and Illness*, 37(3), pp. 385–403. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9566.12199>.
- Paju, B. et al. (2022) 'Collaboration for Inclusive Practices: Teaching Staff Perspectives from Finland', *Scandinavian Journal of Educational Research*, 66(3), pp. 427–440. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00313831.2020.1869087>.
- Palinkas, L.A. et al. (2015) 'Purposeful Sampling for Qualitative Data Collection and Analysis in Mixed Method Implementation Research', *Administration and Policy in Mental Health and Mental Health Services Research*, 42(5), pp. 533–544. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10488-013-0528-y>.
- Patton, M.Q. (2002a) *Qualitative Evaluation and Research Methods*. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=IImbmgEACAAJ>.
- Patton, M.Q. (2002b) *Qualitative Research & Evaluation Methods*. SAGE Publications. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=FjBw2oi8E14C>.
- Penney, J. (2013) 'The Biopsychosocial model: Redefining osteopathic philosophy?', *International Journal of Osteopathic Medicine*, 16, pp. 33–37. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijosm.2012.12.002>.
- Pérez-Jorge, D. et al. (2021) 'Perception and attitude of teachers towards the inclusion of students with hearing disabilities', *Education Sciences*, 11(4). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci11040187>.

- Perri, G. and Bellamy, C. (2012) *Principles of Methodology: Research Design in Social Science*. SAGE. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=alNrjwEACAAJ>.
- Petasis, A. (2019) 'Discrepancies of the Medical, Social and Biopsychosocial Models of Disability: A Comprehensive Theoretical Framework', *The International Journal of Business Management and Technology*, 3(4), pp. 42–54.
- Phasha, N. and Moichela, K.Z. (2011) 'Inclusive Education in South Africa', in A.B. Nsamenang and T.M.S. Tchombe (eds.) *Handbook of African Educational Theories and Practices A Generative Teacher Education Curriculum*. Cameroon: Human Development Resource Centre (HDRC).
- Pivik, J., McComas, J. and Laflamme, M. (2002) 'Barriers and Facilitators to Inclusive Education', *Exceptional Children*, 69(1), pp. 97–107. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/001440290206900107>.
- De Polo, G. et al. (2009) 'Children with disability at school: The application of ICF-CY in the Veneto region', *Disability and Rehabilitation*, 31(SUPPL. 1). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3109/09638280903317880>.
- Powell, D., Hyde, M. and Punch, R. (2014) 'Inclusion in postsecondary institutions with small numbers of deaf and hard-of-hearing students: Highlights and challenges', *Journal of Deaf Studies and Deaf Education*, 19(1), pp. 126–140. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/deafed/ent035>.
- Punch, K.F. (2009) *Introduction to Research Methods in Education*. SAGE Publications. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=IBvMqiaN5EgC>.
- Punch, R., Hyde, M. and Creed, P. (2004) 'Issues in the School-to-Work Transition of Hard of Hearing Adolescents', *American annals of the deaf*, 149, pp. 28–38. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1353/aad.2004.0015>.
- Purdie, N. and Ellis, L. (2005) 'A Review of the Empirical Evidence Identifying Effective Interventions and Teaching Practices for Students with Learning Difficulties in Years 4, 5 and 6. Literature Review.', *Australian Council for Educational Research [Preprint]*, (February).
- Qian Tang (2017) *A guide for ensuring inclusion and equity in education, A guide for ensuring inclusion and equity in education*. Available at: <https://doi.org/ED-2009/WS/31>.
- Radnor, H.A. (2001) *Researching Your Professional Practice: Doing Interpretive Research*. Open University Press (Doing qualitative research in educational settings). Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=60PgtAEACAAJ>.
- Rapp, R. (2018) 'Language, disability, and the creation of systemic barriers', *Disability Studies Quarterly*, 38(4).
- Rapp, W. (2017) *Universal Design for Learning: A practical guide for teachers*. New York, NY: WW Norton & Company.
- Ras, S. (2008) *Inclusive Education: An overview of international experiences and approaches.*, AR Veenendaal, The Netherlands.

- Rees, K. (2017) 'Models of disability and the categorisation of children with severe and profound learning difficulties: Informing educational approaches based on an understanding of individual needs', *Educational and Child Psychology*, 34(December 2017).
- Reisinger, L. (2014) 'Using a Bio-Psycho-Social Approach for Students with Severe Challenging Behaviours', *Learning Landscapes*, 7(2), pp. 259–270. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.36510/learnland.v7i2.664>.
- Rieser, R. (2012) *Implementing Inclusive Education A Commonwealth Guide to Implementing Article 24 of the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities*.
- Robson, C. (2002) *Real World Research: A Resource for Social Scientists and Practitioner-Researchers*. Wiley (Regional Surveys of the World Series). Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=DkplMcAysFQC>.
- Robson, C. (2011) *Real World Research*. Wiley. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=fbHIRwAACAAJ>.
- Robson, C. and McCartan, K. (2016) *REAL WORLD RESEARCH A Resource for Users of Social Research Methods in Applied Settings*. London: Copyright © 2016 John Wiley & Sons Ltd.
- Rodriguez, C.C. and Garro-Gil, N. (2015) 'Inclusion and Integration on Special Education', *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 191, pp. 1323–1327. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.04.488>.
- Rohwerder, B. (2018) 'Disability in North Africa', (April). Available at: <http://www.gsdrc.org/publications/disability->.
- Roth, W.M. and Jornet, A. (2014) 'Toward a Theory of Experience', *Science Education*, 98(1), pp. 106–126. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/sce.21085>.
- Rouse, M. (2008) 'Developing Inclusive Practice: A Role for Teachers and Teacher Education?', *Education in the North*, 16(1), pp. 6–13.
- Ruane, J.M. (2005) *Essentials of Research Methods: A Guide to Social Science Research*. Wiley. Available at: https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=Hk2tF3TH_NUC.
- Rubin, H.J. and Rubin, I.S. (2012) *Qualitative Interviewing: The Art of Hearing Data*. 3rd ed. SAGE Publications. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=T5RDmYuueJAC>.
- Rutledge, P. and Hogg, J.L. (2020) 'In-Depth Interviews', *Author Draft for International Encyclopedia of Media Psychology*, pp. 1–7. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119011071.iemp0019>.
- Ryan, G.W. and Bernard, H.R. (2003) 'Techniques to Identify Themes', *Field Methods*, 15(1), pp. 85–109. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1525822X02239569>.
- Ryan, J. (2007) 'Inclusive Leadership: A Review', *Journal of Educational Administration and Foundation*, 18(2), 92-, pp. 2013–2015.

- Safdar, S. and Rashid, S. (2021) 'Preparation of Pre-Service Teachers for Inclusive Classroom: Challenges and Prospects', *Challenges and Prospects*, 20(4), pp. 2785–2792. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.17051/ilkonline.2021.04.317>.
- Sahli, N. and Benaiss, F.B. (2019) 'Education For All: Promoting Inclusive Pedagogy through Moocs to Advance Research Skills', *Journal of Studies in Language, Culture and Society*, 1(2), pp. 104–114.
- Saidani, A. and Khecheni, K. (2017) *Overview of the higher education system: Algeria*. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264292048-7-en>.
- Saldana, J. (2015) *The Coding Manual for Qualitative Researchers*. 3rd ed. SAGE Publications. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=cDBPrgEACAAJ>.
- Saldaña, J. (2016) *The Coding Manual for Qualitative Researchers*. 3rd edn. London: Sage.
- Salend, S.J. (2001) *Creating Inclusive Classrooms: Effective and Reflective Practices*. Merrill. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=5GacbwAACAAJ>.
- Salend, S.J. (2008) *Creating Inclusive Classrooms: Effective and Reflective Practices*. Pearson/Merrill Prentice Hall (Alternative eText Formats Series). Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=r81KAAAAYAAJ>.
- Sanches-Ferreira, M. *et al.* (2013) 'Portugal's special education law: implementing the International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health in policy and practice', *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 19(5), pp. 457–468. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603116.2014.940067>.
- Sanches-Ferreira, M., Silveira-Maia, M. and Alves, S. (2014) 'The use of the International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health, version for Children and Youth (ICF-CY), in Portuguese special education assessment and eligibility procedures: The professionals' perceptions', *European Journal of Special Needs Education*, 29(3), pp. 327–343. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/08856257.2014.908025>.
- Santangelo, T., and Tomlinson, C. (2012) 'Using differentiation and Universal Design for Learning to instruct students with learning disabilities: What are new teachers prepared to do?', *Action in Teacher Education*, 34(3), pp. 244–258.
- Saunders, M., Lewis, P. and Thornhill, A. (2009) *Research Methods for Business Students*. Prentice Hall (Always learning). Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=u-txtfaCFiEC>.
- Saunders, M.N.K. (2006) *Gatekeeper, Sage Dictionary of Social Research Methods*. Available at: <http://srmo.sagepub.com/view/the-sage-dictionary-of-social-research-methods/n85.xml> (Accessed: 20 January 2011).
- Savage, R.S. and Erten, O. (2015) 'Teaching in Inclusive Classrooms: The Link Between Teachers' Attitudes- Practices and Student Outcomes', *Journal of Psychology & Psychotherapy*, 05(06). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4172/2161-0487.1000219>.

- Schreiber, J.B. and Asner-Self, K. (2010) *Educational Research*. Wiley. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=XK5mPgAACAAJ>.
- Schuelka, M.J. (2018) *Implementing inclusive education*.
- Sebba, J. and Ainscow, M. (1996) 'International Developments in Inclusive Schooling: mapping the issues', *Cambridge Journal of Education*, 26, pp. 5–18. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/0305764960260101>.
- Segen, J.C. (2006) *Concise Dictionary of Modern Medicine*. McGraw-Hill. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=vVNqAAAAMAAJ>.
- Seidman, I. (2019) *Interviewing as Qualitative Research: A Guide for Researchers in Education and the Social Sciences*. Teachers College Press. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=OkmeDwAAQBAJ>.
- Shadreck, M. (2012) 'Bachelor of Education in Service Teacher Trainees' Perceptions and Attitudes on Inclusive Education in Zimbabwe', *Asian Social Science*, 8, pp. 227–232. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5539/ass.v8n13p227>.
- Shakespeare, T. (2013) *Disability Rights and Wrongs Revisited*. Taylor & Francis. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=PTbhAQAAQBAJ>.
- Shakespeare, T., Watson, N. and Alghaib, O.A. (2016) 'Blaming the victim, all over again: Waddell and Aylward's biopsychosocial (BPS) model of disability', *Critical Social Policy*, 37(1), pp. 22–41. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0261018316649120>.
- Shapiro, J.P. (2011) *No Pity: People with Disabilities Forging a New Civil Rights Movement*. New York: Basic Books.
- Shyman, E. (2016) 'The Reinforcement of Ableism: Normality, the Medical Model of Disability, and Humanism in Applied Behaviour Analysis and ASD', *Intellectual and Developmental Disabilities*, 54, pp. 366–376. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1352/1934-9556-54.5.366>.
- Siebers, T. (2008) *Disability Theory*. University of Michigan Press (Corporealities: Discourses Of Disability). Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=o2rBfRuwFukC>.
- Silverman, D. (2016) *Qualitative Research*. SAGE Publications. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=TrwtDAAAQBAJ>.
- Simeonsson, R.J. *et al.* (2006) 'ICF-CY: a universal tool for practice policy and research', *Meeting of Who Collaborating Centres for the Family of International Classifications*, p. P107.
- Simeonsson, R.J. (2009) 'ICF-CY: A universal tool for documentation of disability', *Journal of Policy and Practice in Intellectual Disabilities*, 6(2), pp. 70–72. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1741-1130.2009.00215.x>.
- Singal, N. (2005) 'Mapping the field of inclusive education: a review of the Indian literature', *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 9(4), pp. 331–350. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603110500138277>.

- Singal, N. (2008) 'Working towards inclusion: Reflections from the classroom', *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 24, pp. 1516–1529. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2008.01.008>.
- Smith, D.D. and Tyler, N.C. (2011) 'Effective inclusive education: Equipping education professionals with necessary skills and knowledge', *PROSPECTS*, 41, pp. 323–339. Available at: <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:143504102>.
- Specht, J., *et al.* (2016) 'Teaching in inclusive classrooms: Efficacy and beliefs of Canadian preservice teachers', *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 20(10), pp. 1100–1113. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603116.2016.1145218>.
- Special Education Guide (2020) *Hearing Impairments*, © 2013-2020 Special Education Guide. All Rights Reserved. Available at: <https://www.specialeducationguide.com/disability-profiles/hearing-impairments/>.
- Spratt, J. and Florian, L. (2013) 'Applying the principles of inclusive pedagogy in initial teacher education: from university based course to classroom action', *Revista de Investigación en Educación*, 11(3), pp. 133–140. Available at: <http://webs.uvigo.es/reined/>.
- Srivastava, M., de Boer, A., and Pijl, S. (2017) 'Inclusive education in developing countries: a scoping review', *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 21(9), pp. 981–994.
- Stake, R.E. (2005) 'Qualitative case studies', in N.K. Denzin and Y.S. Lincoln (eds.) *The Sage handbook of qualitative research*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Stake, R.E. (2013) *Multiple Case Study Analysis*. Guilford Publications. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=rQWT5aDHiZYC>.
- Stewart, T.T. and Jansky, T.A. (2022) 'Novice teachers and embracing struggle: Dialogue and reflection in professional development', *Teaching and Teacher Education: Leadership and Professional Development*, 1, p. 100002. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tatelp.2022.100002>.
- Stofile, S.Y. (2008) 'Factors Affecting the Implementation of Inclusive Education Policy: A Case Study in one Province in South Africa', *A thesis submitted in fulfilment of the requirement for a Doctorate in Philosophy in the Faculty of Education, University of the Western Cape* [Preprint], (November).
- Suleymanov, E. (2015) 'The Implementation of Inclusive Education: Teacher's Readiness and Barriers', *European Journal of Education*, 4(2), pp. 150–162.
- Tabane, R.J. (2009) *Integration and learners' feelings of belonging in a desegregated former House of Delegates school*. Phd. University of Pretoria, South Africa.
- Takala, M. and Sume, H. (2018) 'Hearing-impaired pupils in mainstream education in Finland: teachers' experiences of inclusion and support', *European Journal of Special Needs Education*, 33(1), pp. 134–147. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/08856257.2017.1306965>.
- Tansey, O. (2007) 'Process Tracing and Elite Interviewing: A Case for Non-probability Sampling', *PS: Political Science and Politics*, 40(4), p. 24.

- Tayeg, A. (2015) *Effects of Overcrowded Classrooms on Teacher-Student Interactions Case Study EFL Students at Biskra University*. Mohamed Kheider University of Biskra.
- Taylor, S.J. (2004) 'Caught in the continuum: A critical analysis of the principle of the least restrictive environment', *Research and Practice for Persons with Severe Disabilities*, 29(4), pp. 218–230. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2511/rpsd.29.4.218>.
- Taylor, S.J., Bogdan, R. and DeVault, M.L. (2016) *Introduction to qualitative research methods: A guidebook and resource*. 4th ed, *Acta Universitatis Agriculturae et Silviculturae Mendelianae Brunensis*. 4th ed. USA: Hoboken, NJ: John Wiley & Sons. Available at: <http://publications.lib.chalmers.se/records/fulltext/245180/245180.pdf><https://hdl.handle.net/20.500.12380/245180><http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jsames.2011.03.003><https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gr.2017.08.001><http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.precamres.2014.12>.
- Terzi, L. (2004) 'The Social Model of Disability: A Philosophical Critique', *Journal of Applied Philosophy*, 21(2), pp. 141–157. Available at: <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0264-3758.2004.00269.x>.
- Terzi, L. (2014) 'Reframing inclusive education: educational equality as capability equality', *Cambridge Journal of Education*, 44(4), pp. 479–493. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/0305764X.2014.960911>.
- Thakran, S. (2015) 'Learning Disabilities -Types and Symptoms', *International Journal of Applied Research*, 1(5), pp. 149–152. Available at: www.allresearchjournal.com.
- The Algerian Network for the Defence of the Rights of the Child, N. (2011) *Country Profile of Algeria*.
- The National Recognition Information Centre for the United Kingdom (NARIC) (2012) *An Assessment of International Teacher Training Systems: Country Profiles, Algeria*. Available at: https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/193361/DFE-RR243a_country_profiles.pdf.
- Thomas, G. (2013) *How to Do Your Research Project: A Guide for Students in Education and Applied Social Sciences*. SAGE Publications. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=-cSXkQEACAAJ>.
- Thomas, G. (2017) *How to Do Your Research Project: A Guide for Students*. SAGE Publications. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=ZqzDDgAAQBAJ>.
- Thomas, G., Walker, D. and Webb, J. (2006) *The Making of the Inclusive School*. Taylor & Francis. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=DPmFAGAAQBAJ>.
- Thurmond, V.A. (2001) 'The point of triangulation', *Journal of Nursing Scholarship*, 33(3), pp. 253–258. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1547-5069.2001.00253.x>.
- Thwala, S. (2015) 'Challenges Encountered by Teachers in Managing Inclusive Classrooms in Swaziland', *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 6, pp. 495–500. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5901/mjss.2015.v6n1p495>.

- Tomlinson, C. (2014) *The differentiated classroom: Responding to the needs of all learners (2nd ed.)*. Alexandria, VA: ASCD.
- Tongco, M.D.C. (2007) 'Purposive sampling as a tool for informant selection', *Ethnobotany Research and Applications*, 5, pp. 147–158. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.17348/era.5.0.147-158>.
- Topping, K.J. and Maloney, S. (2005) *The Routledge Falmer Reader in Inclusive Education*. Routledge (Readers in education). Available at: https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=ak8R_haUKDMC.
- Trafford, V. and Leshem, S. (2008) *Stepping Stones To Achieving Your Doctorate: By Focusing On Your Viva From The Start: Focusing on your viva from the start*. McGraw-Hill Education (Open UP study skills). Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=z8cd8KuBm58C>.
- Truscott, S.D., Berry, R.A.W. and Lee, K. (2004) 'Special Education', in C.D.B.T.-E. of A.P. Spielberger (ed.). New York: Elsevier, pp. 453–462. Available at: <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/B0-12-657410-3/00445-1>.
- Tschannen-Moran, M. and Hoy, A.W. (2001) 'Teacher Efficacy: Capturing an Elusive Construct', *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 17(7), pp. 783–805.
- UN Committee on the Rights of the Child (CRC) (2009) *General comment no. 12 (2009): the right of the child to be heard*.
- UNESCO (1994) 'The Salamanca statement and framework for action', *Policy*, (June), p. 50. Available at: <https://doi.org/E D -94/WS/ 1 8>.
- UNESCO (2005) 'Guidelines for Inclusion: Ensuring Access to Education for All', [http://lst-iiep.iiep-unesco.org/cgi-bin/wwwi32.exe/\[in=epidoc1.in\]/?t2000=021573/\(100\)](http://lst-iiep.iiep-unesco.org/cgi-bin/wwwi32.exe/[in=epidoc1.in]/?t2000=021573/(100)) [Preprint].
- UNESCO (2009) *Empowering Persons with Disabilities through ICTs*, *Telecom World*. Geneva, Switzerland.
- UNESCO (2017) *A guide for ensuring inclusion and equity in education*. Paris.
- UNESCO (2020) *Inclusive Education: A Guide for Policy-Makers*, UNESCO.
- Unianu, E.M. (2012) 'Teachers' attitudes towards inclusive education', *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 33, pp. 900–904. Available at: <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.01.252>.
- United Nations (2006) *Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities*. New York (or Geneva, though United Nations is the primary entry).
- United Nations Educational, S.C.Organization. and Science, M.E. and Spain. (1994) 'The Salamanca Statement and Framework For Action on Special Needs Education', *World Conference on Special Needs Education: Access and Quality.*, (June), pp. 7–10. Available at: http://www.unesco.org/education/pdf/SALAMA_E.PDF.
- United Nations General Assembly (UNCRC) (1989) *The United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child*.

- United Nations, H.R. (2018) *Committee on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities reviews the report of Algeria, The Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR)*. Available at: <https://www.ohchr.org/en/NewsEvents/Pages/DisplayNews.aspx?NewsID=23488&LangID=E>.
- United States Department of State (2023) *Algeria 2023 Human Rights Report*.
- USDS (2017) *Algeria 2016 human rights report*. . United States Department of State.
- Varma, D. *et al.* (2021) ‘Practical Considerations in Qualitative Health Research During the COVID-19 Pandemic’, *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 20, p. 160940692110437. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/16094069211043755>.
- Vehmas, S. (2004) ‘Ethical Analysis of the Concept of Disability’, *Mental retardation*, 42, pp. 209–222. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1352/0047-6765\(2004\)42<209:EAOTCO>2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1352/0047-6765(2004)42<209:EAOTCO>2.0.CO;2).
- Verity, D. (2010) *Teacher Education for Inclusion: International Literature Review, European Journal of Special Needs Education*.
- Vislie, L. (2003) ‘From integration to inclusion: focusing global trends and changes in the Western European societies’, *European Journal of Special Needs Education*, 18, pp. 17–35. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/0885625082000042294>.
- Waldron, N. and Meleskey, J. (2010) ‘Establishing a Collaborative School Culture Through Comprehensive School Reform’, *Journal of Educational and Psychological Consultation*, 20, pp. 58–74. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/10474410903535364>.
- Walker, J.L. (2012) ‘The use of saturation in qualitative research.’, *Canadian journal of cardiovascular nursing = Journal canadien en soins infirmiers cardio-vasculaires*, 22 2, pp. 37–46.
- Wang, H. (2009) ‘Should All Students with Special Educational Needs (SEN) Be Included in Mainstream Education Provision? - A Critical Analysis’, *International Education Studies*, 2. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5539/ies.v2n4p154>.
- Wapling, L. (2016) *Inclusive education and children with disabilities: Quality education for all in low- and middle-income countries, Cbm*.
- Warnock Mary (1978) *Report of the Committee of Enquiry into the Education of Handicapped Children and Young People*. LONDON HER MAJESTY’S STATIONERY OFFICE. Available at: <http://www.educationengland.org.uk/documents/warnock/warnock1978.pdf>.
- Washington, K.N. (2007) ‘Using the ICF within speech-language pathology: Application to developmental language impairment’, *Advances in Speech Language Pathology*, 9(3), pp. 242–255. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/14417040701261525>.
- Wendell, S. (1996) ‘Who is disabled? Defining disability’, in *the rejected body: Feminist Philosophical Reflections on Disability*. London: Routledge.
- Westby, C. and Washington, K.N. (2017) ‘Using the International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health in Assessment and Intervention of School-Aged Children With Language

- Impairments', *Language, Speech, and Hearing Services in Schools*, 48(3), pp. 137–152. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1044/2017_LSHSS-16-0037.
- Wigle, S.E. and Wilcox, D.J. (1997) 'Teacher and Administrator Attitudes toward Full Inclusion in Rural Mid-America', *Rural Special Education Quarterly*, 16(1), pp. 3–7. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/875687059701600102>.
- Williams, S. *et al.* (2012) 'Methodological Reflections on the Use of Asynchronous Online Focus Groups in Health Research', *The International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 11, pp. 368–383. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/160940691201100405>.
- Wilson, J.D. (2018) 'Appraisal of teachers', in M. Galton and B. Moon (eds.) *Handbook of Teacher Training in Europe*. London: Routledge.
- World Health organization (2002) *Towards a Common Language for Functioning , Disability and Health ICF*.
- World Health Organization (2007) *International classification of functioning, disability and health for children and youth (ICF-CY)*. Geneva, Switzerland.
- World Health Organization (2011) 'Summary World Report On Disability', *World Health*, pp. 1–24. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1136/ip.2007.018143>.
- world health organization (2013) *How to use the ICF: A practical manual for using the International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health (ICF). Exposure draft for comment*.
- World Health Organization (2020) *Deafness and hearing loss*, © 2020 WHO. Available at: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/deafness-and-hearing-loss>.
- world health organization (2022) *Disabilities, regional office for the eastern Mediterranean*.
- Yang, D. *et al.* (2023) 'Parental Involvement and Student Engagement: A Review of the Literature', *Sustainability (Switzerland)*. MDPI. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15075859>.
- Yanow, D. and Schwartz-Shea, P. (2015) *Interpretation and Method: Empirical Research Methods and the Interpretive Turn*. Taylor & Francis. Available at: https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=w_TqBgAAQBAJ.
- Yin, R.K. (2009) *Case Study Research: Design and Methods*. SAGE Publications (Applied Social Research Methods). Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=FzawIAdilHkC>.
- Yin, R.K. (2017) *Case Study Research and Applications: Design and Methods*. SAGE Publications. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=6DwmDwAAQBAJ>.
- Young, J.C. *et al.* (2018) 'A methodological guide to using and reporting on interviews in conservation science research', *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*, 9(1), pp. 10–19. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.12828>.

Zaks, Z. (2023) 'Changing the medical model of disability to the normalization model of disability: clarifying the past to create a new future direction', *Disability & Society*, 0(0), pp. 1–28.
Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09687599.2023.2255926>.

Appendixes

Appendix A: A Letter Requesting Permission to Conduct Research at a Selected School

A Letter Requesting Permission to Conduct Research at a Selected School

Title: Teachers' perceptions and experiences towards inclusive education, case of students with physical and sensory disabilities in the Algerian mainstream schools

Dear School Principal

I, Houria Benkahla, am doing PhD degree at University of the West of Scotland. I am requesting permission to conduct research in your school. The title of my study is "teachers' perceptions and experiences towards inclusive education, case of students with physical and sensory disabilities in the Algerian mainstream schools". The aim of the study is to investigate teachers' perceptions and experiences toward the inclusion of physically and sensory disabled students in the Algerian mainstream schools.

Your institution has been selected, because it is implementing Inclusive Education whereby students with physical and sensory disabilities and nondisabled students are learning in the same classroom. Therefore, I am requesting you, some selected teachers at the school to participate in the study. This study is case study research which takes your school as one of the cases. The research will employ two main types of research instruments namely focus group discussion and individual semi- structured interviews. The data collection process will be done according to consent with the participants and data collected will be confidential. The participants are expected to participate on voluntary bases, and they can withdraw at any stage during the research.

The benefits of this study are twofold. The theoretical significance of this study is that the knowledge gained by this research from the particular context will contribute to the global knowledge of inclusive education. The practical significance of this study is that while developers of curriculum can take the findings of the study as an input, teachers can also modify their teaching strategies and methodologies for teaching inclusive classrooms.

Yours sincerely

Houria Benkahla

Doctoral Student

School principal's

signature

Appendix B: A Letter Requesting Permission to Conduct Research (School A: Arabic Version)

**UWS UNIVERSITY OF THE
WEST of SCOTLAND**

من الطالبة: حورية بن كحلة

العنوان البريدي: 2B Wardrop Street, Paisley, Scotland, UK

العنوان الإلكتروني: [REDACTED]

في 21 أبريل 2022

الموضوع: رسالة لطلب الإذن بإجراء البحث في مدرستكم

إلى السيد مدير المدرسة المحترم

أنا حورية بن كحلة طالبة الدكتوراه في جامعة غرب اسكتلندا. أطلب إذنًا لإجراء بحث في مدرستكم. موضوع دراستي هو "تصورات المعلمين وخبراتهم تجاه التعليم الشامل، نموذج التلاميذ ذوي الإعاقات الجسدية والحسية في المدارس العامة في الجزائر". الهدف من الدراسة هو استطلاع في تصورات المعلمين وخبراتهم تجاه دمج الطلاب ذوي الإعاقة الجسدية والحسية في المدارس العامة في الجزائر.

تم اختيار مؤسستكم لأنها تنفذ التعليم الشامل، حيث يتعلم الطلاب الذين يعانون من إعاقات جسدية وحسية في نفس الفصل الدراسي مع زملائهم العاديين. لذلك أطلب منكم ترشيح بعض المعلمين الذين يدرسون هذه الفئة من التلاميذ للمشاركة في الدراسة.

هذه الدراسة عبارة عن دراسة حالة بحثية تعتبر مدرستكم واحدة من الحالات. سيستخدم البحث نوعين رئيسيين من أدوات البحث وهما المناقشة الجماعية والمقابلات الفردية. ستتم عملية جمع البيانات وفقًا لموافقة المشاركين وستكون البيانات التي يتم جمعها سرية. من المتوقع أن يشارك المشاركون على أسس تطوعية ويمكنهم الانسحاب في أي مرحلة أثناء البحث. لأي سبب من الأسباب التي قد يراها المشارك في الدراسة أنها غير مريحة ولا يرغب بالإجابة عليها. أهمية هذه الدراسة ذات شقين. الشق النظري الذي سيساهم في زيادة المعرفة المكتسبة في مجال التعليم الشامل. أما الشق العملي لهذه الدراسة يكمن في مساعدة المسؤولين والمختصين في إنشاء المناهج الدراسية بتطوير برامج ووسائل لتسهيل السير الدراسي لجميع التلاميذ دون استثناء. بالإضافة إلى ذلك، ستساعد المدرسين في تعديل استراتيجيات ومنهجيات وطرق التدريس الخاصة بهم للتدريس في الفصول الدراسية الشاملة. تفضلوا بقبول فائق الاحترام والتقدير

الطالبة حورية بن كحلة

Appendix C: Participant Information Sheet

Participant Information Sheet

Title of Project: Teachers' perceptions and experiences towards inclusive education, case of students with physical and sensory disabilities in the Algerian primary mainstream schools.

Ethics Approval Number: 19326

Researcher Name: [REDACTED]

Contact Email: [REDACTED]

1. Invitation to research

I would like to invite you to take part in a research study. My name is Houria Benkahla, and I am a postgraduate student at University of the West of Scotland. Before you decide you need to understand why the research is being done and what it would involve for you. Please take time to read the following information carefully. Ask questions if anything you read is not clear or would like further information. Take time to whether or not to take part. This research project aims at investigating teachers' perceptions and experiences towards the inclusion of students with physical and sensory disabilities in the Algerian primary mainstream schools.

2. Why have I been invited?

You have been invited to take part of this study because you are an Algerian teacher who teach students with physical and sensory disabilities in primary mainstream schools.

3. Do I have to take part?

It is up to you to decide. I will describe the study and go through the information sheet, which I will give to you. You will have one week to read the participants information sheet and think about the participation. If you have any questions, please feel free to contact me for further explanation. Once you decide to take part in this study, I will then ask you to sign a consent form to show you agreed to take part. You are free to withdraw at any time, without giving a reason.

4. What will I be asked to do?

Your participation in this study will involve two steps: an online group interview then followed by an individual interview at an agreed venue. The first step, exploratory focus group discussion, this will be conducted to explore your perceptions and to gain further understanding about the situation of inclusive education of physically and sensory disabled learners.

Additionally, it will provide general understanding about the context in which it major aim is to develop ideas and generate themes rather than collecting findings (Oppenheim, 1992b). Moreover, the information and data collected from this stage will demonstrate particular developments for some of the questions for the individual semi-structured interviews in the second phase of the study. In the second phase, the researcher will prepare the questions of the individual semi-structured interviews after examining the initial phase of focus group discussion and after doing extensive reading about relevant literature. In addition to that, instead of depending on general personal answers indicated by the focus group discussion, the researcher used individual semi-structured interviews in order to gather further in-depth information.

The focus group discussion will last between an hour to an hour and half. Additionally, the individual semi-structured interview will last between 40 and 60 minutes. The conversation will be recorded, but as said before it is all voluntary. The recorded interviews sessions will be played back for you to confirm it forms a true record of what you said. If you do not want to be recorded, all of your responses will be written down and then read back to you to ensure that the interview is accurate. You will be then asked to sign.

Your individual data of the interview will be anonymized and given a research code known only by the researcher. A master list identifying participants to the research code data will be held on a password protected computer and on the secure UWS drive accessed only by the researcher.

5. Are there any risks if I participate?

This study does not cause the participants any type of risks.

6. Are there any advantages if I participate?

We cannot promise the study will help you, but your participation will help to increase the understanding of the teachers' views and experiences toward the inclusion of student with physical and sensory disabilities in the Algerian mainstream schools. The result from this study will inform a larger scale project aimed at raising education for students with physical and sensory disabilities in the Algerian mainstream schools. In addition to that, to address any difficulties that face teachers in the inclusive settings. As well as to suggest strategies to implement the inclusive education for physically and sensory disabled students in effective way.

7. What will happen to the results of the research study?

The results of the study will be used to complete a thesis and later to be published in the academic literature. Additionally, the findings of the research will be written up for publication in an academic journal and presented in conference at university and public events. You will not be identified in any publication unless you have given your consent.

8. Data Protection Privacy Notice

The data controller for this project will be University of the West of Scotland (UWS). Your personal data will be processed for the purposes outlined in this notice. The legal basis that would be used to process your personal data will be the provision of your consent.

We will only retain your personal data for as long as is necessary to achieve the research purpose. Data published in this research will not contain any clues that reveal the identity of the participants. Your data will be anonymised and can be presented only through the use of pseudonyms. Regarding the focus group discussion, I will ensure that the participants and I have to follow a few rules to protect the integrity of each participant. First, trying not to refer to each other by names. Secondly, I will give each participant stick or name tags with letters on them. That will assist me in calling on people in an anonymous but respectful way. Thirdly, trying not to name schools. All personal data will be stored on the UWS One Drive.

If you are concerned about how your personal data is being processed, please contact UWS in the first instance at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. If you remain unsatisfied, you may wish to contact the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO). Contact details, and details of data subject rights, are available on the ICO website at: <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/data-protection-reform/overview-of-the-gdpr/individuals-rights/>

Who has reviewed the study?

ESS Ethics Committee-Approval Number: 19326

Contact for further information

If you have any queries or concerns about the research project, please do not hesitate to contact the research team: **Houria Benkahla:** [REDACTED]

Dr Eric C G Baumgartner: [REDACTED]

Dr Carrie Ballantyne: [REDACTED]

Appendix D: Participant Information Sheet (Arabic Version)

UWS UNIVERSITY OF THE
WEST of SCOTLAND

School of Education and Social Science

ورقة معلومات المشارك

عنوان المشروع:

تصورات وخبرات المعلمين تجاه التعليم الشامل، دراسة حالة للطلاب ذوي الإعاقة الجسدية والحسية في المدارس الابتدائية الجزائرية الحكومية.

رقم الموافقة الأخلاقية: 19326

اسم الباحثة: حورية بن كحلة

البريد الإلكتروني للاتصال

1- دعوة للمشاركة في البحث

أود أن أدعوك للمشاركة في دراسة بحثية. اسمي حورية بن كحلة، وأنا طالبة دراسات عليا في جامعة غرب اسكتلندا (University of the West of Scotland). قبل أن تقرر، يجب أن تفهم سبب إجراء البحث وماذا سيتضمن ذلك بالنسبة لك. يرجى تخصيص وقت لقراءة المعلومات التالية بعناية. اطرح أسئلة إذا لم يكن أي شيء تقرأه واضحاً أو إذا كنت ترغب في الحصول على مزيد من المعلومات. خذ وقتك للتفكير فيما إذا كنت تريد المشاركة أم لا. يهدف هذا المشروع البحثي إلى استقصاء تصورات وخبرات المعلمين تجاه دمج الطلاب ذوي الإعاقة الجسدية والحسية في المدارس الابتدائية الجزائرية الحكومية.

2- لماذا تمت دعوتي؟

لقد تمت دعوتك للمشاركة في هذه الدراسة لأنك معلم جزائري تقوم بتدريس طلاب ذوي إعاقات جسدية وحسية في المدارس الابتدائية الحكومية.

3- يجب علي المشاركة؟

الأمر متروك لك لتقرر. سأصاف الدراسة وأستعرض ورقة المعلومات، والتي سأقدمها لك. سيكون لديك أسبوع واحد لقراءة ورقة معلومات المشاركين والتفكير في المشاركة. إذا كان لديك أي أسئلة، فلا تتردد في الاتصال بي للحصول على

الصفحة 1 من 4

مزيد من التوضيح وبمجرد أن تقرر المشاركة في هذه الدراسة، سأطلب منك التوقيع على نموذج موافقة لإظهار موافقتك على المشاركة. أنت حر في الانسحاب في أي وقت، دون إبداء سبب

4- ما الذي سيُطلب مني القيام به؟

ستتضمن مشاركتك في هذه الدراسة خطوتين:

• الخطوة الأولى:

✓ مقابلة جماعية عبر الإنترنت تليها مقابلة فردية في مكان متفق عليه لمناقشة جماعية استكشافية (Focus Group) , سيتم إجراء هذه المناقشة لاستكشاف تصوراتك واكتساب فهم أعمق حول وضع التعليم الشامل للمتعلمين ذوي الإعاقات الجسدية والحسية.

✓ ستوفر هذه المناقشة فهماً عاماً للسياق، حيث يتمثل هدفها الرئيسي في تطوير الأفكار وتوليد المحاور بدلاً من جمع النتائج.
✓ ستستخدم المعلومات والبيانات التي يتم جمعها من هذه المرحلة لتطوير بعض الأسئلة للمقابلات الفردية شبه المنظمة في المرحلة الثانية من الدراسة .

• الخطوة الثانية:

✓ المقابلات الفردية شبه المنظمة، في هذه المرحلة، ستقوم الباحثة بإعداد أسئلة المقابلات الفردية شبه المنظمة بعد فحص المرحلة الأولى من المناقشة الجماعية وبعد القراءة المكثفة للأدبيات ذات الصلة .

✓ سيتم استخدام المقابلات الفردية شبه المنظمة لجمع معلومات متعمقة إضافية، بدلاً من الاعتماد على الإجابات الشخصية العامة التي تشير إليها المناقشة الجماعية.
المدة الزمنية :

✓ ستستغرق المناقشة الجماعية ما بين ساعة إلى ساعة ونصف.

✓ ستستغرق المقابلة الفردية شبه المنظمة ما بين 40 و 60 دقيقة
سيتم تسجيل المحادثة، ولكن كما ذكر سابقاً، المشاركة طوعية بالكامل. سيتم إعادة تشغيل جلسات المقابلات المسجلة لك لتأكيد أنها تشكل سجلاً حقيقياً لما قلته. إذا كنت لا ترغب في التسجيل، فسيتم تدوين جميع إجاباتك وقراءتها لك لضمان دقة المقابلة. سيُطلب منك بعد ذلك التوقيع .
سيتم إخفاء هوية بياناتك الفردية للمقابلة وإعطائها رمز بحث معروف للباحثة فقط. سيتم الاحتفاظ بقائمة رئيسية تربط المشاركين برمز بيانات البحث على جهاز كمبيوتر محمي بكلمة مرور وعلى محرك الأقراص الآمن الخاص بجامعة غرب اسكتلندا (UWS) ولا يمكن الوصول إليه إلا من قبل الباحثة .

5- هل هناك أي مخاطر إذا شاركت؟

لا تسبب هذه الدراسة للمشاركين أي نوع من المخاطر.

6- هل هناك أي مزايا إذا شاركت؟

لا يمكننا أن نعد بأن الدراسة ستستفيد من مشاركةك، ولكن مشاركتك ستستفيد من زيادة فهم راء وخبرات المعلمين تجاه دمج الطلاب ذوي الإعاقة الجسدية والحسية في المدارس الجزائرية العادية. ستنتج النتائج المستخلصة من هذه الدراسة مشروعاً أوسع نطاقاً يهدف إلى الارتقاء بالتعليم للطلاب ذوي الإعاقة الجسدية والحسية في المدارس الجزائرية العادية. بالإضافة إلى ذلك، ستساعد في معالجة أي صعوبات تواجه المعلمين في بيئات الدمج، وكذلك اقتراح استراتيجيات لتطبيق التعليم الشامل للطلاب ذوي الإعاقة الجسدية والحسية بطريقة فعالة.

7- ماذا سيحدث لنتائج الدراسة البحثية؟

سنستخدم نتائج الدراسة لإكمال رسالة (أطروحة)، ومن ثم سيتم نشرها لاحقاً في الأدبيات الأكاديمية. بالإضافة إلى ذلك، سيتم كتابة نتائج البحث للنشر في مجلة أكاديمية وتقديمها في مؤتمرات وفعاليات عامة بالجامعة. لن يتم الكشف عن هويتك في أي من المنشورات ما لم تكن قد أعطيت موافقتك على ذلك.

8- إشعار خصوصية حماية البيانات:

سيكون مراقب البيانات (Data Controller) لهذا المشروع هو جامعة غرب اسكتلندا (UWS)، سيتم معالجة بياناتك الشخصية لأغراض الموضحة في هذا الإشعار. سيكون الأساس القانوني الذي سيتم استخدامه لمعالجة بياناتك الشخصية هو تقديمك لموافقتك. سنحتفظ ببياناتك الشخصية فقط طالما كان ذلك ضرورياً لتحقيق الغرض البحثي. لن تحتوي البيانات المنشورة في هذا البحث على أي أدلة تكشف عن هوية المشاركين. سيتم إخفاء هوية بياناتك ولا يمكن تقديمها إلا باستخدام أسماء مستعارة

(Pseudonyms).

فيما يتعلق بالمناقشة الجماعية (Focus Group) : سأضمن أن يتبع المشاركون وأنا بضع قواعد لحماية خصوصية كل مشارك.

- أولاً: محاولة عدم الإشارة إلى بعضنا البعض بالأسماء.
- ثانياً: سأعطي كل مشارك ملصقات أو بطاقات أسماء عليها أحرف. سيساعدني هذا في مناداة الأشخاص بطريقة مجهولة ولكن محترمة.
- ثالثاً: محاولة عدم ذكر أسماء المدارس.

✓ سيتم تخزين جميع البيانات الشخصية على UWS One Drive.

✓ إذا كنت قلقاً بشأن كيفية معالجة بياناتك الشخصية، يرجى الاتصال بجامعة غرب اسكتلندا (UWS) أولاً على dataprotection@uws.ac.uk: إذا بقيت غير راضٍ، يمكنك الاتصال بمكتب مفوض المعلومات (Information Commissioner's Office - ICO).
تفاصيل الاتصال وتفاصيل حقوق صاحب البيانات .

متوفرة على موقع ICO على الويب: <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/data-protection-reform/overview-of-the-gdpr/individuals-rights/>.

من قام بمراجعة الدراسة؟ لجنة أخلاقيات - ESS رقم الموافقة :
للتواصل للحصول على مزيد من المعلومات. إذا كانت لديك أي استفسارات أو مخاوف بشأن المشروع البحثي، فلا تتردد في الاتصال بفريق البحث :

حورية بن كحلة

الدكتور إريك بومغارتنر

الدكتور كاري بالاتين

Appendix E: Informed Consent Form

School of Education and Social Science

RESEARCH INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Title of Project: Teachers' perceptions and experiences towards inclusive education, case of students with physical and sensory disabilities in the Algerian primary mainstream schools.

Ethics Approval Number: 19326

Researcher Name: Houria Benkahla

Contact Email: [REDACTED]

Please read the following statements and complete all the sections in this form by putting down your initials in the box.

I confirm that I have read and understood the information sheet for the above study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.

I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason to the named researcher.

I understand all information given will be held in strict confidence

I understand that my responses will remain anonymous

I understand that no expenses and payments are involved in this research

I agree to participate in this research project

The Name of the researcher	Date	signature
The name of the participant	Date	signature

To be signed and dated in presence of the participant.

Signed in two copies, one for the participant and one for the researcher.

Appendix F: Informed Consent Form (Arabic Version)

UWS UNIVERSITY OF THE WEST of SCOTLAND

نموذج موافقة

عنوان المشروع:

تصورات وخبرات المعلمين تجاه التعليم الشامل، دراسة حالة للطلاب ذوي الإعاقة الجسدية والحسية في المدارس الابتدائية الجزائرية الحكومية .

رقم الموافقة الأخلاقية: 19326

اسم الباحثة: حورية بن كحلة
البريد الإلكتروني للاتصال

يرجى قراءة البيانات التالية وإكمال جميع الأقسام في هذا النموذج بوضع الأحرف الأولى من اسمك في المربع المخصص .

❖ أؤكد أنني قرأت وفهمت ورقة المعلومات الخاصة بالدراسة المذكورة أعلاه .

❖ أتيت لي الفرصة للنظر في المعلومات وطرح الأسئلة وقد تم الرد عليها بشكل مرضٍ

❖ أفهم أن مشاركتي طوعية وأنتي حر في الانسحاب في أي وقت دون تقديم أي سبب للباحث المذكور اسمه .

❖ أفهم أن جميع المعلومات المقدمة سيتم الاحتفاظ بها بسرية تامة .

❖ أفهم أن إجاباتي ستبقى مجهولة الهوية .

❖ أفهم أنه لا توجد نفقات أو مدفوعات متضمنة في هذا البحث .

❖ أوافق على المشاركة في هذا المشروع البحثي .

التوقيع

التاريخ

اسم المشارك

التوقيع

التاريخ

اسم الباحثة : حورية بن كحلة

ملاحظات هامة :

يتم التوقيع والتاريخ في حضور المشارك .

يتم التوقيع بنسخين، واحدة للمشارك واحدة للباحث

Appendix G: Participant Debrief Sheet

UWS UNIVERSITY OF THE
WEST of SCOTLAND
School of Education and Social Science

DEBRIEF FORM

Title of Project: Teachers' perceptions and experiences towards inclusive education, case of students with physical and sensory disabilities in the Algerian mainstream schools.

Ethics Approval Number: 19326

Researcher Name: Houria Benkahla

Researcher Email [REDACTED]

Thank you for taking part in this research.

Studies revealed that the teachers' perceptions of, attitudes and experiences towards inclusive education are important, since they could affect the level of accommodation and acceptance of learners with disabilities within ordinary schools (Cornoldi *et al.*, 2018). Similarly, Koay *et al.* (2006) stated that the realization of inclusive education relies massively on the teachers' perceptions, attitudes, and experiences towards students with disabilities, including those with physical and sensory disabilities, within mainstream schools.

Teachers who teach disabled students in the mainstream schools have major role in the success of inclusive education as they are in the front line in dealing with them in the classroom. Thus, the perceptions and experiences of teachers towards inclusive education, case of students with physical and sensory disabilities in the Algerian mainstream schools are to be the main focus of the current research. The aim of this study is to give teachers a voice to understand their perceptions and experiences towards the inclusion of students with physical and sensory disabilities in mainstream schools in Algeria.

As a reminder, if you would like to withdraw your data from this project, please contact the researcher at the above email address within two weeks of study completion quoting the code word you made at the start of the interview.

If you would like more information about this project, please contact the researcher at [REDACTED]. If you have any complaints or feel that you have been affected by the study in any way, please contact Dr Iain McPhee (Chair of ESS Ethics Committee) at: [REDACTED]

Thank you once again for taking part.

If you have any complaints or concerns about this research, you can direct these, in writing, to the Chair of the ESS Ethics Committee by email at: ess.ethics@uws.ac.uk. Alternatively, you can contact us by post at: Ethics Committee Chair, School of Education and Social Science, University of West of Scotland, Paisley, PA1 2BE

Appendix H: Participant Debrief Sheet (Arabic Version)

ورقة إحاطة المشارك

عنوان المشروع: تصورات وخبرات المعلمين تجاه التعليم الشامل، حالة الطلاب ذوي الإعاقات الجسدية والحسية في المدارس الجزائرية الحكومية

رقم الموافقة الأخلاقية: 19326

اسم الباحث: حورية بن كحلة

البريد الإلكتروني للباحث:

نشكرك على مشاركتك في هذا البحث ---

أظهرت الدراسات أن تصورات المعلمين ومواقفهم وخبراتهم تجاه التعليم الشامل تعتبر مهمة، حيث يمكن أن تؤثر على مستوى استيعاب وقبول المتعلمين ذوي الإعاقة داخل المدارس الحكومية (كورنولدي وآخرون، 2018). وبالمثل، صرّح (كواي وآخرون، 2006) أن تحقيق التعليم الشامل يعتمد بشكل كبير على تصورات المعلمين ومواقفهم وخبراتهم تجاه الطلاب ذوي الإعاقة، بمن فيهم ذوو الإعاقات الجسدية والحسية، داخل المدارس الحكومية. يلعب المعلمون الذين يدرسون الطلاب ذوي الإعاقة في المدارس الحكومية دورًا رئيسيًا في نجاح التعليم الشامل؛ فهم في الخطوط الأمامية في التعامل معهم داخل الفصل الدراسي. وبالتالي، فإن تصورات المعلمين وخبراتهم تجاه التعليم الشامل، في حالة الطلاب ذوي الإعاقات الجسدية والحسية في المدارس الجزائرية الحكومية، ستكون هي التركيز الرئيسي للبحث الحالي.

يهدف هذا البحث إلى إعطاء صوت للمعلمين لفهم تصوراتهم وخبراتهم تجاه دمج الطلاب ذوي الإعاقات الجسدية والحسية في المدارس الحكومية بالجزائر.

للتذكير: إذا كنت ترغب في سحب بياناتك من هذا المشروع، يرجى الاتصال بالباحث على عنوان البريد الإلكتروني المذكور أعلاه في غضون أسبوعين من الانتهاء من الدراسة، مع ذكر الكلمة السرية التي قمت بإنشائها في بداية المقابلة لمزيد من المعلومات حول هذا المشروع، يرجى التواصل مع الباحث عبر البريد الإلكتروني:

إذا كانت لديك أي شكاوى أو شعرت بأن الدراسة قد أثرت عليك بأي شكل من الأشكال، يرجى التواصل مع الدكتور إيان * ماكفي (رئيس اللجنة الأخلاقية لكلية دراسات التربية والعلوم الاجتماعية) على العنوان التالي

نشكرك مرة أخرى على مشاركتك

Appendix I: Focus group interview questions

Focus group interview questions

The concept of inclusive education and Inclusive education policy

- 1- Explain what you know about inclusive education?
- 2- Explain how much you know about inclusive education policy in Algeria?

Implementation of inclusive education

- 3- Tell me about how you implement the inclusive education policy in your school?
- 4- Explain how you enrol students with physical and sensory disabilities in your schools?
- 5- How does the school as a whole consider the needs of all the students when planning the curriculum and educational programs?
- 6- How does the overall classroom/school environment allow students with physical and sensory disabilities to attend regular schools?

Teacher preparation and professional development opportunities for inclusive education

- 7- Have you had training related to disability or inclusion? Tell me about this training?
What did you learn? How did the training affect you? What training is still needed?
What kind of training would be good?
- 8- What do you think about the allocation of responsibility of a teacher to the number of children of disabilities in the classroom?
- 9- Can you tell me about the kind of teaching strategies that are available to support students with physical and sensory disabilities in your school?

Teachers' views

- 10- What is your view of admitting students with physical and sensory and disabilities into regular school?
- 11- What factors can contribute to the inclusion of children with physical and sensory disabilities in Algerian schools?
- 12- What do you think are the barriers to inclusion of children with physical and sensory disabilities in Algerian mainstream schools?
- 13- How do you feel about inclusive schooling in Algeria?

Curriculum assessment practice and reporting on inclusive education

- 14- How does the school use the assessment strategies to meet the needs of all the students in the school?

15- Tell me how you consider and practice testing and assessment procedures during tests and exams for students with physical and sensory disabilities?

Probing questions types

Tell me more about? Why did you say that? Could you explain that? can you clarify
What did you mean by that? Can you give an example of that?

Appendix J: Focus group interview questions (Arabic Version)

أسئلة المقابلة الجماعية

مفهوم التعليم الشامل وسياسة التعليم الشامل

اشرح ما تعرفه عن التعليم الشامل؟

اشرح مدى معرفتك بسياسة التعليم الشامل في الجزائر؟

تنفيذ التعليم الشامل

أخبرني عن كيفية تطبيقك لسياسة التعليم الشامل في مدرستك؟

اشرح كيف تقوم بتسجيل الطلاب ذوي الإعاقات الجسدية والحسية في مدارسك؟

كيف تراعي المدرسة احتياجات جميع الطلاب عند تطبيق المناهج والبرامج التعليمية؟

كيف تسمح البيئة الصفية / المدرسية الشاملة للطلاب ذوي الإعاقات الجسدية والحسية بالالتحاق بالمدارس العامة؟

فرص إعداد المعلمين والتطوير المهني للتعليم الشامل

هل تلقيت تدريبًا متعلقًا بالإعاقة أو الإدماج؟ أخبرني عن هذا التدريب؟

ماذا تعلمت؟ كيف أثر التدريب عليك؟ ما هو التدريب الذي لا يزال مطلوبًا؟ أي نوع من التدريب سيكون جيدًا؟

ما رأيك في تخصيص مسؤولية المعلم لعدد الأطفال ذوي الإعاقة في الفصل؟

هل يمكن أن تخبرني عن نوع استراتيجيات التدريس المتوفرة لدعم الطلاب ذوي الإعاقات الجسدية والحسية في مدرستك؟

آراء المعلمين

ما هو رأيك في قبول الطلاب ذوي الإعاقات الجسدية والحسية في المدرسة العامة؟

ما هي العوامل التي يمكن أن تسهم في دمج الأطفال ذوي الإعاقات الجسدية والحسية في المدارس الجزائرية العامة؟

ما هي برأيك العوائق التي تحول دون دمج الأطفال ذوي الإعاقات الجسدية والحسية في المدارس الجزائرية العامة؟

ما هو شعورك حيال التعليم الشامل في الجزائر؟

تقييم المناهج والإبلاغ عن التعليم الشامل

كيف تستخدم المدرسة استراتيجيات التقييم لتلبية احتياجات جميع الطلاب في المدرسة العامة؟

كيف تقوم بإجراءات التقييم أثناء الاختبارات والامتحانات للطلاب ذوي الإعاقات الجسدية والحسية؟

أنواع الأسئلة الاستقصائية

أخبرني المزيد عن؟، لماذا قلت ذلك؟، هل يمكن أن تشرح أو يمكنك التوضيح

ماذا تقصد بذلك؟، هل يمكنك إعطاء مثال على ذلك؟

Appendix K: Individual Interview Schedule

Individual Interview Schedule

- **Teachers' understanding of the concept of inclusive education**
 - 1- Could you explain what you know about inclusive education?
 - 2- Do you have any physical or sensory disabled pupils in your class? What type of disability do they have?
- **Inclusive education policies in Algeria**
 - 3- Could you tell me about the inclusive education practises in Algeria?
 - 4- What are your views on inclusive education in Algeria?
 - 5- Could you please explain what professional development opportunities your school, local office of education, or ministry of education offers in inclusive education?
- **Educators' attitudes and experiences toward the inclusive education of physically and sensory disabled pupils**
 - 6- As a general education teacher, what are your experiences with an inclusive classroom?
 - 7- What are your opinions on allowing students with physical and sensory disabilities to attend general school?
- **Inclusive education Strategies**
 - 8- What instructional methods do you use to accommodate students with physical and sensory disabilities in your classroom?
 - 9- Could you provide me with information regarding the school's curriculum and how it is carried out?
 - 10- How are the classroom and school setting set up to accommodate children with physical and sensory disabilities?
 - 11- What types of the instructional skills do general education teachers have to teach both students with disabilities and nondisabled students?
- **The barriers in implementing inclusive education in Algeria**
 - 12- What difficulties do teachers in your schools face while teaching students with physical and sensory disabilities?
 - 13- What developments have been made in resolving the issues you previously mentioned?
- **Teachers views of methods and strategies for improving inclusive education for student with physical and sensory disabilities**

- 14- What strategies do you apply in the classroom to make sure that every student is engaged in the learning process?
- 15- What kind of educational atmosphere do you think is best for pupils with physical and sensory disabilities?
- 16- What adjustments would you make to the educational system to better serve students with physical and sensory disabilities?
- 17- What do you think about the resources provided by the Department of Education to your school to use in implementing inclusive education?
- 18- How can general education teachers meet the needs of students with physical and sensory disabilities in the general education classroom?
- 19- Is there anything more you would like to say?

Appendix L: Individual Interview Schedule (Arabic Version)

أسئلة المقابلة الفردية

ما هي شهادتك؟

كم سنة تعمل كمدرس؟

فهم المعلمين لمفهوم التعليم الشامل

1. ما مفهوم التعليم الشامل او ما يعرف بالادماج؟
2. هل يوجد في صفك تلاميذ من ذوي الاعاقات الجسدية والحسية ؟ ما نوع الإعاقة التي يعانون منها؟

• سياسات التعليم الشامل في الجزائر

3. هل يمكن أن تخبرني عن سياسة التعليم الشامل المطبقة في مدرستك ؟
4. ما هي وجهة نظرك حول التعليم الشامل في الجزائر؟
5. هل يمكن من فضلك توضيح فرص التكوين المهني التي تقدمها مدرستك أو وزارة التربية والتعليم في التعليم الشامل؟

• مواقف المعلمين وخبراتهم تجاه التعليم الشامل للتلاميذ المعوقين جسدياً وحسياً

6. كمدرس تعليم عام ، ما هي خبراتك مع الفصل الدراسي الشامل؟
7. ما رأيك في السماح للطلاب ذوي الإعاقات الجسدية والحسية بالالتحاق بالمدارس العامة؟

استراتيجيات التعليم الشامل

8. ما هي الأساليب التعليمية التي تستخدمها لتدريس الطلاب ذوي الإعاقات الجسدية والحسية في صفك؟
9. هل يمكن أن تزودني بمعلومات عن المنهاج الدراسي وكيف يتم تنفيذه مع التلاميذ ذوي الاحتياجات الخاصة ؟
10. كيف يتم إعداد الاقسام و المدارس لادماج الأطفال ذوي الإعاقات الجسدية والحسية؟
11. ما هي أنواع المهارات التعليمية التي يجب على المعلمين تدريسها للطلاب ذوي الإعاقة وغير المعوقين؟

• معوقات تطبيق التعليم الجامع في الجزائر

12. ما هي الصعوبات التي يواجهها المعلمون في مدارسكم أثناء تعليم الطلاب ذوي الإعاقات الجسدية والحسية؟
13. ما هي التطورات التي حدثت في حل القضايا التي ذكرتها سابقاً؟

آراء المعلمين حول الأساليب والاستراتيجيات لتحسين التعليم الشامل للطلاب ذوي الإعاقات الجسدية والحسية

14. ما هي الطرق و الاستراتيجيات التي تطبقها في القسم للتأكد من مشاركة كل التلاميذ ؟
15. ما هو الجو التعليمي الذي تعتقد أنه الأفضل للتلاميذ ذوي الإعاقات الجسدية والحسية؟
16. ما هي التعديلات التي يمكنك إجراؤها على النظام التعليمي لخدمة الطلاب ذوي الإعاقات الجسدية والحسية بشكل أفضل؟
17. ما رأيك في الموارد التي توفرها وزارة التعليم لمدرستك لاستخدامها في تنفيذ التعليم الشامل؟
18. كيف يمكن للمعلمين تلبية احتياجات الطلاب ذوي الإعاقات الجسدية والحسية في فصل التعليم العام؟
19. هل هناك أي شيء آخر تود أن تقوله؟

Appendix M: A Sample of data transcription

Participant Five

Gender: Female

Diploma degree: bachelor degree

Teaching experience: 16 Years

1- Could you explain what you know about inclusive education?

Inclusive education involves placing learners with special needs in a supportive setting to which they can adjust.

2- Do you have any physical or sensory disabled pupils in your class? What type of disability do they have?

Yes, I have two pupils with physical and sensory disabilities in my classroom. One with hearing impairment and one with visual impairment.

3- Could you tell me about the inclusive education practices in Algeria?

The participant asked about what I mean by inclusive education practices.

I explained the question in different manner to make it clear.

What are your school's policies on inclusive education?

Although we are still looking into it, my school currently does not have any rules regarding inclusive education. They might aid us in creating inclusive education programs, so perhaps we will have one in the future. Additionally the responsible for this situation should be the Ministry of Education, which has failed to provide us with any guidance regarding the creation of policies.

4- What are your views on inclusive education in Algeria?

I believe that at this time, regular schools are unable to meet the needs of learners with disabilities. It is deficient in a number of aspects that would enable pupils with disabilities to adapt to life in the mainstream schools. Consider a shortage of supplies and tools as well as lack of teacher training in special needs.

5- Could you please explain what professional development opportunities your school, local office of education, or ministry of education offers in inclusive education?

The teacher now receives a three-week training program right away after winning the contest to get a job as a teacher. Along with an extended six-month training program held on weekends and during holidays (winter and spring breaks), however we have not covered subjects related to inclusive education and students with special needs during this training.

6- As a general education teacher, what are your experiences with an inclusive classroom?

It is not a wise decision. Both the classroom and the school are unprepared to meet the needs of Special need pupils. Despite my long career as a teacher, I still found it difficult to educate students who had disabilities. We did not get any training or guidance from the ministry of education on how to instruct these pupils. Besides that, there are shortage of equipment and instruments in the resource room.

7- What are your opinions on allowing students with physical and sensory disabilities to attend general school?

In fact, inclusive education is crucial because it involves all types of students, and it is important that every student's needs are met. However, some adjustments must be made to the educational program, classrooms, schools, and teachers' training to better suit their needs.

8- What difficulties do teachers in your schools face while teaching students with physical and sensory disabilities?

It is common to experience disciplinary issues when working with a large number of students. They will be noisy and annoying the other pupils with disabilities.

There is no use of technology in class, so classrooms are not equipped to accommodate learners with hearing or visual impairments. The blackboard is still our main tool to deliver lessons. I believe that those who have hearing impairments will benefit from using visual aids. In addition, those who have vision impairments will benefit from listening to audio-recorded lectures.

Nine years have passed since I started working in this school, and I have never seen a single paper relating to inclusive education. There are no clear regulations that help teachers to deal with students with special needs.

9- What developments have been made in resolving the issues you previously mentioned?

I do not currently see any changes being made to better assist students with special needs. I believe that the Ministry of Education is the sole body that has the power to affect change because they are in charge of developing curricula, training educators, and providing funding for schools to upgrade their facilities.

10- What instructional methods do you use to accommodate students with physical and sensory disabilities in your classroom?

I check their understanding from time to time without letting them feel that they are different.

I invite them to take part in the class through calling from the list.

I demonstrate my appreciation and support.

I place student with disabilities in the front row in the classroom, next to those without disabilities so they can help them out.

When you put the students with impairments next to the students without disabilities, how do the parents of the children act? Have they ever objected to your suggestion that their kids help the disabled students?

I have not heard any complaints or unfavourable comments regarding this matter from the parents of nondisabled students.

11- Could you provide me with information regarding the school's curriculum and how it is carried out?

The problem of an inadequate curriculum is made worse by large numbers of students. Which force the teachers to quickly teach everything on the educational program in order to complete everything within the allotted time.

12- How are the classroom and school setting set up to accommodate children with physical and sensory disabilities?

As I previously stated the classroom and schools are not modified to suit students with special needs including those with physical and sensory disabilities. for example, large number of students in the class I typically have at least 30 students in my class, but sometimes there are more. Additionally, there are stairs inside and in front of the class, as well as out-of-date teaching tools and equipment.

13- What types of the instructional skills do general education teachers have to teach both students with disabilities and nondisabled students?

It is so disappointing that the majority of educators in general education are unprepared to deal with students with disabilities. Personally, I do not think I am qualified to teach them. I miss a number of abilities and skills. For instance: communication skills, sign language, braille, and how to deal with them in emergency cases, etc.

14- What strategies do you apply in the classroom to make sure that every student is engaged in the learning process?

I ask the student to rephrase the task's objectives as I reaffirm them. I used a random call technique throughout the class to gauge learners' comprehension of the subject matter, and I

used it again when the task is given. In my opinion, learners with disabilities would profit from these techniques.

15- What kind of educational atmosphere do you think is best for pupils with physical and sensory disabilities?

The ministry of education should create assistive and adaptive materials. They are necessary for us to manage the disabled pupils easily.

Provide teachers with training in inclusive education, so they can handle students with disabilities appropriately.

Ensuring that the classroom and school are ready to receive disabled children such as providing them with suitable chairs, desks, walkways, toilets, hearing aids, etc.

16- What adjustments would you make to the educational system to better serve students with physical and sensory disabilities?

To enable such children with disabilities to receive an education, the educational system should be completely redesigned and schools should be improved. The government should raise awareness of inclusion.

As I mentioned earlier teachers' training is very important.

Encouraging the use of technology to deliver lessons like using projectors.

Equip the resource room with necessary tools.

17- What do you think about the resources provided by the Department of Education to your school to use in implementing inclusive education?

Most schools still lack materials and supplies for their resource rooms. Which limit the teachers' ability to handle the needs of disabled learners.

18- How can general education teachers meet the needs of students with physical and sensory disabilities in the general education classroom?

I try to give them assignments that are broken up into more manageable parts.

I follow up frequently to make sure they are progressing as planned.

I frequently provide immediate assistance and feedback.

However, these are not enough I still emphasize on teachers' training.

19- Is there anything more you would like to say?

I have nothing to add, I hope my answers could help you in your research.

Appendix N: Thematic Analyses for individual interviews

Data Analyses for the individual semi-structure interviews:

- 1- Reading all transcripts carefully and become familiar with the data
- 2- Generating initial codes from the transcripts:

Initial codes from all transcripts (P1 to P20)

- The physical presence of disabled pupils in regular schools
- The right of disabled students to enrol in regular schools
- The existence of inclusive education
- Lack of teachers training and personal development in inclusive education
- Inadequate school services and facilities
- Inclusive education is great concept
- The educational environment does not support the inclusion of disabled students
- Providing teachers with training in inclusive education
- Defining disability from social model perspectives
- Lack of in-service training in inclusive education
- The headmaster of school is in charge of the enrolment of disabled learners
- Dealing with students who have disabilities falls primarily on general educators.
- Lack of pre-service training in inclusive education
- Teachers made great efforts to include disabled pupils
- Enhancing school facilities and services
- Lack of training makes teaching in an inclusive classroom difficult.
- The education of disabled students
- Using Various teaching methods
- Using group/pair work
- Insufficient knowledge of Inclusive Education policies.
- Lack of support from the ministry of education
- Acknowledging the diversity among learners
- Hard job for teachers due to insufficient knowledge of inclusive education policy
- Lack of confidence among teachers as result of inadequate guidance
- Modifying the curriculum and providing sufficient teaching resources
- Describing inclusive education by referencing the disabilities that students had.
- Chance for disabled students to socialize
- Providing extra time
- Peer assistance
- Assignment modification
- Lack of funding from the government.
- Special schools to serve students with disabilities
- Lack of classrooms adaptation
- Inclusive education is suitable when essential modifications are made.
- The attendance of disabled students in regular classroom conditioned by their number
- Suitable setting for disabled pupils to adapt
- Disengagement from parents

- Lack of staff member at school
- Providing further care and attention to disabled students
- Disabled learners sharing the same setting with non-disabled peers
- Collaboration
- Inappropriate Curriculum
- Poor instructional Resources and materials
- Huge class size
- Inclusive education is unwise since there are no adequate services and facilities
- Raising awareness of inclusive education
- Challenging teachers` experience because of the absence of collaboration between policymakers, parents, and teachers
- Behavioural problems
- Special classrooms for disabled students
- Raising teachers` motivation

3- Searching for themes

<p>Theme one: Teachers` understanding of the concept of inclusive education</p> <p>Codes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The physical presence of disabled pupils in regular schools • Defining disability from social model perspectives • The education of disabled students • Describing inclusive education by referencing the disabilities that students had. • Chance for disabled students to socialize • The attendance of disabled students in regular classroom conditioned by their number • Suitable setting for disabled pupils to adapt • Providing further care and attention to disabled students • Disabled learners sharing the same setting with non-disabled peers 	<p>Theme two: The inclusive education policy in Algeria</p> <p>Codes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The right of disabled students to enrol in regular schools • The existence of inclusive education • The headmaster of school is in charge of the enrolment of disabled learners • Dealing with students who have disabilities falls primarily on general educators. 	<p>Theme three: Instructional strategies used in the inclusive classroom</p> <p>Codes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Using Various teaching methods • Using group/pair work • Providing extra time • Peer assistance • Assignment modification • Explaining concept several times • Check understanding • Placing disabled students in the front rows in classroom
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<p>Theme four: The barriers in implementing inclusive education in Algerian primary schools</p> <p>Codes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of teachers training and personal development in inclusive education • Inadequate school services and facilities • Lack of pre-service training in inclusive education • Lack of in-service training in inclusive education • Insufficient knowledge of Inclusive Education policies. • Lack of support from the ministry of education • Lack of funding from the government. • Special schools to serve students with disabilities • Lack of classrooms adaptation • Inappropriate Curriculum • Poor instructional Resources and materials • Huge class size • Disengagement from parents • Lack of staff member at school • Behavioural problems • Special classrooms for disabled students 	<p>Theme five: Teachers' perceptions, attitudes, and experiences toward the inclusive education of physically and sensory disabled students</p> <p>Codes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inclusive education is great concept • The educational environment does not support the inclusion of disabled students • Lack of training makes teaching in an inclusive classroom difficult. • Teachers made great efforts to include disabled pupils • Acknowledging the diversity among learners • Hard job for teachers due to insufficient knowledge of inclusive education policy • Lack of confidence among teachers as result of inadequate guidance • Inclusive education is suitable when essential modifications are made. • Inclusive education is unwise since there are no adequate services and facilities • Challenging teachers' experience because of the absence of collaboration between policymakers, parents, and teachers 	<p>Theme Six: Teachers' perspectives on methods and strategies to improve inclusive education for physically and sensory disabled pupils in Algeria</p> <p>Codes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Providing teachers with training in inclusive education • Enhancing school facilities and services • Modifying the curriculum and providing sufficient teaching resources • Collaboration • Raising awareness of inclusive education • Raising teachers' motivation
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4- Review Themes

<p>Theme one: Teachers' understanding of the concept of inclusive education</p> <p>Codes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The physical presence of disabled pupils in regular schools • Defining disability from social model perspectives • The education of disabled students • Describing inclusive education by referencing the disabilities that students had. • Chance for disabled students to socialize • The attendance of disabled students in regular classroom conditioned by their number • Suitable setting for disabled pupils to adapt • Providing further care and attention to disabled students • Disabled learners sharing the same setting with non-disabled peers 	<p>Theme two: The inclusive education policy in Algeria</p> <p>Codes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The right of disabled students to enrol in regular schools • The existence of inclusive education • The headmaster of school is in charge of the enrolment of disabled learners • Dealing with students who have disabilities falls primarily on general educators. <p>Sub-theme: Instructional strategies used in the classroom</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Using Various teaching methods • Using group/pair work • Providing extra time • Peer assistance • Assignment modification • Explaining concept several times • Check understanding • Placing disabled students in the front rows in classroom
<p>Theme four: The barriers in implementing inclusive education in Algerian primary schools</p> <p>Codes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of teachers training and personal development in inclusive education • Inadequate school services and facilities • Lack of pre-service training in inclusive education • Lack of in-service training in inclusive education • Insufficient knowledge of Inclusive Education policies. • Lack of support from the ministry of education • Lack of funding from the government. • Special schools to serve students with 	<p>Theme three: Teachers' perceptions, attitudes, and experiences toward the inclusive education of physically and sensory disabled students</p> <p>Sub-theme: Positive perceptions, attitudes, and experiences toward the inclusive education</p> <p>Codes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inclusive education is great concept • Teachers made great efforts to include disabled pupils • Acknowledging the diversity among learners • Inclusive education is suitable when essential modifications are made. <p>Sub-theme: Negative perceptions, attitudes, and experiences toward the inclusive education</p> <p>Codes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The educational environment does not support the inclusion of disabled students • Lack of training makes teaching in an inclusive classroom difficult. • Hard job for teachers due to insufficient knowledge of inclusive education policy • Lack of confidence among teachers as result of inadequate guidance • Inclusive education is unwise since there are no adequate services and facilities

<p>disabilities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of classrooms adaptation • Inappropriate Curriculum • Poor instructional Resources and materials • Huge class size • Disengagement from parents • Lack of staff member at school • Behavioural problems • Special classrooms for disabled students 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Challenging teachers' experience because of the absence of collaboration between policymakers, parents, and teachers <p>Theme five: Teachers' perspectives on methods and strategies to improve inclusive education for physically and sensory disabled pupils in Algeria</p> <p>Codes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Providing teachers with training in inclusive education • Enhancing school facilities and services • Modifying the curriculum and providing sufficient teaching resources • Collaboration • Raising awareness of inclusive education • Raising teachers' motivation
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5- Defining themes: thematic map

Appendix O: Ethics approval letter

14/04/2022

Dear Houria Benkahla,

Your application 18004: resubmission of ethics application form , submission 19326, has been approved by the Education and Social Sciences SAIEC. You may now proceed with your study. This approval is valid for the duration of the study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Yours sincerely

ESS Academic Integrity and Ethics Committee